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2nd update on the report on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies and administrative registers and guidelines

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WP11 - Linking HBM, health studies and registers

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Abbreviations

AACE	American Association of Clinical Endocrinologist
ACD	acute contact dermatitis
AD	Alzheimer's disease
AD	atopic dermatitis
ADG	anogenital distance
ADHD	attention deficit hyperactivity disorder
ADI	Alzheimer's Disease International
AD-SOS	amplitude-depend SOS
AHAA/NLHBI	American Heart Association and National Heart Lung and Blood Institute
AKI	acute kidney disease
ALP	alkaline phosphatase
ALS	amyotrophic lateral sclerosis
ALT	alanine transaminase
AMH	anti-Müllerian hormone
As	arsenic
ASCVD	atherosclerotic CVD
ASD	autism spectrum disorder
ASDEU	Autism Spectrum Disorders in the European Union
AST	aspartate transaminase
B	blood
BaP	Benzo[a]pyrene
BCSS	Basic Clinical Scoring System
BLL	blood lead level
BMC	bone mineral content
BMD	bone mineral density
BMI	body mass index
BP	blood pressure
BPA	bisphenol A
B-Pb	lead measured in blood
BUA	broadband ultrasound attenuation
C	cholesterol
CAD	coronary artery disease

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Cd	cadmium
CDR	Clinical Dementia Rating Scale
CHD	coronary heart disease
CHF	congestive heart failure
CKD	chronic kidney disease
CLD	chronic liver disease
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CNS	central nervous system
Cr (III)	tetravalent chromium
Cr (VI)	hexavalent chromium
CRP	C-reactive protein
CT	computed tomography
CV	cardiovascular
CVD	cardiovascular disease
CysC	cystatin C
DALY	disability-adjusted life year
DAT-SPECT	single photon emission tomography
DBP	diastolic blood pressure
DDT	p,p'-dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane
DICA	Diagnostic Interview for Children and Adolescents
DILGOM	Dietary, Lifestyle and Genetic determinants of Obesity and Metabolic syndrome
DM	diabetes mellitus
DMA	dimethylated metabolites
DNPR	Danish National Patient Registry
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data protection officer
DSM	Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders
DTC	differentiated thyroid cancer
DXA	dual energy/photon X-ray absorptiometry
EASI	Eczema Area and Severity Index
eBMD	estimated BMD
ECG	electrocardiogram
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency

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EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
eGFR	estimated glomerular filtration rate
EGIR	European Group for the Study of Insulin Resistance
EHES	European Health Examination Survey
EHIS	European Health Interview Survey
ELSPAC	European Longitudinal Study of Pregnancy and Childhood
EMG	electromyography
ESKD	end-stage-kidney disease
EU	European Union
FALS	familial ALS
FDOPA PET	fluorodopa positron emission tomography
FeNO	fractional exhaled nitric oxide
FEV ₁	forced expiratory volume in 1 s
FEV ₁ %	forced expiratory volume in 1 s per forced vital capacity, FEV ₁ /FVC
FFQ	food frequency questionnaire
FRAX	Fracture Risk Assessment Tool
FRS	Framingham Risk Score
FVC	forced vital capacity
GBD	Global Burden of Disease
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
GGT	gamma-glutamyl transferase
GHS	Globally Harmonised System
GINA	Global Initiative for Asthma
GSM	grey scale median
GW	gestational week
HbA1C	glycated haemoglobin
HBM4EU	Human Biomonitoring for European Union
HBV	hepatitis B virus
HCC	hepatocellular carcinoma
HDI	hexamethylene diisocyanate
HDL	high-density lipoprotein
HES	Health Examination Survey

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HF	heart failure
Hg	mercury
HIS	Health Information Survey
HMW	high molecular weight
HR	hazard ratio
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
iAs	inorganic arsenic
ICD	International Classification of Diseases
ICD	irritant contact dermatitis
ICD-10	International Classification for Diseases 10
ICD-11	International Classification for Diseases 11
ICPC-2	International Classification for Primary Care
IDF	International Diabetes Federation
IFG	immunoglobulin E
IGT	impaired glucose tolerance
IHD	ischemic heart disease
JIS	Joint Interim Statement
LDL	low-density lipoprotein
LFT	liver function test
LMN	lower motor neuron
LMW	low molecular weight
MBRN	Medical Birth Registry of Norway
MBzP	monobenzyl phthalate
MBzP	monobenzyl phthalate
MDI	Methylene diphenyldiisocyanate
MetS	metabolic syndrome
MI	myocardial infarction
MMA	monomethylated metabolites
MMP	mono-methyl phthalate
MoBa	Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study
MRI	magnetic resonance imaging
MS	multiple sclerosis
MTA	material transfer agreement

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NAFLD	non-alcoholic fatty liver disease
NASH	non-alcoholic steatohepatitis
NCEP-ATP III	National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III
NCV	nerve conduction velocity
NEP	N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone
NHANES	National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey
NHCP	National Hub Contact Point
NMP	N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone
NorPD	Norwegian Prescription Database
OCC	Odense Child Cohort
OECD	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OP	organophosphate
OR	odds ratio
OTA	ochratoxin A
PAC(s)	plastic associated chemical(s)
PAD	peripheral artery/arterial disease
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
Pb	lead
PD	Parkinson`s disease
PEF	serial peak expiratory flow
PFAS	per- and polyfluoroalkyl substance
PFHpA	perfluoroheptanoic acid
PFOA	perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS	perfluorooctane sulfonates
PI	principal investigators
PIC	personal identification code
PIH	pregnancy induced hypertension
PIVUS	Prospective Investigation of the Vasculature in Uppsala Seniors
PNS	peripheral nervous system
POP(s)	persistent organic pollutant(s)
p-PDA	p-phenylenediamine
PPE	personal protective equipment
Prick tests	skin puncture test

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PVC	polyvinyl chloride
QALY(s)	quality-adjusted life years
QUI	quantitative ultrasound index
QUS	quantitative ultrasound
RADS	reactive airways dysfunction syndrome
REACH	Regulation, Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RfD	reference dose
ROS	reactive oxygen species
RR	relative risk
RRT	renal replacement therapy
SBP	systolic blood pressure
SCORAD	Scoring Atopic Dermatitis Index
Scr	serum creatinine
SI	stiffness index
SMD	standardised mean difference
SMR	standardised mortality ratio
SNC	sinonasal cancer
SOP	standardised operating procedures
SOS	speed of sound
SSS	Simple Scoring System
T1DM	type 1 diabetes mellitus
T2DM	type 2 diabetes mellitus
TC	total cholesterol
TDI	toluene diisocyanates
THL	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare
U	urine
UK	United Kingdom
UMN	upper motor neuron
UN	United Nations
URR	unit relative risk
US	ultra sound
USA	United States of America
WHO	World Health Organisation

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WMD Weighted Mean Differences
YLD years lived with disability
YLL years of life lost

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Abstract

Many environmental substances (chemicals and heavy metals) are associated with adverse health effects such as increased risk of cardiovascular disease, several types of cancer, metabolic syndrome, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, neurological disorders, problems with kidney and liver function, reproductive health problems and cognitive development. Therefore, it is essential to be able to monitor the human exposure levels to such substances and their associations to health.

In order to demonstrate possible adverse health effects of chemical exposures on human health, it is important to obtain both exposure and health information among the same individuals. Chemical exposures to humans are usually measured using Human Biomonitoring studies (HBM). These studies often include some health information mainly obtained through self-reported questionnaire(s). Self-reported health information could suffer from reporting bias, as well as awareness bias. People do not necessarily remember which diseases they have been diagnosed with and when, which leads to reporting bias. They may also be unaware of their health condition, as many diseases can be asymptomatic for a long time, which again leads to awareness bias.

More extensive health information could be obtained through health examination surveys which include also objective health measurements. In some of the HBM4EU partner countries, HBM studies have been combined with health examination surveys. There are several countries which have health surveys without a HBM module. The principal investigators of these health surveys report that in most cases it would be possible to add an HBM module to their health survey even though several potential obstacles for this type of combination were identified.

An alternative way to obtain improved health information on HBM participants is to link individual HBM data to existing administrative registers on health such as a cause of death registers or hospitalisation data. This is not possible in all countries due to lack of common identifiers between different data sources or due to legal restrictions within the country. But in the countries where this can be done, such as in the Nordic countries, this is a cost-effective way to obtain information on both disease history and disease onset (disease incidence) based on the diagnoses registered in the health register data. Nevertheless it is important to be aware of that data from administrative registers may not be complete, but are limited to only those who sought medical care for their symptoms or disease.

Although a lot of evidence already exists on adverse health effects due to exposure to environmental chemicals, there are still large knowledge gaps. Because an experimental study in humans is unethical in most cases, the evidence has to heavily rely on observational studies. Thus, more studies of high quality are needed, including a large sample size and with standardised methods of measurement chemical exposures and health outcomes. The use of standardised operating protocols is essential to ensure high quality and comparability of the results across studies.

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Introduction

The European Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU) is a joint effort of 30 countries, the European Environmental Agency and the European Commission, co-funded under Horizon 2020.

The main objective of the HBM4EU is to use Human Biomonitoring (HBM) to assess human exposure to chemicals in Europe in order to better understand the associated health impacts and to improve chemical risk assessment. HBM4EU will generate knowledge on chemical exposure levels in the population and their health effects.

This report is the 2nd update and extension of two previous Deliverables namely 11.1 and 11.3.

In parallel to HBM studies, health examination surveys (HES) are conducted in many European countries. HESs is population surveys where information is collected by questionnaire(s), through physical measurements and analysis of biomarkers from collected biological samples. HBM studies and HESs have a lot of similarities in required infrastructure and used procedures which support the possibility to combine them into one study. This would provide more cost-effective data collection and more extensive data sources including both information on chemical exposures, and health and determinants of health. Part A of this report, opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, summarises the updated information on country perspectives for possibilities to combine HBM and health studies in the coming years.

All European countries have at least some national or regional administrative health related registers. If these registers and HBM data include common identifiers and the national legislation allows, linking HBM data to register data provides another cost-effective way to obtain more comprehensive health information both on disease history, follow-up and about HBM study participants. In part B of this report, availability of administrative registers and possibility for their use in HBM studies, provides an update of the register availability and one theoretical study and case studies from five countries demonstrating how this type of record linkage has been/could be done and what kind of information it would provide.

Part C of this report provides an extended review of the potential health effects of the HBM4EU priority substances and summarises known methods; self-reported questionnaire information, objective health measurements and/or laboratory analysis, and diagnoses (International Classification of Diseases: ICD-10 and ICD-11, and International Classification of Primary Care - ICPC-2) from medical records, for their identification.

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Part A: Opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies

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2 Executive summary

HBM studies and health examination surveys have many common characteristics especially on the infrastructure they require to be conducted. Both study types rely heavily on survey based data collection which includes both questionnaires and collection of objective measurements during the fieldwork. Therefore, it would be cost-effective to combine HBM and health survey studies, and not to conduct them in parallel as currently happens in many countries.

A survey was prepared for the HBM and health study Principle Investigators to better understand how commonly these two study types are already combined and what opportunities and obstacles relates to the possible linkage of these studies. Survey was distributed through National Hub Contact Points in three different occasions to obtain the most up-to-date information.

In many health examinations and targeted health surveys, ethical approvals are broad enough to cover also the analysis of environmental chemicals. In addition, in many health surveys, biological samples such as blood and urine are collected and stored for future use. Therefore, including an HBM module to health surveys would often be theoretically possible, however this has not been done due to lack of funding. Furthermore, chemical measurements are not considered relevant for the aims of the studies and due to possible logistic reasons.

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3 Initial remarks

In past years Task 11.1 has evaluated twice the opportunities and obstacles of combining ongoing and/or planned HBM and health studies (health examination surveys (HESs), cohort studies, dietary surveys, occupational studies, etc.) using a structured online questionnaire distributed through the National Hub Contact Points (NHCP) within HBM4EU. Details on the questionnaire and the results of the previous rounds from 2017 and 2018 are published in the Deliverables 11.1(Tolonen, 2018) and 11.3 (Tolonen, 2019), respectively.

In 2020, a third and final update round of the evaluation was conducted. This report provides a summary of the main findings from all three evaluation rounds serving altogether as an update of previous work. The findings are furthermore summarised in a short report which has been submitted to a scientific journal.

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4 Objectives

The specific objectives of this evaluation were to:

- create an inventory of the recently completed, ongoing and planned health studies which could be linked to HBM studies,
- gather information about biological samples collected in the health studies and stored for future use,
- collect information about whether ethical approvals for the studies cover the use of the available biological samples for HBM, and
- assess possible opportunities and obstacles related to combining HBM and health studies.

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5 Methodology

Experiences and expectations of combining HES and HBM study designs were evaluated in 2017-2020 using an electronic questionnaire targeted to principal investigators (PIs) of recently conducted, ongoing or planned health studies across Europe. PIs of potentially relevant studies were identified by the National Hub Contact Points within the HBM4EU to identify the studies of interest in the respective countries. In 2017 and 2018, the questionnaire was distributed through NHCPs to the study PIs (Figure 1). In 2020, a short 2-page summary of the results from the previous rounds was prepared (see below) and distributed to the NHCPs for their review. Study PIs were asked to contact Task 11.1 leader if they had new studies which should be included in the evaluation. Those that responded received a link to the online questionnaire.

Furthermore, an additional open-ended questionnaire, allowing the collection of more detailed descriptions, was developed and targeted to PIs on studies already succeeding in combining HBM and HES at national level (Germany, France and Israel).

Figure 1: Timeline in Task 11.1

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6 Key findings

6.1 Overview of reported findings

PIs of 76 studies from 20 European countries and Israel responded to the electronic questionnaire (Figure 2A). Most of the included studies were characterised either as health examination studies, either targeted or conventional HES (n=34, 45%), combined HBM and HES (n=19, 25%) or HBM studies (n=15, 20%), whereas a minor proportion of the surveys were characterised as occupational, dietary or other type of study (n=8, 11%) (Figure 2B).

Figure 2: A) Distribution of countries from which data was reported and B) Frequency of type of study design

6.2 Opportunities for adding HBM to ongoing or planned HES

6.2.1 Biological samples

Among the studies that did not already perform combined HES and HBM (n=57), 89% already included or could in the future include the collection of biological samples. The most frequently collected and stored sample matrices were plasma, whole blood and/or serum samples and urine samples (64%), with either first morning void or spot urine samples as the most frequent type of urine samples (Figure 3A).

6.2.2 Chemical measurements

The most frequent chemical substances reported to be measured or planned to be measured in HES and HES-related surveys were phthalates (37%), bisphenols (35%) and cadmium (35%) (Figure 3B).

6.2.3 Ethical approval

PIs on HES and HES related studies (n=42) were asked about whether they had ethical approvals covering measurements of chemicals in collected samples. In total, 26 studies (62%) already had ethical approvals covering chemical measurements and another 9 PIs reported that they could obtain ethical approval. Thus, in total 35 studies (83%) already had or subsequently could obtain ethical approval.

Figure 3: Availability of biological samples (A) and chemicals' measurements (B) in studies that were not combined HBM and HES (n=57)

6.3 Reported obstacles for adding HBM to HES

According to responses to the question of defining obstacles for adding HBM to HES, the most common reasons for omitting an HBM module from HES were a) lack of funding and b) lack of capacity for chemical analysis. Often the PIs considered HBM module irrelevant for the primary study focus of the health study.

6.3.1 Funding

The survey revealed significant differences in funding sources across European regions for the reported studies: in the Eastern and Western region approximately 90% of the studies had governmental funding, whereas several funding sources were reported in the Northern and Southern regions. Only 56% of the studies from the Northern region and 24% from the Southern region were mainly funded by the government, with other funding sources reported being public grants as well as international funding sources (Figure 4). Concerning studies already succeeding in combining HBM and HES at national level, all three combined programmes, namely from Germany, France and Israel, were initiated and implemented at the governmental level with the driving forces behind the programmes being primarily either under environmental or health ministerial direction. Likewise, funding of the programmes was secured through ministerial funding primarily from the health and environmental ministries.

Figure 4: Main funding sources according to region

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6.4 Experience from combined HES-HBM studies

One of the main advantages reported by the three studies which had already combined HBM and HES on national level was the utilisation of the same infrastructure for recruitment of participants and questionnaire distribution and simultaneous collection of biological samples and health parameters, resulting in more cost-effective data collection with more health information on each participant. Also, a combined study programme allowed investigating links between chemical exposures and health-related outcomes, although the timing between exposure and outcome can be challenging in a cross-sectional study design. However, while survey content is broadened due to expanded data collection, balancing participants' burden with research interests of both a HES and an HBM module can be challenging. In addition, the amount of collected biological samples has a limitation. This will restrict the number of possible analyses and a prioritisation of available sample volume between measurement of health biomarkers and exposure biomarkers may be needed. Furthermore, coordination of the activities between several research groups with different aims can be challenging and time consuming.

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7 Summary of key findings

Findings from this survey under HBM4EU showed that there is a great potential to combine HBM and HES in EU and associated states. Several examples have shown that combining HBM and health surveys is feasible and provides several logistical and financial but also scientific advantages including access to a wide range of information about population health status, chemical levels of exposure in the body and its determinants.

However, combining HBM and HES requires detailed planning and good collaboration between research groups to be successful.

Finally, for a successful combination of health and biomonitoring programmes at national level, national prioritisation and political support are required including sustainable funding during the conduction of the combined programme.

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9 Appendix

9.1 Appendix 1: Summary of the outcomes from Task 11.1.

Summary of the outcomes from Task 11.1 Opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies

Aim of Task 11.1

The main aim of the Task 11.1 was to

1. create an inventory of the recently completed, ongoing and planned health studies which could be linked to HBM studies,
2. gather information about existing biological samples collected in the health studies and stored biological samples for future use,
3. collect information about whether ethical approvals for the studies cover the use of the available biological samples for HBM, and
4. assess possible opportunities and obstacles related to combining HBM and health studies.

Methodology

National Hub Contact Points were requested to identify study principle investigators (PIs) of recently conducted or planned health studies that potentially could add an HBM component. These PIs were asked to fill in the online survey about recently conducted, ongoing or planned health studies that potentially could add an HBM component around mid-2017 and again in early 2018. Also a qualitative questionnaire was distributed to PIs from studies in three countries (Germany, France and Israel) succeeding in combining health examination surveys (HES) and HBM modules.

Countries which responded

Out of the 28 national hubs, information on PIs was obtained from 19 countries with more than one identified PI from several of the identified countries.

Overview of reported studies

In total, 61 different studies were reported as being conducted or planned to be initiated. Because one of the objectives of Task 11.1 was to evaluate the existing biological samples collected in health studies and stored in biobanks for future use, studies with no collection of biological samples (n=4) were excluded. In addition, 2 studies were excluded due to missing data leaving 55 studies for further analyses.

Table 1. Frequency of the reported studies according to region and country (n=55)

Region	Number of studies (%)
Northern Europe	20 (36%)
Denmark (n=10), Finland (n=1), Latvia (n=3), Lithuania (n=1), Sweden (n=5)	
Eastern Europe	6 (11%)
Czech Republic, (n=4), Slovakia (n=2)	
Southern Europe	22 (40%)
Cyprus (n=2), Greece (n=3), Italy (n=3), Portugal (n=3), Slovenia (n=3), Spain (n=8)	
Western Europe	6 (11%)
France (n=1), Germany (n=1), Luxembourg (n=2), Netherlands (n=1), Switzerland (n=1)	
Other	1 (2%)
Israel (n=1)	
Total	55 (100%)

Regions are defined according to the United Nations geoscheme, with the exception of categorizing Cyprus into Southern Europe instead of Asia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/United_Nations_geoscheme_for_Europe).

Availability of biological samples

Vast majority of the studies (n=38, 93%) reported that biological samples were collected and stored for future use. Most frequent stored samples were blood samples, either whole blood, plasma or serum.

Ethical approval for chemical measurements in health studies

Ethical approval covering the measurement of chemicals in collected samples was available in 21 studies (58%). In addition, out of the 15 PIs from studies who responded that ethical approval was currently not available, another 9 PIs responded that ethical approval for measuring chemicals could be obtained in the future. Thus, in total 30 studies (83%) had approval or could obtain approval for chemical measurements in the future.

Summary of findings

- In total, 61 different studies were reported as being conducted or planned to be initiated
- 93% of the included studies had biological samples available
- 63% of the studies measured or planned to measure chemicals
- Main issues for not measuring chemicals were lack of funding
- 83% of HES already had or could obtain ethical approval in the future
- Experiences from countries succeeding in combining HBM and HES reveals a great potential to utilize existing logistical infrastructures but some obstacles such as limitations in number of data to include

Reference:

Stine Agergaard Holmboe (RegionH), Anna-Maria Andersson (RegionH), Hanna Tolonen (THL), Sónia Namorado (INSA), Carlos Dias (INSA), Baltazar Nunes (INSA). Part A. Opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies in Deliverable 11.3 Reporting on opportunities and obstacles of combining HBM and health studies, availability of health studies with biological samples, availability of administrative registers, and guidelines for combining HBM and health studies. May 2019

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Availability of chemical measurements

More than half of the studies (n=26, 63%) reported that chemicals were measured or planned to be measured. The most frequent measured chemicals were phthalates (n=16, 39%), bisphenols (n=14, 34%), and cadmium (n=14, 34%). Main issues for not measuring chemicals were lack of funding in relation to handling of extra samples or laboratory analyses of chemicals. Other reasons were logistical issues and lack of knowledge about chemicals.

Identified opportunities and obstacles

There are EU or EU associated countries with health programmes that have succeeded in combining a HBM module with HES, namely Germany, France and Israel. Experiences from these countries were evaluated and summarised below:

Potential opportunities and advantages

- Great potential to utilize existing logistical infrastructure from HES and thus, reduce cost of the surveys
- Access to a wide range of detailed nutrition and health-related data
- Possibility to investigate links between exposures and health related outcomes
- The public awareness and interest in HES issues has a positive influence on the perception of HBM

Potential obstacles

- Limitations in the size of questionnaire and other health parameters
- Lack of flexibility in data access between databases
- Lack of communication between the HES and HBM modules

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Part B: Availability of administrative registers and possibility for their use in HBM studies

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2 Executive summary

Health information for HBM studies can be obtained either through questionnaires or objective measurements during fieldwork. Alternative method to obtain health information is through record linkage from administrative registers. However, this is not possible in all countries due to national legal restrictions.

Most of the countries have at least birth, cause of death and cancer registers covering the specific country. Personal identifiers used in the registers can vary. However, in theory many of the national personal identifiers could be used for record linkage if the same identifier is available in the HBM study sample.

Conducting record linkage generally requires ethical approval and informed consent from the study participants. GDPR has not changed the protocols substantially, but nowadays conducting record linkage requires more time than previously.

Record linkage is a cost-effective way to obtain information on disease history as well as follow-up data for onset of new events.

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3 Background

Human Biomonitoring (HBM) aims at assessing nutritional status and/or the exposure to environmental chemicals and their metabolites in the human body, usually through analyses of blood, urine, hair, breast milk or tissues in individuals or a population group. It may provide an aggregated measure of the level of exposure to nutrients and chemicals through different exposure pathways.

In many countries, information obtained through HBM studies can be linked to different population registers to assess e.g. disease history and to obtain follow-up information on disease onset. As an example, one can define a healthy baseline population and study the risk of developing various conditions or diseases. This report summarises information collected through the HBM4EU National Hub Coordinators who distributed a web questionnaire about availability of health-related administrative registers in 28 out of 30 countries participating in the HBM4EU project, and how they can be linked to HBM data. The report also presents one theoretical study from Austria and case studies from Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, Norway and Sweden demonstrating how record linkage can be or has been done in practice.

Key results from the questionnaire and one theoretical study and case studies were:

- Availability of health-related administrative registers varies substantially between the countries.
- In countries where each citizen has a national identification code, such as in the Nordic countries where it is systematically used in all registers, record linkage is easier to conduct in practice.
- In some countries, legislation does not allow record linkage even though every citizen has a national identification code.
- Generally, approval from a privacy commission and the register owner is needed for record linkage. In most countries, approval from an ethical committee is also required as well as informed consent from the HBM study participants.
- The introduction of GDPR in May 2016, conducting the record linkage studies has become more time-consuming.

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Administrative registers, such as registers of cancer, in- and out-patient hospitalisations and mortality registers, may provide nationally representative data on morbidity and mortality in a country. In many countries such registers are nationally representative, or there are several regional registers covering the majority of a country. In principle, if register information is recorded using a personal identification number or other types of identification which would be available also in HBM studies, a record linkage can be conducted if allowed by the national data protection regulation. This type of record linkage can provide a cost-effective data source for morbidity and mortality follow-up and for obtaining baseline health information (Figure 5.)

Figure 5: Information to be obtained through record linkage

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4 Objectives

The aim of the report is to provide an overview of the existing health related administrative registers among HBM4EU partner countries together with possibilities to link this register information to the HBM or health surveys. Additionally, this report will provide a series of case studies demonstrating how record linkage has been done in six countries. These case studies will provide practical information from six countries on what the requirements for such record linkage are (data protection, ethics, technical and practical procedures etc.) and what kind of register data can be obtained.

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5 Methods

This report builds on the previous HBM4EU Deliverables 11.1 and 11.3. Information reported here has been obtained through an online questionnaire and case studies conducted by participants in Task 11.5.

5.1 Online questionnaire

An electronic questionnaire (Questback survey) was prepared to obtain information about the availability of the participating countries' health-related administrative registers and find out if they could be linked to HBM/health studies and with each other. The details about the questionnaire were published in the HBM4EU Deliverable 11.1 (Tolonen, 2018).

A questionnaire link was distributed to the National Hub Contact Points through the HBM4EU National Hub Coordinator three times: in 2017, 2019 and at the end of 2020-early 2021. In each round, information from new countries was obtained or previously provided information was updated (2017 - 19 countries; 2019 - 22 countries; 2020 - 28 countries). Figure 6 presents countries with have provided their response in these three rounds.

Figure 6: Contributing countries

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5.2 Case studies

For the case studies, each of the partner countries involved in Task11.5 were asked to select at least one already conducted study in their own country where HBM and health survey data had been linked. In the framework of these case studies, they documented which health related administrative registers these HBM/health surveys had been or could/have been linked to, what are the legal and ethical requirements in each country for doing this as well as how EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has possibly changed the procedures since its implementation.

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6 Administrative registers and possibility for record linkage

6.1 Availability of health-related administrative registers

Information provided in Table 1 is based on information reported by the National Hub Contact Points or the persons they delegated the task to.

Most of the countries reported that they have at least a birth register (79%); a cause of death register (75%) and a cancer register (82%). Many countries also have registers on hospitalisations (in- and/or out-patient) and a more limited number of countries also reported that they have registers on prescription of medications or malformations. Several countries reported other disease specific registers, such as registers for injuries and accidents, diabetes, stroke, tuberculosis and HIV/AIDS. Other registers mainly included data related to different occupational health issues (Table 1).

Table 1: Availability of different health related administrative data sources by country

Country	Birth register	Cause of death	Hospitalisations		Prescription of medications	Malformations	Disease specific		Other
			In-patient	Out-patient			Cancer	Other	
AT – Austria	Yes	Yes					Yes		
BE – Belgium	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	
CH - Switzerland	Yes	Yes					Yes	Yes	
CY - Cyprus	Yes	Yes					Yes	Yes	
CZ – Czech Republic	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
DE – Germany							Yes		
DK – Denmark	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes		Yes
EE – Estonia	Yes	Yes			Yes		Yes	Yes	
EL – Greece	Yes	Yes							
ES – Spain			Yes	Yes			Yes		
FI – Finland	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
FR – France	Yes					Yes	Yes	Yes	
HR – Croatia							Yes		
HU – Hungary	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		
IS – Iceland	Yes	Yes			Yes				

Country	Birth register	Cause of death	Hospitalisations		Prescription of medications	Malformations	Disease specific		Other
			In-patient	Out-patient			Cancer	Other	
IE – Ireland							Yes	Yes	
IL – Israel	Yes	Yes					Yes	Yes	
IT – Italy	Yes	Yes	Yes						
LT – Lithuania		Yes					Yes	Yes	Yes
LU – Luxembourg	Yes	Yes					Yes	Yes	
LV – Latvia							Yes	Yes	Yes
NL – Netherlands	Yes	Yes							
NO – Norway	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes
PL – Poland	Yes		Yes						
PT – Portugal	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes		
SE – Sweden	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
SK – Slovakia	Yes	Yes	Yes					Yes	
SI - Slovenia	Yes	Yes	Yes		Yes	Yes	Yes		

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6.2 Available identifiers and possibility to link

In 43% of the countries, an individual, national level identification code is used in all reported registers and in addition, in 32% of the countries, it is used in some of the registers. There were only 11% of the countries that did not have any identifiers used in any of the reported registers (Table 2).

Table 2: Availability of identifiers in registers and possibility for record linkage between different data sources

Country	Identifier(s) used in the registers	Possibility to link and potential limitations
AT	Individual, national level identification code	Not all registers include ID, and access and use of some of the registers is not allowed
BE	Patient identifier exists but it is not used in all registers	Linkage is possible between some of the registers
CH	Varies between registers. Some registers have individual, national level identification code, some use non-personal identifier, and some don't have any identifier at all.	For some registers, linkage is not allowed and in general, heavy legal restrictions are in place. Requires approval from register owner and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used
CY	Mainly individual national level identification code, but some registers use registers specific identifiers or non-personal identifiers.	Difficult due to missing common identifier between registers.
CZ	Individual national level identification code	Linkage is allowed by law among the registries within the National Health Information System. The linkage with external sources is very restricted. Requires approval from the register owner and only de-identified data are provided.
DE	Data is stored in pseudonym	Linkage is not possible
DK	Mainly individual, national level identification code, but some registers have a register specific code	Generally, linkage can be done except for those registers which use register specific code. Requires approval from the ethics committee and register owner.
EE	Mainly individual national level identification code, but some registers have a register specific code	Generally, linkage can be done, but requires approval from the ethics committee and register owner.
EL	No identification at all in the registers	Linkage is not possible
ES	Varies between the registers from individual national level identification code, register based identifier to no identifier at all	Linkage is not allowed
FI	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible with the approval from register owner and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used
FR	No information provided	

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Country	Identifier(s) used in the registers	Possibility to link and potential limitations
HR	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible when registers use the same unique identifier and the legal framework is in place. Requires approval from the ethics committee and register owner
HU	Individual, national level identification code	It is not allowed to link registers due to legislation
IE	Some registers have register specific code and other don't have any personal identifiers	Not currently possible
IL	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible for some of the registers but requires approval from the privacy commission and register owner. For some registers, linkage is not allowed. Requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used.
IS	Individual, national level identification code	Requires authorisation from the Icelandic Data Protection Authority as well as approval from ethical committee and register owner.
IT	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible with the approval from the register owner
LT	Mainly individual, national level identification code but some registers don't have any identifiers	For most of the registers, linkage is possible with the approval from the register owner and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used
LU	Wide variation between registers, some of them having individual, national level identification codes, many don't have any identifiers at all and some data are stored in pseudonym	
LV	Mainly individual, national level identification code, but some registers have register specific codes	For most of the registers, linkage is possible with the approval from the register owner and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used
NL	Individual, national level identification codes	Linkage is possible but requires approval from privacy commission and register owners and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used
NO	Mainly individual, national level identification code, but some registers have register specific identifier	Linkage is possible but requires approval from privacy commission and ethical committee and informed consent from participating individuals
PL	No personal identification	
PT	Varies between registers, most of the registers have register specific identifier and only a few use individual, national level identification code	Difficult due to variety of identifiers and restrictions by legislation
SE	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible, but requires approval from the ethical committee and register owner, and requires informed consent from individuals when HBM/health survey data is used

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Country	Identifier(s) used in the registers	Possibility to link and potential limitations
SI	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible, but requires approval from privacy commission and register owner
SK	Individual, national level identification code	Linkage is possible for organisations which are entitled for that by law. Requires approval from privacy commission and register owner.

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7 Record linkage methods

Record linkage allows us to generate new data by combining existing data sources. It is a cost-effective way to obtain additional information from HBM/health survey participants about their background and health as well as follow-up health information. Through record linkage we can obtain rich, up-to-date information about health parameters as well as the socio-economic position of individuals if this type of register data is available. This allows us to study relationships among variables reported in different data sources and provides us with a more holistic research view.

Through record linkage we can also minimise participant burden during the data collection and through that work towards General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation EU 2016), Article 5 on the data minimisation principle. The GDPR also provides some prerequisite for data linkage which generally come up in the process of obtaining ethical approval and informed consent from the study participants. In practice this means that detailed information about data needs have to be provided as well as details of data sources to be used for linkage and the lawfulness of processing such data. Details on how these requirements are to be fulfilled vary between countries and therefore it is important to consult each country's own Data protection officer on these questions.

Possibilities to conduct record linkage vary substantially between countries due to differences in availability of administrative registers, availability of identifiers to be used for record linkage, and national legislation and practices. It has been shown that in Europe, among EU Member States, the majority has some level of record linkage to support their health status monitoring or health policy development. Also, many countries allow record linkage for scientific research (Haneef 2020).

Technically, record linkage can be done using deterministic methods, probabilistic methods or a combination of these two. Also, some other less commonly used methods exist (Rule-based, fuzzy approach, information retrieval).

The deterministic method is based on exact matching of data sets using unique identifiers or a combination of data fields that uniquely identify individuals. Unique identifiers are often national personal identification numbers, while the combination of fields can be for example a person's name and date of birth. The deterministic method assumes that there is no coding errors or missing information on identifiers used for linkage. Figure 3 provides a simple example of deterministic linkage.

Figure 7: Example of the deterministic linkage process

Image from

https://toolkit.data.gov.au/Data_Linking_Information_Series_Sheet_3:_Deterministic_linking_and_linkage_keys.html

The probabilistic method uses a number of identifiers, in combination, to identify and evaluate links, and it is generally used when unique identifiers don't exist, or their quality is not good enough for deterministic linkage. The probabilistic method requires the following five steps to be completed: 1) data cleaning and standardisation, 2) blocking, 3) linking, 4) clerical review and 5) evaluating data quality. Examples of the probabilistic record linkage algorithms are the Fellegi-Sunder Method, Machine Learning and Bayesian Record linkage techniques (Asher 2020). Figure 4 provides an example of the required steps.

Diagram 1: Key steps in probabilistic linking

Figure 8: Example of the steps for probabilistic linkage process

Image from

<https://toolkit.data.gov.au/Data Linking Information Series Sheet 4: Probabilistic linking.html>

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8 Case studies

8.1 Austria

Austria has some experience with linking individual health or exposure data from surveys to register data. Recently a retrospective cohort study linking personal occupational exposure to cobalt and Causes of Death Register has been performed (Marsh et al., 2017; Wallner et al., 2017). The 2017 cobalt study also utilised some biomonitoring data (Hutter et al., 2016), but only to validate environmental exposure data. Similar register linkage studies have been conducted before (e.g.: Moshhammer and Neuberger, 2009).

The possibilities and problems regarding the record linkage of a past cross-sectional biomonitoring study to current register data as an easy way of turning the cross-sectional study into a (prospective) cohort study has been evaluated here.

Based on our previous experiences with the cobalt study we set out to obtain permission for a record linkage study using biomonitoring data from two cross-sectional studies on synthetic musks in blood.

8.1.1 Description of the selected HBM study

Two biomonitoring studies examining synthetic musks in blood were selected for this exercise. Both studies included people living in Vienna. The studies' aims were to assess population exposure to synthetic musks and to examine sex, age and life-style factors as exposure determinants. An examination of health effects of synthetic musks was not intended originally.

The first study (Hutter et al., 2005, 2009) was conducted in 2002 among students mostly from the Medical Faculty of the University of Vienna. Blood samples of 100 healthy students (55 female, average age 25 years) were collected and analysed.

A second study (Hutter et al., 2010) was conducted in 2005 among female patients of the department of angiology of a Viennese hospital and samples from 53 elderly women (aged more than 50 years) were analysed.

From all participants of both studies written informed consent was obtained. The consent forms were kept for documentation purposes and also because participants received a small expense allowance and the form also served as a receipt. Blood samples were pseudonymised using project-specific IDs, and the key between IDs and personal identification was documented on the consent forms to enable later cross-checking in case the participants asked about their personal analysis results. Thus, name and birth date of each participant could be linked to individual blood musk levels. Because consent forms were only stored on paper, extraction of personal identifiers (name and birthdate) for further processing would encompass some administrative work which at the time was hard to justify.

Theoretically the data of these two past studies on synthetic musks could be used as a starting point for a prospective cohort study. Some of the identified musks have been shown to have allergenic, mutagenic, and/or endocrine disruptive potential. Thus, an examination of health outcomes, most interestingly some cancer types, is principally of interest. We are well aware that especially among the students; frequency of cancers would be low during a relatively short follow up. The number of examined elderly women was small for a meaningful cohort study. But theoretically we could have envisaged our studies as a part of a multi-centre investigation contributing to a larger pooled study.

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8.1.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

The ethical approvals (EK 321/2001, EK 368/2004) of the original studies covered only the cross-sectional study part and no follow-up studies or record linkages. At the time when these studies were performed in early 2000s, record linkage with the Austrian Mortality Register was possible without personal approval and without special ethical approval, as mortality data then were considered non-sensitive. But a follow-up was at this time not intended.

So far, mostly the Causes of Death Register has been used for data linkages. In the Causes of Death Register, individual persons are found by name and birth date. This has been prone to some error, but in general worked well for previous cohort studies. In the cobalt worker study (Wallner et al., 2017); nearly 2000 workers with an occupational history dating back partly before the year 1970 were followed until the year 2014. Of this cohort, 177 participants had died, but a record linkage with the Causes of Death Register was possible for 159 only, giving an inaccuracy of 10%. Of course, the accuracy of record linkage will depend on time period under study and on the age at recruitment into the cohort because younger participants will more often change their name or leave the country before their death. A new and common personal identifier is planned for Austrian registers (see below) that will also enable cross-linkage between registers. As of January 2021, the legal details are not yet clarified, and therefore it is not clear if this identifier will also be useful for cross-linkages with cohort study data.

In 2013, the law mandating the Austrian Statistics Institute (Statistik Austria) with updating and the rules for the Cancer Register management was amended. Statistik Austria has always validated Cancer Register data by crosslinking the register with the Causes of Death Register: It is a sign of quality of a Cancer Register if most of the cancer events have already been reported to the Cancer Register before death. In 2013, the legal department of the government (Verfassungsdienst des Bundeskanzleramtes) pointed out that there is no legal basis for a crosslinking of different registers, even if they are managed by the same national agency. It therefore decided that the old practice was no longer allowed. This also had implications for cohort studies.

While the internal problem of Statistik Austria was soon fixed, it took 2 years of lobbying to get an amendment of the Austrian University Law (Forschungsorganisationsgesetz (FOG), § 2f Abs. 6 und 7) explicitly allowing cross-linking of cohort data with the Causes of Death Register. According to this law, it is now possible to link cohort data with the Causes of Death Register provided there is a positive decision from an Ethics Committee. For the cobalt study (Wallner et al., 2017), such a decision was easily obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Innsbruck. In the current pilot study, among other aims, we set out to test the feasibility of acquiring a positive decision from the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Vienna.

8.1.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

8.1.3.1 Patient/hospitalisations register(s)

In Austria, currently hospitalisation data are only stored in anonymous format. Therefore, a linkage between individual data and hospital admissions is not possible. Austrian hospital admission data have so far been utilised for time series studies (e.g. effects of daily temperature or air pollution), but not for cohort studies. Anonymous data are available from Statistik Austria and also from the national health agency (Gesundheit Österreich GmbH, GÖG). Statistik Austria has provided information (e-mail 2018/12/17), that a personalised version of the hospitalisation register is planned. A common personal identifier ("bereichsspezifisches Personenkennzeichen Amtliche Statistik" bPK-AS) for future use in all national registers is envisaged, but before this is in place, some technical, legal, and ethical issues must be resolved. It is not clear when this new identifier

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will be implemented and therefore, researchers are currently restricted to comparing names and birthdates (see above for details).

8.1.3.2 Cancer Register

The Austrian Cancer Register is kept by Statistik Austria. Its legal basis is the Krebsstatistikgesetz (1969) and the Krebsstatistikverordnung (1978) which are currently under revision. Currently, cases are stored with name and birth date, but data access from outside institutions/researchers is not possible. The use of bereichsspezifisches Personenkennzeichen Amtliche Statistik (bPK-AS) is planned for the future. Data have been available since 1983. Anonymous and pooled data (e.g. by district, year, and 5-year age group) are available for scientific analysis (e.g. time trends, ecological studies, Hutter et al 2019). Every doctor who diagnoses a cancer is legally required to report that case to the register, but reporting is not complete, although for most types of cancer more than 80% of all cases are reported. Each reported case is tracked and the date of first diagnosis is established. New Cancer Register data are therefore published with about 2 years delay with some missing cases being added even a few years later.

Linkage of cohort data with the Cancer Register is theoretically possible via the “safecenter” of Statistik Austria. The procedure of “safecentre” would be the following: To that end I would receive a test sample of data from Statistik Austria. With the help of this sample set I would need to develop a SAS procedure to examine the full data set. I would send the procedure and my data set to Statistik Austria for further processing. I would only receive pooled results (like odds ratios etc.). Statistik Austria estimates a working time of 40-60 hours and currently (2019) hourly working costs are set to EUR 95.-.

8.1.3.3 Causes of Death Register

Causes of death data are collected by Statistik Austria. Each death occurring in Austria is reported. Deaths of Austrian citizens that occur outside of Austria might be recorded if Statistik Austria is notified. Anonymous and pooled data have been available since 1947. Causes of death were first reported using ICD 5, since 1953 using ICD 6, since 1959 ICD 7, since 1969 ICD 8, since 1990 ICD 9, and since 2002 ICD 10. Forms to translate codes of diagnoses from one version to another are available upon request.

Anonymised data (e.g. cause of death 3-digit code, date of death, district of home address, sex, age-group) were previously available for scientific analyses like time series analyses (Neuberger et al., 2013, 2007, Moshhammer et al., 2013).

A linkage of cohort data to the Cause of Death Register was possible in previous times without much ado (Moshhammer and Neuberger, 2004). As described above, in 2013 this linkage possibility was blocked by a new legal interpretation of data privacy issues. This problem was fixed in 2015, but now an ethical approval is required before data linkage.

Statistics Austria charges a fixed price of EUR 500.- for each search of mortality data and additional fee of EUR 100.- per year to be searched for.

8.1.3.4 Address Register

In the cobalt study (Marsh et al., 2017; Wallner et al., 2017) we originally linked the individual data only with the Cause of Death Register. We soon discovered that the linkage was incomplete. Likely causes were: (a) wrong spelling of a name, change of name e.g. due to marriage, (b) move out of Austria / loss to follow-up.

In order to better understand and quantify the errors, we also linked the individual data to the Austrian address register. Until the year 2000, address registers were kept in each district

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separately and only in 2000 all local registers were pooled into one electronic national register run by the Ministry of the Interior. According to its homepage (<https://www.bmi.gv.at/413/Buergerinnen/start.aspx#auskunft>), every person is entitled to request individual data from the address register. Individuals are tracked via their full name and a second identifier, either the birth date or their ID in the register. The costs are EUR 14.30 plus EUR 3.30 per person. For the cobalt study, only persons who were still living in Austria in 2000 were found. For these we retrieved the following information: still living in Austria or either moved out of the country or died. The date of death or of leaving the country is not very accurate as the register is only updated monthly. No cause of death or any other details are provided. Nevertheless, the address register helped us to better assess loss to follow up and indeed find some additional deaths that were not found by linkage to the Cause of Death Register.

The cobalt cohort consisted of 1965 workers. Of these, 177 had died, but cause of death could only be extracted from the Cause of Death Register for 159 persons (89.8%). Hence, in the case of the cobalt cohort, about 10% of all deaths were missed by linkage with the Cause of death register. The cobalt cohort was special as the observation period covered a long time, beginning in the 1950s. It was also special because the industrial plant is located in Reutte, Tyrol, which is close to the German border. Thus, a relatively high percentage of the cohort members were German citizens or moved to Germany after retirement.

8.1.4 How record linkage is conducted

Linkage with The Address Register should be possible in the same way as it has been done with the cobalt cohort. But because this is only a feasibility study with no true scientific rationale regarding a sound research hypothesis, we abstained from actually performing the linkage.

Among the other registers only linkage with the Cause of Death Register seemed feasible. Currently no linkage is possible to the hospital admission register and record linkage to the Cancer Register seemed technically too challenging. It might be worthwhile though to investigate this option later.

To allow record linkage with the Cause of Death Register, permission from an Ethics Committee is mandatory. When in 2012 we first planned a record linkage for the cobalt study, we had already aimed for an approval from the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Vienna. By then this was not yet legally required, but the occupational health practitioner at the industrial plant who then would have been responsible for data handling and especially for the pseudonymisation process was afraid of the responsibility and asked for an ethics approval. The Ethics Committee then declared that for a pure record linkage study without direct involvement of individuals, no approval was necessary. And they explained that they are not responsible for personal data protection issues. When by the end of 2014 all obstacles were finally overcome, we decided not to apply for an approval in Vienna but in Innsbruck (Innsbruck is the capital of Tyrol where the industrial plant is situated), and the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Innsbruck (vote AN2014-0380 on 2015/01/29) approved of the study without much delay or administrative efforts on our part.

In order to be able to link the musk study data to the Cause of Death Register, we applied for an approval at the Ethics Committee of the Medical University of Vienna. In a first step, we had to complete a complex online form that is rather designed for (blinded) clinical intervention studies, but not for studies from the field of environmental epidemiology and certainly not for a study consisting of cross-linking of different data sets without actual contact to humans. The form consists of at least 10 sub-pages (more for some study types) with fields about the study type (with a selection mostly of types for clinical intervention studies), the principal investigator, details (sex, age, disease state and number) of participants, funding, planned interventions and

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pharmaceuticals used, insurance, participating centres, etc. Many parts of the form are not really applicable for observational studies and with the information distributed among different sub-pages it is not easy to check if the information is complete.

In addition, we provided a 2-page study description. Here we explained that we needed the approval because of legal requirements and also that this is a theoretical study where we only want to check if register data linkage is feasible in principle. We explained that it would be very useful in environmental epidemiology if existing cross-sectional data could be extended into a cohort study by making use of existing registers. In the description and the electronic form, we described the study as “prospective” and “register based”.

In the first response to our submission the secretariat of the committee informed us that our study description is formally incorrect. Because we are using existing data the study is not prospective but retrospective. We should also delete the term “register”. They also wanted more detailed information on the expected duration of the study which was not the time under observation (i.e. from the inception of the cohort in 2002 and 2005 until the last update of the register in 2017 or 2018), but how long it would take us to extract the data. They also asked us to provide the old approvals from 2002 and 2005. Because the PI of these old studies was different from the PI of the new study, we were also asked to add the former PI as one of the responsible team members (E-mail from 2019/01/31). These points were amended, and the request again submitted on the same day. On 2019/02/02 and 2019/02/04 some further minor changes were requested from the secretariat (new version number of the new submission, adding the former PI also to the electronic form, etc.). Finally, the electronic submission was accepted and in the following days the forms were also printed, signed, and delivered in person to the committee.

On 2019/03/12 the committee ruled (EK 1118/2019): the submission is still incomplete and therefore a positive approval can only be issued after the missing information and further documents are provided. They asked for more details regarding the intended statistical methods. In the original submission document, it was stated that a Cox proportional hazard regression was planned. It is not clear what else the commission wanted to hear. They wanted to know if a data linkage makes sense from the point of power estimates. Given the fact that only a few of the students from 2002 will already have died, it is quite clear that the study would likely not have sufficient power. But the aim of the study is not to study cancer risk from synthetic musks, but only to see if such a study is principally possible. This was certainly explained in the original document. Since the document had also mentioned that this is a study in the framework of the EU project HBM4EU, they asked to provide more information about HBM4EU and WP11 especially. They asked to hand in two versions of the new application. One with changes marked and one clean version. No updated documents were submitted from us.

8.1.5 Outcome of the record linkage study

We did not obtain the necessary ethical approval that would have allowed us the data linkage. But with more pertinacity we would likely have succeeded. But for a purely theoretical endeavour we did not feel the gains worth the effort.

From previous cohort studies we know that linkage with the Cause of Death Register is principally possible. With the necessary requirements, especially an ethical approval, available, the further steps are comparatively easy and quick. With the cobalt study it took only about 2 weeks at reasonable costs until the results of the data linkage (date of death and cause of death of every cohort member found in the register) were received.

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Completeness of the Cause of Death Register is always an issue. The cobalt cohort was special as the industrial plant from which the participants were recruited is situated on the very border to Germany. In the case of the first synthetic musk study we would also expect a higher amount of loss to follow up because students are prone to a higher mobility and to changes of name e.g. due to marriage. We would expect fewer problems with the second synthetic musk study on elderly women from Vienna. Generally, we would suggest cross-checking cause of death data with the Address Register. This proved very informative in our cobalt study. Because the inception of the synthetic musk studies was after the year 2000, the address register should be fairly complete.

8.1.6 Possible limitations/problems encountered/expected

The Cause of Death Register only reports cause and date of death. Any other variables of interest (exposure to synthetic musks, confounding factors, etc.) would need to be drawn from the original cross-sectional data set that also included a detailed questionnaire. For data security reasons, individual questionnaire data, biomonitoring data, and personal identifiers have been kept separately. Building a comprehensive data set would be technically possible but administratively challenging. According to current Austrian law, a positive ethics approval is mandatory before such a merged data set is created. In spite of the legal situation, ethics committees are not well prepared to deal with this kind of issues.

Some of the encountered problems with the ethics approval could be circumvented had we foreseen the possibility of a record linkage when the musk studies had been planned and first submitted for an ethics approval. But usually investigators want to reduce the application for an ethics vote to a minimum and hesitate to ask for more than they are currently planning for fear of additional difficulties. So, if the later application of biomonitoring data for additional scientific study questions is not fully foreseeable at study inception, it is not very common to already foresee later linkage studies. Also, an ethic approval is only delivered for a one-year period. So, if you want to keep it valid for future use, you would have to apply for continuation every year. This request is not as complicated as the first submission, but it still must be done.

The future will show how and when a common personal identifier will be introduced in Austrian administrative registers and how this identifier will be accessible for health researchers.

8.1.7 Impact of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

Prior to the GDPR, data protection regulations were often not well defined, and responsibilities and rights were not always clear. Therefore, we placed great hope into the GDPR even though it was clear that in some instances the new rules would introduce additional administrative burdens. But to the best of our knowledge the European rule has not really led to fundamental changes in the complex and unclear hierarchies, structures and regulations regarding data exchange and data protection in Austria.

8.2 Czech Republic

8.2.1 Description of the selected study cohort

The CELSPAC platform (Central European Longitudinal Studies of Parents and Children) includes an on-going, prospective, observational, longitudinal, birth cohort based on the ELSPAC study (European Longitudinal Study of Pregnancy and Childhood; www.elspac.com).

In the Czech Republic, the participants have been initially recruited in 1991-1992 during the pregnancy of mothers and followed until the adulthood of offsprings (N=5.151). This population is currently reassessed and called as the CELSPAC: Young Adults (short name the YA study, www.celspac.cz).

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Extensive data on family, health, psychological, environmental, social, educational, economic and other aspects of development and growing up of the first post-communist generation in the South Moravian Region have considerable research potential. The YA study aims to investigate the health status and health markers of young adults aged around 30 years. Basic and supplementary examinations were performed together with data collection by questionnaires (health status, lifestyle, environmental, socioeconomic factors etc.). Biological samples (blood samples, urine and buccal smear samples) were collected, processed, and archived at -80 °C.

Some ELSPAC children now have children of their own, and they are involved in the CELSPAC: TNG study (Central European Longitudinal Studies of Parents and Children: The Next Generation study, short name the TNG study; www.celspac.cz). The TNG study is a new prospective longitudinal population-based birth cohort initiated as a collaborative project of Masaryk University and University Hospital in Brno, Czech Republic. The study is designed to follow up 10,000 children from their prenatal period to adolescence to assess multiple factors potentially affecting children health within the concept of the exposome i.e., addresses multiple factors (genetics, lifestyle, environmental, socioeconomic, GIS etc.). Detailed information is being collected through questionnaires as well as from medical records related to mother physiological characteristics, pregnancy and birth. Biological samples (blood samples, urine, stool, breast milk, and buccal smear samples) were collected, processed, and archived at -80 °C.

Here we will describe our planned procedures on how to link initial data from the TNG study with follow-up data, including biological samples.

The study is conducted in Brno, the second largest city in the Czech Republic. The study is designed as a population-based observational birth cohort.

Women are being recruited in the 38th week of pregnancy. A detailed description of the ELSPAC study is in Piler et al (2017).

The pilot phase of the TNG study showed that 63% of the approached mothers are willing to participate in the study. 90% of the mothers who joined the study agreed to donate venous blood for the study purposes. There was no difference between mothers who agreed/disagreed with study participation in terms of education, parity and marital status.

The CELSPAC study is designed to identify early environmental and genetic factors of normal and abnormal growth, development and health during foetal life, childhood and adulthood. A special attention is being paid to prenatal and early postnatal developmental abnormalities, postnatal psychomotor development, neurobehavioral disorders and immune system disorders.

8.2.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

The Czech Republic is a member of the EU. Thus, the GDPR Regulation is applied directly, and personal data handling is entirely compatible with the Czech Data Protection Act on personal data processing (Law. No. 110/2019 Coll.) and Healthcare Services Act (Law. No. 372/2011 Coll. as amended).

Masaryk University (MU) also has internal norms regulating the data protection by the University directive No. 1/2018 "Personal Data Processing and Protection". MU has appointed the data protection officer (DPO).

In the CELSPAC platform, we apply a high level of the data protection which is guaranteed both by the internal regulation on the data protection in CELSPAC studies (Regulation of the Director of Center RECETOX No. 1/2018 governing the processing of personal data in CELSPAC), and also by the internal processes controlled by the ELSPAC Ethics Committee and the Management Board

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(Regulation of the Director of Center RECETOX No. 1/2015 on the Management of Long-term Studies). The protection of minors and also vulnerable persons is guaranteed by these internal norms of the CELSPAC cohort studies and also by internal policies supervised by the ELSPAC Ethics Committee and the Management Board of ELSPAC studies (Regulation of the Director of Center RECETOX No. 1/2015 on the Management of Long-term Studies). A participant can complain against the procedure of Masaryk University, which will process personal data on the basis of voluntary participation, to the Office for Personal Data Protection.

The ELSPAC study and the YA study have been approved by the ELSPAC Ethics Committee, Masaryk University, Brno, the Czech Republic (www.elspac.com; Ref. No. ELSPAC/EK/1/2014; Ref. No. ELSPAC/EK/2/2019). The TNG cohort study has been approved by the Ethics Committees of the University Hospital Brno (No. 20140409-01).

The Ethics Committees approved that the statutory requirements, internal regulations of Masaryk University, as well as ethical requirements of the research were met, particularly focused on the privacy protection, protection of personality and human dignity of probands, their possibility of a free withdrawal from the study, as well as the transparency of the collection and storing of data or biological samples.

The studies participants were asked to participate on a voluntary basis and were provided with an information brochure about the contents of the surveys and possible future uses of the data and samples. All participants have provided written informed consent containing detailed information in the Czech language. Anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw his/her participation, data, and samples at any time without any consequences. Participating mothers signed informed consent on behalf of their newly born baby.

Current informed consent for the TNG study covers obtaining data from National Health Registries (registers of hospital discharges, cancer registers, etc.) and processing of health data by other institutions. All data and samples are available for secondary use in further research and development purposes. The mothers` informed consent has been given for indefinite time.

The record linkage will be performed through a contract with the administrator of the National Health Registries (Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic), who needs to approve the process.

8.2.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

8.2.3.1 Patient/hospitalisations register(s)

The proposed study will be based on a linkage of data from the birth cohort and the hospitalisations register - National Registry of Hospitalised Patients. The register was established in 1960, easily accessible data have been available since 1994. The register is one of the National Health Registries, administered by the Institute of Health Information and Statistics of the Czech Republic. The register includes information about healthcare provider, patient and the hospital stay (timing, diagnoses, performed procedures, outcome, etc.). The register was established by law and has close to 100% coverage of the Czech population.

8.2.4 How record linkage is conducted

The proposed process of record linkage is as follows: Masaryk University and University Hospital Brno as controllers will authorise the Institute of Health Information and Statistics as a processor to analyse the study data, including linkage with the National Registry of Hospitalised Patients. The identifier used for linkage will be the national identification number (birth number). The execution of this research study will be free of charge for all partners. The controllers will get anonymised

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results of the statistical analysis. The new EU General Data Protection Regulation set new standards for processes, which are reflected in the study data collection procedures.

8.2.5 Outcome of the record linkage study

The linkage would allow us to obtain disease (hospitalisation) history, possibly prior (for mothers), or after the baseline (the birth of the child). The primary outcome of the study will be hospitalisation of the child for different diagnoses and looking for its possible determinants. The register includes only basic SES data (family status, occupation, place of residence).

8.2.6 Possible limitations/problems encountered/expected

The process relies on ad hoc contractual agreement between researchers and the administrator of the national registries. Appropriate informed consent for this processing is needed.

8.3 Denmark

8.3.1 Description of the selected HBM study

The Odense Child Cohort (OCC) is an ongoing, prospective cohort of maternal and child health and development based in Odense, Denmark. We have around 2500 active mother-child pairs that have been followed since early pregnancy from 2010-12.

The women invited for the study were all living in the municipality of Odense at the time of recruitment. Odense is the fourth largest city of Denmark (approx. 200.000 inhabitants), but the municipality also includes some rural areas. We have no reason to believe that women from the Odense area should differ from other Danish women.

Women were eligible for the study if they were living in the municipality of Odense and were newly pregnant (gestational week 10-16) between January 1st 2010 and December 31st 2012 (N=6707). They were approached at the ultrasound examination at Odense University Hospital or at a voluntary information meeting. Of the 6707, 4017 accepted to receive information about the cohort, and 2874 (43 %) agreed to participate. The women completed a questionnaire about health, lifestyle and social factors at the time of inclusion and had a blood sample drawn. The women and their children have been followed continuously since then and will be until the children turn 18 years.

We wanted to link data from the OCC to the Danish National Patient Registry (DNPR). The aim is to investigate the association between maternal perfluoralkyl substances (PFASs) during pregnancy and the rate of hospitalisation due to infectious disease in their children. The maternal PFASs concentrations have been measured in the serum samples collected in early pregnancy. From the DNPR, we can obtain information on all hospitalisations with an ICD-10 code for infectious disease by linking to the unique social security number that all Danish citizens have.

8.3.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

For the Odense Child Cohort, current ethical approval allows receiving data on hospital admissions from the Paediatric Department as well as record linkage.

8.3.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

8.3.3.1 Patient/hospitalisations register(s)

The Danish National Patient Register (DNPR) is a register of all hospital contacts within the Danish Health Care System. In relation to every examination or treatment within a hospital, a range of information is registered, including when and where a patient is hospitalised and information on the patient's diagnoses, treatments, examinations, operations etc. Information on hospitalised patients

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(inpatients) is available from 1977 and onwards, whereas information on emergency unit patients, outpatients and psychiatric patients has only been available since 1995. The DNPR is administered by the National Health Data Authority (“Sundhedsdatastyrelsen”), which is a government agency. They also grant permission for researchers to receive data from the register.

8.3.4 How record linkage is conducted

The unique Danish Social Security number (“CPR number”) is used to link to the registers. The 10-digit number consists of the date of birth followed by a random, unique number (DDMMYY-RRRR). This identification number is available both in the cohort data as well as in all the register data.

For record linkage there is no fixed price. The amount charged will depend on the data requested and time required for the processing of the data request (hourly price).

The goal obtaining requested data is 30 workdays, but they state on their webpage that the waiting time is longer at the moment.

Personal identification number from children of mothers with available serum PFAS (N=1699) from the Odense Child Cohort were submitted to the Danish National Patient Registry. All hospitalisations with an ICD-10 code for infection were recorded. Children were followed from birth until a median age of 3.6 years. Data were provided pseudoanonymised.

Introduction of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has not changed the procedures but actual process takes more time than before and the number of institutions with direct access to the register data has been limited.

8.3.5 Outcome of the record linkage study

We have obtained information on hospitalisation due to any infectious disease for the children in The Odense Child Cohort from birth and for a mean time of 3.5 years. Currently we are not obtaining any follow-up information on them.

8.4 Finland

8.4.1 Description of the selected health study

The DILGOM 2007 Survey (Dietary, Lifestyle, and Genetic determinants of Obesity and Metabolic syndrome) (Konttinen 2018) was conducted in 2007 as a sub-study of the national FINRISK 2007 study (Peltonen 2008, Vartiainen 2010). The main aim of the DILGOM 2007 study was to provide a comprehensive overview on lifestyle, environmental and genetic factors associated with obesity, metabolic syndrome and type 2 diabetes.

The FINRISK 2007 sample was a random sample drawn from the Population Information System. The sample comprised 10 000 persons aged 25-74 years from five geographic areas in Finland: the capital area, South-western Finland, North Karelia, Northern Savo, and Ostrobothnia. A total of 6258 subjects (63%) participated in the FINRISK 2007 study from January to March 2007. All of those who participated in the FINRISK 2007 study were invited to the DILGOM 2007 study. In total, 5024 (80%) of them participated during the period from April to June 2007. The DILGOM 2007 study included a health examination and health questionnaires.

Dietary habits/dietary intake over the past 12 months were assessed using a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) self-administered by participants and reviewed by a study nurse. The FFQ was developed in the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) and has been validated against dietary records (Karttinen 2012).

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The health examination was performed by a trained nurse. The examination covered anthropometric measurements of weight, height, waist and hip circumference, and blood pressure. Also blood samples were drawn. Part of the samples were analysed for serum lipids (total cholesterol, HDL, cholesterol, and triglycerides) when the samples arrived at the central laboratory of THL. LDL was derived through a calculation method. Other analysed biomarkers included high-sensitive CRP, leptin, and fasting glucose. The rest of the blood samples were stored at -70°C for future use.

For environmental exposures, part of the DILGOM samples (n=1000) were analysed for PFAS (PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, PFDS, PFHxA, PFHpA, PFNA, PFDA, PFU(n)dA, PFDoA, PFTTrDA, PFTTeDA).

8.4.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

The DILGOM obtained the ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the Helsinki and Uusimaa hospital district (229/E0/06 on 3 April 2007). Each participant provided a written informed consent.

Ethical approval and informed consent define that the data and collected samples can be used for medical research and to study public health problems. It also states that the data can be linked to data collected under main study Finrisk 2007. Finrisk 2007 ethical approval (229/E0/2006 on 20 June 2006) and informed consent define that data can be linked to administrative registers: mortality information from the Statistics Finland, hospitalisations and Cancer Register information from the National Research and Development Centre for Welfare and Health (Stakes) – currently the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL) and work disability pension information from the Finnish Centre for Pensions and medication information from the Social Insurance Institution of Finland.

There is no fixed time limit for using the data. The informed consent defines that the data will be used over several decades.

8.4.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

8.4.3.1 Patient/hospitalisations register(s)

The Care Register for Health Care (Hilmo) includes information on the activities and patients treated at the health centres, hospitals, and other institutions providing in-patient care as well as home-nursing service providers (<https://thl.fi/en/web/thlfi-en/statistics/information-on-statistics/register-descriptions/care-register-for-health-care>). The Care register for Health Care does not, however, cover institutional care of child welfare or housing services for substance abusers. The register is a continuation of the Hospital Discharge Register established in 1969, which was replaced with the Care Register for Health Care as of 1994. In 2011, the Care Register for Health Care was widened to cover outpatient primary health care (Register for Primary Health Care Visits; Avohilmo). The data controller is the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL).

Health service providers submit information (i.e. care notifications) to the register according to the guidelines and instructions provided by THL. Basic data in a care notification for Care Register for Health Care cover the following topics:

- **Service provider** (code, code extension, service branch, speciality)
- **Data on the patient/client** (personal identity number, municipality of residence, country code for non-Finnish residents)
- **Data on start of care** (referring party, code and code extension of the institution that referred the patient, waiting list entry date and date of admission, type of admission, route

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of admission, code of the place of discharge [if the person was admitted from another institution])

- **Data on the treatment received by the patient/client and on the grounds for a client relationship** (reason for seeking care, diagnoses, external cause, type of accident, need for care on date of admission/discharge/count, procedures and interventions, decision on long-term care (yes/no), patient has an advanced cardiac condition (yes/no), patient is a psychiatric patient (yes/no), number of home days)
- **Data on discharge from care** (date of discharge, further treatment/which services, code and code extension of the institution of further treatment)
- **Additional data on procedures involving patients with advanced cardiac condition** (type of procedure, class of procedure, functional capacity (New York Heart Association (NYHA) Classification, risk score, complications, level of urgency)
- **Additional data on psychiatric patients** (route of admission to psychiatric inpatient care, length of involuntary care as care days, number of admissions to psychiatric inpatient care, GAS at admission and discharge, medication, coercive measures, meetings with relatives or others)

Basic data in a care notification for Register for Primary Health Care Visits (Avohilmo) covers the following topics:

- **Basic data about the service event** (client's personal identity number, client's municipality of residence, postcode of the client's place of residence, service provider, service unit of the service provider, event record code)
- **Data on contact type and assessment of the need for treatment** (date and time of contact, date and time of assessment of the need for treatment, occupation (person assessing the need for treatment), urgency of care, type of visit, outcome of assessment of the need for treatment)
- **Appointment data** (date and time of appointment booking, date and time of booked appointment, occupation, service type, contact type)
- **Service event data** (date and time, service event starting time, date and time, service event closing time, occupation (person delivering care), service type, contact type, client group, urgency, type of visit, first visit, reasons for visit/diagnoses, external cause (accidents), type of accident, procedures and interventions, vaccination data and medication data, dental health care (DMFT index, CPI index))
- **Follow-up care** (service event cancellation, reason for service event cancellation)

8.4.3.2 Cancer Registry

The nationwide registration of cancer cases in Finland began in 1953 (<https://cancerregistry.fi/information/data-protection-notice/>). Registration has been compulsory from 1961 onwards. Health care organisations in Finland have statutory obligation to provide information on every cancer case or strong suspicion of cancer to the Cancer Registry. The data controller of the Cancer Registry is the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL), based on national legislation, but the data processor and technical administrator is the Finnish Cancer Registry maintained by the Finnish Cancer Society.

The data content of the register is as follows:

- Personal ID
- Gender

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- Date of diagnosis of cancer
- Age at diagnosis
- Primary site of cancer based on ICD-O-3 code (International Classification of Diseases for Oncology)
- Histological type of cancer based on ICD-O-3 code
- Number of total cancer diagnoses for person at current diagnosis date
- International Classification of Childhood Cancer, 3rd edition (ICCC3)
- Behaviour of cancer (i.e. benign / semimalignant / carcinoma in situ / malignant)
- Cancer laterality
- Basis method of diagnosis (i.e. clinical examination, surgery, X-ray, histology from primary tumour or metastase, autopsy (microscopic or macroscopic), cytology, specific laboratory)
- Stage of cancer at diagnosis
- Primary treatment
- Patient status at the register close date (i.e. alive, dead due to cancer, dead due to other cause, lost to follow-up) (requires permission also from Statistics Finland)
- Autopsy information (requires permission also from Statistics Finland)
- Cause of death based on ICD-7 codes (until 1995) or ICD-10 codes (from 1996 onwards) (requires permission also from Statistics Finland)
- Date of exit from follow-up
- Municipality at time of diagnosis
- Municipality code recorded on year of diagnosis
- University hospital district
- Hospital district

The classification of the cancer cases is based on the following classifications:

- From 1955 to 2007 ICD-7 codes (have been converted automatically by means of a translation matrix into ICD-O-3 codes)
- Since 2008 ICD-O-3 codes

8.4.3.3 Medical Prescription Register(s)

The Social Insurance Institution of Finland (Kela) compiles the registers on reimbursements for prescription medicines (i.e. reimbursement and purchases of medicines qualifying for an on-the-spot reimbursement at the pharmacy (prescription file) and on entitlements to special rates of reimbursement in respect of medicines (https://www.kela.fi/en_US/web/en/description-of-statistics18)).

Information on reimbursements and purchases for prescription medicines has been available from 1995 onwards. It should be noted that the information is limited to outpatients only. The data content is as follows:

- ATC (Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical classification and defined daily doses, Finnish Medicines Agency) code of medicine
- Drug identification number
- Number of packages purchased
- Reimbursement category of medicines

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- Diseases conferring an entitlement to special rate of reimbursement to medicines with limited reimbursability (three-digit code, available at Kela's website)
- Medicine expenses
- Reimbursement for medicine expenses
- Extra reimbursement for medicine expenses
- Patients' contribution to medicine expenses
- Purchase date of medicine
- Electronic prescription
- Date / renewal date of the prescription
- Physician specialisation (National Supervisory Authority for Welfare and Health, Valvira),
- Drug identification number of medicines prescribed by physician, if the product has been substituted for equivalent drug product
- The reason why drug product has not been substituted for equivalent drug product although it would have been possible (eg. physician/patient has refused the substitution)
- The expenses of which reimbursement has been calculated
- Dose dispensing (letter code)
- Patient's municipality of residence (numeric code)
- Patient's hospital district (numeric code)

Information on entitlements to special rates of reimbursement respect of medicines has been available from 1964 onwards. Data content of the register covers the following topics:

- Disease/medicine conferring an entitlement to special rate of reimbursement (three-digit code, available at the Social Insurance Institution of Finland's website)
- The period of the reimbursement entitlement (starting to ending time (yyyymm))
- Diagnosis of the disease (ICD-code) (comprehensively available from 2000 onwards)

8.4.3.4 Causes of Death Register

The register includes information on causes of death from 1936 onwards based on the death certificates that are complemented with data on deaths from the Population Information System of the Population Register (http://www.stat.fi/til/ksyyt/index_en.html). The data controller is Statistics Finland which annually produces causes of death data of permanent residents of Finland. The causes of death data from the previous year are available at the end of the following year. The data from 1936 to 1968 are presented in table format in paper publications, while from 1969 onwards, the data are available in a time series database.

The data content is as follows:

- Causes of death according to age, sex and other demographic factors
- Circumstances of the death

The classification of causes of death is based on the following classifications:

- Since 1996: the 10th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10)
- From 1987 to 1995: the national classification of diseases 1987
- From 1969 to 1986: the international classification ICD-8

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8.4.3.5 Other register(s)

The Population Register Centre in Finland and local register officers maintain The Population Information System which includes the basic information about Finnish citizens and foreign citizens residing permanently in Finland. Further, it also includes information about buildings, construction projects, residences and real estate. The data content is as follows:

Personal data:

- Name
- Personal identity code
- Address
- Citizenship
- Native language
- Family relations
- Date of birth and death (if applicable)

Building data:

- The building code
- Location
- Owner
- Area
- Facilities
- Network connections
- Intended use
- Year of construction

Statistics Finland also provides information on educational level and socioeconomic status.

8.4.4 How record linkage is conducted

In general, carrying out medical research needs approval by the relevant regional Ethical committee and a written informed consent from all participants. Further, to access data in confidential registers and records for research purposes requires authorisation application to be submitted and approved by data controller.

The procedures to obtain access to the register information and to perform record linkage related to health and social data changed in May 2019 in connection with enacting the Act of Secondary use of Health and Social Data

(<https://stm.fi/documents/1271139/1365571/The+Act+on+the+Secondary+Use+of+Health+and+Social+Data/a2bca08c-d067-3e54-45d1-18096de0ed76/The+Act+on+the+Secondary+Use+of+Health+and+Social+Data.pdf>). This legislation also takes into consideration the requirement of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

If data is requested only from one register, the data request will be made for this specific register owner (controller) unless this register owner has delegated the authorisation to provide access to their data to the central data permit authority called Findata (<https://www.findata.fi/en/>). If data is needed from several different registers, the request is done through the Findata. Findata is a health and social data permit authority operating independently in the Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (THL). It was established on 1st April 2020 to provide a one-stop shop for the

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secondary use of health and social data. The activities are based on the Act on the Secondary Use of Health and Social Data (552/2019).

The data obtained from a single register owner (controller) is usually delivered with identity numbers. Data controllers require a confidentiality agreement to be signed by all of the researchers and other persons who come into contact with encoded or pseudonymised data. Data provided by Findata has to be analysed in a secure analytic environment (<https://www.findata.fi/en/services/services-for-customers/>).

8.4.4.1 Procedures for a single register owner (controller)

Regarding **THL**'s registers, the application form and its appendices should be submitted by e-mail (kirjaamo-at-thl.fi) or by mail to Registry of THL. In brief, the applicant should fill in the following information in the application: title of the study, person in charge of the study, contact information, reason for applying for permission (i.e. new application/ application to extend the previous application), purposes for which the requested data are to be used, estimated total duration of the study and publication plan. Further, the following appendices are obligatory: non-disclosure agreements of persons processing the research data (a separate form), a description of the research data to be compiled (a separate form), a research plan and a draft description of the scientific research data file (template available on the website of the Office of the Data Protection Ombudsman). In some cases, additional appendices are required (e.g. opinion of an Ethics Committee).

After THL receives the application, the documents are checked and, if necessary, further information may be requested from the applicant. When all the necessary information is received, THL either grants or refuses authorisation. After receiving authorisation to access data, the material is requested from THL by e-mail (tietopyynnöt-at-thl.fi).

The fee for a decision on research authorisation in Finland is €750 and on international research authorisation €1000 as of March 2021. Further, the fee for research data sampling is determined by the working hours required to retrieve and process the data.

For detailed information, please see the website:

<https://thl.fi/en/web/thlfi-en/statistics/information-for-researchers/authorisation-application>.

To access the information generated by **Kela** (the Social Insurance Institution of Finland), the application form (online form available at Kela's website) and its supporting documents should be sent by e-mail to Kela (kirjaamo at kela.fi). Required supporting documents are an up-to-date research plan, a specification document, a description of the scientific research data file, a publication plan, confidentiality agreements and invoicing details. Applications may also have to include copies of permits from other organisations, statements by research ethics committees, and copies of the informed consent form and cover letter. It should be noted that if the purpose is to combine register data with data gathered directly from the research subjects (e.g. by interviews or surveys), either the consent form signed by the subjects or the information notice must state clearly what types of data obtained from the Social Insurance Institution (Kela) will be combined with such information.

The application is processed and evaluated by the Kela's Administration and Facility Management Unit. The Unit has estimated that an evaluation process takes approximately 2-3 months.

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The fees for the decision are as follows (value-added tax is added to the fees):

- New permit or permit covering a large dataset: €1000
- As above except if related to a thesis: €150
- Extension of a permit: €300

The application process and data delivery are free of charge to government authorities which have a right specified in law to obtain such data free of charge. For others, the charge is based on time used (€121 per hour).

After a favorable decision and permission to access the data, Kela's unit for administration and statistics will retrieve the requested data. For detailed information, please see the website:

<https://www.kela.fi/web/en/research-data-requests>

To access the information collected by **Statistics Finland**, the application for a license to use statistical data and its appendices (pledge of secrecy of holder of permission to use data and research plan) must be addressed to the Registrar's Office of Statistics Finland (postal address: FI-00022 Statistics Finland) or be submitted via email (Kirjaamo at stat.fi). The application process will take from a week to months depending on the application. After a favorable decision, an agreement concerning the details and fees of the data delivery should be signed by both parties (Statistics Finland and recipient). Statistics Finland will charge €105 per hour for preparing the data for research purposes. The data is either delivered to the research group's organisation or analysed via a remote access service.

For detailed information, please see the website:

https://www.stat.fi/meta/tietosuoja/kayttolupa_en.html

8.4.4.2 Procedures for Findata

When data from more than one register owner (controller) is needed, permission and data request is made to Findata. Data request is submitted through online form (<https://www.findata.fi/en/services/data-requests/>). An application can be submitted by only those who have a personal identity code registered in the Finnish Population Information System. In addition to the application form, descriptions on the content of the statistics, the data to be extracted, restrictions to the data, and the data sources, i.e. registers, are requested in the data request form.

Data is by default provided in pseudonymised format unless there are specific reasons to obtain identifiable data. For data use, secure platform at Findata should be used.

The fee (<https://www.findata.fi/en/services/pricing/>) for a data request decision is €1000. If the data is needed for a thesis, the fee is €250. In addition to the permission fee, data processing fee of €115 per hour will be charged as well as an annual fee for the use of remote access environment. There are different environmental fees depending on data size varying between €187.5–€460/month. On top of these, costs for extracting and delivering data by data controllers are charged.

8.4.5 Outcome of the record linkage study

The DILGOM 2007 data has been linked to the Care Register for Health Care, Register for Primary Health Care Visits, Cancer Register, registers on reimbursements for prescription medicines (i.e. reimbursement and purchases of medicines qualifying for an on-the-spot reimbursement at the pharmacy (prescription file)) and on entitlements to special rates of reimbursement in respect of medicines, and Causes of Death Register to obtain information about disease history, use and

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purchase of prescribed medications and follow-up data on morbidity and mortality. Retrieved disease history and follow-up information has not been limited to any specific disease but information on all hospital visits and deaths has been obtained.

Also information about educational level, occupational level and socio-economic position has been obtained from the Statistics Finland.

Until now, no analyses have been performed using information on PFAS and register data but this possibility should be further explored in the future. On the other hand, combination of survey data and register information has been used for other health related analyses such as a recent study looking how different risk factors (obesity, smoking) affect the cancer risk (lung cancer, colorectal cancer) (Pitkäniemi 2020).

8.4.6 Possible limitations/problems encountered/expected

Occasionally there have been substantial delays in obtaining permissions for data use and actual data due to limited resources within data controller. GDPR has also resulted in that register owners (controllers) are more strict on wording of the informed consent even for older studies for which informed consent had been obtained before the era of the GDPR. This has caused unnecessary delays in obtaining linked data.

Now when the main responsibility for providing permissions and register data was moved to Findata, this process should get more fluent. Findata has a limitation for the response time set on the Act on Secondary Use of Health and Social Data. In principle, Findata should provide data use permission within 3 months from the date the full application has been provided unless the request includes several registers and is very complicated. After the permission has been provided, the data should be provided within 30 days after the detailed data request has been obtained.

8.5 Norway

8.5.1 Description of the selected HBM study

The Norwegian Mother and Child Cohort Study (MoBa) is a prospective population-based pregnancy cohort study conducted by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (Magnus 2016). The participants were recruited from all over Norway in 1999-2008, and 41% of the invited women consented to participate. The cohort now includes some 114,500 children, 95,200 mothers and 75,200 fathers. The mothers answered questionnaires three times during pregnancy, when the child was 6, 18 and 36 months, and also at irregular timepoints after this (at child age 5, 7, 8 years). The father answered a separate questionnaire in mid-pregnancy.

MoBa includes information from The Medical Birth Registry of Norway, which comprises data on all births in Norway, and has information about pregnancy, delivery, and health of the mother and the neonate for all births in Norway (Irgens 2000).

For this case study, a sub-study within MoBa, MoBa-ETox, will be described. MoBa-ETox is a part of the first phase of the Norwegian Human Environmental Biomonitoring Program and includes 2,999 pregnant women with available blood and urine samples from MoBa. Essential and toxic metals in blood (including Cd, Hg and Pb) have been analysed in addition to some vitamins, hormones and correction factors (Caspersen 2019).

Eligibility of participants in MoBa ETox also required that they had been included in the HARVEST study, where ~11,000 triads (mothers, fathers and children) in MoBa have been genotyped. Additional inclusion criteria were i) available data from questionnaire 2-6 or father questionnaire (questionnaire 1 was already a criterion for HARVEST inclusion), and ii) available maternal

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plasma, urine and whole blood samples. The Norwegian Environmental Biobank subsample includes women who were pregnant in 2002-2008.

The aim of the Human Environmental Biobank Norway, MoBa ETox sub-study, is to obtain knowledge about nutritional and heavy metal status during pregnancy and to examine their importance for mother and child's health later in life.

8.5.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

The present-day procedure for acquiring data from MoBa-Etox is a four-stage exercise:

1. A detailed project protocol is required as a basis for the three following stages. The study protocol should include information about the research question, methods, data sources and a variable list. An exact description of exposures, confounders and outcomes is required. Tentative titles for future publications and co-authors are an advantage.
2. All studies, whether using questionnaire data or biobank material, have to start with obtaining ethical approval from one of Norway's seven Regional Ethical Committees. The activities of the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REC) are founded on the Norwegian law on research ethics and medical research. The seven regional committees are made up of people with different professional backgrounds, lay representatives and representatives for patient groups. The committees are appointed by the Ministry of Education and Research for a four-year term. Applications for new projects have deadlines nine times per year. Applicants from a research institution outside of Norway must have a partner affiliated with a *Norwegian research* institution, and *research* competence corresponding to PhD level. Applications for project changes have no deadlines and are handled continuously. All changes, included letting new researchers get access to data, have to be approved by REC. The application to REC includes the detailed study protocol, see point 1.
3. Then a DPIA approval is needed. (*Data Protection Impact Assessment - DPIA*). The Norwegian Data Protection Authority (Datatilsynet) has made public a list of processing activities that it considers likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of data subjects and that **always** will require a DPIA. Such an assessment must be carried out before the processing of personal data is initiated. The principal investigator (PI) is responsible for getting a DPIA done. At NIPH, a Department Director decides if a DPIA is necessary. If yes, the PI is responsible to fill in the DPIA, and it has to be reviewed and approved by i) the internal privacy ombudsman (personvernombudet) and ii) by the person assigned within each division at NIPH.
4. Finally, the application for access to data from MoBa has to be filled in. For details about application for access to data, see <https://www.fhi.no/en/more/access-to-data/applying-for-access-to-data/>. Both the Ethical Approval and completed/approved DPIA has to be included in the application. When the application has been approved, the PI has to fill in a collaboration agreement and a data transfer agreement, while MoBa administration drafts a Material transfer agreement (MTA) with MoBa. When all these agreements have been signed, the MoBa data unit in Bergen will be responsible for preparing the data.

If a project has international employees, access to data can only be provided via a secure access platform, for example the Service for Sensitive Data (TSD) at the University of Oslo (<https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>). Exceptions to this must be justified separately.

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The process of getting through these four stages has hitherto taken 1.5 - 2 years per project.

Requests for data linkages will affect time spent in case processing and the cost. As case manager, the MoBa data unit will, in addition to writing scripts and extracting data, spend time in dialogue with the other registries. You can also expect the applications process to take longer if you want to link data from several sources.

Figure 9: Flow of data for record linkage in MoBA

The process of linking data sets can be performed in different ways. MoBa has a central data unit in Bergen and uses centralised linkage. Linkage between different sources is possible because the personal identifier is replaced by a project-specific serial number. With centralised linkage, the information from several sources is gathered at one source and given a series of new serial number that goes across all data sources. You receive all files at the same time and can link these files using the serial number. Illustration of centralised data linkage is provided in Figure 9.

8.5.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

8.5.3.1 Medical Birth Registry of Norway

Web-information: <https://www.fhi.no/en/hn/health-registries/medical-birth-registry-of-norway/medical-birth-registry-of-norway/>

The Medical Birth Registry of Norway (MBRN) is a national health register containing information about all births in Norway. It was established January 1, 1967. All maternity units in Norway must notify births to the MBRN. The notification form includes the name and personal identity number of the child and parents, as well as information about maternal health before and during pregnancy, and any complications during pregnancy or birth. This includes information about medicine use in pregnancy, labour interventions, birth complications, maternal complications after birth, whether the baby is born alive, any diagnoses in the child or evidence of congenital abnormalities. Information about the mother's occupation, smoking and alcohol habits are only registered if the mother consents. This also applies to information about assisted conception. All pregnancies ending after week 12 are notifiable to the MBRN, including terminations after week 12.

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The Norwegian Institute of Public Health manages the MBRN and is the register and data controller. Collection and processing of health data in the Medical Birth Registry is governed by the MBRN-regulations (<https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2001-12-21-1483>) (in Norwegian only).

Electronic notification of births

The country's maternity units are responsible for notifying births to the MBRN. The Ministry of Health and Care Services, pursuant to the MBRN Regulations, requires health authorities to notify births electronically. The aim is to streamline and improve the reporting quality of birth notification. Any systems that will provide electronic notification of birth must be approved by the MBRN.

Assisted conception

The MBRN is also responsible for collecting, registering and analysing data for children born following assisted conception in Norway. All public and private institutions that are licensed to carry out assisted conception must notify the MBRN about treatments that result in pregnancy. The purpose is to identify whether assisted conception represents an increased risk for health problems during pregnancy.

Links to other registers

To ensure data quality, the MBRN is routinely linked with the Central Population Register. For the production of statistics and in connection with research projects, the MBRN can be linked with the other central health registries (Cancer Registry of Norway, Cause of Death Registry, Norwegian Prescription Database, Norwegian Surveillance System for Communicable Diseases, the Central Tuberculosis Registry and the Norwegian Immunisation Registry).

Access to research data and statistics

The MBRN will help to make data easily accessible and has a designated section that retrieves and prepares data from the birth register for researchers and others.

8.5.3.2 Norwegian Patient Registry

Web page: <https://www.helsedirektoratet.no/tema/statistikk-registre-og-rapporter/helsedata-og-helseregistre/norsk-pasientregister-npr>

The Norwegian Patient Registry is owned by The Directorate of Health and Care Services. It registers information from the specialist health services.

- Person information (unique personal identification number or other id-identification number, municipality)
- Administrative information (reference person, treating institution, consultation and/or referral to hospital, patient rights, time of death etc).
- Medical information (subject area, diagnosis, diagnosis codes, time of start and termination of treatment, payment rate, information on use of force, drug use etc)
- Social information (living conditions, need of care etc)
- Information on accidents and injuries (reason for contact/injury/severity), activity at time of injury, place of injury, timepoint of injury, employment area)
- Information from
- Information from the Emergency Medical Communication Centre (AMK-sentral) (timepoint, route, prehospital time response, happening- end delivery place, sex and address)

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8.5.3.3 The Cancer Registry of Norway

Web page: <https://www.kreftregisteret.no/en/General/About-the-Cancer-Registry/>

The Cancer Registry of Norway collects data and produce statistics of the cancer prevalence in Norway and has an extensive research activity. It has also got the administrative responsibility for the public screening programmes in Norway - the Norwegian Breast Cancer Screening Programme and the Norwegian Cervical Cancer Screening Programme.

The Cancer Registry of Norway was established in 1951 and is thus one of the oldest national cancer registries in the world. This, combined with the unique personal identification number used in Norway, makes the Cancer Registry's data suitable, also internationally; by establishing new knowledge through research and spreading information on cancer.

The Cancer Registry of Norway is part of South-Eastern Norway Regional Health Authority and is organised as an independent institution under Oslo University Hospital Trust, with its own board.

All medical doctors in the country are instructed by law to notify new cancer cases to the Cancer Registry. Cancer must be notified in case of cancer suspicion, even without a verified cancer diagnosis, and also if cancer is first diagnosed by autopsy. In case of doubt, a notification must be sent.

8.5.3.4 Medical prescription registries

Norwegian Prescription Database (NorPD) (<https://www.fhi.no/en/hn/health-registries/norpd/>) gives an overview over all prescription drugs dispensed from pharmacies in Norway. Drugs used in hospitals, nursing homes and for animals are also included.

NorPD contains a complete listing of all prescription drugs dispensed by pharmacies in Norway since 2004. Drugs supplied to hospitals and nursing homes are also partly included, but not at an individual level. The database also contains information about prescription of drugs to animals.

All the pharmacies in Norway register prescriptions electronically, and the information is sent in monthly reports to NorPD (via Statistics Norway). The patient's personal ID number and the prescribers ID number are replaced by a unique pseudonym by Statistics Norway. This makes it possible to link drug use to individuals without knowing their identity.

Personal information is not disclosed from the NorPD. The database is governed by the national regulation of 17 October 2003 about the collection and processing of health data in the Norwegian Prescription Database (see below).

The legal basis for the NorPD is the Regulation "Forskrift om innsamling og behandling av helseopplysninger i Reseptbasert legemiddelregister (Reseptregisteret)". The aims of the NorPD are described in § 1-3; to collect and process data on drug consumption by humans and animals to:

1. Describe drug use patterns, highlighting changes over time.
2. Promote and facilitate research and reviews of the safety and effectiveness of the drug use.
3. Serve as a management tool for the authorities in order to ensure prescribing quality in addition to general surveillance, control and planning.
4. Give the prescribers a basis for internal control, as part of an audit method to improve the quality of prescribing practices.

Use and delivery of data from the NorPD is evaluated according to the aims listed above.

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8.5.3.5 Norwegian Cause of Death Registry

The Norwegian Institute of Public Health is data controller (<https://www.fhi.no/en/hn/health-registries/cause-of-death-registry/>) and (<https://www.fhi.no/hn/helseregistre-og-registre/dodsarsaksregisteret/dodsarsaksregisteret2/>) of the Norwegian Causes of Death Registry which has information about persons who were in Norway when they died, or at the time of death were registered as citizens of Norway but died abroad. The register forms the basis for the yearly causes of death statistics published by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health.

The aim of the Register is to survey causes of death over time. Thus one can follow the development of mortality for heart infarction, cancer, accidents or suicide. Through data from the Cause of Death Register one can survey the health situation of the population, control the quality of our health services and study causes of disease.

Norway is obliged to publish official statistics on causes of death. All deaths are reported by a physician who fills in a death notice.

Researchers and others can apply for data from the Causes of Death Registry via an application at www.helsedata.no.

In the Norwegian Mother, Father and Child Cohort Study, facilitation of the data file including - linkage - additional variables in the dataset - changes in the data file made available costs NOK 1087/hour (approximately 110 euros/hour). Adding to this comes a price for receiving data from the Health registries, e.g. the Cancer Registry of Norway requires a minimum of Euro 1000 to facilitate access to data.

8.6 Sweden

8.6.1 Description of the selected HBM studies

From Sweden two alternative studies were selected to be presented (A and B).

Study A. An example study that is already published 2015 (Skerfving 2015). The study was chosen since it provides an excellent example of how historical HBM data on lead exposure could be utilised for linkage to data that provide a proxy for cognitive function.

The study included children age 7-12 who lived in or around the cities of Landskrona and Trelleborg, two towns in Southern Sweden, between 1978 and 2007.

Every year from 1978 to 2007, all children in the selected school classes were invited and out of them around 100 boys and girls provided blood samples. This number constituted about 60% of the potentially eligible participants.

The aim of the example study was to assess the associations of low-level lead exposure in early childhood and teenage cognitive performance. Each child was questioned about parents' smoking habits and own hobbies, in particular those involving Pb exposures (for example, shooting air guns).

Study B. We selected a planned study to illustrate the process of combining Human Biomonitoring data with Swedish register data; Lead or cadmium exposure and risk of myocardial infarction, stroke or kidney disease.

The study will include participants in Northern Sweden Health and Disease Study (The Västerbotten Intervention Program or the Northern Sweden MONICA Study). Collection of questionnaires, medical data and blood samples was performed 1986-2014, when the participants were 25-74 years old.

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Those within Northern Sweden Health and Disease Study with previously performed chemical analysis of lead and/or cadmium in blood (N≈3000 available in year 2020; the Environment Pollutant Cohort) are available for the study.

The aim is to assess associations between exposure to lead or cadmium and risk of myocardial infarction, stroke or kidney disease.

8.6.2 Ethical and data protection approvals

To conduct record linkage, participant's informed consent, ethical approval and a research plan are required in the application to the record holder (i.e. Statistics Sweden or the National Board of Health and Welfare).

Study A. The study was initially approved by the regional ethical review board at Lund University. At blood sampling, the parents gave written informed consent and the children gave oral consent. Additional approval was obtained for record linkage to Statistics Sweden.

The study was approved by the Ethics Committee at Lund University as well as at Statistics Sweden. According to the legislation, all information on effect parameters was processed in a temporary data file at Statistics Sweden, and thus, the authors only obtained de-identified (i.e. pseudomised) data, according to the legislation at the record holder (Statistics Sweden).

Study B. The study was approved by the regional ethical review board in Umeå, Sweden (Dnr 2015-464-31 "Environmental pollutants and health in the population of Norrbotten and Västerbotten – a study in a subcohort within the large biobank cohorts VIP, MONICA and the Mammography Screening Project"). The participants gave written informed consent to participate in future research at the health examination.

The ethical approval from 2015 included record linkage to disease registers in general. Additional permissions are needed from the register holders; Statistics Sweden and National Board of Health and Welfare when applying for data from there.

According to the legislation, the research needs to be started within 2 years of the ethical approval, but there is no time limit for finalisation. The research related to this ethical approval started directly after we got the approval. The first step was to combine data from individuals with participation in any of the three cohorts within Northern Sweden Health and Disease study, and with chemical analysis performed for any environmental pollutants in blood or urine = The Environmental Pollutant Cohort. Thus, the 2-year limit of starting the research was fulfilled.

For the planned study those with data on lead and/ or cadmium in blood were selected and a datafile was created including the relevant background information from the health examinations.

8.6.3 Available and relevant administrative registers for record linkage

Study A. There are high-quality national registries of school performance and IQ test results for teenagers in Sweden. An HBM study on lead exposure was conducted between 1978 and 2007 on 3176 primary school children in Southern Sweden. Each child's unique personal identification number was used to link to various national registers. The aim was to assess measures of school performance and IQ as a function of the blood lead in childhood accounting for socioeconomic factors.

School performance. Data on performance at the end of the subjects' nine-year compulsory schooling (usually at age 16) was collected from the national register at Statistics Sweden. The IQ data were received from the National Service Administration and the Military Archives.

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Covariates: Included questionnaire information obtained by the participants. From Statistics Sweden, additional information on the children's and parents' country of birth, parents' education and total family income (used as an index of SES) were obtained. From the National Service Administration and the Military Archives, the researchers received information on the over-all IQ of the children's fathers.

Study B. Relevant outcomes for the planned study (myocardial infarction, stroke and kidney disease) can be identified through disease registers administered by the National Board of Health and Welfare (Cause of Death Register, National Patient Register (in- and outpatient)). Additional relevant data for the planned studies are available in Medical prescription register (also administered by the National Board of Health and Welfare) and additional socioeconomic data from registers administered by Statistics Sweden (register of total population, longitudinal integrated database for health insurance and labour market studies (LISA) register of income).

Most of the nation-wide health-related registers in Sweden have a very long tradition and have a very high coverage (almost 100%). A few registers were established more recently such as the Prescribed Drug Register (2005). All registers contain the individual person identification number. The national patient register contains diagnosis according to the international classification of diseases (ICD-10 codes), and dates of diagnosis. The Cause of Death Register contains information on sex, date of birth, cause of death (ICD-coding) and date of death, residence, and marital status. The Prescribed Drug Register contains information on prescribed drugs including the dates of prescription, dosage and whether the drug was collected from the pharmacy by the patient.

8.6.4 How record linkage is conducted

Study A. Each child's unique personal registration number was used to link to the registers.

The researchers apply for linkage and after the record holder (Statistics Sweden) approve the linkage (2nd ethical review), the researchers provide the record holder with the personal registration number. The cost is 1100 SEK (about 110€) per hour of work linking the data. The whole process depends on the staff availability and the number of requests, but in total the process takes approximately slightly less than one year. After the record linkage has been done, the research group get pseudomised data without any identifier. The record holder performs the linkage to all the relevant registers available. If additional linkage is needed outside, the record holder contributes to that linkage. The record holder could – if asked – store the key to the identification for later updating.

Study B. The researcher applies for data from the register holder/holders. If approved by the register holders, the researcher provides the research holder with a datafile containing the HBM- and health data and a personal registration number. In this case Statistics Sweden and the National Board of Health and Welfare collaborate and Statistics Sweden perform the linkage with the registers and communicate with the researcher. The researcher will get a pseudomised datafile without any identifier back.

No major changes in procedures of record linkage occurred due to the new EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

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Detailed guidelines how to do the record linkage with different Swedish registries can be found online at:

- Statistics Sweden <https://www.scb.se/en/services/guidance-for-researchers-and-universities/> Inpatient and cause of Death Register <https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/en/statistics-and-data/registers/>
- Prescribed Drug Register <https://www.socialstyrelsen.se/en/statistics-and-data/registers/register-information/the-swedish-prescribed-drug-register/>

8.6.5 Outcome of the record linkage study

Study A. We also obtained supporting SES information from register.

Study B. In addition to the relevant outcomes from disease registers at the National Board of Health and Welfare, supporting SES information was applied for from registers held by Statistics Sweden:

- register of total population: migration, immigration, country of birth;
- longitudinal integrated database for health insurance and labour market studies (LISA): socioeconomic group, county, occupation/occupations, education; register of income (IoT).

The application was sent to Statistics Sweden in September 2019, with the prognosis that it would take four months to be assigned an administrator. The researcher was assigned an administrator at Statistics Sweden in the middle of January 2020, so this time plan was correct. After this communication started between the researcher and the administrator about the project.

8.6.6 Possible limitations/problems encountered/expected

Applying for and performing register linkage is a long process.

The data must be analysed and stored at a location with high security. It should not be possible to download the data to personal computers/laptops. Only a limited number of researchers should have access to the data. No back-identification of participants is allowed.

Study B. The researcher was assigned an administrator (January 2020) four months after the application was sent to Statistics Sweden (September 2019), which was according to the expected time plan. The administrator at Statistics Sweden judged that the approved ethical application from 2015 was not specific enough. A more detailed description of from which registers information will be applied for as well as which variables will be applied for was requested. Therefore, an additional ethical application was sent to the Swedish Ethical Review Authority (which replaced the regional ethical review boards from 2019) in March 2020. The answer was received in May 2020 with the decision that the additional application was denied, with the motivation that the changes were to extensive. It was recommended to write a new full ethical application for the study.

The plan now is that the researcher will write a new ethical application to the Swedish Ethical Review Board, including all relevant registers with name as well as which variables will be applied for. However, it was decided to wait with this study, because additional chemical analysis on lead and cadmium in blood (n~1400) are planned in studies within Northern Sweden Health and Disease study. These can be included in the Environmental Pollutant Cohort and also in the planned study, to increase power.

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9 Discussion and conclusions

From the questionnaire provided to the National Hub Coordinators we have learned that availability of health-related administrative registers varies substantially between the countries. In most countries at least birth register, a causes of death register and a cancer register exists. Also registers on hospitalisations are commonly available. Obviously at this point we have to remember, that our inventory may be incomplete and some information for specific countries may be missing.

Most of the countries do have a national personal identification code (PIC) which is also used by most of the available administrative registers in the country. In about half of the countries which do have this, PIC can also be used to conduct record linkage, but for another half of the countries, national legislation does not support this type of activities.

The case studies have demonstrated that conducting a record linkage of HBM/health studies to administrative registers is possible, but procedures vary between countries as well as availability of administrative registers.

In general, record linkage requires approval from the ethics committee as well as register owner, but it also has to be stated in the informed consent which participants have signed. Therefore, it is important to consider the possible need for record linkage already when planning studies and include these both to the informed consent but also to the original request of approval by the ethics committee.

As demonstrated by the case studies, obtaining additional information on disease history and follow-up of the disease onset through record linkage is very cost-effective. In most countries, obtaining this type of register data costs only a couple thousand euros. If for example, follow-up would be done through re-contacting all original study participants on an annual basis to obtain health disease history from the previous year that would be substantially more expensive due to salary costs of the people doing the re-contacting.

In most countries record linkage also provides very good coverage for the information obtained from the administrative registers. For example, in the Nordic countries as well as in Czech Republic where both HBM/health studies and administrative registers are systematically using national personal identification codes, coverage of the register data is close to 100%.

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Part C: Potential health effects of the priority substances

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2 Executive summary

Several environmental chemicals are associated with different health outcomes. Many of these health outcomes contribute substantially to the disease burden in Europe. Therefore, it is important to understand the association between chemicals and health and how to measure different health outcomes.

Based on the HBM4EU scoping documents and extended literature review, latest evidence on the associations between environmental chemicals and different health outcomes were compiled. For health outcomes also measurement guidelines are provided.

Although there is increasing evidence on observational HBM studies on humans, we still have need for new, relatively large studies on this domain using standardised data collection methods. Also more studies from Europe are needed since the current evidence is mainly based on studies from USA and Asia.

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3 Background for health outcomes and environmental chemical exposure

The aim of this work is to compile scientific knowledge on the associations between the chosen health outcomes and HBM4EU priority substances. The second aim is to present different measurement methods related to the health outcomes which can be used to facilitate the combining of HBM and health examination surveys. By collecting information about chemical exposure, its public health burden can be understood and further utilised in policy making and protection of the EU general public.

As already demonstrated in the HBM4EU Deliverable 11.3, Part C (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-11-3-report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-hbm-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guid/>), several chemicals have shown or are suspected to have adverse health effects for number of health outcomes. A common approach to study and report these adverse health effects is to take a specific chemical as a focal point and see which health outcomes it is known to be associated. In this report, we have turned the picture other way around, i.e. taking a specific health outcome to the focus and see which chemicals have adverse effects to this specific health outcome. This perspective would support public health approach when determining possible risk factors for health outcomes.

To collect the current scientific evidence, HBM4EU substance specific scoping documents were used, and extended literature searches were conducted among the health outcomes and priority substances. The search methodologies varied between the outcomes, as some health outcomes yielded more evidence than others. If several studies on a specific outcome had been published, focus was placed on systematic reviews and review articles and in reporting their findings. For health outcomes with less evidence, individual epidemiological studies were also included. Focus on possible vulnerable populations, such as foetuses, children or occupational exposure was additionally investigated to provide a comprehensive approach of the environmental chemical exposure and current public health evidence.

Human Biomonitoring is an important tool to assess human health burden caused by environmental chemicals. To deepen the understanding on the association of chemical exposure and specific health outcomes, future Human Biomonitoring studies should gather detailed health data using standardised methods. Standardised operating procedures (SOPs) for numerous health outcomes are available from the European Health Examination Survey (EHES) manual (<http://www.ehes.info/publications/index.htm>) as well as from previous HBM4EU Deliverable 11.3 (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-11-3-report-on-opportunities-and-obstacles-of-combining-hbm-and-health-studies-availability-of-health-studies-with-biological-samples-availability-of-administrative-registers-and-guid/>).

In the current report, recommendations on methods for assessing the health outcomes are discussed. In addition, questions recommended for the included outcomes from the HBM4EU standardised questionnaire, EHES questionnaire and European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) questionnaire have been compiled to Appendix 22.2.

It is widely recognised that the framework for legislation on chemicals in EU should be improved so that the legislation stipulates the inclusion of potential combination effects when assessing chemicals' risks. More knowledge is still needed before the risk posed by combination effects can be fully incorporated into the risk assessment of chemicals.

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4 Burden of selected health outcomes in Europe

Disability-adjusted life year (DALY) is a summary measure of disease burden. It combines the burden of both premature mortality and morbidity. One unit of DALY corresponds to one lost year of 'healthy' life (Department of information, evidence and research, 2018). For DALYs, years of life lost (YLL) due to premature mortality and years lost due to disability (YLD) are summed up. The DALY methods have been continuously developed in the framework of the Global Burden of Disease (GBD) Study (Department of information, evidence and research, 2018; GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2020).

DALYs for health outcomes covered in this deliverable were explored using the GBD Results Tool (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2020), and the results for selected outcomes are compiled in Table 3. In 2019, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) were the leading cause of disease burden causing about 24% of all DALYs in Europe, followed by cancers (17% of DALYs).

Table 3: The disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) for selected health outcomes in Europe in 2019¹ among all age groups, men and women combined unless otherwise specified.

Health outcomes	Health outcome for DALYs	Number of DALYs ²	Percent ³	Rate per 100,000 ⁴
Diabetes	Diabetes mellitus (type 1 and 2)	8,449,667	3.0	995
Neurological development	Neurological disorders	16,220,382	5.8	1,910
	Alzheimer's disease and other dementias	5,847,083	2.1	689
	Parkinson's disease	1,327,668	0.5	156
	Autism spectrum disorders (ASD)	567,560	0.2	67
	Attention-deficit / hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)	96,625	0.03	11
Liver function	Total burden related to non-alcoholic fatty liver disease	615,026	0.2	72
	Cirrhosis and other chronic liver diseases	5,688,518	2.0	670
Renal function	Chronic kidney disease	3,289,302	1.2	387
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)	COPD	7,301,683	2.6	860
Asthma	Asthma	1,843,323	0.7	217
Skin irritation and inflammation	Dermatitis	1,198,450	0.4	141
Reproductive health	Male infertility (among men)	33,869	0.02	8
	Female infertility (among women)	47,709	0.04	11

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Health outcomes	Health outcome for DALYs	Number of DALYs ²	Percent ³	Rate per 100,000 ⁴
Cardiovascular disease (CVD)	CVD	66,487,684	23.9	7,830
	Hypertensive heart disease	2,640,259	1.0	311
	Coronary heart disease	34,385,736	12.3	4,049
	Stroke	18,836,539	6.8	2,218
Cancer	Total cancers	46,685,131	16.8	5,498
	Leukemia	1,640,006	0.59	193
	Tracheal, bronchus and lung cancer	9,988,808	3.6	1,176
	Colon and rectum cancer	5,762,063	2.1	679
	Kidney cancer	1,303,377	0.5	153
	Kidney cancer	176,829	0.1	21
	Thyroid cancer	1,199,008	0.4	141
	Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	2,357,905	1.6	572
	Prostate cancer (among men)	3,892,322	2.9	891
	Breast cancer (among women)	1,261,096	0.9	289
Ovarian cancer (among women)				

¹The figures were obtained from the GBD Results Tool (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2020)

²The absolute numbers of DALYs

³Proportion of DALYs relative to DALYs for all causes

⁴DALYs per 100,000 population

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5 Introduction of environmental chemicals

In HBM4EU, two rounds of prioritisation of substances have been performed between years 2016-2018. For each of the selected priority substances, a scoping document has been prepared and is available at the HBM4EU website at <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/the-substances/>. In this chapter, a short description of the HBM4EU priority substances, exposure routes, possible vulnerable populations and measurement matrices is presented based on the scoping documents and current literature.

5.1 Acrylamide

Acrylamide (also called 2-propenamide, acrylic amide, ethylene carboxamide) is a low molecular weight, highly water soluble and organic compound manufactured for various uses in chemical industry. Acrylamide is biodegradable and not persistent and does not bioaccumulate. However, release to the environment may happen from the industrial use. Acrylamide is mostly found in water and soil, but rarely in air. In water and soil it is highly mobile; it does not bind to the soil but instead moves rapidly into the ground water. Glycidamide is the main metabolite, from which also the genotoxicity and carcinogenicity of acrylamide derive from (HBM4EU, 2020).

The industrial and laboratory use of acrylamide includes mainly the production of polyacrylamides, which are mostly used as flocculants to clarify drinking water and treat wastewater. Acrylamide and polyacrylamides are also applied in the production of dyes, organic chemicals, permanent-press fabrics, textiles, pulp and paper products. In addition to the chemical industry use, acrylamide is used in building and construction, health service and scientific research. Furthermore, it is generated during food processing at temperatures above 120 degrees Celsius under low moisture conditions as high temperatures in frying, roasting and baking cause acrylamide to produce. Food sources of acrylamide are typically coffee, fried potato products, biscuits, cereals, roasted nuts, olives in brine, prunes, dates, baby food and protein-based foods such as meat. Tobacco smoke is also a source of acrylamide. In Europe, acrylamide is manufactured or/and imported in 100 000-1000 000 tonnes per year (HBM4EU, 2020).

Exposure to humans occurs via inhalation, ingestion and dermal uptake. For the general population, the principal exposure pathway is oral uptake through ingestion of food, tobacco smoke and water. For the occupational groups, inhalation and dermal contact at the workplace where acrylamide is used or produced is an important exposure route. Transplacental exposure is also possible, but more research is needed. The most vulnerable groups to exposure are infants, toddlers, children and pregnant women. Furthermore, workers of the industrial sites and manufacturing are among the highly exposed groups (HBM4EU, 2020).

According to animal studies, acrylamide has neurotoxic, carcinogenic, genotoxic and mutagenic effects. Furthermore, immune toxicity and developmental toxicity as well as harmful reproductive effects (especially in males) have been suspected. In humans, occupational exposure has been shown to provoke neurotoxicity in the peripheral nervous system through prolonged or repeated exposure. In addition, there is a concern of carcinogenic effects of acrylamide in humans. Acrylamide may also adversely affect fetal growth and can cause allergic reactions in contact with the skin. Furthermore, acrylamide can act as an endocrine disruptor (HBM4EU, 2020).

Acrylamide and the main metabolite glycidamide can be measured in serum. Also urinary metabolites of acrylamide, mercapturic acids of acrylamide and glycidamide (AAMA and GAMA, respectively), and the hemoglobin adducts of acrylamide and glycidamide (AAVal and GAVal) are used as biomarkers (HBM4EU, 2020).

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At the EU level regulatory measures regarding acrylamide are established. Acrylamide is registered under REACH and is included in the candidate list of substances of very high concern (SVHC) due to its putative carcinogenic and mutagenic effects. Based on the EU and REACH regulations, acrylamide is prohibited in cosmetics and the use of acrylamide is banned in plastic materials and articles in contact with food. The EU has also settled mitigation measures and benchmark levels in order to decrease acrylamide levels in food (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.2 Aniline family

Aniline is the simplest member of the primary aromatic amines, and in anilines, one or more hydrogen atoms of the benzene ring are replaced by amino (-NH₂) group. Anilines consist of a variety of different substances and they are used in various industrial chemicals (HBM4EU, 2020). Worldwide production of anilines was expected to reach nearly 5.62 million tons in 2016 (Aster, 2014).

The common use of anilines is as an intermediate in the production of different chemicals such as rubber chemicals, dyes, some pesticides, drugs and polyurethane based polymers. It is also used in pH regulators and water treatment products. Anilines are created as degradation products from e.g. azo-colourants, pharmaceuticals and from aromatic isocyanates applied for polyurethane polymers, lacquers, foams and adhesives. Also smoking is regarded as a source of exposure. Occupational exposure is the main route of exposure, but also protecting the general population from the health hazards of anilines is needed. Vulnerable populations include workers, such as hairdressers (HBM4EU, 2020).

Anilines have significant health hazards. Carcinogenicity and genotoxicity are the main health concerns. In humans, aromatic amines can cause methemoglobinemia. Furthermore, anilines can cause skin and respiratory sensitisation. Anilines can be measured from urine or blood (HBM4EU, 2020). Some of the common anilines are introduced below.

4,4-methylenebis(2-chloroaniline) (MOCA) and 4,4-methylenedianiline (MDA) are authorised under the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) by the European Commission (EC). These are genotoxic carcinogens and a threshold for carcinogenic effects has not been established. Occupational exposure exists, but general population is not exposed to these substances. Both of them absorb easily through skin, and biomonitring from urine samples is the best method for the assessment of occupational exposure. MOCA is mostly used as a curing agent of the polyurethane products. MDA is one of the degradation products and main metabolites of methylene diphenyldiisocyanate (MDI, CAS 101-68-8), and also MDI exposure happens occupationally and urine is the measurement matrix applied. Diisocyanates are extensively used in different applications (e.g. foams, sealants, coatings). They are prominent occupational respiratory sensitisers causing e.g. asthma, and sensitisation can happen at very low exposure levels. The use of the diisocyanates MDI, TDI and HDI is suggested to be restricted in the EU, and this is done mainly by improving the control of diisocyanates use. Better understanding of the exposure routes of isocyanates, such as via air, direct skin contact, or via ingestion of aerosols is required in order to target risk management measures. P-Phenylenediamine (CAS 106-50-3) (p-PDA) is a typical contact allergen, which is present in cosmetics and e.g. in hair dyes and tattoo inks. Many occupational allergies have been caused by this substance, and the main health hazard is its skin sensitising ability. However, regular biomonitring is lacking although it can be measured from urine or blood. p-PDA is not under REACH restrictions, but some risk management option analysis or informal hazard assessment are either under development or completed. Also, the use of sensitising aromatic diamines like 2,5-TDA in hair dyes is not considered safe (HBM4EU, 2020).

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Many of the aniline derivatives are at the list of restricted substances under REACH. The use of some of the common anilines such as bladder carcinogens 2-naphtylamine and benzidine has been restricted in the EU, and therefore there is no exposure to these compounds. Furthermore, various anilines have been registered only for intermediate use, and although they also form serious health hazards, the exposure is limited due to intermediate use (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.3 Aprotic Solvents

Solvents are qualitatively grouped as non-polar, polar aprotic and polar protic solvents. Various aprotic solvents exist, and they are often used in different applications as in Ph regulators, water treatment, anti-freezing and coating products, lubricants and greases, adhesives and sealants, air care products, polishes and waxes, washing and cleaning products, among others. Their use also comprises laboratory chemicals, agriculture, forestry and fishing. In the second prioritisation process within HBM4EU four aprotic solvents having similar toxicological profile were included, namely 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), 1-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one (NEP), N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC) and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF). In the HBM4EU, it was proposed that the priority group of substances is called “repro-toxic aprotic solvents”. According to ECHA the production volumes of these four solvents are following: NMO, DMAC and DMF 10 000-100 000 t/year and NEP 1000-10 000 t/year (HBM4EU, 2020).

Both occupational and general public exposure occurs via dermal, oral/inhalation or trans-placental routes. The most vulnerable groups of people include industrial workers, pregnant women and young children (HBM4EU, 2020). All four aprotic solvents (NMP, NEP, DMAC and DMF) are considered as potentially damaging the unborn child according to CLP Regulation. The solvents and their levels in substances and products are heavily regulated via e.g. REACH, EU, ECHA, and various restrictions and legislation concerning their use exist. Furthermore, these four solvents are in the SIN-list (Substitute It Now!), which is an extensive database of chemicals likely to be restricted or banned in the EU (HBM4EU, 2020).

Repro-toxic aprotic solvents are regarded as toxic for reproduction and development, but the evidence is derived mainly from animal studies. There is also evidence of developmental and reproductive toxicity considering solvent exposure in humans. However, the epidemiological evidence is thus far scarce (HBM4EU, 2020).

Measurement matrices include urine and blood plasma (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.4 Arsenic

Arsenic (As) is a natural component on earth’s crust, as it can be found in soil and groundwater in a number of countries, in highest quantities in South East Asia, Mexico and United States (WHO Arsenic, 2018). Arsenic is found in the environment in its metallic form as well as in inorganic and organic complexes (HBM4EU, 2020). The toxicity of arsenic depends on its form (inorganic or organic) and species. The toxic species are inorganic forms, such as arsenious acid (As[III]), arsenic acid (As[V]), monomethylarsonic acid (MMA), dimethylarsinic acid (DMA) and trimethylarsine oxide (TMAO). Organic arsenic, which is consumed in food (fish and seafood) is less harmful for human health (WHO Human Biomonitoring, 2015).

Arsenic is mainly used in alloys of lead and in semiconductor electronic devices. Arsenic and its compounds, especially the trioxide, are applied in the manufacturing of pesticides, treated wood products, herbicides and insecticides. Arsenic is also used in some medicines despite its poisonous characteristic in higher doses (HBM4EU, 2020).

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The sources of exposure are both natural and anthropogenic. Most commonly exposure happens through contaminated drinking water, by using water in food preparation, through irrigation of crops, in different industrial processes, by eating contaminated food or smoking tobacco. Also occupational exposure occurs in several industries, including e.g. gold mining, arsenic production, wood preservation, glass manufacturing and smelting operations. Occupational exposure happens via inhalation or dermal contact. Children are the most vulnerable and sensitive group of arsenic exposure, and also occupational exposure poses a risk for industrial workers (WHO Arsenic, 2018; HBM4EU, 2020).

Arsenic has been shown to have severe health effects from short- and long-term exposure. Inorganic arsenic has been confirmed to have carcinogenic features, for example bladder, lung and skin cancers have been associated with long-term exposure. Other associated effects reported are developmental disorders, diabetes, abnormal glucose metabolism, pulmonary disease, cardiovascular disease, increased adverse pregnancy outcomes and infant mortality. Also, exposure in utero and early childhood has been linked to increased mortality in young adults (WHO Arsenic, 2018). Health effects of subchronic arsenic exposure in children are similar to those in adults (WHO Human Biomonitoring, 2015). However, toxic effects of iAs vary significantly between individuals and populations, since it depends on variations in iAs metabolism related to age, gender and life stage such as pregnancy or lactation, nutritional status or genetic polymorphisms related to iAs biotransformation (HBM4EU, 2020).

Preferred biomarker for determination of arsenic and its chemical forms is urine, although measurements of total As in urine do not show information of As species. As inorganic and organic arsenic species have a short half-life in blood and invasive collection, it limits the collection of arsenic biomarkers in blood, hair and nails. Sometimes blood is used, however. Speciation methods are regarded essential for drawing accurate conclusions in arsenic exposure and risk assessment due to differences in toxicity of various arsenic forms (HBM4EU, 2020; Vahter, 1999; Janasik et al., 2015).

In Europe, the exposure to arsenic is systematically regulated. Regulations regarding arsenic in food are established by Commission Regulation (EC) No 2015/2016. Also the EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM Panel) has assessed the human health risks of arsenic in food. Arsenic exposure is also regulated through REACH, with the aim of high level of protection for human health and environment (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.5 Bisphenol A

Bisphenol A (BPA) is one of the most commonly produced and used plastics worldwide. It is applied e.g. in certain plastics, epoxy resins, plastic toys, dental materials, consumer goods and thermal papers (Caporossi & Papaleo, 2017; HBM4EU, 2020).

Exposure routes include food, water, air and skin. A large majority of human population is exposed to BPA. However, occupational exposure has been detected to be higher in petrochemical-, plastic-, food canning-, paint and resins industries as well as among cashiers than in the general population (HBM4EU, 2020; Caporossi & Papaleo, 2017). Children and adolescents have been identified as having higher urine BPA concentrations than adults, indicating higher exposure or slower metabolic processes (Calafat et al., 2008).

BPA acts as an endocrine disruptor, xenoestrogen in particular. Bisphenol A (BPA) is associated with increased risks of endocrine disrupting effect targeting steroid and thyroid hormones, fetal development, reproductive and sexual dysfunction, breast and prostate cancer (or at least breast tissue remodeling) and altered immune system activity. It is also linked to obesity, metabolic

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dysfunctions, diabetes and cardiovascular disease in adults and effects on cognitive and behavioral development in children. The toxic effects of BPA are still controversial. However, it is estimated that BPA exposure could be linked to multitude of health outcomes in humans. Other bisphenols, especially many substitutes of BPA have been less studied; however the data implies that they are also oestrogenic and therefore tend to produce similar health effects than BPA (HBM4EU, 2020; Caporossi & Papaleo, 2017; Rochester & Bolden, 2015).

The preferred measurement method for assessing BPA exposure is through random spot urine sample due to its high detection rate and un-invasive nature (Stojanoska et al, 2017). It is notable, that as BPA has a relatively short half-life, measurements can be used as a snapshot for a single exposure measurement, but they are not robustly usable at assessing risks (HBM4EU, 2020).

For protection against BPA exposure, the European Commission has taken actions by banning the use of BPA in infant feeding bottles (Commission Directive 2011/8/EU) and restricting the use of BPA in certain food-contact materials (Commission Regulation (EU) 2018/213). The amount of BPA allowed in children's toys has also been limited. Additionally, since 2016, the use of BPA has been restricted in thermal paper and the ban took effect as of 2020 within the European Union. Although the relevance of BPA exposure and its effects on human health have been widely agreed on, there is a lack of consensus on the cut off values (Total Daily Intake- limits) by the different agencies (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.6 Cadmium

Cadmium (Cd) levels in the environment vary and derive from both natural (erosion of parent rocks, volcanic eruptions and forest fires; 10-50%) and anthropogenic sources (plastics, automobile radiators, alkaline batteries, mining activities, fertilisers, sewage sludge and inappropriate waste disposal; 50-90%). The world consumption of cadmium has continuously elevated to a global supply of 22,000 metric tons during the twentieth century having remained at this level since 2000 (HBM4EU, 2020).

Exposure of cadmium happens through air, water and soil. The general population is exposed through food, water (5-10% of ingested Cd is absorbed) and tobacco smoke (10-50% of inhaled Cd is absorbed). Cd-rich foods include seafood, liver, kidney, wild mushrooms, flaxseed and cocoa powder. However, 80% of the contamination from food comes from cereals, potatoes and vegetables grown in contaminated soil. Vulnerable groups include e.g. individuals with iron deficiency, pregnant and postmenopausal women, new-borns, toddlers and the elderly. Additionally, smokers, vegetarians and people who have high consumption of seafood might have higher intake of Cd compared to general population. Furthermore, people exposed occupationally may also be at risk (HBM4EU, 2020; Tinkov et al., 2017; Olsson et al., 2002).

Cadmium is associated with several health effects, such as cancers, metabolic disorders, obstructive lung disease and osteoporosis. International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) has classified cadmium (Cd) compounds as human carcinogens (Group 1). Kidneys are a major location of Cd accumulation. The same level of exposure in more sensitive groups – postmenopausal women and elderly – can also lead to bone effects such as osteoporosis and increased risk of fractures. In addition to kidneys, the important organs affected by Cd exposure are bones and respiratory system (the latter via inhalation). Furthermore, possible effects of Cd can take place regarding endocrine, reproductive, developmental and cardiovascular systems (HBM4EU, 2020; Nordberg et al., 2015; Bernard, 2016; Tinkov et al., 2017; Tellez-Plaza et al., 2008; Tellez-Plaza et al., 2013).

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Cadmium is mostly measured from urine reflecting long term accumulation/exposure (occupational or really excessive exposure). At low level environmental situations urine Cd levels are influenced by several factors including physiological variations, stress conditions or silent pathophysiological conditions. Blood measurements of Cd are also possible in whole blood or in red blood cells, while most laboratories do not have sensitive enough measures to detect accurate measurements of plasma or serum. In contrast to urinary Cd, Cd levels in blood also represents a more recent exposure, which can't be well differentiated (HBM4EU, 2020; Nordberg et al., 2015; Bernard, 2016).

As cadmium is listed in Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 as human carcinogen (Carc. 1B) and as the evidence shows increasing toxicity, both national and international agencies regulate its exposure. For example WHO has regulated the amount of Cd in drinking water, the Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JEFCA) has recommended the maximum Cd intake from food and use of Cd is restricted in certain products according to REACH (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.7 Chromium (VI)

Chromium (Cr) exists in oxidation states ranging from -2 to +6, but is mostly found in the environment in the trivalent (+3) and hexavalent (+6) oxidation states. Hexavalent form, Cr(VI) is more toxic than trivalent form. The occurrence of Cr(VI) is rare naturally and thus Cr(VI) compounds are mostly man-made products and by-products. Large industrial emissions occur in metallurgical, chemical and refractory brick industries. Cr(VI) is used in metal plating, manufacture of pigments and dyes, corrosion inhibitors, chemical synthesis, refractory production, leather tanning and wood preservation. Within the EU, Cr was produced with 219 500 tonnes in the largest producing country, Finland, in 2006, which made of 99% of the total EU Cr production. In the EU, there is a 3 to 4.5% annual growth in the demand of Cr according to the European Commission (HBM4EU, 2020; Blade et al., 2007).

Chromium is mobilised through air, water and soil. Regarding the general population, exposure occurs mostly by ingestion of Cr-contaminated soil, food and water, but also through inhalation of ambient air. Also tobacco smoking is an important exposure source, including the hexavalent state. Occupational exposure occurs primarily through contaminated air. Vulnerable groups include children and workers in many industries (HBM4EU, 2020).

Cr (VI) is classified as a human carcinogen (Group 1) by IARC and it is associated with increased lung cancer risk among workers in certain industries and also cancer of the nose and nasal sinuses. Cr(VI) is also genotoxic and causes, additionally, other harmful health effects such as skin irritation, ulceration, sensitisation, allergic contact dermatitis, lung fibrosis, pulmonary edema and congestion and damage to nasal epithelium (HBM4EU, 2020; Rahman et al., 2019. Costa et al., 2006; Schneider et al., 2012).

In occupational settings, the distribution of inhaled Cr(VI) permits the measuring of Cr in urine, whole blood, plasma and blood cells. Since Cr(VI) is largely reduced to Cr(III) in the body, the specification methods are not useful in Human Biomonitoring (HBM4EU, 2020).

The use of some Cr(VI) compounds are authorised under the European REACH regulation. The EU and various countries in the EU have determined regulations for limiting maximal Cr(VI) concentrations for instance in working places, drinking water, food, cosmetics, leather articles and toys (HBM4EU, 2020; Rahman et al., 2019).

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5.8 Diisocyanates

Diisocyanates are a group of chemicals consisting of two isocyanate functional groups in varied structures. Diisocyanates are considered as a part of the aniline family since they are metabolised as respective amine. The most used diisocyanates which cause harmful health effects include methylene diphenyldiisocyanate (MDI), toluene diisocyanates (TDI) and non-aromatic hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI). There are also various other compounds prevalent in Europe, which however are manufactured or imported in smaller, yet notable amounts. Five of them: NDI, XDI, TMXDI, TRIDI and TODI are under evaluation of ECHA for harmonised hazard classification, and only limited information regarding them is available (ECHA, 2020; Delfino, 2002; ECHA, 2016, Baur et al., 2014; Tarlo et al., 2008; Wisnewski et al., 2001; HBM4EU, 2020).

Diisocyanates are extensively used in various industry applications; mostly in the manufacturing of polyurethanes used for various purposes and as hardeners in industrial paints, glues, varnishes and resins. Diisocyanates are produced with an annual volume of 2.5 million tons in the EU, and 95% of this figure consists of MDI, TDI and HDI (HBM4EU, 2020).

Exposure to consumers happens via products containing diisocyanates, especially glues. Also exposure via polyurethane foams used in e.g. construction activities is common. Occupational exposure takes place mostly via inhalation and skin but also through the gastro-intestinal tract. Vulnerable groups include at least certain occupational groups such as workers in polyurethane manufacturing, welding, sawing, painting and construction sector (HBM4EU, 2020).

Already very low exposure levels of diisocyanates may cause health harms. All diisocyanates cause similar health effects: they are potent skin and respiratory tract sensitisers and produce carcinogenic effects. In occupational health, improvements in hygiene have caused diisocyanate-induced skin and respiratory sensitisation conditions to diminish. However, diisocyanate asthma and skin sensitisation are prevalent concerns in occupational health (HBM4EU, 2020).

Diisocyanate metabolites (diamines) can be measured from urine or by using adduct analysis. Adduct analysis is conducted by using either albumin or hemoglobin adducts. In urine biomonitoring elimination kinetics and timing of the sampling need to be carefully considered, whereas in adduct analysis the timing issue is less important (HBM4EU, 2020).

To reduce the number of occupational diseases caused by diisocyanates the EU is planning to restrict the use of diisocyanates at the workplaces. This restriction consists of a mandatory training on safe working practices for the workers handling materials containing diisocyanates. In addition, there are plans to set up a binding occupational limit value for the diisocyanates in the EU (ECHA, 2020; Delfino, 2002; ECHA, 2016, Baur et al., 2014; Tarlo et al., 2008; Wisnewski et al., 2001; HBM4EU, 2020).

5.9 Flame retardants

Flame retardant (FR) is a component or mixture added to a consumer product or building materials to reduce the flammability and ensure product safety. FRs are extensively used in consumer products and building materials such as electronics, textiles and furnishings, automobiles and other vehicles, building insulation, flooring, appliances and ducting. There are both inorganic and organic FRs in use, and in HBM4EU the synthetic organic FRs are in focus. Three primary types of synthetic organic flame-retardants exist: bromine (Br), chlorine (Cl) and phosphate (P). Since the 1970s, the polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and hexabromocyclododecane (HBCDD) were the primary FR compounds, but these are restricted nowadays due to their persistence,

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toxicity and bio accumulative characteristics. However, many replacement compounds are used, typically brominated, chlorinated and organophosphate compounds (HBM4EU, 2020).

Human exposure to FRs can occur through many exposure pathways such as inhalation, ingestion and dermal exposure, and the exposure pathways may vary based on the compound properties and FR use. Infants and children are regarded as vulnerable groups of exposure (HBM4EU, 2020).

PBDEs and HBCDDs have various hazardous health effects such as potential endocrine, neurotoxic and carcinogenic effects. Also tetrabromobisphenol A (TBBPA) has potential hazardous properties. Furthermore, replacement FRs can also have adverse health effects, and there is insufficient evidence regarding toxicity of new FRs. Regarding carcinogenicity there is limited information on long-term and chronic health effects (HBM4EU, 2020).

There are different matrix to measure flame-retardants, for instance, PBDEs (highly lipophilic FRs) are commonly detected in human serum and breast milk. Some novel brominated flame retardant (NBFRs) and many organophosphate esters (OPEs) are metabolised in the body, and their metabolites are detected in urine. However, metabolic pathways are uncertain for many FRs (HBM4EU, 2020).

A small number of FRs are restricted both in the EU and at the international level. The PBDEs and HBCDD are limited in use by the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants. Also various replacement/alternative FRs are registered under REACH, but a number of FR compounds are currently not regulated. There is a lack of information regarding the use, exposure pathways and toxicity of many of these compounds (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.10 Lead

Lead (Pb) is a toxic metal, which occurs naturally in the earth's crust (Lead poisoning and health, 2019). Exposure of lead and its organic compounds derives from multiple man-made substances such as petrol additives and lead-based paints. Also, considerable exposure to humans is caused by inorganic lead or lead salts (lead pipes and solders in plumbing systems, lead-soldered cans, batteries etc.). According to ECHA, Pb is manufactured and/or imported in 1 000 000 – 10 000 000 tons per year in Europe (HBM4EU, 2020).

To some extent, exposure occurs from direct contact with Pb-based products, but the most common method of human exposure is environmental: air, water and soil. Human exposure routes are inhalation, oral and trans-placental. Inhalation exposure includes inhalation of Pb particles, oral exposure ingestion of Pb-contaminated dust, water or food and trans-placental exposure Pb in bone releasing into blood during pregnancy. Physiological factors (e.g. age, pregnancy, fasting) and physiochemical characteristics of particles (e.g. size, solubility and lead species) influence gastrointestinal absorption of Pb. Children and occupational groups with exposure to Pb are one of the most vulnerable population groups affected (HBM4EU, 2020).

Pb can affect every organ system in the body. The principal organs affected are the central and peripheral nervous system, and the cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, renal, endocrine, immune and hematological system. Pb is regarded as a human carcinogen and it is toxic to human reproduction and development by damaging fertility and the unborn child. Pb can also cause hypertension, anemia as well as neurodevelopmental and cognitive effects in humans. In children, Pb is associated with a wide range of toxicity, and intense and acute high-dose exposure to Pb can cause symptomatic poisoning. No safe levels of Pb exposure exist (WHO Lead poisoning and health, 2019; HBM4EU, 2020).

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The most suitable specimen for blood Pb measurement is venous blood collected by using “lead-free” tubes and needles. Since collecting of venous blood is sometimes difficult, capillary blood from a finger is also used for screening purposes (HBM4EU, 2020). Long-term uptake can be determined in vivo from bone (skeleton) and teeth as lead tend to accumulate there. While blood-Pb serves as an indicator of recent exposure, bone-Pb is an indicator of long-term exposure (Abass et al., 2017). Furthermore, bone-Pb measurement is regarded to be a better indicator of Pb dose than blood-Pb in some situations, and some studies have reported significant relations between bone-Pb and diseases and adverse effects (Esteban & Castaño, 2009).

Many regulations and legislations are defined regarding exposure to lead. The EU’s Drinking Water Directive (98/83/EC) defines the health limit value of Pb in drinking water, another EU directive (2013/39/EU) regulates the Pb levels of inland surface water, and the directive 2008/50/EC sets limits for Pb in air. In addition, regulatory limit values have also been set for Pb in soil and foodstuffs. Occupational exposure is regulated by the Chemical Agents Directive (98/24/EC) (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.11 Mercury

Mercury (Hg) is a highly toxic metal, which is naturally and ubiquitously present in the earth’s crust and environment. The sources are both natural and anthropogenic. Mercury exists in three main forms, which are not equally harmful: elemental (metallic), inorganic, and organic. Elemental mercury is the only metal that is liquid at room temperature, and it is also known as “quicksilver”. Elemental mercury is commonly used in human activities in e.g. electrical equipment and lamps, medical and laboratory equipment and dental amalgams. Industrially it is used in the production of chlorine gas and caustic soda. Inorganic mercury compounds, such as mercuric oxide, are applied in the production of batteries, polyvinylchloride and pigments. The organic form of mercury, methylmercury, accumulates in aquatic organisms in waterbodies and bio-accumulates into the food chain. Other organic mercury compounds have been used in fungicides, antiseptics and disinfectants, but have mostly been discontinued. Ethylmercury is used in very small amounts in vaccines and pharmaceuticals (HBM4EU, 2020).

Human exposure to all forms of mercury occurs through dermal, inhalation, oral and trans-placental route. Mercury in water resources poses the greatest risk to humans since it is converted by micro-organisms into the extremely toxic form methylmercury. Methylmercury is easily absorbed by animals and ends up into the food chain. Elemental mercury can react in the atmosphere to form inorganic mercury, which is deposited in water resources and land. The primary route of human exposure to mercury is through the consumption of fish and shellfish containing methylmercury. The most vulnerable and sensitive groups to the adverse effects of mercury are fetuses, newborn babies and young children. Also heavy seafood consumers belong to the risk population (e.g. Arctic populations, tropical riverine or coastal communities) as well as people working or residing in mining areas. All populations worldwide are exposed to mercury at some level, but a great variability exists in exposure within and across countries and regions (HBM4EU, 2020; Basu et al., 2018).

Mercury poses a significant global threat to human health. Methylmercury, being very poisonous, has a substantial effect on the central nervous system even at very low levels. Methylmercury is neurotoxic with its poisoning characterised by discrete anatomic areas of the brain. Also developmental neurotoxicity is observed. Birth defects or other reproductive adverse effects can occur. Prolonged or repeated exposure can cause damage to organs such as liver. According to IARC, methylmercury compounds are possibly carcinogenic to humans whereas metallic and inorganic mercury compounds are classified as not carcinogenic. A link of mercury to Alzheimer’s

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disease has been recognised as well as to endocrine disruptive effects, but further research and evidence is needed. Also the possible relation of mercury to metabolic syndrome, immune-toxicity and cardiovascular effects need further investigation (HBM4EU, 2020; Grandjean & Landrigan, 2006, 2014).

Mercury concentrations can be measured in different human matrices: hair, urine, blood, nails, breast milk, cord tissues, cord blood and the placenta. The choice of matrix depends on the time of sampling after exposure, whether chronic or acute exposure is investigated and which types of mercury compounds are assessed (HBM4EU, 2020; Višnjevec et al., 2014).

The Minamata Convention on Mercury launched in 2017 is an international commitment in addressing mercury pollution, and it has been ratified by the EU. In Europe, heavy regulations exist in restricting mercury pollution and human exposure. The European Commission introduced the Community Strategy Concerning Mercury in 2005, which consists of a comprehensive plan to address mercury use and pollution. European legislation concerning mercury includes instructions on food safety, chemicals, environment, consumer products and occupational health and safety. Due to the European policies, new releases of mercury to the environment are on decline. However, the Europeans are still exposed to legacy mercury and to mercury, which originates outside the EU (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.12 Mycotoxins

Mycotoxins are secondary metabolites produced by microfungi. Mycotoxins occur worldwide, as they are natural contaminants in agricultural commodities such as cereal grains, nuts, oilseeds, fruits, dried fruits, vegetables, cocoa and coffee beans, wine, beer, as well as herbs and spices (HBM4EU, 2020; Smith et al., 2016). Most prevalent Mycotoxins include Aflatoxins, Ochratoxin A, Patulin, Fumonisin, Zearalenone, Nivalenol and Deoxynivalenol (WHO Mycotoxins, 2018).

Chronic and even acute exposure to mycotoxins exists. General population is exposed by the oral route, via the ingestion of contaminated foods. Exposure routes include also inhalation and dermal absorption, especially relevant in occupational exposure (HBM4EU, 2020; Fromme et al., 2016; Viegas et al., 2018). The prevalence of mycotoxins among Europeans seems to be high, as 69% of the study population in Sweden had detectable amount of toxins in their urine samples (Wallin et al., 2015), similar results were found in Spain (Coronel et al., 2011) and in Croatia (Sarkanj et al., 2013). Infants and young children as well as specific occupation groups such as farmers are regarded as vulnerable to mycotoxins exposure (HBM4EU, 2020).

Mycotoxins pose a risk for human and animal health. The main human and animal health burdens are connected to chronic toxicity, such as carcinogenic, teratogenic, immunotoxic, nephrotoxic and endocrine disrupting effects (HBM4EU, 2020; Al-Jaal et al., 2019).

Measurement matrices include urine, serum and breast milk (HBM4EU, 2020).

The European Commission has launched comprehensive mycotoxins regulations for food in order to facilitate world trade and protect consumer's health. Hazardous limits for the level of mycotoxins in human food and animal feed expressed as tolerable daily intake (TDI) and tolerable weekly intake (TWI) are outlined (Commission Regulations (EC) No 1881/2006) (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.13 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) are man-made chemicals that have been produced globally since the 1950s. PFAS are a group of synthetic fluorinated compounds, which are widely used in industrial and consumer products including stain- and water-resistant coatings for fabrics and carpets, oil-resistant coatings for paper products approved for food contact, floor polishes,

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pesticide formulations, fire-fighting foams and mining and oil well surfactants (European Commission Food & Safety, 2019). The preeminent benefits of PFASs lie on their highly durable composition and unique surfactant properties (Rappazzo et al., 2017). Due to the adverse health effects that have been associated with the use of PFASs, a chemical composition called GenX has been developed to substitute PFASs. However, so far very few studies have focused on GenX and little evidence have been generated on its possible human health effects. According to the United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, 2019), GenX's toxicity is similar to PFASs.

Human exposure to PFAS is unavoidable, due to the wide spread and accumulation of PFASs in surrounding environment and organisms. 70% of the human exposure comes through food, especially fish and dairy products (Ericson et al., 2008). Smaller exposure pathways are drinking water and air although they are not significant exposure routes among the general population (HBM4EU, 2020). Children are especially vulnerable to the exposure of PFASs (HBM4EU, 2020; KEMI, 2017). Children have been detected to have higher serum concentrations of PFAS in comparison to adults (Mondal et al., 2012).

The most common and well researched forms of PFAS are perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS). PFOA and PFOS are long-chain perfluorinated compounds, which have been classified as having several adverse health effects, such as carcinogenic features, liver toxicity, neurotoxicity, toxicity for reproduction and specific target organs as well as effects on thyroid and lipid metabolism (HBM4EU, 2020; Barry et al., 2013). Also immunotoxicity and developmental toxicity of PFOA as well as endocrine disrupting effects have been detected (Grandjean & Clapp, 2015). Several long-chain perfluoroalkyl acids have been identified as being highly persistent, bio-accumulative and toxic (EFSA CONTAM Panel, 2018; HBM4EU, 2020). Additionally, there are also concerns about short-chain PFASs, which have been assumed to be less bio-accumulative, however still persistent and found in drinking water and food, including vegetables (HBM4EU, 2020).

PFASs are mostly measured from blood or breast milk (HBM4EU, 2020). Human exposure to PFASs is documented in various studies in Europe and worldwide; most of these studies focused on blood or breast milk concentrations of PFOS and PFOA, but various other forms of PFASs have also been investigated. There seems to be good correlation between the measurement results of human breast milk and blood, even though PFOS is measured at low concentrations in breast milk and at high concentrations in blood. In European studies, the time trends of PFAS exposure has been researched; mostly the samples are drawn from blood (serum or plasma) or breast milk; serum seems to be the most typical matrix measured (HBM4EU, 2020; UNEP 2016). Serum samples are routinely collected during epidemiological studies, while environmental samples relevant to multiple exposure pathways such as drinking water, diet, air and dust samples are not (Tittlemier et al., 2007).

The European Commission has agreed on regulatory and non-regulatory actions regarding PFASs, which are aligned with the chemicals strategy for sustainability (toxic-free EU environment) and the Green Deal. A joint REACH restriction proposal aiming to limit the health risks to human and environment from the use and production of PFASs for non-essential uses has been launched. Several regulatory processes have also been launched by ECHA (HBM4EU, 2020).

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5.14 Pesticides

Pesticides are diverse chemical compounds, which are applied in order to get rid of pests including insects, rodents, fungi and unwanted plants and weeds. Pesticides are used in public health, agriculture and private homes; with the help of pesticides vectors of diseases and pests that harm the crops are eliminated. More than 1000 pesticides are used worldwide with each of the pesticides having different properties, features and toxicological effects. The toxicity depends on the functions and other factors of the pesticides; e.g. insecticides are more toxic to humans than herbicides (WHO Pesticides, 2020; WHO Pesticide residues in food, 2020).

Pesticides are classified according to their chemical composition and nature of active ingredients. The classification entails four main groups: organochlorines, organophosphorus, carbamates as well as pyrethrin and pyrethroids. Insecticides are an important group of pesticides and can be further divided into several sub-classes. Pyrethroids form one of the major classes of insecticides in the EU and also worldwide. In relation to other major classes of insecticides, such as organophosphates and carbamates, pyrethroids pose lower acute toxicity in mammals. However, epidemiological studies of pyrethroids are scarce, and therefore a complete picture of low-level environmental and dietary exposure effects on human health cannot be formed (Kaur et al., 2019; HBM4EU, 2020).

Humans are exposed to pesticides via ingestion, inhalation or penetration through skin. For the general population, pesticide residues in food cause the main source of exposure. The most vulnerable populations include infants, children, pregnant women, agriculture farm workers and pesticide applicators (HBM4EU, 2020; Kaur et al., 2019; Spear, 1991).

Pesticides pose potentially toxic characteristics on humans by manifesting both acute and chronic health effects. Via disturbing the oxidative balance, pesticides induce long-term health effects such as carcinogenesis, neurotoxicity, neuro-degeneration, cardiovascular, respiratory, renal, endocrine and reproductive problems (HBM4EU, 2020; Kaur et al., 2019).

Urine, blood/serum and hair are used as measurement matrices. Urine is better matrix than blood, since pesticides included in HBM4EU are generally metabolised and excreted within few days (HBM4EU, 2020).

The EU authorises and regulates the use of pesticides, for instance by restricting use and limiting the maximal residue concentrations in food (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.15 Phthalates and Hexamol® DINCH

Phthalates, more specifically ortho-phthalates, are the most commonly used plasticisers worldwide, with a consumption of 7.5 million tons annually. Ortho-phthalates represent 80% of plasticisers market in Europe. Phthalates are applied in hundreds of products, including vinyl flooring, adhesives, detergents, lubricating oils, automotive plastics, children's toys and personal care products. Depending on the molecular structure, they are differentiated into low molecular weight (LMW) ortho-phthalates and high molecular weight (HMW) ortho-phthalates. The LMW (including DiBP, BBzP, DnBP, DEP and DMP) are more volatile having plasticising and solvent-like properties. In addition to polyvinyl chloride (PVC) products they are used in plasticisers, paints, dispersions, adhesives and solvents. DEP and DnBP are also used in enteric-coated capsules/tablets. The most common LMW's are diethyl phthalate (DEP) and dimethyl phthalate (DMP), which are used in cosmetics, insecticides and pharmaceutical applications. The HMW (including DEHP, DiNP, DiDP and DPHP) are used in flexible PVC products such as floorings, wires and cables, sport equipment, toys, synthetic leather, coated textiles, footwear and medical

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devices. The most common HMW's are di-isononyl phthalate (DiNP), di-ethyl hexyl phthalate (DEHP) and di-isodecyl phthalate (DiDP) (European Plasticisers Initiative, 2019; Koch & Angerer, 2012; Wittasek et al., 2011; HBM4EU, 2020).

Hexamoll® DINCH® is a non-phthalate substitute regarded low in toxicity, and is used in similar-type PVC-products as phthalates. Regulatory restrictions have changed the phthalate industry and placing of the products on the market - some older and well-known phthalates (such as DEHP and DnBP) are not so common anymore. However, people might be exposed to newer phthalates like DiNP and DPHP or substitutes like DINCH®. Furthermore, the consumer products from Asia and U.S. can contain phthalates as the authorisation requirements do not apply to imported goods (HBM4EU, 2020; Koch & Angerer, 2012; Bizzari et al., 2009).

Exposure routes are via ingestion, inhalation and dermal contact. The most common exposure route for HMW phthalates, such as DEHP and DiNP, is through eating and drinking food that has been in contact with products containing phthalates. Exposure through contact with articles and the skin or mucous membrane, infants mouthing articles, as well as inhalation of vapour and dust particles carrying phthalate molecules in air are also possible. Especially, for LMW phthalates other sources than foods are assumed to contribute to a major degree of the exposure. The vulnerable groups include pregnant women, fetuses and young children (HBM4EU, 2020).

Phthalates are known to exhibit a variety of effects on the reproduction and development of offspring, summarised as "phthalate syndrome" due to an anti-androgenic mode of action. Notably, not all phthalates have the same endocrine disrupting potency or developmental effects, nor are all effects of exposure to a mixture of chemicals widely enough known (HBM4EU, 2020).

The degradation products (metabolites) of phthalates are most often measured, as the parental compounds are metabolised rapidly (Table 4: Phthalate diesters and their corresponding metabolites). Urine concentrations of these compounds are usually higher than in blood. Furthermore, urine is the best measurement matrix for phthalate exposure, however other matrices such as blood, saliva, faeces, amniotic fluid or breast milk can be used (HBM4EU, 2020; Radke et al., 2019; Stojanoska et al., 2017).

Table 4: Phthalate diesters and their corresponding metabolites (HBM4EU, 2020; Kolossa-Gehring et al., 2017; Liao et al., 2017)

Phthalates	Metabolites
Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP)	Mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP) Mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl)phthalate (MEHHP) Mono-(2-ethyl-5-oxohexyl) phthalate (MEOHP) Mono-(2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate (MECPP)
Diethyl phthalate (DEP)	Mono-ethyl phthalate (MEP)
Dimethyl phthalate (DMP)	Mono-methyl phthalate (MMP)
Dibutyl phthalate (DBP)	Mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP)
Butyl benzyl phthalate (BBzP)	Mono-benzyl phthalate (MBzP) Mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP)
Di-n-butyl phthalate (DnBP)	Mono-n-butyl phthalate (MnBP)

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Phthalates	Metabolites
Diisobutyl phthalate (DiBP)	Mono-isobutyl phthalate (MiBP)
Dicyclohexyl phthalate (DCHP)	Mono-cyclohexyl phthalate (MCHP)
Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2- dicarboxylate (Hexamoll® DINCH®)	DINCH metabolites cyclohexane-1,2-di-carboxylic acid-mono(hydroxyl-isononyl) ester (OH-MINCH) cyclo-hexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid-mono(oxo-isononyl) ester (oxo-MINCH) cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylic acid-mono-(carboxy-iso-octyl) ester(cx-MINCH)

Due to the negative health effects on reproduction and development seen in animal studies, which can also be considered relevant to humans, the EU has restricted the amount of DiDP, DnOP and DiNP in children toys and childcare articles that can be placed in children's mouth. DEHP, BBzP, DnBP and DiBP are additionally restricted in any plasticised materials. DEHP, DnBP, BBzP, DEMP, DnPeP, DiPeP and DHNUP are further prohibited for use in cosmetics in the EU. Additionally, new chemical compositions with lower toxicity have also been developed to be used as alternatives for the endocrine disruptive and repro-toxic chemicals, e.g. Hexamoll® DINCH® (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.16 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are a group of chemicals composed of carbon and hydrogen atoms, and they are omnipresent environmental pollutants found in the air, water and soil. In the environment there are more than one hundred PAHs usually occurring as complex mixtures. PAHs are formed as a result of incomplete burn of coal, oil and gas, in car emissions, tobacco smoke or in food cooked over charcoal. Additionally, smaller amount of particles are released in the air by anthropogenic and natural sources, such as dust from Sahara or volcanoes' eruption particles. PAHs are measured in the air as Particulate Matter (PM), generally categorised on the basis of the particulate size. PAHs are also found in many consumer articles and mixtures (HBM4EU, 2020; Mumtaz et al., 1996).

Inhalation is the main route of human exposure, however also ingestion and dermal absorption occur. According to epidemiologic studies, workers exposed to PAHs have higher cancer mortality rates, which makes the workers exposed to PAHs a vulnerable population group. Also children living in the proximity of the industrial sites would be regarded as a high risk group (HBM4EU, 2020).

Many PAHs are either known or suspected as carcinogenic and mutagenic compounds (e.g. benzo(a)pyrene, dibenzo(a, h) anthracene, etc.). Besides causing carcinogenic and mutagenic effects PAHs are effective immune-suppressants. Furthermore, in animal studies endocrine and developmental toxicity has been detected (HBM4EU, 2020; Mumtaz et al., 1996).

There are methods to measure some PAHs (such as BaP) and many of its metabolites from urine, and often spot urine samples are used (HBM4EU, 2020; Guo et al., 2018; Esteban & Castaño, 2009).

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PAHs are regulated based on the National Emission Ceilings Directive 2001/81/EC and REACH. The use of PAHs has been limited to specific threshold concentrations in consumer articles, and the restrictions are even stricter regarding toys and childcare articles (HBM4EU, 2020).

5.17 UV-filters

UV filters, including benzophenones, are vastly used in cosmetics, personal care products, food contact materials, coating products, fillers, modelling clay, finger paints, inks, textiles and other consumer products. UV-absorbers and UV filters including benzophenone-1 and benzophenone-3 are added to food packaging. In Europe, benzophenones are manufactured and/or imported into 1 000 to 10 000 tonnes per year (HBM4EU, 2020).

There is a high potential for the general public to be exposed to benzophenones. Release to the environment is likely to occur from industrial and indoor use (e.g. machine wash detergents, personal care products, paints and coatings, fragrances and air fresheners). Vulnerable population groups include e.g. children and pregnant women (HBM4EU, 2020).

Below, adverse health effects and specific uses are introduced according to different subclasses of UV-filters.

Benzophenone 3 (BP-3) has a low acute toxicity profile. It is not regarded as being irritating to the skin and the eyes. The results from animal studies have showed alterations in liver, kidney and reproductive organs. BP-3 is listed in the Community Rolling Action Plan (CoRAP) list because of potential endocrine disruption.

Benzophenone is possibly carcinogenic to humans (Group 2B, IARC classification, based on sufficient evidence in experimental animals). Available evidence shows that it is not genotoxic, but is categorised as carcinogenic in category 2. It may alter endocrine signaling through various effects on receptors. Known critical effects are on liver and kidney.

Benzophenone 1 (BP-1) is used as a UV filter, but it is also a major metabolite of BP-3. The concentrations of BP-1 found at the cosmetic products are neither irritating nor sensitising. The available toxicity studies show low acute and sub-chronic toxicity of BP-1, and it is not mutagenic. BP-1 is on the European Commission priority list of potential endocrine disruptors.

Benzophenone-2 (BP-2) is a UV-filter, which is used in personal care products. BP-2 may disturb thyroid hormone homeostasis by inhibiting or inactivating thyroid peroxidase – these effects are even more pronounced in the absence of iodide. Both BP-2 and BP-3 have been shown to exert uterotrophic effects and BP2 has been shown to bind to estrogen receptors.

4-Methylbenzylidene camphor (4-MBC) is found in cosmetics and in drinking water. The current, available data does not suggest genotoxicity, mutagenic potential or phototoxicity of 4-MBC. However, 4-MBC is suspected to have a mild endocrine disrupting effect on the thyroid gland.

3-benzylidene camphor (3-BC) is a potential endocrine disruptor. Experiments in vivo and in vitro have revealed oestrogenic activity. Also, 3-BC has been found to interrupt sexual development and maturation in animal models.

4-hydroxy benzophenone (4-HBP) is used as an industrial UV-filter. It has a potential to disrupt endocrine activity and fetal growth.

4-methylbenzophenone (4-MBP) is used in paints and varnishes and in food packaging but not in cosmetics. It is expected to be a non-genotoxic carcinogen, but the available data regarding human toxicological effects is thus far insufficient (HBM4EU, 2020).

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BP-3 and BP-1 including metabolites are directly measured and quantified in urine. However, urine may not be the preferred matrix for measurements of the most lipophilic UV filters such as 3-BC and 4-MBC. UV-filters can also be measured from blood (HBM4EU, 2020).

There are several EU regulations considering benzophenones, such as the restrictions of BP-3 in cosmetic and sunscreen products. BP, BP2 and BP3 are on the SIN (Substitute it now!) list. It should be recognised, however, that there are regulatory gaps regarding benzophenones, and the knowledge on the exposure pathways and human health effects is incomplete (HBM4EU, 2020).

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6 Selected health outcomes and their association with environmental chemicals

The health outcomes and their identified associations with the HBM4EU prioritised environmental chemicals are presented in the following chapters. The selection of health outcomes is based on those included in Deliverable 11.3 (<https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>). The health outcomes are cardiovascular diseases, metabolic syndrome and diabetes, reproductive health, fetal development, kidney function, liver function, osteoporosis, cancer, hematological system, asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, skin irritation and inflammation and cognitive development and neurological disorders.

An overview of each health outcome is given following with measurement methods applicable in HBM studies. Finally, the identified associations with environmental chemicals based on current research literature are presented.

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7 Cardiovascular diseases

Authors: Elonheimo Hanna (THL), Haverinen Elsi (THL), Paalanen Laura (THL)

Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of disease burden in the world (Roth et al., 2020). Cardiovascular disease (CVD) covers a group of disorders of heart and blood vessels and includes hypertension (high blood pressure), coronary heart disease (CHD) (heart attack), cerebrovascular disease (stroke), peripheral vascular disease, heart failure, rheumatic heart disease, congenital heart disease and cardiomyopathies (WHO Cardiovascular disease, 2021). In this chapter, the focus is on three major CVD conditions, namely hypertension, CHD and stroke.

The behavioural risk factors for CVD include unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, smoking and harmful use of alcohol (WHO CVDs, 2017). These risk factors increase the risk of elevated blood pressure, blood glucose or blood lipids as well as overweight and obesity, which are called intermediate CVD risk factors.

7.1 Hypertension

Hypertension, i.e. elevated blood pressure, is a major cause of disease and premature death worldwide (GBD 2017 Risk Factor Collaborators, 2018; World Health Organisation, 2019). According to the May Measurement Month survey carried out in 2016–2017, the prevalence of hypertension was highest in Europe (Beaney et al., 2018). However, this finding may partly be related to demographic differences between the regions.

Blood pressure is expressed as two values, with the systolic blood pressure value representing the pressure in blood vessels when the heart contracts or beats, and the diastolic value representing the pressure in the vessels when the heart rests between beats (WHO Hypertension, 2019). The basic cut-offs for hypertension are as follows: systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg. A more thorough classification is presented in Table 5 (Chobanian et al., 2003). However, mortality from both CHD and stroke increases linearly from levels as low as systolic blood pressure 115 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure 75 mmHg upward (Lewington et al., 2002).

Table 5: Classification of blood pressure for adults aged 18 or older (Chobanian et al., 2003)

Category	Systolic blood pressure (mmHg)	Diastolic blood pressure (mmHg)
Normal	<120	and <80
Prehypertension	120-139	or 80-89
Stage 1 hypertension	140-159	or 90-99
Stage 2 hypertension	≥ 160	or ≥ 100

Blood pressure tends to increase with age, and thereby the prevalence of hypertension is higher among the elderly. Modifiable risk factors of hypertension include unhealthy diet, physical inactivity, smoking, alcohol consumption as well as overweight or obesity (WHO Hypertension, 2019). More specifically, the major dietary risk factor is salt consumption but the dietary risk factors also include a diet high in saturated fat and trans fats as well as low fruits and vegetable intake.

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In the Global Burden of Disease 2015 Study, the DALYs related to systolic blood pressure of at least 140 mmHg were estimated to be around 143,037,000 globally, 7,214,700 in Western Europe, 5,525,200 in Central Europe and 15,106,900 in Eastern Europe (Forouzanfar et al., 2017).

7.1.1 Identifying hypertension among participants

For HBM studies, data on hypertension of the study subjects can be obtained either through medical records, by objective measurement during the study visit or through self-reported information with the study questionnaire. Medical records usually use the International Classification of Diseases, 10th revision (ICD-10), to record diagnoses. For hypertension, the ICD-10 codes are:

- I10 essential (primary) hypertension,
- I11 hypertension and hypertensive heart disease,
- I12 hypertension and chronic kidney disease,
- I13 hypertension, hypertensive heart disease and chronic kidney disease,
- I15 secondary hypertension and
- I16 hypertensive crisis

with more detailed sub codes among these categories (Beckman, 2014; WHO ICD-10, 2019).

The corresponding codes in the ICD-11 classification are BA00–BA04 (WHO ICD-11, 2020).

In some countries also primary care (outpatient) information may be available. They may also use the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2) codes for hypertension, which are K86-K88 (WONCA, 2016).

Blood pressure measurement is the basis of hypertension assessment. A detailed standard operating procedure (SOP) for blood pressure measurement is available for adults in the European Health Examination Survey (EHES) Manual (Tolonen, 2016) and for children in the HBM4EU Deliverable 11.3.

In addition to blood pressure values, information on the use of antihypertensive medication is needed when the aim is to identify hypertensive persons. In this case, the final definition in a Human Biomonitoring study should include the following three components: systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg and/or the use of antihypertensive medication. Therefore, a question on the use of antihypertensive medicine is recommended to be included in a survey questionnaire.

Questions on high blood pressure and the use of antihypertensive medication recommended in different projects vary and those recommended by HBM4EU, European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) (Eurostat, 2018) and EHES (Tolonen, 2016) are presented in Appendix 22.2.

The term “elevated blood pressure” is more suitable than “hypertension” in cases where the assessment is based on measured blood pressure only and data on the use of antihypertensive medication is not available.

7.2 Coronary heart disease

Coronary heart disease (CHD, also called ischemic heart disease, IHD) is a disease of the blood vessels which supply the heart muscle (OECD/European Union, 2020; WHO CVDs, 2017). CHD leads to restricted blood flow to the heart. Acute myocardial infarction, i.e. heart attack is an acute manifestation of CHD.

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In 2019, CHD was the number one disease causing DALYs among people aged 50 years and older globally (GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2020). Among all age groups, CHD was the second largest cause of DALYs. In EU member states, CHD was the leading cause of death in 2017 with about 12% of all deaths attributed to CHD (OECD/European Union, 2020). The gender difference in CHD deaths is remarkable: Death rates for CHD were more than 80% higher for men than women in EU countries in 2017.

7.2.1 Identifying CHD among participants

Data on CHD can be obtained through medical records, objective measurements and self-reported information with a study questionnaire.

Previously diagnosed CHD can be identified from medical records using diagnosis codes. The ICD-10 codes for CHD include the codes I10–I25 (WHO ICD-10, 2019):

- I20 angina pectoris,
- I21 acute myocardial infarction,
- I22 subsequent ST elevation and non-ST elevation myocardial infarction,
- I23 certain current complications following ST elevation and non-ST elevation myocardial infarction (within the 28 day period),
- I24 other acute ischemic heart diseases and
- I25 chronic ischemic heart disease.

The ICD-11 codes for acute CHD are BA40–BA43 and BA4Z, for chronic CHD BA50, BA51, BA5Y and BA5Z, and additionally BA6Z for unspecified CHD. The ICD-11 codes for diseases of coronary artery include codes BA80–BA86, BA8Y and BA8Z (WHO ICD-11, 2020). The corresponding ICPC-2 codes are K74–K76 (WONCA, 2016).

The clinical examinations related with CHD include conventional coronary angiography and the less invasive computed tomography (CT) coronary angiography (Gorenoi et al., 2012). The amount and the nature of plaque can be determined with these screening methods. Carotid ultrasound examination, also a less invasive method, is a third screening tool (Cohen et al., 2013). Carotid ultrasound is used to evaluate the appearance of plaques and flow characteristics in the carotid artery (see Appendix 22.1). Coronary and carotid artery atherosclerosis often go together and therefore, carotid artery ultrasound examination can also give complementary information on CHD status. Both angiography and ultrasound have been utilised in Human Biomonitoring studies. However, coronary angiography and carotid ultrasound examination may not be feasible in all large-scale Human Biomonitoring studies. This is especially so if the scope of the study is wide.

Another tool used in clinical settings, but which has also been utilised in some biomonitoring studies, is electrocardiogram (ECG) (Mancini et al., 2014). Protocol for ECG measurement can be found in HBM4EU Deliverable 11.3 <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>.

Elevated blood pressure or hypertension is an essential risk factor for CHD and is recommended to be included in the study protocol of a Human Biomonitoring study. Some Human Biomonitoring studies have also utilised the blood lipid values, which are useful in estimating the CVD risk of a person. Therefore, serum total cholesterol, preferably also low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol and high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol as well as triglyceride determinations are recommended. Also fasting blood glucose is a recommended measurement, whenever feasible.

Administrative register information such as medical records, if available, is useful in identifying CHD among the study participants, and has been utilised in a major part of previous Human Biomonitoring studies on CHD.

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If administrative register information is not available, the most feasible source of information on CHD may be self-reported information. Furthermore, self-reported information can also be used to complement other data sources.

The HBM4EU standardised questionnaire, the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) (Eurostat, 2018) and the European Health Examination Survey (EHES) Manual include recommended questions on CHD (Tolonen, 2016) (Appendix 22.2).

In addition, questions on a) coronary bypass surgery (ever) and b) coronary angioplasty (balloon distension) (ever) and c) congestive heart failure provide crucial information on CHD history of a person.

7.3 Stroke

Cerebrovascular disease is a disease of the blood vessels supplying the brain (World Health Organisation, 2017). Stroke is an acute cerebrovascular event which is most often caused by a blockage preventing blood from flowing to the brain. The three major types of stroke are ischemic stroke, hemorrhagic stroke and transient ischemic attack (TIA) (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2020).

In 2019, stroke was on the second position among diseases causing most DALYs among people aged 50 years and older globally (GBD 2019 Diseases and Injuries Collaborators, 2020). Among all age groups, it was the third largest cause of DALYs. In EU countries, strokes are the second largest contributor of all deaths, accounting for about 8% of all deaths (OECD/European Union, 2020).

7.3.1 Identifying stroke among participants

Stroke is most commonly an acute event, and clinically used examinations of stroke are not feasible in Human Biomonitoring study settings. Administrative register information such as medical records, if available, are very useful in identifying previous stroke cases, and have been used widely in biomonitoring studies.

People with a previously diagnosed stroke can be identified from medical records with ICD codes. The ICD-10 codes for the wide class of cerebrovascular disease are I60–I69 (WHO ICD-10, 2019). These stand for

- I60 nontraumatic subarachnoid hemorrhage,
- I61 nontraumatic intracerebral hemorrhage,
- I62 other and unspecified nontraumatic intracranial hemorrhage,
- I63 cerebral infarction,
- I64 stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction,
- I65 occlusion and stenosis of precerebral arteries, not resulting in cerebral infarction,
- I66 occlusion and stenosis of cerebral arteries, not resulting in cerebral infarction,
- I67 other cerebrovascular diseases,
- I68 cerebrovascular disorders in diseases classified elsewhere and
- I69 sequelae of cerebrovascular disease

The ICD-11 code for category „Cerebral ischaemic stroke“ is 8B11 (WHO ICD-11, 2020). The ICPC2 codes for stroke are K90 (stroke / cerebrovascular accident) and K91 (cerebrovascular disease) (WONCA, 2016).

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Regarding objective measurements in study settings, the measurements of stroke risk factors, such as blood pressure, blood lipids and fasting glucose, are recommended.

For many studies, the most feasible source of information on stroke may be self-reported information. Self-reported information may also be used to complement other data sources.

The HBM4EU standardised questionnaire, the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) (Eurostat 2018) and the European Health Examination Survey (EHES) Manual (Tolonen, 2016) include questions on stroke, which serve as feasible models to include to Human Biomonitoring study questionnaires (Appendix 22.2).

7.4 Environmental chemicals associated with cardiovascular diseases

7.4.1 Bisphenols

Bisphenol A is a well-known endocrine disruptor, and the mechanisms related with CVD symptoms in individuals have been suggested to lie on induction of oxidative stress and inflammation, epigenetic changes (Han & Hong, 2016), involvement with nuclear receptors and ion channels (Zhang et al., 2020).

Rancire et al. (2015) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to study the association between BPA exposure and the risk of cardiometabolic disorders. Three out of five prospective studies had findings supporting the association of BPA exposure and coronary artery disease (CAD) incidence. A positive linear association between U-BPA and CVD was detected in four out of five cross-sectional studies. Additionally, the authors identified three studies focusing on hypertension. A positive association between urinary-BPA concentration and hypertension was detected in two out of the three cross-sectional studies. Comparing the highest and the lowest U-BPA concentrations the pooled OR for hypertension was 1.41 (95% CI 1.12-1.79).

Han & Hong (2016) examined BPA exposure's association with hypertension and cardiovascular diseases based on findings from different NHANES cycles between years 2003-2012. The review presented inconclusive results, as one study indicated positive association between BPA exposure and CVDs (Lang et al., 2008), one study inconclusive results (Melzer et al., 2012) and no association was detected in two studies (Lakind et al., 2012 and Olsen et al., 2012). Another review by Chrysant (2015) identified two additional studies to the above presented by Bae et al. (2012 & 2015). Both studies showed some evidence of an association between BPA exposure and hypertension.

Argacha et al. (2019) reviewed the role of non-air related pollutants in relation to cardiovascular system. Alimentation was in focus, as through it, humans are exposed to POPs such as dioxins or pesticides and plastic associated chemicals (PACs) such as BPA. Epidemiological studies revealed positive associations of exposures to POPs and PACs with arteriosclerosis and CVD incidence. POPs and PACs had effects on pathways leading to oxidative stress, insulin resistance and angiotensin potentiation. Thus, non-air related environmental stressors have an important role in the burden of CVD.

Cai et al. (2020) examined NHANES data (2003-2014) (n=9139, aged ≥20 years) to estimate associations between urinary BPA concentrations and five specific CVD outcomes and total CVD. Regarding the quartile analysis, highest level of urinary BPA was associated with increased prevalence of myocardial infarction (MI) (OR 1.73, 95% CI 1.11-2.69) and stroke (OR 1.61, 1.09-2.36) compared to those in the lowest quartile. Increase in BPA concentration (per unit, µg/g creatinine) was significantly associated with 19%, 19%, 25%, 29%, 20% and 16% increased ORs of prevalence of congestive heart failure (HF), coronary heart disease (CHD), angina pectoris, MI,

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stroke and total CVD among total participants, respectively. The associations in men were more apparent.

Melzer and Osborne et al. (2012) followed 758 incident coronary artery disease (CAD) cases and 861 controls for nearly 11 years from the European Prospective Investigation of Cancer (Norfolk, UK). Per-SD (4.56 ng/mL) increments in urinary BPA concentration were associated with incident CAD in age-, sex-, and urinary creatinine-adjusted models (n=1 919, OR 1.13 (CI 95% 1.02-1.24), p=0.017). Taking into consideration of CAD risk factor adjustment, the estimate showed similarity but slightly missed 2-sided significance (n=1 744, OR 1.11 (1.00-1.23), p=0.058). Fully adjusted models taking into account early CAD, BMI >30, abnormal renal function, additional adjustment for vitamin C, C-reactive protein and alcohol consumption produced similar estimates with associations (p≤0.05). Thus, associations between higher BPA exposure and CAD incidence showed similar trends as the previous cross-sectional NHANES study of 2003-2004 and 2005-2006, where higher urinary BPA concentrations were associated with heart disease.

Melzer and Gates et al. (2012) investigated associations between BPA exposures and angiographically graded coronary atherosclerosis. U-BPA levels were compared with grades of severity of CAD using angiography of 591 patients (n=385 severe CAD, n=86 intermediate CAD and n=120 normal coronary arteries). The models were adjusted for BMI, occupational social class and diabetes status. The median (unadjusted) U-BPA concentration for normal coronary arteries was 1.28 ng/mL and for severe CAD 1.53 ng/mL. In comparison to those with normal coronary arteries, U-BPA concentration was markedly higher among those with severe CAD (OR per u-BPA SD=5.96 ng/MI OR 1.43, 1.03-1.98, p=0.03), and nearly significant for intermediate disease (OR 1.69, 0.98-2.94, p=0.06). However, when the remaining groups were combined there was no significant U-BPA difference compared to the patients with severe CAD.

Furthermore, in a cross-sectional study by Melzer et al. (2010), the aim was to scrutinise the associations between U-BPA concentrations and health measures based on the NHANES data of adults aged 18-74 years (n=1 455 from the years 2003-04 and n=1 493 from the years 2005-06). Models were adjusted for age, sex, race/ethnicity, education, income, smoking, BMI, waist circumference and urinary creatine concentration. The main outcomes included reported diagnoses of heart attack and CHD, among others. There was an association between higher BPA concentration and CHD in 2005/06 (OR per z-score increase in BPA=1.33, 95% CI 1.01-1.75, p=0.04) and in pooled data (OR=1.42, 1.17-1.72, p=0.001).

Shankar & Teppala (2012) examined 1380 adults who participated in an NHANES study to investigate the association of hypertension (cut-off set at 140/90 mmHg) and exposure to BPA. A positive association between increasing levels of urinary BPA and hypertension was observed, even after adjusting for age, gender, race/ethnicity, smoking, body mass index (BMI), diabetes mellitus and total serum cholesterol (C) levels. Compared to the referent group (tertile 1) the multivariate-adjusted odds ratio of hypertension for tertile 3 was 1.50 (95% CI 1.12–2.00), P-trend = 0.007. Similar results were observed among Thai women taking part in their Thai National Health Examination Survey (Aekplakorn et al. 2015). In a previous NHANES cycle (2009-2010) less clear association was observed among the participants, and it decreased even more after adjusting for subsample weighting (Shiue et al., 2014). Among pregnant women, higher concentrations of BPA during pregnancy were associated with a decrease in systolic blood pressure (SBP) ($\beta = 0.91$ mmHg; 95%CI: $-1.65, -0.17$) (Warembourg et al., 2019). In a novel study, bisphenol A, F and S (BPF and BPS) associations with hypertension were examined. For BPA, higher adjusted odds ratios (ORs) for individuals in the middle and high exposure groups in comparison to the reference group of BPA (OR 1.30 and 1.40) were detected. Additionally, the participants in these groups had 3.08 and 2.82 mmHg higher SBP in comparison to the lowest group. For BPS, the

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participants in the tertiles (2 and 3) had adjusted OR of 1.49 and 1.48 and similar increases in SBP as BPA. Interestingly, no significant association of BPF and hypertension was detected. (Jiang et al., 2020). Only one other review study was detected to examine BPS exposure and CVD, however, the six studies identified were all conducted in vivo (Zhang et al., 2020).

7.4.2 Phthalates

Lind and Lind (2012) conducted a review to scrutinise whether POPs (such as polychlorinated biphenyls, dioxins and pesticides) and PACs as associated with CVD. There seemed to be an association between PACs, such as BPA and phthalates, and CVD based on e.g. occupational exposure and geographical factors (case-control and cohort studies included). Regarding associations between exposure to POPs and other cardiovascular (CV) risk factors, such as hypertension, evidence was not too strong and was mainly based on cross-sectional data. Prospective population-based data is still lacking regarding the associations between overt CVD and POPs. Thus, the role of POP exposure in the pathogenesis of CVD is still unclear.

In a review, Lu et al. (2018) examined 10 epidemiological studies focusing on phthalates and hypertension. Six of the ten studies were NHANES studies from different study cycles. Two of these studies focused on children aged 8–19 years (Transande et al., 2013; Trasande et al., 2015), three included children older than 8 years (Shiue et al., 2013; Shiue et al., 2014; Shiue et al., 2014) and one study focused on adults over 20 years (James-Todd et al., 2016). All of the above mentioned studies found associations between phthalate metabolites and hypertension. For children, increases in SBP z-scores and/or prehypertension were also seen. The two remaining non-NHANES studies revealed no association for self-reported hypertension (Dong et al., 2017) and inverse association between MEP metabolite and DBP (Olsen et al., 2012).

Pregnant women's exposure to phthalates was examined in the HELIX-study focusing on environmental exposures effects on mothers and their children. In the study, 10 metabolites were measured from urine in two pregnancy trimesters through several urine samples, revealing decreased systolic and/or diastolic blood pressure (SBP and/or DBP) during pregnancy to be associated with higher phthalate levels (Warembourg et al., 2019). Olsen et al. (2012) assessed coronary risk of elderly population using the Framingham Risk Score (FRS) and serum levels of four phthalate metabolites. Only monomethyl phthalate (MMP) was associated with LDL-cholesterol and monoethyl phthalate (MEP) with DBP. No strong association with FRS was identified in this study population.

Shiue (2013) aimed to investigate the relationship between urinary phthalate concentrations and risk of stroke in a national population-based cross-sectional study. The data was derived from the NHANES (2001-2004). The study cohort of 2001-2002 was n=11010 (incl. 204 strokes), and the study cohort of 2003-2004 was n=10 122 (incl. 212 strokes). Of 13 phthalate concentrations, the mean values of mono-n-butyl phthalate (2001-2002: 131.27 +- 685.62 and 43.02 +- 117.70, p=0.0001; 2003-2004: 114.36 +- 555.41 and 49.48 +- 153.53, p=0.008) and mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate (2001-2002: 13.60 +- 37.05 and 5.48 +- 10.55, p<0.001; 2003-2004: 10.56 +- 38.37 and 5.94 +- 14.76, p=0.038) concentrations were significantly higher in people with stroke. According to the results, U-phthalate concentrations were potentially associated with increased risk of stroke. However, causality could not be confirmed.

Su et al. (2019) randomly selected 180 subjects out of 336 CHD patients and 360 non-CHD controls to measure urinary metabolites of phthalate esters. The geometric means of urinary phthalates metabolites were significantly higher among CHD patients in hospital than among those being discharged; the metabolites being three Di-(2-ethylhexyl)-phthalate (DEPH) metabolites, mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (MEHP), mono-(2-ethyl-5-hydroxyhexyl) phthalate and mono-(2-ethyl-

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5-oxohexyl) phthalate. The participants in the higher tertiles of urinary MEHP, MnBP and MiBP had an increased risk for CHD compared to the participants in the lowest tertile: ORs were 2.77 (95% CI 1.22-6.28), 2.90 (1.32-6.4) and 3.19 (1.41-7.21), respectively and after adjusting for confounders. To conclude, exposure to DEHP and dibutyl phthalates were positively associated with CHD.

A cross-sectional population-based study by Lind and Lind (2011) investigated the role of BPA and phthalates in relation to atherosclerosis (n=1016, aged 70 years). Ultrasound was used to record the prevalence of overt plaques, and BPA and 10 phthalate metabolites were analysed from serum. Carotid plaques were associated with mono-methyl phthalate (MMP) with an inverted U-shaped manner even after adjustments for typical risk factors such as BMI, gender, smoking, cholesterol, blood pressure etc. (p=0.004). Furthermore, high levels of BPA, mono-isobutyl phthalate (MiBP), MMP and high levels of mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (MEHP) were associated with plaque grey scale median (GSM) and echogenicity of the plaques (p<0.0001 after adjustment). Echogenicity of the plaques suggested a role for plaque-associated chemicals in atherosclerosis.

7.4.3 Per- and polyfluorinated substances

Hutcheson et al. (2020) conducted a case-control study to evaluate the relationship between PFAS and stroke and any modifying effects of diabetes. Cases (n=3 921, aged ≥20 years) had diabetes, whereas control group (n=44 285) were non-diabetic. The data were collected in the C8 Health Project. Four PFAS compounds were investigated: perfluorohexane sulphate (PFHxS), perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA). Among the exposure group, 238 stroke cases were identified and respectively 643 among the non-exposed. A history of stroke was significantly inversely associated with serum PFHxS (OR 0.75, 0.64-0.88) and PFOS (OR 0.81, 0.70-0.90) but not PFNA (OR 1.04, 0.94-1.15) or PFNA (OR 0.89, 0.70-1.14) among those with diabetes. No associations were observed between PFAS and stroke among those without diabetes.

Honda-Kohmo et al. (2019) explored the relationship of PFAS with CHD among persons with diabetes. Data of 5270 adults derived from the C8 Health Project, and four PFAS were separately investigated (PFHxS, PFOA, PFOS and PFNA). In adjusted models, all PFASs were inversely associated with CHD. ORs (95% CI) were 0.72 (0.65-0.79) for PFHxS, 0.90 (0.81-0.96) for PFOA, 0.90 (0.81-0.99) for PFOS and 0.88 (0.76-1.02) for PFNA. Similar inverse relationships were observed for people with or without chronic kidney disease.

In a study examining pre-diabetic adults (n=957), only a small association between PFOS, PFOA, PFHxS, EtFOSAA, MeFOSAA, PFNA and blood pressure was detected at baseline. Furthermore, there were no longitudinal changes in BP over time or increased incidence of hypertension over the 15 years follow-up time (Lin et al., 2020). In recent study among healthy Chinese adult population (n=1273), PFAS substitute chlorinated polyfluorinated ether sulfonic acids (Cl-PFESA) was associated with increased prevalence of hypertension and elevated DBP 1.31 mmHg (95% CI 0.13-2.50). Moreover, it seemed that women were more susceptible to changes associated with Cl-PFESA (Mi et al., 2020).

In one study, gestational and childhood exposure to PFOA, PFNA and PFHxS during pregnancy, 3, 8 and 12 years from 221 mother-child pairs and cardio-metabolic risk factors (glucose-and lipid measurements, BP, anthropometrics) was examined. Gestational serum PFAS concentrations were generally higher than childhood PFAS concentrations. PFHxS seemed to have a positive association with insulin, waist circumference and mean SBP and DBP. Higher gestational and foetal exposure to PFOA and PFHxS was associated with unfavourable cardio-metabolic risks in

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adolescence (Li et al., 2021). Inconclusive results have been found on PFAS exposure among pregnant women. Pregnancy induced hypertension (PIH) and PFAS exposure was discovered in one study (Huang et al. 2019) as another study revealed high detection rate of PFAS in the placenta but no evidence on hypertensive disorders during pregnancy (Bangma et al., 2020).

7.4.4 Pesticides

In a systematic review by Zago et al. (2020), 24 articles were identified assessing occupational pesticide exposure and CVD. MI and exposure to pesticides (chlorpyrifos, coumaphos, carbofuran, ethylene bromide, mancozeb, ziram, metalaxyl, pendimethalin and trifluralin) showed an increased risk (1.8 to 3.2). Furthermore, primaphos, fenitrothion, malathion and deltamethrin were associated with a BP increase. Environmental contamination by tetrachlorodibenzo-p-dioxin was associated with CVD with risk of 1.09-2.78 and organochlorine, 1.19-4.54.

Lind and Lind (2020) conducted a review to examine whether POPs (incl. OC pesticides and PFAS) are associated with lipid abnormalities, atherosclerosis and CVD. Strong evidence was found to support the finding that POPs of different classes could be associated with lipid abnormalities, carotid atherosclerosis and overt CVD like MI and stroke.

Sekhotha et al. (2016) reviewed literature to investigate the association between the agrochemical particles/pesticides and CVD among farmers. The CV outcomes in the selected studies included MI, CHF, stroke, arrhythmia and sudden death. A relationship between agrochemicals particle/pesticides and CVD was detected.

Lee et al. (2012) performed a prospective study to evaluate whether plasma concentrations of selected POPs predict incident stroke among elderly people. 21 different POPs were measured from plasma of 898 participants aged 70 years of the Prospective Investigation of the Vasculature in Uppsala Seniors (PIVUS), and stroke diagnosis was derived from hospital records. 35 participants had a hospital-treated stroke during the five year follow-up. Across quartiles of summary measures of OC pesticides, the adjusted ORs were 1.0, 1.2 (95% CI 0.3-4.2), 2.3 (0.7-6.9) and 3.0 (1.0-9.4) (P for trend=0.03). The adjusted ORs among participants ≥ 90 percentile of the summary measures were 4.0 (1.1-14.6) for OC pesticides and 9.5 (2.3-38.9) for ≥ 95 percentile. Among the elderly, background exposure to POPs seemed to have a crucial role in development or progression of stroke.

Lind et al. (2012) used data from the population-based study (n=1016, 70 years of age) to determine the prevalence of carotid artery plaques. Ultrasound was used to investigate the carotid artery plaques, and the number of carotid arteries with plaques was recorded (0, 1 or 2). 23 different POPs were analysed (incl. 5 pesticides and one brominated compound, among others). Seven of the POPs (PCB congeners) were significantly associated with the number of carotid arteries with plaques even after adjusting for multiple risk factors (p=0.002-0.0001). In conclusion, POPs may be a risk factor for MI.

Han et al. (2017) analysed three nonspecific pyrethroids (pesticides) metabolites in urine in association with CHD risk. 72 CHD patients and 136 healthy controls were included in the case-control study. The median concentrations of the three metabolites among CHD patients were 1.93, 1.07 and 1.09 $\mu\text{g/L}$, whereas the corresponding values were 1.03, 0.42 and 0.74 $\mu\text{g/L}$ among the healthy subjects. Thus, the values were significantly higher among CHD patients. Upper tertile of urinary pyrethroid metabolites was associated with an increased risk of CHD in comparison to the lowest tertile.

Furthermore, two studies focusing on pregnant women and their exposure to pesticides, and one on prenatal exposure were discovered. Kahn et al. (2018) in their review and Saldana et al. (2009)

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in an individual study found some evidence of pesticide exposure and hypertension. Both the review as well as the individual study (Kahn et al., 2018; Saldana et al., 2009) concluded that limited data on the risk exist and more research on early exposure is required. The prenatal exposure study followed mothers and their daughters for nearly 40 years (39-47 years of follow-up), and discovered that prenatal dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) exposure and its metabolite dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE) were associated with hypertension. The association of DDT prenatal exposure and hypertension showed association even after adjusting for independent hypertension risk factors (La Merrill et al., 2013).

Accumulation of contaminants is high in fish and marine mammals, which raised a concern of pesticide exposure among Arctic population which consume a high number of fish foods. 11 pesticides and their metabolites were measured from blood plasma among 1614 adult Inuits. OR for hypertension was not statistically significant among the population exposed to pesticides, even after adjusting for confounders. However, a higher risk of hypertension was associated with increasing p,p'-dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) concentrations among the youngest (OR 1.42 (95% CI 1.08–1.85)). (Valera et al., 2013.)

7.4.5 Flame retardants

Li et al. (2014) included 24 studies with 147 634 patients in a systematic review and meta-analysis. The aim was to explore whether elevated serum levels of alkaline phosphatase (ALP) and phosphate contribute to higher risk of CVD and total mortality in people with normal or preserved renal function. There was a linear association of serum levels of ALP and phosphate with risks of CHD and CVD events as well as deaths. Regarding phosphate, the RRs for CVD deaths and CVD events were 1.05 (95% CI 1.02-1.09) and 1.04 (1.03-1.06), respectively. Furthermore, the RR of phosphate on total mortality was 1.33 (1.21-1.46) regarding the high phosphate group. Also the higher levels of serum phosphate contributed to a higher mortality rate in diabetic and CVD patients. To conclude, a positive association of serum level phosphate and total mortality in people with normal or preserved renal function was observed.

7.4.6 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Burstyn et al. (2005) examined the relationship between exposure to PAHs and mortality from ischemic heart disease (IHD) (418 cases) in a cohort of 12367 male asphalt workers. The average follow-up was 17 years, and the workers came from Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Israel, the Netherlands and Norway. Exposure to benzo(a)pyrene was positively associated with mortality from IHD. The highest RR for fatal IHD was detected for average benzo(a)pyrene exposures of 273 ng/m³ or higher (RR 1.64, 1.13-2.38). Corresponding results were detected with coal tar exposure. Even with adjusting with smoking, there was approximately 20-40% excess risk of IHD among the highest PAH-exposure categories. PAH exposure can be associated with fatal IHD, and a coherent exposure-response relation of the association was detected.

Several studies have focused on blood pressure changes and PAH exposure. Firstly, Shiue (2015) studied the association between urinary PAHs and adult CVD and cancer using data from NHANES cycle 2011-2012 (n=5560, aged 20-80 years). Urinary PAHs were higher in people with CVD. Especially urinary 4-hydroxyphenanthrene was associated with hypertension (OR 1.33, 95% CI 1.00-1.76, p=0.048, population attributable risk (PAR) 5.1 %), whereas heart attack was mostly associated with urinary 1-hydroxypyrene (OR 1.47, 1.05-2.06, p=0.027, PAR 1.7%). In a Korean National Environmental Health Survey 2012-2014, urinary PAH metabolites and hypertension were examined among 6478 participants. For 1-hydroxyphenanthrene, the urinary levels were significantly higher among the participants having hypertension in comparison to the non-hypertension group (Lee et al., 2020). In a cross-sectional study, housewives' hair and

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hypertension risk was examined among 405 women. Over 26 PAH compounds were analysed from the hair samples. However, only acenaphthylene was associated with an increased risk with hypertension (Wang et al., 2016). Among Mexican population (n=11 218) a dose-dependent positive association was found between PAHs and hypertension (aOR for high exposure 1.40, 95% CI 1.01-1.94) (Bangia et al., 2015). In a NHANES study 2001-2008, 2-naphthalene and 2-phenanthrene were positively associated with hypertension (P trend = 0.008 and P trend = 0.02 respectively) among adult population in the USA (Ranjbar et al., 2015). One occupational exposure study was identified where outdoor workers (n=374) exposure to hydroxypyrene was measured from urine. The results suggested occupational exposure to be negatively associated with SBP and DBP (Sancini et al., 2014). Among children, one study focused on boys going to school close to oil refinery in Saudi Arabia. In 184 boys, the proximity to oil refinery increased the risk of prehypertension, revealing an over 4-fold increase in prehypertension after controlling for confounders (p= 0.001) (Trasande et al., 2015).

7.4.7 Cadmium

Tinkov et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to examine the association between Cd exposure and atherosclerosis as well as to investigate the potential mechanism of this association. 31 studies were included in the review (13 cohort studies, 19 cross-sectional studies and one study included in both categories). 18 studies were included in the meta-analysis (11 cohort and 7 cross-sectional studies). Elevated urinary Cd levels were associated with higher CVD mortality (HR 1.34, 95% CI 1.07–1.67) and with elevated blood Cd levels (HR 1.78, 1.24–2.56). Analysis restricted to never smokers revealed similar results with some imprecision. An association between Cd exposure markers (blood and urine) and CHD, stroke, and peripheral artery disease (PAD) was also observed. Furthermore, Cd exposure was associated with atherogenic changes in lipid profile. High Cd exposure was associated with higher total cholesterol (TC) levels (OR 1.48, 1.10–2.01), higher LDL-C levels (OR 1.31, 0.99–1.73) and lower HDL-C levels (OR 1.96, 1.09–3.55).

Chowdhury et al. (2018) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of epidemiological studies exploring the association of As, Pb, Cd and Hg with CVD. 37 studies (n=348 259) reporting risk estimates for total CVD (n=15 274), CHD (n=13 033) and stroke (n=4205) for levels of As, Pb, Cd, Hg (and Cu) were included. RR for Cd was 1.33 (1.09-1.64) for CVD, 1.29 (0.98-1.71) for CHD and 1.72 (1.29-2.28) for stroke. A linear dose-response relation for Cd with CVD outcomes was detected. Exposure to Cd was associated with an increased risk of CVD and CHD.

Tellez-Plaza et al. (2013) evaluated the association between Cd exposure and CVD by conducting a systematic review of 12 epidemiological studies. The RRs for CVD, CHD, stroke, and PAD were 1.36 (95 % CI 1.11-1.66), 1.30 (1.12- 1.52), 1.18 (0.86-1.59) and 1.49 (1.15-1.92), respectively. The RRs for CVD in men, women and never smokers were 1.29 (1.12-1.48), 1.20 (0.92-1.56) and 1.27 (0.97-1.67), respectively. An association between Cd exposure and CVD, especially for CHD, was detected. There were a limited amount of studies with stroke, HF and PAD outcomes.

In a meta-analysis by Caciari et al. (2013), six case-control studies on occupational exposure were included. There was a higher prevalence of hypertension and higher values of both SBP and DBP among the exposed subjects. Prevalence of hypertension in the cases was higher with LOG OR of 1.8, 95% CI 1.030-3.196, p=0.039. The recorder mean SBP was higher than 2.3 mmHg in comparison to the controls (0.948-3.702, p=0.001). Furthermore, DBP was more significant in the cases as the mean DBP was higher than 1.5 mm Hg in comparison to the controls (0.284-2.812, p=0.016).

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Martins et al. (2021) conducted an updated systematic review to assess the potential relationship between Cd exposure and altered BP and/or hypertension. 38 studies were included (29 cross-sectional, 3 case-control, 5 cohort and 1 interventional study) with blood- or urine-Cd levels as the most common biomarker measured. There was a positive association between blood Cd levels and BP and/or hypertension based on various studies. However, there were only a small number of population-based studies on never-smokers, which might have been a confounding factor. Furthermore, due to contradictory results, the relationship between urinary Cd levels and BP and/or hypertension was left unverified.

Oliver-Williams et al. (2018) evaluated the association between baseline urinary-Cd and longitudinal changes in BP by analysing 3047 U-Cd samples from three geographical areas among American Indian communities. There was an association between higher levels of U-Cd at baseline and faster rates of increase in DBP and SBP (p for trend= 0.001 and 0.02, respectively). Furthermore, the estimated change per year in DBP and SBP were 0.18 mmHg (0.05-0.31) and 0.62 mmHg (0.37-0.87) in the upper quintile of Cd level in comparison to -0.11 mmHg (-0.24-0.02) and 0.21 mmHg (-0.04-0.46) in the lowest quintile, respectively. Finally, a one-unit increase in U-Cd was associated with 10% higher hypertension risk (95% CI 1.01-1.20). It was concluded, that BP increased at a faster pace in the individuals, who had higher U-Cd values at the baseline.

In a review by Satarug et al. (2017) seven studies with positive association between Cd exposure and hypertension were presented and especially women seemed to be more susceptible to the adverse health effects in comparison to men. However, the authors state that more evidence is required to consolidate the exposure effects. In another systematic review, Martins et al. (2021) identified 38 studies focusing on hypertension and Cd exposure. A positive association between blood Cd levels and BP and/or hypertension based on various studies was detected. However, methodological discussions mainly on confounding relating to smoking hindered the evidence of the relationship.

Wang et al. (2018) examined the association between Cd exposure and BP/hypertension and furthermore the relation between Cd and BMI in a NHANES sample of 32791 adults, aged over 20 years (NHANES 1999-2014). The biomarkers were U-Cd and B-Cd. In black women, a two-fold increase in B-Cd was associated with 0.54 mmHg (95% CI 0.49-0.58) and 0.05 mmHg (0.04-0.06) increases in SBP and DBP, respectively. In Mexican-American women, there were SBP and DBP increases of 0.92 mmHg (0.73-1.11) and 0.85 mmHg (0.65-1.05), respectively. Furthermore, there were significant associations between B-Cd and hypertension in Mexican-American women (systolic risk per twofold B-Cd, OR 1.31, 95% CI 1.07-1.61 and diastolic risk per twofold B-Cd, OR 1.55, 1.17-2.05). Finally, U-Cd was significantly associated with hypertension in all participants (OR 1.14 per twofold, 1.07-1.21). There were some inconsistencies in the associations between Cd exposure and BP/hypertension within BMI categories; a negative interaction between B-Cd and obesity regarding their effects on SBP (RERI= -0.30, -0.56- -0.03, ratio of ORs 0.55, 0.35-0.89). All in all, Cd had an effect on BP/hypertension, and there were some differences by sex and ethnicity. Furthermore, the negative interaction between Cd exposure and obesity affected SBP risk.

7.4.8 Arsenic

Several updates on systematic reviews and meta-analysis on As exposure and CVD outcomes have been conducted throughout the past years.

Most recent systematic review and meta-analysis was published by Xu et al. (2020). They examined the pooled association between the RR of each CVD endpoint and low-level As concentration in drinking water. 28 studies were included. There was a significant positive association between the risks of most CVD outcomes and drinking water As concentration (p -value

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for trend <0.05). Furthermore, significant increased risks of CHD and CVD mortality and combined fatal and non-fatal CHD, CVD, carotid atherosclerosis disease and hypertension were detected in people exposed to drinking water with As concentration of 10 µg/L in comparison to those exposed to drinking water with As concentration of 1 µg/L.

Chowdhury et al. (2018) examined in their systematic review and meta-analysis risk ratios for As exposure and CVD (RR 1.30, 95% CI 1.04-1.63), CHD (RR 1.23, 95% CI 1.04-1.45) and stroke (RR 1.15, 95% CI 0.92-1.43). A linear dose-response relation for As with CVD outcomes was found.

Moon et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review of epidemiological studies among the general population of the association between As exposure and all CVD, CHD and stroke. 12 studies were included in the literature review (n=408 945); and further 11 in the meta-analysis. Seven of the studies were conducted at high levels of water As and five studies at low to moderate levels. Compared to 10 µg/l, the RRs for 20 µg/l water As was 1.09 (CI 95% 1.03-1.14) (number of studies = 2) for CVD incidence, 1.07 (1.01-1.14) (n=6) for CVD mortality, 1.11 (1.05-1.17) (n=4) for CHD incidence, 1.16 (1.07-1.26) (n=6) for CHD mortality, 1.08 (0.99-1.17) (n=2) for stroke incidence and 1.06 (0.93- 1.20) (n=6) for stroke mortality. Despite the small number of studies, some evidence of association between As and CVD across different levels of exposure was shown.

A systematic report/review by the Swedish Council/SBU Assessment of methods in health care and social services (2017) aimed to investigate the association between occupational exposure to chemicals and CVD. 164 articles were included. There was an association between workplace exposure to As and heart disease. According to the report, chemical exposures in the workplace were associated with CVD.

Kuo et al. (2017) analysed the association between As metabolism and cancer, CVD and diabetes-related outcomes in 26 epidemiologic studies. Ten studies were on CVD (3 prospective cohort, 1 case-control and 6 cross-sectional study). Study outcomes were hypertension (n=5), carotid atherosclerosis (n=3) and overall CVD (n=2). Three As metabolism biomarkers were investigated (iAs%, MMA% and DMA%). Higher MMA% was usually associated with higher risk of carotid atherosclerosis and clinical CVD but not with hypertension. However, even regarding incident CVD and prevalent carotid atherosclerosis the results were not statistically significant.

In the systematic review by Tsuji et al. (2014) low-level iAs exposure (i.e., <100–150 mg/L arsenic water concentration) and CVD in human populations were investigated. 13 cohort and case-control studies from US, Taiwan, Bangladesh, and China were included and scrutinised for evidence for derivation of a reference dose (RfD). Furthermore, for additional information, 8 cross-sectional and ecological studies from the US were investigated. The strongest evidence for establishing the departure point for a candidate RfD based on a combined endpoint of mortality from IHD and other heart diseases was detected from prospective cohort data from Bangladesh. A no-observed-adverse-effect level of 100 mg/L for As in water was supported, corresponding to an iAs dose of 0.009 mg/kg-day (based on population-specific water consumption rates and dietary iAs intake). Regarding the studies from the US, evidence of the association between low-As exposure and CVD risk factors (e.g. diabetes, obesity and hypertension) was less clear. A RfD for CVD was 0.003-0.009 mg/kg-day in the US studies.

Previously, Moon et al. (2012) updated the systematic review (Navas-Acien et al. 2005), which investigated the association between As exposure and CVD. The authors identified 18 studies and combined them with the previous 13 studies from the original review by Navas-Acien et al. (2005). Pooled RRs were calculated by comparing the highest versus the lowest exposure category across the studies. For high exposure (As in drinking water >50 µg/L), the RRs for CVD, CHD, stroke, and

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PAD were 1.32 (95 % CI 1.05–1.67), 1.89 (1.33–2.69), 1.08 (0.98–1.19), and 2.17 (1.47–3.20), respectively. The evidence was shown to be inconsistent at low-moderate As levels. The evidence of the causal association between high chronic As exposure and clinical CV endpoints was strengthened. Moon et al.'s meta-analysis strengthened the results from the original review by Navas-Acien et al. (2005).

Abhyankar et al. (2012) included 11 studies in their systematic review focusing on both low- (3) and high (8) Arsenic exposure levels and hypertension or elevated blood pressure. When comparing the highest and lowest As exposure categories, the pooled OR for hypertension was 1.27 (95% CI 1.09-1.47, p-value for heterogeneity= 0.001, I²=70.2%). Both areas of exposure (low- and high exposure levels) suggested a positive association between the exposure and the adverse health outcome. However, the writers point out the limited number of studies, lack of evidence on the causality of the interference, heterogeneity and methodological limitations of the studies and lack of prospective evidence as challenges in the strength of the evidence.

Nong et al. (2016) explored the association of urine As with predicted 10-year atherosclerotic CVD (ASCVD) risk in US adults with hypertension. Cross-sectional data of 1570 adults with hypertension, aged 40-79 years, from NHANES 2003-12 was used. In men, after adjustment for sociodemographic factors, urine dilution, ASCVD risk factors and organic As intake from seafood, participants from the highest quartiles of U-As had higher 10-year predicted ASCVD risk than in the lowest quartiles with the increases of 24% (95% CI: 2-53%) for total As, 13% (2-25%) for dimethylarsinate and 22% (5-40%) for total As minus arsenobetaine separately. In women, the increases were 5% (-15-29), 10% (-8-30) and 0% (-15-19), respectively. To conclude, even low level As exposure can cause increased ASCVD risk in men with hypertension.

7.4.9 Lead

The previously introduced systematic review and meta-analysis by Chowdhury et al. (2018) concluded, that RR for Pb was 1.43 (1.16-1.76) for CVD, 1.85 (1.27-2.69) for CHD and 1.63 (1.14-2.34) for stroke. A linear dose-response relation for Pb with CVD outcomes was shown. Exposure to Pb was associated with an augmented risk of CVD and CHD.

Navas-Acien et al. (2007) conducted a systematic review to explore the evidence on the association between Pb exposure and CVD outcomes in humans. 30 studies (12 in general and 18 in occupational populations) of clinical CV endpoints and 32 studies on intermediate CV endpoints were included. There was a positive association detected between Pb exposure and BP in studies of different settings, and in many studies a dose-response relationship was observed. Furthermore, among general populations, a positive association of Pb exposure with clinical CV outcomes (CV, CHD, stroke mortality and PAD) was detected, but the number of studies was small. Blood Pb level of < 5 µg/dL seemed to be a threshold for these associations in some of the studies. A causal relationship between Pb exposure and hypertension could be established. Regarding the association between Pb exposure and clinical CV outcomes, the evidence of a causal relationship was suggestive but not sufficient. Finally, the evidence was suggestive but insufficient for establishing a causal relationship between Pb exposure and heart rate variability.

The earlier mentioned report by the Swedish Council/SBU Assessment of methods in health care and social services (2017) detected an association between exposure to Pb and CVD. There was evidence that workplace exposure to Pb was associated with heart disease, stroke and high BP.

Kim et al. (2020) evaluated the effects of low blood lead level (BLL) (BLL <10 µg/dL) on hypertension among Pb-exposed male workers in the Republic of Korea. The cohort of 12 060 male workers went to an annual medical check-up for Pb between the years 2000 and 2004. 7 341

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men had a peak BLL < 10 µg/dL, and were therefore included in the study. The Pb-exposed workers were divided into four quartiles according to the peak BLL. SBP (β 0.04, $p < 0.01$) and DBP (β 0.06, $p < 0.01$) elevated in relation with a 1 µg/dL increase in BLL. There was a statistically significant OR of hypertension in the fourth vs. first BLL quartile (OR 1.54, 95% CI: 1.26-1.89). To conclude, there was a statistically significant association with SBP and DBP and peak BLL, and a BLL ≥ 6.87 µg/dL was associated with hypertension.

Bulka et al. (2019) assessed the associations of Pb with blood and pulse pressure trajectories by prospectively following the participants ($n=255$) from a randomised trial for the prevention of As-related skin cancer. B-Pb was measured at baseline and at 3 biennial follow-up examinations. In adjusted models, Pb was linearly associated with increased SBP but not with DBP or pulse pressures.

The association between B-Pb levels and SBP/DBP/hypertension was evaluated in a study of Gampelunghe et al. (2016). The investigated cohort included 4 452 persons aged 46-67 years from Sweden between 1991 and 1994. In the fourth quartile, B-Pb was associated with significantly higher SBP and DBP (point estimates 1-2 mmHg) and increased prevalence of hypertension (OR=1.3, CI 95% 1.1-1.5) versus the other quartiles after adjustments for sex, age, smoking, alcohol, waist circumference and education. Significant associations were also detected when exploring B-Pb as a continuous variable. In conclusion, low-level Pb exposure increased BP and the risk of hypertension.

Han et al. (2018) included 21 688 workers in an occupational population-based study in order to investigate associations between BLL and BP. The workers with >17.5 µg/dL BLL had 1.34 mmHg and 0.70 mmHg average differences in SBP and DBP in comparison to workers with ≤ 4.6 µg/dL BLL. Furthermore, an adjusted OR for hypertension was 1.11 (1.08-1.15) when comparing these two different BLL groups. To summarise, BLL was positively associated with SBP and DBP and with the morbidity of hypertension in occupational populations with a high concentration of Pb.

Almeida et al. (2017) examined the association of BLL with BP and hypertension in a population-based study in a southern Brazilian city. 948 adults with the age of 40 and older were randomly selected. After adjustments, participants of the fourth quartile of B-Pb had 0.06 mmHg (95% CI 0.04-0.09) average difference in DBP compared to those in the quartile one. Furthermore, the participants of the 90th percentile of B-Pb distribution had 0.07 mmHg (0.03-0.11) higher DBP in comparison to the participants in the 10th percentile of B-Pb. Also, comparing the highest to the lowest B-Pb quartiles, the adjusted OR for hypertension was 2.54 (1.17-5.53). Finally, the participants in the 90th percentile of B-Pb had higher OR for hypertension in comparison to the participants in the 10th percentile of B-Pb (OR=2.77, 1.41-5.46). To conclude, BLL was positively associated with DBP and with the odds of hypertension.

7.4.10 Mercury

Hu et al. (2021) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to investigate the relationship between chronic Hg exposure and CVD outcomes. 14 studies of more than 34000 participants from 17 countries were included. There was an association between Hg exposure and increase in nonfatal IHD (RR 1.21, 0.98-1.50), all-cause mortality (RR 1.21, 0.90-1.62), CVD mortality (RR 1.68, 1.15-2.45) and mortality due to other heart diseases (RR 1.50, 1.07-2.11). Instead, no association was detected between Hg exposure and stroke. Regarding occupational inorganic Hg exposure, there was an association with similar increase in different mortality outcomes. There was a J-shaped relationship between Hg exposure and different fatal/nonfatal outcomes, and the turning points of hair Hg concentrations were 1 µg/g for IHD and 2 µg/g for stroke and all CVD.

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Another study by Hu et al. (2018) examined the potential association between Hg biomarkers and hypertension or BP by conducting a systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis. The meta-analysis included 29 studies. Comparing the highest and lowest Hg exposure categories, the pooled OR for hypertension was 1.35 (95% CI: 0.99-1.83) for populations with hair Hg ≥ 2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ in comparison with the OR of 1.12 (0.82-1.52) for populations with hair Hg <2 $\mu\text{g/g}$. Positive associations were also detected for highest versus lowest Hg exposure categories on systolic and diastolic BP. Furthermore, for both hypertension and SBP, a nonlinear dose-response relationship with an inflection point of 3 $\mu\text{g/g}$ was detected.

The previously introduced systematic review and meta-analysis by Chowdhury et al. (2018) showed that on the contrary to other investigated metals, Hg showed no association with CV outcomes.

Furthermore, Gallego-Viñas et al. (2019) systematically reviewed the possible association between chronic Hg exposure and BP among children and adolescents (the mean ages ranging from three to 17 years). Eight studies were included (5 cohort, 1 cross-sectional and 1 case-control study). Four of the articles assessed prenatal exposure, two both prenatal and postnatal exposures and two postnatal exposures. A positive significant association was detected between chronic Hg exposure and BP in children or adolescents according to four studies (three of them analysing prenatal exposure). However, designs of the studies were heterogeneous and different covariates were used in the studies. Therefore, the studies were difficult to compare, and the evidence of an association was scarce.

7.5 Highlights

Based on our review, environmental substances such as pesticides, BPA, phthalates, PFAS, PAHs, FRs (especially phosphate) and heavy metals of Cd, Hg, As and Pb were associated with an increased risk of CVDs and CV outcomes. Varying results were found for BPA, phthalates and PFAS, and for heavy metals As and Hg. In relation to environmental substances, CVDs have been extensively studied compared to some other disease categories. The included studies were mostly based on population or occupational settings and some of the studies were conducted among vulnerable groups, such as children, pregnant women or elderly people. The confounding risk factors of CVDs (such as smoking, BMI, diabetes, cholesterol levels and other blood values, age, gender and even race/ethnicity) were mostly taken into account in the analyses of the selected studies. Many of the studies investigated a multitude of CVDs. Although some of the studies explored various chemicals or metals at the same time, mixed chemical exposure was not included in these HBM studies.

Measurement methods varied in the biomonitoring studies through all the CVD outcomes. Hypertension/ BP was most often measured and the methodological choices and cut-off measures were clearly stated. Only few biomonitoring studies used register or questionnaire data. For CVD, the two clinical examinations used were artery ultrasound and electrocardiogram (ECG). Other measurement tools were Computer-Assisted Personal Interviewing (CAPI) questionnaire system, self-report of a clinician-based diagnosis or CVD event. Stroke in the selected studies was based on self-reporting, diagnosis or review of medical and hospital records. Furthermore, measurements of lipid and blood glucose levels were used to assess stroke risk.

To conclude, there is tentative supportive evidence of the association between environmental substances and increased risk of CVDs and various CV outcomes. The causality, however, was not often confirmed, and the findings were inconclusive regarding some of the substances.

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8 Metabolic syndrome and diabetes

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8.1 Metabolic syndrome

The burden of non-communicable diseases is increasing worldwide. Metabolic syndrome, previously known as syndrome X or insulin resistance is a combination of characteristics increasing the risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) to three-fold and type 2 diabetes (T2DM) to five-fold (O'Neill & O'Driscoll, 2015). According to the International Diabetes Federation (2005), metabolic syndrome (MetS) is defined when a person has central obesity and two of the following; raised triglycerides, reduced HDL-cholesterol, raised blood pressure or raised fasting plasma glucose. There are also several other definitions of MetS with small deviations from the IDF definition (WHO, 1998; EGIR, 1999; AACE, 2003; NCEP-ATP III, 2004; AHAA/NHLBI, 2004; JIS, 2009). Estimates on the prevalence of MetS differ according to the definition and population examined, however several European studies have estimated prevalence to be somewhere between 13-35% among large European cohorts, most usually around 25% (Scuteri et al., 2015; Waterhouse et al., 2009; The DECODE group, 2006; Nilsson et al., 2007).

Metabolic syndrome is a major cause for morbidity and mortality in Europe and in addition to the significant individual disease effects; decreased quality of life and disability, also economic costs to societies and health care systems are indisputable. Globally, obese individuals were found to have one third greater medical costs in comparison to their normal weight peers (Withrow & Alter, 2011). Within EU-28 obesity related direct costs have been estimated to be around € 81 billion annually and for diabetes costs rise to over € 300 billion (Health costs in the European Union, 2014). Furthermore, Scholze et al. (2010) estimated economic costs to health services with patients with metabolic syndrome and hypertension to be 24,427 million euros in Germany, 1,900 million euros in Spain and 4,877 million euros in Italy.

Within the European population, obesity is affecting over 200 million adults; a staggering number corresponding to over 50% of the adult population (EU Commission Nutrition and obesity prevention, 2006). For children, the number of overweight and obese children is approximately 25% of the population and is estimated to grow by 400 000 children each year (EU Commission Nutrition and obesity prevention, 2006). Obesity, one of the crucial components of MetS, is also the main factor increasing the risk of type 2 diabetes, as 70% of the risk is associated with weight gain (Heindel et al., 2017). People with insulin resistance, prediabetes or T2DM also often meet other criteria of MetS and reversely, individuals with MetS are at higher risk of developing diabetes (Wilson et al., 2005).

For retrieving information on metabolic syndrome from register data the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) and the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC) – coding can be used. MetS ICD-code is in the currently used ICD-10 classification E88.81 and in the previously used ICD-9 277.7. In 2022, the new ICD-11 the new ICD-11 will be implemented and the new code will be 5A44 insulin resistance syndromes. (WHO ICD-11, 2020; WHO ICD-10, 2019). In the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC) coding, metabolic syndrome is coded as T99 (endoc./metab./nutr.disorder) (WONCA, 2016).

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8.1.1 Standardisation of the definition of metabolic syndrome

In the past decade several expert groups and institutions have attempted to find an agreement on how to define metabolic syndrome. Despite several attempts to harmonise the criteria no conclusion has so far been reached. The challenge between the definitions occurs when scrutinising the definitions; all definitions identify people at risk, however different definitions identify different individuals. For instance, in a DECODE study (2006) from 2116 participants with defined MetS diagnoses by three different definitions, only 33,4% were identified by all three definitions. This discrepancy between the identification can partly be explained by different approaches. For example, the World Health Organisation (WHO), European Group for the Study of Insulin Resistance (EGIR) and American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists' (AACE) focus on insulin resistance, as National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III's (NCEP-ATP III) and International Diabetes Federation's (IDF) have an obesity-centric approach (Kassi et al., 2011).

Previous literature identifies the existence of multiple definitions and the challenges it has caused in the academic and clinical work; as for instance studies using different definitions are not comparable due to different cut-off points. Due to this discrepancy several studies have focused on comparing the most used definitions and their merits alongside each other to find the most useful definitions for clinical and research work. In 2005 International Diabetes Federation (IDF) and in 2009 Joint Interim Statement (JIS) made an effort to harmonise the definitions and find a golden standard for the definition of metabolic syndrome. Nonetheless, still several definitions are used in the clinical and research purposes. The most used definitions are by:

- World Health Organisation (WHO) (1998) (in the reference list under Alberti & Zimmet, 1998)
- European Group for Study of Insulin Resistance (EGIR) (1999) (in the reference list under Balkau & Charles, 1999)
- American Association of Clinical Endocrinologists' (AACE) (2003) (in the reference list under Einhorn et al., 2003)
- National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III's (NCEP-ATP III) (2004)
- American Heart Association and National Heart Lung and Blood Institute (AHA/NHLBI) (2004) (in the reference list under Grundy et al., 2005)
- International Diabetes Federation's (IDF) (2005)
- Joint Interim Societies (JIS) (2009) (in the reference list under Alberti et al., 2009)

The latest definition by Joint Interim Statement (JIS) harmonises the previous criteria by International Diabetes Task Force on Epidemiology and Prevention, National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute, American Heart Association, World Heart Federation, International Atherosclerosis Society and International Association for the Study of Obesity. In Table 6 below, the different definitions are presented.

Table 6: Metabolic syndrome definitions

Clinical measure	WHO (1998)	EGIR (1999)	NCEP-ATP III (2001)	AACE (2003)	IDF (2005)	AHA (2004)	JIS (2009)
Criteria needed for definition	insulin resistance + two further criteria needed	insulin resistance + two further criteria needed	Three of the following	indicates risk factors	Central obesity (WC) + 2 of the following	Three of the following	3/5
Insulin resistance	IGT, IFG, type 2 DM, insulin resistance	Plasma insulin \geq 75 th percentile	none	IGT or IFG	none	none	none
Body weight/ waist circumference / BMI M= men F= female	M: WHR > 0.90 F: WHR > 0.85 and/or BMI > 30 kg/m ²	M: WC \geq 94 cm F: WC \geq 80 cm	M: WC \geq 102 cm F: WC \geq 88 cm	BMI \geq 25 kg/m ²	Increased WC (population specific) Europids: M: \geq 94 cm F: \geq 80 cm	M: WC \geq 102 cm F: WC \geq 88 cm	Population - and country specific definitions Europids: M: \geq 94 cm F: \geq 80 cm
Lipid metabolism	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 35 mg/dl (0.9 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 39 mg/dl (1.0 mmol/l)	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 35 mg/dl (0.9 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 39 mg/dl (1.0 mmol/l) or receiving treatment	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 40 mg/dl (1.03 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 50 mg/dl (1.3 mmol/l)	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 40 mg/dl (1.03 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 50 mg/dl (1.29 mmol/l) or receiving treatment	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 40 mg/dl (1.03 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 50 mg/dl (1.3 mmol/l) or receiving treatment	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/L) and/ or M HDL-C < 40 mg/dl (1.03 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 50 mg/dl (1.3 mmol/l) or receiving treatment	TG \geq 150 mg/dl (1.7 mmol/l) M HDL-C < 40 mg/dl (1.0 mmol/l) F: HDL-C < 50 mg/dl (1.3 mmol/l) or receiving treatment
Blood pressure (mmHg)	\geq 140/90 or receiving treatment	\geq 140/90 or receiving treatment	\geq 130/85 or receiving treatment	\geq 130/85	\geq 130/85 or receiving treatment	\geq 130/85 or receiving treatment	\geq 130/85 or receiving treatment
Glucose	IGT, IFG or T2DM diagnose,	IGT or IFG (but not T2DM) Fasting	>110 mg/dl (6.1 mmol/l) including	IGT or IFG (but not T2DM) Fasting	\geq 100 mg/dl (5.6 mmol/l)	\geq 100 mg/dl (5.6 mmol/l)	\geq 100 mg/dl or receiving medication

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Clinical measure	WHO (1998)	EGIR (1999)	NCEP-ATP III (2001)	AACE (2003)	IDF (2005)	AHA (2004)	JIS (2009)
	HOMA-IR > 1.775	glucose ≥ 6.1 mmol/l	diagnose for T2DM	glycaemia 6.1-6.9 mmol/l or 7.8 mmol/l (140 ng/dl) 2 hours after OGTT	(includes T2DM)		
Others	micro-albuminuria			other features of insulin resistance			

M= male, F= female, IGT= impaired glucose tolerance, IFG=impaired fasting glucose, FPG= fasting plasma glucose, T2DM= type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, WC= waist circumference, WHR= waist to hip ratio, BMI= body mass index, TG= triglycerides, HDL-C= high-density lipoprotein cholesterol

Standardised and harmonised data collection is a vital part of Human Biomonitoring and health survey studies conducted in Europe. In the European Health Examination Survey –project (EHES) standardisation of measurement methods was established as well as the protocols that should be utilised to ensure high quality and comparability of the data collection and analysis. EHES protocols provide guidelines for standardised measurement methods in European health examination surveys (EHES, 2018). For HBM studies, no agreement has been set to which metabolic syndrome definition to use, which might further hinder the comparability of the studies. Furthermore, in HBM studies MetS requires biological measurements and anthropometrics as self-reported data might provide less accurate data. In the next chapter comparison of the definitions and their concordance is presented among adults and children.

For standardised measurement protocols of blood pressure, waist circumference, and height and weight, as well as sample collection and analysis procedures for HDL cholesterol, triglycerides and glucose among adults are provided in the EHES protocols at <http://www.ehes.info/manuals.htm>. Blood pressure and anthropometric measurements for children are available in the HBM4EU Deliverable 11.3. For obesity, the HBM4EU, EHES and EHIS standardised questions are presented in Appendix 22.2.

8.1.2 Defining metabolic syndrome in adults, adolescents and children

Although the major components of MetS are similar, their emphasis and threshold values vary greatly within the definitions. As the prevalence of MetS is highly dependent on the definition used, a review of literature was conducted to compare different definitions and their concordance.

According to the DECODE study by Qiao et al. (2006) among European population (n=10 000) there was a considerable discrepancy between individuals identified by the different definitions. From 2116 men who had metabolic syndrome by any of the three definitions of the WHO, NCEP-ATP III and IDF, only 707 (33.4%) met the criteria of all three, among 2096 women the respective number was 793 (37.8%). Among Irish cohort (n=1716) IDF identified higher prevalence of MetS in adults than NCEP-ATP III (Waterhouse et al., 2009). Among an Italian cohort (n=2051) Prevalence

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of MetS was significantly higher when using AHA and IDF definitions when compared to the ATP III definition (Mancia et al., 2010) and in a Swedish cohort (n=5047) MetS prevalence according to the IDF definition was higher in comparison to NCEP-ATPIII or EGIR definitions Nilsson et al. (2007). Among an Iranian cohort study (n=1200) prevalence of MetS was found to be highest with JIS's definition (39.3%), followed by IDF (34.2%), AHA/NLHBI (33%), ATP III 2004 (30.6%), WHO (28%) and ATP 2001 (26.2%). Concordance was considered to be high with JIS, IDF and AHA/NLHBI definitions. Similar agreements in the kappa values were detected by Ramli et al. (2013) when high level of agreement between the IDF and JIS was observed (Kappa index = 0.87), while there was a lower level of agreement between the IDF and NCEP-ATP III (Kappa index = 0.58). (Esmailzadehha et al., 2013.)

Literature in paediatric and adolescent metabolic syndrome reveals similar challenges as adults' MetS definition, as no agreed criteria exists (de Ferranti et al. 2004; Vanlancker et al., 2017; Weiss et al., 2013). Additional limitations in defining the syndrome among adolescents are due to challenges in defining the cut-off points, pubertal and racial differences and lack of cardiovascular events (Weiss et al., 2013). Currently the most commonly used definitions are by de Ferranti et al. (2004), Cook et al. (2003) and IDF consensus definition for children and adolescents (2007).

De Ferranti et al. (2004) based their definition of adolescent metabolic syndrome on The Adult Treatment Panel III (ATP III) and the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey done in the United States for adolescents between the ages 12-19 years, by adjusting the definitions and measurements to appropriate cut-off points and percentiles in triglyceride, HDL, fasting glucose, central obesity (waist circumference) and hypertension. Cook et al. (2003) similarly used data from the Third National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, but based their definition and cut-off points on National Cholesterol Education Program guidelines before the revision of ATP III. Using the same data, the MetS prevalence among adolescents by Cook et al. (2003) was 4 %, whereas in the de Ferranti et al.'s (2004) study the respective number was 10%. In 2007, IDF came out with definition of metabolic syndrome for children and adolescents (Zimmet et al., 2007).

In a European population based study (Vanlancker et al., 2015) 1004 healthy adolescents were compared by IDF, NCEP-ATPIII modified by Cook, Pediatric American Heart Association (AHA), WHO and Joliffe and Janssen's definitions. The Joliffe and Janssen definition resulted in the highest prevalence (3.8%) and WHO in the lowest (1.6%). No differences were found between age groups or sexes. The biggest agreement was between AHA and NCEP-ATPIII. Reinehr et al. (2007) compared eight definitions of metabolic syndrome prevalence among 1205 German children (4-16 years old, Caucasian children, 965 (80%) obese and 84 (20%) normal weight children) by using the criteria from Weiss, Viner, de Ferranti, Cook, WHO, EGIR, ATPIII and IDF. The frequency of MetS varied significantly between the definitions from 6-39%. Notably, Weiss, Viner, De Ferranti and Cook are meant to be used on children and adolescents as WHO, EGIR, ATPIII and IDF are definitions for adults. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome was most sensitive by using De Ferranti et al. (39%), followed by Weiss et al. (29%), Cook et al. (21%), Viner et al. (18%), IDF (14%), ATPIII (13%), EGIR (8%) and WHO (6%). A total of 114 (9%) children fulfilled the criteria in the proposed definitions for children or adolescents and 22 (2%) in all proposed definitions.

However, the stage of puberty also had an impact on the prevalence of MetS; de Ferranti and Cook reported 3-5 fold higher prevalence in pubertal adolescents compared to pre-pubertal children. In other definitions, pubertal stage did not influence the occurrence of MetS. Similar MetS detection rates were observed in other studies (Braga-Tavares & Fonseca, 2010; Saffari et al., 2012; Agudelo et al., 2014).

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8.2 Diabetes

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is caused by beta-cell dysfunction, but additionally insulin resistance has an effect. The burden of diabetes is globally increasing, as over 435 million people were diagnosed with diabetes in 2015 (Tuduri et al., 2018), and alarmingly the number of children and adolescents with T2DM is increasing (Stojanoska et al., 2017). Currently, over 90 % of all diabetes cases account from T2DM (Kuo et al., 2013). As for MetS, also T2DM is associated with life-style related factors, such as excess calorie assumptions and sedentary life-style (Thayer et al., 2012). Prediabetes is a stage that occurs on people who have impaired fasting glucose (IFG), impaired glucose intolerance (IGT) or elevated glycated haemoglobin (HbA1C). Prediabetes poses people at higher risk of developing diabetes and its complications, however the stage is still reversible back to normoglycemia by committing to healthier lifestyle choices. (Punthakee et al., 2018.)

Economic costs of both type 1 and type 2 diabetes are growing in Europe, partly because of the number of new cases, aging population and due to the complications associated with the disease. Within five EU countries (Spain, Germany, Italy, France and UK) the direct and indirect costs were estimated in 2010. The prevalence was estimated to vary between Italy's 4.8% to Germany's 8.9%. The total costs of diabetes were estimated to range between €5.45 bn (Spain) to €43.2 bn (Germany). Expenditure on insulin and oral antidiabetic medication ranged between 6.2% and 10.5% of total direct costs (Kanavos et al., 2012).

For retrieving diagnose codes from the ICD 10-coding, type 1 diabetes has code E10 and type 2 E11. In the upcoming ICD-11 coding, type 1 will be 5A10 and type 2 5A11. (WHO ICD-10, 2019). In the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC) –coding, diabetes is coded as T89 (Diabetes insulin dependent) and T90 (diabetes non-insulin dependent).

8.2.1 Measurement methods for diabetes

The WHO diagnostic criteria for diabetes and glucose abnormalities was updated in 2006 (Report of a WHO/IDF Consultation, 2006). The diagnostic criteria for diabetes for fasting plasma glucose was set at ≥ 7.0 mmol/l (126 mg/dl) or 2-h plasma glucose ≥ 11.1 mmol/l (200 mg/dl). The fasting plasma glucose cut-off point for Impaired Fasting Glucose (IFG) was set at 6.1 mmol/l. The oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) should be retained as a diagnostic test as fasting plasma glucose alone fails to diagnose approximately 30% of cases of previously undiagnosed diabetes. Currently, OGTT is the only means of identifying people with IGT and it is frequently needed to confirm or exclude an abnormality of glucose tolerance in asymptomatic people. OGTT testing should be used in individuals with fasting plasma glucose 6.1– 6.9 mmol/l (110–125 mg/dl) to determine glucose tolerance status. Currently HbA1c is not considered a suitable diagnostic test for diabetes or intermediate hyperglycaemia. Table 7 below presents the WHO (2006) recommendations.

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Table 7: The WHO 2006 recommendations for diagnostic criteria for diabetes, impaired glucose tolerance and impaired fasting glucose

Definition	Criteria	Cut-off limits
Diabetes	Fasting plasma glucose 2-h plasma glucose*	≥7.0 mmol/l or ≥11.1 mmol/l
Impaired fasting glucose	Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) 2-h plasma glucose*	<7.0 mmol/l and ≥7.8 and <11.1 mmol/l
Fasting plasma glucose	fasting plasma glucose 2-h plasma glucose*	6.1 to 6.9 mmol/l and (if measured) <7.8 mmol/l

EHES protocols can be found on the following procedures from <http://www.ehes.info/manuals.htm>. For diabetes the HBM4EU, EHES and EHIS standardised questions are presented only in Appendix 22.2.

8.3 Environmental chemicals associated with metabolic syndrome and diabetes

In the recent years, interest has grown towards understanding the association of environmental chemical exposure and their possible effects on the aetiology and pathophysiology of metabolic disturbances through endocrine disruption. WHO (2019) defined endocrine disruption as following “An endocrine disruptor is an exogenous substance or mixture that alters function(s) of the endocrine system and consequently causes adverse health effects in an intact organism, or its progeny, or (sub)-populations.” The mode of actions of EDCs include changes in the function of nuclear receptors such as estrogenic- (ERs), antiandrogenic- (ARs), progesterone-, retinoid- and thyroid-receptors (TRs) and in addition, in non-nuclear steroid hormone receptors (serotonin-, dopamine-, norepinephrine receptors) which are involved in the steroid biosynthesis and metabolism (Diamanti-Kandarakis et al., 2009). Other identified pathways include effects of epigenetic modifications in obesity-related genes, alteration in adipogenesis, interaction with peroxisome proliferator-activated receptors (PPAR γ) which increase lipid accumulation, as well as interaction with sex steroids and corticosteroid receptors (Diamanti-Kandarakis et al., 2009). Yet, several critical pathways are still unidentified.

The concept “window of vulnerability” focuses on examining vulnerable populations and timing of chemical exposure in relation to periods in early development when exposure can lead to long-lasting health effects in foetus, or in general in children (European Commission, Study for the strategy for a non-toxic environment of the 7th EAP, 2017). Additionally, work related exposure has been detected to be higher among certain occupational groups and industries (Caporossi & Papaleo, 2017; Leso et al., 2016), and furthermore, socioeconomic status may also increase vulnerability to certain chemicals (European Commission, Study for the strategy for a non-toxic environment of the 7th EAP, 2017). For instance, higher Bisphenol A concentrations have been measured among people with low socioeconomic background, whereas wealthier people are more likely to be exposed to higher quantities of perfluorinated compounds (European Commission, Study for the strategy for a non-toxic environment of the 7th EAP, 2017). Similar results have been seen already in children and adolescents, as higher BPA and BPS levels were detected in children living in families with lower income in comparison to children from higher income families (Jacobson et al., 2019). Very few studies have thus far focused on EDCs economic burden,

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however in a study exploring the costs of endocrine disrupting chemicals in the European Union, prenatal BPA exposure was identified to have a 20-69% probability of causing 42 400 cases of childhood obesity, with associated lifetime costs of €1.54 billion (Legler et al., 2015).

8.3.1 Bisphenols

8.3.1.1 Reviews on metabolic disturbances/MetS

According to the reviews and systematic reviews found in this literature search a positive association between BPA exposure, obesity and glucose metabolism were found (Rancire et al., 2015; Rochester, 2013, LaKind et al., 2013; Stojanoska et al., 2017; Kuo et al., 2013; Sowlat et al., 2016). For blood pressure and lipid metabolism results were suggestive, however less literature was available (LaKind et al., 2013; Rancire et al., 2015).

Several systematic reviews have been conducted in the past years to evaluate the current knowledge on BPA exposure and metabolic/glucose disturbances. According to Rochester's (2013) systematic review on metabolic diseases and BPA exposure, 22 studies were identified. 18 of these studies observed a positive association between BPA exposure and metabolic disturbances. Notably, there was variation in the strength of the studies, observed BPA concentrations and study populations.

Another systematic review was able to identify 17 studies on obesity related health outcomes and 10 studies on insulin resistance and BPA exposure (Stojanoska et al., 2017). 14 out of the 17 obesity related studies revealed a positive association and all of the studies including insulin resistance showed positive associations with BPA exposure (Stojanoska et al., 2017).

Rancire et al. (2015) conducted a large systematic review focusing on different MetS components. They identified 16 studies on obesity, overweight, adiposity and elevated waist circumference, 12 publications on diabetes, prediabetes or hyperglycemia and three publications on hypertension. From the 16 obesity related publications 13 studies identified a positive association with higher BPA urine concentrations and increased anthropometrics. After their meta-analysis (12 studies included), higher BPA exposure was significantly associated with obesity and elevated waist circumference among adult population. From the 12 diabetes related studies, eight were cross-sectional and seven found a positive association between higher BPA concentrations and diabetes, prediabetes or hyperglycemia. From the three studies focusing on hypertension, two presented a significant association, as one study reached the level of significance after restricting to participants without previous history of hypertension.

Interestingly, LaKind et al. (2013) scrutinised 39 obesity and BPA exposure related studies, from which 16 showed some positive associations in certain MetS components. However, they concluded the results to be inconsistent as statistically significant associations were detected mainly from two data sources: NHANES studies in USA (obesity) and Sognan study in China (BMI & WC). Glucose metabolism and diabetes outcomes were identified in 20 studies, from which six suggested positive associations in different glucose-related components. Noteworthy is that, most of the studies showed null results and only NHANES-based analyses reported statistically significant positive associations. For lipid metabolism six studies were identified from which four showed positive associations.

Sowlat et al. (2016) conducted a systematic review to analyse current knowledge on T2DM and BPA exposure. From 3108 hits, 13 original papers were included to the analysis. The authors state that the findings of these studies were controversial; few studies indicated a significant positive association between BPA exposure and T2DM (5 studies), while some other failed to detect any relationship.

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Furthermore, in a systematic review BPS and BPF were discovered to have similar endocrine disrupting effects such as BPA, thus more research is required (Rochester & Bolden, 2015).

8.3.1.2 Obesity

In a study conducted after the review of Rochester and Bolden (2015) examining BPS and BPF, Liu et al. (2019) investigated the association of obesity and BPA BPS and BPF among children and adolescents in the US, coming to a conclusion that exposure to BPF and obesity showed a significant association. Interestingly, the association was stronger among boys, which might suggest possible sex differences. Another prospective study showed correlation between exposure to BPA and BPS and later development of diabetes (Rancire et al, 2019). In a study based on the 2013-2016 NHANES survey of a similar population, BPA was not significantly associated with obesity, in contrast to BPS and BPF (Jacobson et al., 2019). Another study on several NHANES surveys concluded that many discrepancies can be observed concerning the correlation of BPA with obesity and recommended additional studies (Okubo et al, 2019). It is worth to note that there are still discussions as to the most accurate assay of total BPA and this may hamper some of the conclusions (Gerona et al, 2019).

In studies focusing on prenatal exposure and childhood the results have so far shown inconsistent results for BPA exposure. For instance, in a Mexican-American CHAMACOS-cohort focusing on mothers and their children, an association between higher urinary BPA levels and higher adiposity was identified in nine year-old children. Intriguingly, in the same study, exposure of BPA during mothers' pregnancy was associated with decreased BMI, body fat and weight among their 9-year old daughters. (Harley et al., 2013.) In another US study, prenatal and early-childhood BPA exposures were not associated with increased BMI among children between 2–5 years of age, but higher early-childhood BPA exposures were associated with increased growth during this period (Braun et al., 2014). In a Spanish cohort, a positive association was detected in prenatal BPA exposure and age-specific z-scores for BMI and waist circumference in four year old children (Valvi et al., 2013). The concordance between different population-based cohorts in BPA exposure and low-birth weight babies has been inconclusive, as some studies have shown positive, some negative and some null results (Chevalier & Fenichel, 2015).

Among older children, high urinary BPA levels were associated with overweight among 9-12 year old girls in China, with an odds ratio of 2.32 (95% CI 1.15-4.65). No similar effect was detected in older children or boys. Dose-response relationship revealed an increased risk of overweight with increased urine BPA levels ($p=0.006$). (Li et al., 2013.) In a NHANES data 2003-2008, high urinary BPA levels were associated with increased obesity, but not with overweight in 6-19 year olds, however the association was statistically significant only in white children and adolescents in comparison to Hispanic and black children (Trasande et al., 2012).

8.3.1.3 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes

Teppala et al. (2012) investigated association of BPA exposure and MetS among 2104 NHANES participants during the years 2003-2008. NCEP-ATP III definition was used as a MetS criteria. In the analysis BPA was positively associated with MetS, and the observed association was independent of confounding factors (age, gender, ethnicity, smoking, alcohol intake, PA levels and urinary creatinine) (P -trend=0.02). This study was the first to examine MetS as an outcome.

As already presented in the systematic reviews, high discrepancy between BPA exposure and diabetes still exists. Mostly this has been explained by methodological differences in outcomes, measurement methods and exclusion criterias used. For example association between BPA and DM has been stronger in the NHANES studies in comparison to studies conducted elsewhere, this has been explained by different methodological choices, see LaKind et al.'s (2013) review.

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Shankar and Teppala (2011) examined NHANES data from 2003-2008 and association of DM. Compared to the reference group (tertile1), the multivariate-adjusted OR of diabetes associated with the highest quartile (tertile 4) was 1.68 (95% CI: 1.22–2.30) (p-trend = 0.002).

BPA exposure at low dose may have a role in increasing risk of T2DM, directly acting on pancreatic cells in which BPA induces the impairment of insulin and glucagon secretion, decreases cell growth, increases apoptosis and triggers insulin resistant states. Pregnancy, pre- and perinatal periods was detected to be particularly susceptible for BPA action (Povvisiero et al., 2016.).

8.3.1.4 Lipid abnormalities

In a large meta-analysis conducted from NHANES cycles 2003-2014, 4606 children (under 18 years) and 10 989 adults (over 18 years). Urinary BPA levels and LDL-C, HDL-C, TC, TG and ApoB were examined in linear regression models. No association were detected among urinary BPA levels and the different lipid markers (Dunder et al., 2019). Among Chinese over 40 year olds (n=1872) lipid profile and development of incident dyslipidemia at baseline and after 4 years was examined. In the follow-up participants with high BPA at both baseline and follow-up showed an additional 2.9% increase in LDL-C (95% CI: 0.02-6.0) and 6.12% increase in TG (95% CI: 0.7-11.8), as compared with those who maintained low BPA levels. Participants who had high BPA at baseline and follow-up had increased odds of developing hyper-LDL cholesterolemia (OR 1.93, 95% CI: 1.0-3.7). (Wang et al., 2020.)

8.3.1.5 Hypertension/blood pressure

Reviews and individual studies concerning elevated blood pressure/hypertension are presented in the cardiovascular diseases and are not repeated here.

8.3.2 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

8.3.2.1 Reviews on metabolic disturbances/MetS

In a systematic review by Rappazzo et al. (2017) 16 studies were identified examining the effects of prenatal and childhood PFAS exposure and different adverse health outcomes in children. Among the different metabolic outcomes examined, only development of dyslipidemia suggested positive association with PFAS exposure. Parallel results were observed in a review by White et al. (2011) studying PFOA exposure and metabolic disturbances among children and adult populations. Christensen et al. (2019) examined data from the NHANES-studies from years: 2007-2008, 2009-2010, 2011-2012 and 2013-2014. According to their data, most PFAS failed to show consistent associations in statistical models. PFNA was associated with increased risk of MetS, increased WC, elevated triglyceride, decreased HDL when controlling for multiple PFAS. Whereas PFDE, PFOA, OFHxS, MPAH and PFUnDA were associated with decreased risk of certain MetS components, most consistent pattern shown with PFUnDA.

In a recent review focusing on epidemiologic evidence on associations between exposure to per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and the development of obesity, diabetes and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease/ non-alcoholic steatohepatitis, 22 studies were identified on obesity, 32 on diabetes and only 1 for non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. Overall, from the 55 studies approximately 2/3 reported positive associations between per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and the prevalence of obesity and/or type 1, type 2 or gestational diabetes (15 for obesity and 21 studies for T2DM). (Qi et al., 2020.)

8.3.2.2 Obesity

When examining vulnerable populations, children have been detected to have higher serum concentrations of PFAS in comparison to adults (Mondal et al., 2012). In a Danish cohort study of

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pregnant women and their offspring after 20 years, an association between low-dose in utero exposure to PFOA and the prevalence of overweight and high waist circumference was detected among female children. For male participants, the association was also visible, however not statistically significant. (Halldorsson et al., 2012.) In a study by Braun et al. (2016), PFOA exposure in utero was associated with higher adiposity in children aged 8 years, but no association was discovered with PFOS, PFNA or PFHxS exposures.

Adults' obesity related to PFASs was examined in a Danish Diabetes Prevention Program Trial (cohort study) among 957 participants for over 15 years. The initial lifestyle intervention consisted of training in diet, physical activity, and behavior modification, with the major goals of achieving weight loss with subsequent maintenance and a minimum recommended physical activity (150 mins/week). Participants randomised to placebo received standard information about diet and exercise. The PFAS concentrations were similar in both intervention arms. Higher plasma PFAS concentration and increase in weight and hip girth was seen over the follow-up time among adults at high risk for diabetes, but a lifestyle intervention attenuated these associations (Cardenas et al., 2018.).

8.3.2.3 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes among pregnancy, early life exposure

In Project Viva from 1999 to 2002, pregnant women (n=1540) first trimester plasma samples were analysed for eight PFAS compounds. At 28 weeks to women completed 1-hour nonfasting 50 gram oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT) and if abnormalities were identified, continued with 3-hour testing and screening for gestational diabetes. Four categories were developed; normal glycemia (reference group), isolated hyperglycemia, impaired glucose tolerance and gestational diabetes mellitus. As a result, PFASs were not associated with glucose tolerance categories (Preston et al., 2020.).

In nested case-control study by Xu et al. (2020) 165 pregnant women with GDM and 330 controls participated by in OGTT test (similar to Preston et al.'s study). PFOS and PFOA were detected at relatively high serum levels (medians 6.57 ng/mL and 8.07 ng/mL). The serum levels of PFBS and PFDoA were significantly higher in the GDM group in comparison to the controls ($p = 0.02$ and $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, quartile analysis showed OR of GDM significantly to increase at the highest PFBS and PFDoA levels.

Among Spanish pregnant women, PFOS and PFHxS have been associated with impaired glucose intolerance or gestational diabetes mellitus, and PFOA with increased maternal total cholesterol, which might imply PFAS exposure during pregnancy to influence maternal lipid metabolism and glucose tolerance (Matilla-Santander et al., 2017).

In a female nurses case-control study the potential demographic and lifestyle factors, plasma PFAS and T2DM prevalence were examined. 793 cases during the over six year follow-up were observed. PFOS and PFOA were associated with elevated risk for T2DM. Interestingly, shorter breastfeeding duration and higher intake of certain foods (such as seafood and popcorn) were significantly associated with higher plasma concentrations of PFASs among controls (Sun et al., 2018.).

8.3.2.4 Lipid abnormalities and hypertension

In a recently published research, 18 different serum PFAS concentrations were measured in 940 adolescents (mean age 16.4 years) in a Norwegian cross-sectional Fit for Futures study. PFOS, PFNA, PFDA and pePFUnDA serum concentrations were positively associated with apolipoprotein B, total- and LDL cholesterol among the adolescents. The highest vs. lowest quartiles of total PFAS, PFNA and PFDA concentrations were positively associated with the risk of dyslipidemia:

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OR 2.24 (95% CI: 1.10–4.54), OR 2.30 (95% CI: 1.16–4.57) and 2.36 (95% CI: 1.08–5.16). The highest vs. lowest quartiles of total PFAS, PFHxS, PFOS and PFOA concentrations were positively associated with the risk of hypertension: OR 1.91 (95% CI: 1.12–3.26), OR 2.06 (95% CI: 1.16–3.65), 1.86 (95% CI: 1.08–3.19) and 2.08 (95% CI: 1.17–3.69). PFHxS and PFHpS concentrations were positively associated with obesity (Averina et al., 2021.).

In another Norwegian cross-sectional study, 891 mother-child pairs were examined for PFAS exposure and elevated lipids during pregnancy. PFAS and lipid samples were obtained at mid-pregnancy and analysed for 19 different PFASs. As a result, higher PFOS concentration was associated with total cholesterol, which increased by 4.2mg/dL per inter-quartile shift (95% CI: 0.8-7.7). Five different compounds of PFASs were positively associated with increase in HDL cholesterol, and PFOA, PFNA, PFDA, PFUnDA, PFHxS, PFHpS and PFOS had elevated HDL associated with the highest quartile of exposure (Starling et al., 2014.).

In US, 888 prediabetic adults from the Diabetes Prevention Program (DPP) and DPP Outcomes Study, who had measurements of six different plasma PFAS concentrations at baseline (1996-1999) and repeated measures of blood lipids over 15 years of follow-up were included in a study by Lin et al. (2019). Higher total cholesterol at baseline per doubling was observed of PFOA (β : 6.1 mg/dL, 95% CI 3.1-9.04), PFHxS, β : 2.2 mg/dL, 95% CI 0.2-4.3), and PFNA, β : 2.9 mg/dL, 95% CI 0.7-5.0). PFOA, PFOS, PFHxS and PFNA predicted higher risks of incident for hypercholesterolemia and hypertriglyceridemia, however the effects were seen only in the placebo group and not the lifestyle intervention group (Lin et al., 2019).

8.3.3 Phthalates

8.3.3.1 Reviews on metabolic disturbances/MetS

Our examination of the available review literature suggests a positive association between Phthalates and obesity related factors (Stojanoska et al., 2017; Radke et al., 2019; Golestanzadeh et al., 2019) and glucose metabolism (Radke et al., 2019; Stojanoska et al., 2017; Kuo et al., 2013).

Golestanzadeh et al. (2019) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on paediatric (0-18 years) studies focusing on phthalate exposure and cardio-metabolic risk factors. Eight studies were identified to focus on children's dyslipidemia, from which only MEOHP showed significant correlation in the pooled results. No other correlation was detected between LMWP or HMWPs. 26 studies were identified to concentrate on obesity. In the meta-analysis pooled correlation was significant for BMI (for both LMWP and HMWP), BMI z-score (for both LMWP and HMWP) and for some high molecular weight metabolites in waist circumference (MEHP, MEHPP and MBzP). Also Stojanoska et al. (2017) identified ten studies, all identifying positive associations on phthalate exposure and obesity, higher BMI or increased waist circumference in adults and in children, the highest effect being on DEHP, DEP and DBP. Additionally, all 11 identified studies on insulin resistance and related effects revealed positive associations.

In a systematic review by Radke et al. (2019), current evidence and strength of the studies between different phthalates and diabetes or insulin resistance were examined. They concluded a moderate association for DEHP exposure and diabetes, and for insulin resistance four out of five studies indicated a positive association between the exposure and outcome. For DBP and DiBP exposure, the evidence was considered moderate due to strong positive associations in one diabetes study and coherent results for insulin resistance. For DiNP, DBP, and DEP previous studies were less consistent and lacked coherence.

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Song et al. (2016) assessed in their review endocrine disruptors effect on development of T2DM. Six studies were included in their analysis. High urinary phthalate concentration (highest vs. lowest concentration categories) showed the pooled relative risk of 1.48 (95% CI: 0.98-2.25).

Gao et al., (2021) conducted a systematic review on prenatal phthalate exposure and gestational metabolic syndrome (GSM). Fourteen studies were included, two using one-spot urine sample and other studies used 1-4 urine samples. The included studies observed inconclusive results on the consistency of the association between phthalates and GSM in pregnant women cross-sectionally or longitudinally, regardless of phthalates species or GSM indicator.

8.3.3.2 Individual studies on MetS

In the NHANES (2001-2010) data, higher concentrations of all urinary phthalate metabolites were detected among participants with MetS. In more detail, high DEHP-metabolite concentrations were associated with increased odds in men, while in women highest association with MetS was with MBzP-metabolite (James-Todd et al., 2016). Among adolescents, urinary phthalate metabolites and association with MetS was examined from the NHANES data (2003-2014), supporting a positive association between MnBP-metabolites and MetS. Adolescents with intermediate concentrations had over two-fold higher odds of MetS than adolescents with lowest concentrations (T2: OR 2.66 95% CI 0.98-7.24 and T3: OR 2.11 95% CI 0.71-6.27). Higher metabolite-concentrations were also associated with individual MetS components (higher waist circumference, high triglycerides, low HDL) especially among male participants (Gaston & Tulve, 2019.).

In a recent study, Milošević et al. (2020) divided 305 subjects to three different categories; obese (BMI >30 kg/m²), patients with T2DM diagnosis and healthy, normal weight controls. In the obese subgroup, the sum of all urinary phthalate metabolites (nine measured) was significantly associated with TG levels (p = 0.031) together with derived TC/HDL (p=0.023) and TG/HDL (p=0.015) ratios. Among the T2DM subgroup, HOMA-IR and urinary MEP concentration was positively associated (p = 0.016). Furthermore, in the T2DM subgroup urinary MEHP levels were associated with glucose serum levels (p = 0.02). For the control subgroup, log₁₀MEP levels were negatively correlated with total cholesterol (p = 0.0051) and LDL serum levels (p = 0.0015).

The association of insulin resistance, MetS and cumulative risk of phthalate exposure (daily intake (DI) and hazard index (HI)) among younger adults was examined by Ko et al. (2019). 435 military personnel in Taiwan participated in the assessment of dimethyl phthalate (DMP), diethyl phthalate, dibutyl phthalate, benzyl butyl phthalate (BBzP), and di (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate. Higher DMP levels were associated with an increased odds of high HOMA-IR (OR 1.7, 95% CI 1.1–2.6) and MetS (OR 2.33, 95% CI 1.3-4.3). Higher BBzP and hazard index were associated with an increased odds of abdominal obesity (OR 1.8, 95% CI 1.18–2.8) (Ko et al., 2019.).

8.3.3.3 Lipid abnormalities

757 mother-child pairs were measured for phthalates during first, second and third trimester of pregnancy. Children's non-fasting lipids, glucose and insulin levels were measured at age 9. An interquartile range (IQR) higher natural log transformed third trimester maternal urine phthalic acid concentration was associated with a 0.20 (95% CI 0.07-0.34) standard deviation score higher triglycerides concentration among boys. An IQR higher natural log transformed second trimester maternal high molecular weight phthalates and di-2-ethylhexylphthalate (DEHP) urine concentration were associated with a 0.19 (95% CI 0.31-0.07) respectively 0.18 (95% CI 0.31-0.06) SDS lower glucose concentration among boys. (Sol et al., 2020). In a similar study, examining 248 Mexican children, higher concurrent levels of mono-3-carboxypropyl phthalate (MCPP), monoethyl phthalate (MEP), and dibutyl phthalate metabolites (DBP) corresponded with lower total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein (LDL-C) in boys (IQR increment in MCPP

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corresponded with 7.4%, lower total cholesterol and 12.7% lower LDL-C. In girls, higher urinary di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate metabolites (Σ DEHP) correlated with lower LDL-C. (Perng et al., 2017.)

8.3.3.4 Blood pressure/hypertension

Studies focusing on the association of phthalates and blood pressure/hypertension are presented in chapter Cardiovascular diseases.

8.3.4 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

8.3.4.1 Individual studies on MetS

Two studies have focused on coke oven workers and their exposure to PAHs (Zhang et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2017). Both studies observed some association to development of different MetS components; Zhang et al. (2020) concluded that high urinary levels of 1-Hydroxynaphthalene (1-NAP) and 2-Hydroxyfluorene (2-FLUO) presented a significant dose-response relationship with increased prevalence of MetS and furthermore, 1-NAP was positively associated with low HDL-C (p for trend = 0.003). Yang et al. (2017) who focused on the association of PAH exposure and DM concluded that elevated urinary 4-hydroxyphenanthrene (4-OHPH) was significantly associated with increased risk of diabetes (p for trend = 0.003). Coke workers in the highest 4-OHPH quartile had an adjusted OR of 2.80 (95% CI: 1.37–5.71) for diabetes in comparison to the lowest quartile.

In a NHANES study (2001-2008) eight urinary metabolites of four PAH components were examined among 1878 non-diabetic adults. The metabolite 2-FLUO was significantly associated with increased insulin resistance and 3-Hydroxyfluorene (3-FLUO) was significantly associated with decreased β -cell function ($p < 0.05$). Additionally, increased concentrations of 2-FLUO (OR 1.25) 1-Hydroxyphenanthrene (1-PHEN) (OR 1.36, 95%) and 2-Hydroxyphenanthrene (2-PHEN) (OR 1.49) were significantly associated with a higher prevalence of MetS after adjusting for covariates (Hu et al., 2015.).

Using the same NHANES cycle data (2001-2008) as Hu et al. (2015), Ranjbar et al., (2015) examined 4765 adult participants and the exposure to PAHs and MetS components. Firstly, there was a dose-dependent association between obesity and 2-NAP (p trend < 0.0001), however the authors observed in the same study that the higher exposure to 1-NAP was associated with lower risk of obesity (p trend = 0.0004). For BMI, participants in the highest quintile of 2-NAP, 2-FLUO, 3-FLUO and 2-PHEN had a 66-80% greater chance of having 3 or more related risk factors (obesity, T2DM, hypertension or dyslipidemia) in comparison to the lower levels. Also, T2DM risk was significantly higher in the high quintiles of 1-NAP, 2-NAP, 2-PHEN and 1-pyrene. Similarly 1-NAP, 2-NAP, 2-FLUO, 3-FLUO and 2-PHEN were associated with higher likelihood (38-68%) for dyslipidemia and for 2-NAP and 2-PHEN for hypertension (Ranjbar et al., 2015.).

8.3.4.2 Obesity

In an Iranian study, 186 children aged 6-18 years participated in two measurements of urinary PAHs, six months apart. For children without any cardiometabolic risk factors, exposure to 2-naphtol, 9-phenanthrol, and Σ OH-PAH were associated with increased risk of obesity, and exposure to 1-hydroxypyrene was associated with higher risk of cardiometabolic risk factors in children who had excess weight (Poursafa et al., 2018.).

Among children (6-11 years) and adolescents (12-19 years) urinary PAHs and childhood obesity was assessed in a NHANES study (2001-2006). Overall, 3189 children were included and BMI z-score, WC, and obesity were positively associated with the molecular mass sum of the PAHs and the total sum of naphthalene metabolites (Scinicariello & Buser, 2014.).

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Among Chinese adults (n=2716) with poor lung function Hou et al. (2017) found a positive association between several different urinary OH-PAHs and diabetes in participants with central obesity or normal weight ($p < 0.05$).

8.3.4.3 Glucose abnormalities/Diabetes

In a recent systematic review and meta-analysis, Khosravipour and Khosravipour (2020) examined the literature on urinary PAH metabolites and diabetes. Six cross-sectional studies (with 24 406 participants in total) were included. Significantly higher odds of DM in the highest in comparison to the lowest category of urinary naphthalene, fluorine, phenanthrene and total OH-PAH metabolites were observed. The pooled OR was estimated for naphthalene at 1.47 (1.17-1.78), fluorine 1.50 (1.29-1.71), phenanthrene 1.41 (1.21-1.60), and total OH-PAHs 1.61 (1.01-2.21). In addition, a significant association per 1-fold increase in FLU (OR 1.09, 95% CI: 1.00-1.19) and PHEN (OR 1.19, 95% CI: 1.08 -1.30) metabolites were seen. Studies of Yang et al., 2014, Hou et al., 2017, Ranjbar et al., 2015 were included in the analysis (presented in the previous chapter) and in addition, Stallings-Smith et al., 2018 and Alshaarawy et al., 2014 were included. Both Stallings-Smith et al. and Alshaarawy et al. used NHANES adult data from different cycles (2005-2014 and 2005-2006, respectively) observing some association between exposure and development of DM.

8.3.5 Pesticides

8.3.5.1 Reviews on DM

Evangelou et al. (2016) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis on observational studies focusing on pesticide exposure and DM. 22 individual studies were identified. The pooled OR between the highest and lowest tertile of any type of pesticide exposure and DM was 1.58 (95% CI: 1.32-1.90) with large heterogeneity in the results. Studies focusing particularly on T2DM (n=13) showed similar trends (OR between highest and lowest tertile) was 1.61 (95% CI: 1.37-1.88) with no heterogeneity.

Another systematic review (Jaacks et al., 2015) focusing on Asian population and pesticide exposure identified 19 individual articles on POPs and non-persistent pesticides and diabetes/diabetes related outcomes. The authors state that positive associations were reported between serum concentrations of polychlorinated dibenzodioxins and dibenzofurans (PCDD/Fs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and several organochlorine pesticides (DDT, DDE, oxychlorane, trans-nonachlor, hexachlorobenzene, hexachlorocyclohexane) with DM. PCDD/Fs were also associated with blood glucose and insulin resistance, but not with beta-cell function. Furthermore, the authors raised concern about the limitations in the evidence; most studies were cross-sectional, only few studies had addressed selection bias and confounding factors and most effect estimates had wide confidence intervals.

8.3.5.2 Individual studies on MetS

Pesticide exposures effect to development of MetS has so far yielded some evidence of association. 548 community members from Anniston, USA, were included in the study where nine different pesticides were examined from blood samples. NCEP-ATP III definition was used as criteria for MetS. Seven pesticides showed significant associations to MetS across the quintiles in each of the unadjusted models (p,p'-DDT, p,p'-DDE, HCB, β -HCH, oxychlor, tNONA, Mirex) (Rosenbaum et al., 2017.).

Park et al. (2010) examined similarly to Rosenbaum et al. (2017) community members (50 non-diabetic cases and 50 controls) exposure to organochlorine pesticide and MetS. The authors found that after adjusting for all other confounders except for BMI, beta-hexachlorocyclohexane and heptachlor epoxide were positively associated with MetS (OR across tertiles of β -HCH (1.0, 3.2

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and 4.4) and heptachlor epoxide (1.0, 4.0 and 6.0), revealing p-trend 0.01 and <0.01. Interestingly, when analyzing the five components of MetS individually, the components were positively but not statistically significantly associated with heptachlor epoxide.

A cohort study (average follow-up time 2.64 years) was conducted to assess the incidence of MetS among Korean farmers (n=1162). The authors calculated relative risks to estimate the relationship between pesticide exposure and MetS. Participants who had been exposed to pesticides had an elevated incidence in comparison to the non-exposed (20.7% vs. 12.1%, p<0.01). To date, this has been the only study to assess the relationship between incidence of MetS and pesticide exposure (Kim et al., 2019.).

8.3.5.3 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes and obesity

Xiao et al. (2017) presented in their review current knowledge on insecticide exposure and risk of diabetes in humans. All age groups, study designs and insecticides (organochlorines, organophosphorus, carbamates, pyrethroid mixtures and other insecticides and their subgroups) were included in the study. The authors presented both human and animal studies included in the review, concluding that exposure to insecticides increases the risk of developing obesity and type 2 diabetes, even though some inconsistent results do exist. The authors further claim that the discrepancy between results maybe due to dose, duration and exposure, methods used, diet and designs (especially in animal studies). Furthermore, the authors point out the relatively small number of obesity and pesticide related studies in comparison to glucose abnormalities/DM. Only four studies were identified, having highly inconsistent results.

In a US long cohort study, CARDIA, participants were followed for up to twenty years aiming to examine the possible association of 8 organochlorine pesticides, 22 polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and 1 polybrominated biphenyl (PBB). The investigation revealed that some OC pesticides and PCBs predicted excess adiposity, dyslipidemia, and insulin resistance among participants without diabetes (Lee et al., 2011.).

8.3.5.4 Blood pressure/hypertension

Studies focusing on the association of pesticides and blood pressure/hypertension are presented in the chapter Cardiovascular diseases.

8.3.5.5 Lipid abnormalities

A 23 year long cohort study examined exposure to POPs (including organochlorine pesticides (OCPs) and polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs). A very higher number of POPs were detected among the participants (32 POPs in ≥75% of participants; 23 PCBs, 8 OCPs and PBB-153). POPs in young adults were associated with blood lipids measured up to 23 years later. Positive associations between PCBs and most lipid components were observed however no associations with any of the lipid outcomes was observed among the eight OCPs (Suarez-Lopez et al., 2019.).

8.3.6 Cadmium

Heavy metal exposure has been shown to have several adverse health effects among general population, and especially among occupational exposure. Interestingly, Jeong et al. (2018) investigated possible risk factors for development of MetS among Korean blue-collar workers. The authors found that in addition to lifestyle factors, working with metals increased the risk of MetS (OR 1.8, 95% CI: 1.058-3.013).

8.3.6.1 Obesity

In a review by Tinkov et al. (2017) the association between overweight, obesity and Cd exposure seemed to be so far controversial. The authors concluded that human studies on obesity and Cd

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are scarce and the results contradictory. Among girls and women the association of BMI and Cd exposure seemed to be more prevalent (Kim et al., 2015; Skalnaya et al., 2014). At the same time, Tinkov et al. (2017) state that several studies (n=6) show no interaction between obesity, anthropometrics and Cd exposure. Laboratory and experimental studies (n=14) demonstrated Cd's effect on adipose tissue physiology, and further with obesity pathogenesis.

8.3.6.2 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes

Meta-analysis of fifteen studies on Cd exposure and risk of diabetes or related metabolic disturbances (HOMA-IR, HOMA- β , IGT, FPG, HbA1c, prediabetes risk, fasting insulin) showed that among the highest versus lowest cadmium exposure categories, an increased risk of diabetes incidence was detected (OR= 1.38, 95 % CI: 1.12-1.71). Notably, studies that used urine as exposure assessment had the highest values (Tinkov et al., 2017). Satarug et al. (2017) present in their review studies that show an association between Cd exposure and diabetic risk. The studies suggest oxidative stress and chronic inflammation among individuals with high exposure of Cd to possibly increase the risk of diabetes and obesity. A review by Kuo et al. (2013) concluded based on three studies (Swaddiwudhipong et al., 2010; Barregard et al., 2013; Moon, 2013) that the epidemiologic evidence does not seem to suggest an association with diabetes.

Cd exposure's effects on gestational diabetes (GDM) were examined in nested case-control study in China. Urinary Cd levels were higher among the pregnant women having GDM and revealing an increased risk on GDM (Ptrend =0.003). Compared to the first tertile of Cd, the adjusted odds ratios (95% confidence intervals) of GDM risk were 2.08 (1.29, 3.36) for the second tertile and 2.09 (1.32, 3.33) for the third tertile. (Li et al., 2020). The association of GDM and Cd exposure are further strengthened by similar results by Liu et al. (2018) and Xing et al. (2018).

8.3.6.3 Lipid abnormalities

In a Chinese occupational cross-sectional survey (n=1489), demographic data, blood Cd level and lipid profile in cadmium exposed workers from seven cadmium smelting factories were collected. Mean blood cadmium concentration of workers with dyslipidemia was significantly higher than that of workers without dyslipidemia (p <0.01). Elevated Cd levels were also associated with increased BMI (p<0.01). The prevalence of high TC, high TG, Low HDL-C and high LDL-C rose with increases in blood cadmium levels dose-dependently. The odds ratios for dyslipidemia across the increasing blood cadmium quartiles were 1.21 (95% CI: 1.16-1.55), 1.56 (95% CI: 1.11-1.87), 1.79 (95% CI: 1.26-2.25) respectively to the reference group of 1.0 (Zhou et al., 2016). In a NHANES study (2007-2010) higher urinary Cd levels were associated to LDL-cholesterol after adjusting for confounding (Obeng-Gyasi, 2020).

8.3.6.4 Blood pressure/hypertension

Studies focusing on the association of cadmium and blood pressure/hypertension are presented in chapter Cardiovascular diseases.

8.3.7 Arsenic

8.3.7.1 Obesity

Eick and Steinmaus (2020) presented in their review causation of arsenic exposure and obesity based on animal and human studies. The animal studies (n=6) seemed to provide some evidence of arsenic exposure and development of obesity, as human studies (n=11) did not consistently confirm the association. Farkondeh et al. (2019) presented seven epidemiological studies focusing on adults' obesity and As exposure, revealing similarly to Eick and Steinmaus (2020) inconsistent findings on the association. For both reviews, the authors suggest the inconsistent results be due to differences in arsenic dose, form and route of exposure. Only one study was identified to assess

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children's As exposure and development of obesity and other metabolic disturbances. For elementary aged school children better arsenic methylation capability was observed in comparison to junior high school students, and furthermore higher BMI values and higher total As concentration were associated with higher HOMA-IR values in children and adolescents in Taiwan (Lin et al., 2014).

8.3.7.2 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes

Kuo et al. (2013) identified nine studies focusing on high level As exposure and type 2 diabetes, concluding limited to sufficient association. With low to moderate level exposure, 19 studies were identified and insufficient data was found to support the association. The study group concluded in their systematic review that evidence from current studies is suggestive, but not yet sufficient to understand the relationship between As exposure and development of diabetes. In a systematic review by Leso et al. (2016) occupational chemical risk exposure and risk of diabetes were assessed. In this review, occupational workers in smelters and glass-workers were identified as a risk group. However, the results were inconclusive, as in some studies the association was statistically significant and in others no association was detected.

8.3.7.3 Blood pressure/hypertension

Studies focusing on the association of arsenic and blood pressure/hypertension are presented in chapter Cardiovascular diseases.

8.3.7.4 Lipid abnormalities

In a recent systematic review Zhao et al. (2021) assessed lipid metabolism dysfunction and arsenic exposure. Five studies were included in the analysis. The authors concluded that As exposure can affect lipid metabolism by reducing serum HDL levels and increasing serum LDL levels.

One smaller study was found to examine occupational exposure among firework workers. 57 cases and 57 controls were recruited in the study. TC, TG, HDL-C, LDL-C and lipoproteins, apolipoproteins A and B were measured. No significant differences were detected between the TC, TG, HDL-C and LDL-C levels between the groups. Apo-A1 level in the exposed employees was lower than the normal range and significantly less than in the control group. (Ledda et al., 2018.)

8.3.8 Mercury

8.3.8.1 Reviews on MetS/DM

The evidence between Mercury (Hg) and metabolic disorders were examined in Tinkov et al.'s (2015) systematic review, suggesting sufficient association between total Hg exposure and obesity, DM, insulin resistance, hypertension and dyslipidemia, however the current evidence was not sufficient to present causality. The authors presented 13 human studies, which indicated some effects in blood pressure and Hg exposure. Six studies on obesity showed association with exposure to Hg, as one study failed to show any association. For glucose metabolism/DM the results were more inconclusive; six studies showed positive link and three (including one systematic analysis) found no association in human studies. Additionally, dyslipidemia and atherosclerosis showed inconsistent results.

Similar results were discovered in Roy et al.'s (2017) systematic review focusing on diabetes, metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance and Hg exposure. They included 34 studies in their analysis and concluded that there is evidence that suggests a possible association between Hg and incidence of MetS and/or DM. However, the authors conclude again that the evidence is not consistent. As challenges for comparisons, the authors stated that in the included studies there was lack of mention on the Hg specie or the type of diabetes examined in the studies.

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The third systematic review concluded that data from model organisms suggest a possible association between Hg exposure and development of MetS, albeit human data is still inconclusive (Planchart et al., 2018). The reasons for inconsistency in the data were explained by complexity of defining MetS, its cultural differences among populations, different development stages among populations and sex-differences, which makes identifying exposure-related outcomes challenging (Planchart et al., 2018).

8.3.8.2 Glucose abnormalities/diabetes

In a prospective cohort study of American young adults (20-32 yrs), following them for 18 years measuring their toenail mercury levels, revealed an increased risk of diabetes compared the highest and the lowest quintiles of Hg exposure. HR was 1.65 (1.07-2.56; P for trend = 0.02). This longitudinal study suggests that people with high mercury exposure during their young adulthood might have increased risk of DM later in life (He et al., 2013).

Another study focusing on Inuits (n=2640) over 18 years of age assessed the possible link between fish (accumulation fro Hg high) and DM. 5 µg/L increase in whole blood mercury had a positive association with fasting glucose (p < 0.001), and 2-h glucose (p = 0.01). Hg was weakly associated with impaired fasting glycemia (OR 1.03, 95% CI: 1.02-1.05), and T2DM (OR 1.02, 95% CI: 1.01-1.04) (Jeppesen et al., 2015.).

In a National Nutrition and Health Survey in Taiwan during years 2005-2008 total of 646 adults were measured for blood and urine Hg and dietary habits, medical history, socioeconomic status and lifestyle habits were collected. Participants who had T2DM had significantly higher red blood cell Hg (RBC-Hg) levels in comparison to non-diabetics. OR of 1.64 (95%CI: 1.14-2.35) was observed between RBC-Hg and T2DM (Tsai et al., 2019.).

8.3.8.3 Blood pressure/hypertension

Two systematic reviews were identified on assessing Hg exposure and hypertension. The studies are presented in chapter Cardiovascular diseases.

8.3.9 Lead

8.3.9.1 Reviews on MetS

Planchart et al. (2018) identified in their review 18 studies evaluating associations between Pb and MetS components (1 prospective, 17 cross-sectional or case-control studies). Seven studies reported statistically significant associations between Pb exposure and MetS. Five focused on adults and two on children. Four studies found no association with urine/blood Pb and diabetes, and similarly four studies found no association between blood Pb and MetS using anthropometric measures. The authors conclude that the data available is still inconsistent and requires further examination.

One more study in addition to the ones included in the Planchart et al.'s (2018) review, was by Park et al. (2019), who examined blood Pb and MetS risk. 2833 participants were included in the study. SBP, DBP, TG and fasting plasma glucose demonstrated significant differences by blood lead level (p < 0.001). SBP and DBP, WC, fasting plasma glucose and TG levels were positively correlated with blood lead level (p < 0.005), whereas HDL-C was negatively correlated (r = -0.038, p < 0.005).

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8.4 Highlights

The prevalence of metabolic diseases has increased and is still increasing among adults as well as children. Although changes in lifestyle factors are recognised as driving this trend, role for ubiquitous EDCs with obesogenic and adipogenic effects are also indicated. Hence, novel approaches to tackle the challenge are needed. Assessing the health effects of EDCs is challenging due to their complex qualities and diverse pathways, such as dose-response relationship, mixed-chemical exposure, sex-differences, sensitive windows of exposure and insufficient data coverage.

Although some MetS components have been widely researched (e.g. obesity and glucose metabolism), others have gained less focus (dyslipidemia and hypertension). From chemical perspective, BPA and Phthalate exposure have been more widely examined in relation to other EDCs associated with MetS, such as PFASs and heavy metals.

Current evidence on the associations of metabolic disturbances and EDC exposures are inconclusive and fragmented, hence establishing harmonised and standardised Human Biomonitoring procedures among the European population are needed. Rigorous and ongoing Human Biomonitoring in combination with health monitoring could provide comprehensive information on EDC exposure and association of metabolic disturbances.

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9 Reproductive health

Authors: Rambaud Loïc (ANSP), Riou Margaux (ANSP)

9.1 Markers of reproductive health presentation

The human reproductive system develops early at embryonic and foetal stages. The reproductive system evolves from birth, and even before, to the end of puberty. Different markers unchanged in time are thus needed to measure, standardise, valid and allow comparisons.

Under the HBM4EU project, seven markers of reproductive health were selected: anogenital distance, cryptorchidism, hypospadias, semen quality, sperm DNA damage, reproductive hormones and fertility, and fecundity. Each marker has a clinical diagnosis, sometimes ICD codes, monitoring of population and enables an assessment of reproductive health. Recently, other female markers were proposed such as endometriosis, fibromas and polycystic ovary syndrome (Rigou et al. 2020).

9.1.1 Anogenital distance

AGD is an important clinical measure of EDCs' health effects in environmental toxicology and it has been identified as one of the endpoints in the US Environmental Protection Agency guidelines for reproductive toxicity studies.

Anogenital distance (AGD) is the distance between the anus and the external genitalia and can be measured among new-borns, children or adults. A short male AGD is strongly associated with genital malformations at birth and reproductive disorders in adulthood (Schwartz et al. 2019). Regulated by dihydrotestosterone, AGD is a hormone-sensitive marker of development in rodent models, and presumably reflects the gestational androgen exposure (Salazar-Martinez et al. 2004). In humans, there is a sex difference in AGD length between normal males and normal females (50–100%) (Le Moal et al. 2016). Clinical measurement of AGD may provide a means of 'looking back in time' and discerning the level of androgen exposure during the "Masculinisation Programming Window" during early gestation. It can serve as a lifelong biomarker of the action of androgens in utero, or conversely, on the androgen effect's disruption. It has been used as a non-invasive biomarker of androgen disruption in utero by several groups of investigators (Thankamony et al. 2016).

AGD can be measured in mm or using anogenital index (AGI, dimensionless).

According to the International Classification for Diseases 10 (ICD-10) the code which should be used for anogenital distance is Q55.8 for males and Q52.8 for females. In the ICPC-2 code, X83 "Congenital anomaly genital female" and Y84 "Congenital genital anomaly (male), other" could be used.

The AGD is measured using a Vernier caliper. The newborn infant is in the dorsal decubitus position; both hips are flexed and light pressure is exerted on the infant's thighs until the examiner's hand touches the subject's abdomen (Salazar-Martinez et al. 2004). In males, a short AGD is measured from the center of anus to the posterior base of scrotum (AGD anoscrotal or ASD) and a long AGD is measured from the center of anus to the cephalad insertion of the penis (AGD anopenile or APD). Correspondingly, in females, a short AGD is measured from the center of anus to the posterior fourchette (AGD anofourchette or AFD) and along AGD from the center of anus to the top of clitoris (AGD anoclitoris or ACD) (Dalsager et al. 2018; Arbuckle et al. 2020).

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9.1.2 Cryptorchidism

Cryptorchidism is defined as the non-descent or the absence of at least one testicle in the scrotum.

It is the most common male genital defect at birth (Toppari et al. 2010). Testicular descent is normally controlled by endocrinal factors. Testicular descent occurs in two phases, an abdominal descent phase during the first trimester and an inguinal scrotal descent phase during the third trimester. The two phases are influenced by testicular androgens (Gurney et al. 2017; Toppari et al., 2014). Chemical substances with endocrine-inducing effects can lead to the risk of cryptorchidism in sons of mothers exposed during pregnancy (Brucker-Davis et al. 2003). Cryptorchidism represents one of the commonest congenital malformations in boy newborns with incidences of 2-9% (Toppari et al. 2010). The diagnosis of cryptorchidism is mainly done by physical examination (palpable tests), but in some cases may also require laparoscopic surgery (non palpable undescended tests) which is not feasible in the population studies (Jamalalail, Guerra, and Leonard 2016).

According to the International Classification for Diseases 10 (ICD-10) the code for cryptorchidism is Q53 named "Undescended testicle". Moreover, codes 55.0 "Absence and aplasia of testis – Monorchism" and 55.2 "Other congenital malformations of testis and scrotum such as testis migrans" could be used too. In the ICD-11 the codes are LB52 "Cryptorchidism", LB52.0 "Ectopic testis", LB52.1 "Undescended testicle, unilateral", LB52.2 "Undescended testicle, bilateral", LB52.Y "Other specified cryptorchidism" and LB52.Z "Cryptorchidism, unspecified". The relevant ICPC-2 code is Y83 "Undescended testicle".

9.1.3 Hypospadias

Hypospadias is a urogenital birth defect affecting infant boys with an incidence of one in 200 (Keays and Dave 2017).

Hypospadias is the second most common genital anomaly at birth with incidences of 0.2-1% (Toppari et al. 2010). The diagnosis of hypospadias is made after birth during physical exam. However, hypospadias result from incomplete urethral closure during development of the external genitalia, between the 8th and 12th gestational weeks (Hughes et al. 2001). Hypospadias is a midline fusion defect of the male ventral urethra causing an abnormal location of the urethral meatus. The standard classification of hypospadias is based on location of the urethral meatus: distal, midshaft, or proximal. Some studies have shown a positive relationship between potential exposures to endocrine-disrupting chemicals during pregnancy and hypospadias in male children (Kalfa et al. 2015; Nassar et al. 2010; Skakkebaek 2016).

According to the International Classification for Diseases 10 (ICD-10) the code for hypospadias is Q54. Moreover, codes 55.5 "Congenital absence and aplasia of penis" and 55.6 "Other congenital malformations of penis" could be used. For the ICD-11 codes are; LB53.0 "Hypospadias, balanic", LB53.1 "Hypospadias, penile", LB53.2 "Hypospadias, penoscrotal", LB53.3 "Hypospadias, scrotal", LB53.4 "Hypospadias, perineal", LB53.Y "Other specified hypospadias" and LB53.Z "Hypospadias, unspecified". For the ICPC-2 the code is Y82 "Hypospadias".

The diagnosis of hypospadias is usually made after birth during a physical exam (Keays & Dave 2017).

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9.1.4 Semen quality

Semen quality is an important marker for couple fecundity (ability to conceive), and is not a single outcome measure but an overall term that includes four main indicators (Rolland et al. 2012):

- Sperm concentration (spermatozoa/ml)
- Sperm count (millions of sperm per milliliter)
- Morphology (% normal spermatozoa)
- Mobility (% motile spermatozoa)

Investigators often dichotomise outcomes according to guidelines adopted by the World Health Organisation, most recently including sperm concentration of 15,000,000/mL or more, motility of 40% or higher, and normal morphology 4% or higher. The assessment of these parameters requires a spermogram in a specialised laboratory. There is an ICD-code for this exam: Z31.4. Other codes exist such as R86 “Abnormal findings in specimens from male genital organs” including semen, to measure azoospermia or oligospermia N46 “Male Infertility” could be used. In the ICD-11 the relevant codes are under GB04 “Male infertility”; GB04.0 “Azoospermia”, GB04.Y “Other specified male infertility”, GB04.Z “Male infertility, unspecified” (see. Fertility and Fecundity section below).

A possible decline in semen quality has prompted discussion after a meta-analysis in 1992 suggested a decline of 0.9 millions/ml per year during a 50-year period from 1940 to 1990 (Carlsen et al. 1992) and the results were confirmed in a further reanalysis (Swan, Elkin, and Fenster 1997). Another recent published meta-analysis including studies from 1973 to 2011 reported a similar yearly decline of 0.7 millions/ml (Levine et al. 2017).

It is also possible to estimate the sperm quality at the population level using ART databases. In a French study, a national sample of men partners of infertile women was selected to estimate the sperm quality of men closed to the general population between 1989 and 2005. This study showed also a significant and continuous decrease of about 1.9 % per year in sperm concentrations during the study period (Rolland et al. 2012).

9.1.5 Sperm DNA damage

Damage to the male genetic complement contained within sperm may lead to delayed fertilisation, compromised implantation and infertility (Sakkas and Alvarez 2010). In the literature, a number of hypotheses have been proposed to explain how environmental factors, including chemical agents, could affect sperm DNA integrity. However, there is still uncertainty about the best laboratory tests to identify and quantify such DNA damage (Pacey 2010).

Methods suggested to reveal this anomaly are based either on the detection of low-molecular-weight DNA fragments, either on the visualisation of endogenous nicks in the DNA molecule. Comet assay belongs to the former category, while sperm chromatin structure assay (SCSA) and terminal deoxyribonucleotidyl transferase-mediated dUTP fluorescein-dUTP nick-end labelling (TUNEL) assay represent the latter one (Tesarik, Mendoza-Tesarik, and Mendoza 2006).

Several parameters could be measured to evaluate sperm DNA damage such as the threshold DNA fragmentation index (DFI = number of spermatozoa with single-stranded DNA divided by the sum of spermatozoa with single-stranded and double-stranded DNA) is a marker of sperm DNA damage. Evenson et al. proposed to divide patients into three categories with regard to their individual fertility potential according to DFI as follows: excellent <15%, good 15–30% and fair to poor >30% DFI (Evenson and Wixon 2006). Sperm chromatin dispersion (SCD) test, based on the observation that spermatozoa with fragmented DNA fail to produce the characteristic halo of

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dispersed DNA loops that is observed with non-fragmented sperm DNA after acid denaturation and removal of nuclear proteins, was another form for sperm DNA evaluation. (Tesarik, Mendoza-Tesarik, and Mendoza 2006). An analysis of genotype or DNA methylation could be another option to evaluate sperm DNA damage.

For instance, a Saudi study evaluated sperm DNA quality of the male partners (n=384) in Saudi infertile couples. Saudi male partners showed increasing level of sperm DNA fragmentation index (DFI) at 25.4 (range, 5–97). Men with normal semen parameters had a significantly lower DFI (17.5; range, 5–32) than did men with abnormal semen parameters (49; range, 21–97, $p < 0.001$). Patients with abnormal sperm morphology showed a high rate of DNA fragmentation (Binsaleh et al. 2015.).

9.1.6 Reproductive hormones

Reproductive hormone levels are potential indicators of endocrine disruption among the general population. Furthermore, their levels are easily quantifiable in blood. The male reproductive hormones include testosterone, luteinising hormone, sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG), INSL3, inhibin b and follicle stimulating hormone. For females, the reproductive hormones include prolactin, oxytocin, estradiol, progesterone, activin, prostaglandin F2 α , prostaglandin PGE2, human chorionic gonadotrophin, placental lactogen, gonadotropin releasing hormone, relaxin and AMH (anti-Müllerian hormone). AMH is the only hormone that can give an idea of ovarian reserves since there is no oocyte quality marker (Le Moal et al. 2016).

9.1.7 Fertility and Fecundity

Fertility is commonly defined as the ability of a couple to achieve pregnancies that survive to birth. Clinical infertility is defined as the inability to become pregnant after 12 months of unprotected intercourses. Infertility may be due to medical, genetic or environmental causes. There are several pathologies favoring infertility like polycystic ovary syndrome, ovarian failure or endometriosis among females. In addition, there are male pathologies such as testicular failure and environmental factors (oxidative stress or endocrine disruptors) which affect fertility.

Fecundity is a woman's biological ability to reproduce based on the monthly probability of conception.

Looking for an association between chemical exposure and infertility could provide information on the effect of chemical exposure on overall reproductive fitness. For epidemiological studies, information on fertility and fecundity can be obtained through self-reporting.

Many ICD-10 codes could describe fertility such as N80 "Endometriosis", E28.2 "Polycystic ovarian syndrome", E28.3 "Primary ovarian failure", N46 and N97 for "Male infertility" and "Female infertility". In the ICD-11 similar codes are 5A80.1 "Polycystic ovary syndrome", GA30.6 "Premature ovarian failure", GA31.0 "Primary female infertility", GA31.1 "Secondary female infertility", GA31.Z "Female infertility without specification whether primary or secondary", GA10 "Endometriosis", GB04 "Male infertility", GB04.0 "Azoospermia", GB04.Y "Other specified male infertility" and GB04.Z "Male infertility, unspecified".

9.2 Environmental chemicals associated with reproductive health

It is important to remember that endocrine disruptors are substances with many specific characteristics. Indeed, it is known that their effects can be more harmful depending on the windows of exposure, for instance, the period of the 1000 days of the child is very important. The substances can affect pregnancy and child development. Moreover, effects are possible even at

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low doses; the dose-response curves are not necessarily monotonous. Studies in recent years also show a multiplicity of mechanisms of action. All this makes the study of their effects very complex.

9.2.1 Phthalates

Phthalates affect several markers of reproductive health. The state of the art is sometimes not clear about associations between this substance and these markers. In this deliverable are presented the information collected during the five last years in the literature and evidences found before and described in the scoping document. This review focuses on biomonitoring studies in the general population. There are other studies in wildlife, in animal experiments that are not considered here.

9.2.1.1 Anogenital distance

The literature on effects of exposure to endocrine-disrupting chemicals like phthalates on anogenital distance (AGD) is much discussed. Generally, AGD appears like an easily obtainable marker of male reproductive health. Although not consistently, maternal exposure to phthalates has been associated with shorter AGD in male offspring. In 2005, Swan et al. study showed for the first time a significant association between maternal exposure to several phthalates (MnBP, MEp, MBzP, MiBP) measured in urine, and reduced AGD in the male offspring was reported (Swan et al. 2005). Later, Swan et al. showed a significant association between MEHP, MEOHP, MEHHP and AGD in boys but not in girls to confirm previous results (Swan et al. 2015). However, one year later, another study showed no associations between phthalates exposure and AGD (Jensen et al. 2016).

Another study conducted in America showed a statistically significant inverse association for mono-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (MEHP) and APD in boys ($B = -1.57$ mm, $p = 0.02$). Among girls, they found inverse associations for tertiles of MEHP with AFD and ACD (Wenzel et al. 2018).

Another study compared the associations of phthalates exposure and AGD according to the sex. The results of subgroup analyses indicated that in boys, the sum of di-2-ethylhexyl phthalate (Σ DEHP) metabolites had significant association with the risk of shortened anopenile distance (AGDAP) ($\beta = -0.915$, 95% CI: -1.629, -0.2) and anoscrotal distance (AGDAS) ($\beta = -0.857$, 95% CI: -1.455, -0.26). In addition, other urinary phthalates were associated with short AGDAP. They also observed significant association between monobenzylphthalate (MBzP) and ano-fourchette distance (AGDAF) in girls ($\beta = 0.178$, 95% CI: 0.045, 0.311). This study provided findings on a significant association of exposure to PDEHP metabolites, MBP, MEP, and MiBP with shortened AGDAP in boys (Zarean et al. 2019). According to a recent study, a significant inverse relationship between DEHP levels and anogenital distance index of newborn males exists ($p = 0.019$) (Sunman et al. 2019).

Many articles have been published during the last decade; Zarean et al. (2019) have done a review on 10 articles. All of them are observational studies and evaluated the associations between phthalates exposure and AGD in girls or boys. Nine out of ten articles had a decreased of AGD with phthalates exposure (Zarean et al. 2019). The last one did not find any association between phthalates exposure and AGD and it is cited above (Jensen et al. 2016).

More evidence exists now to believe that there is an association between phthalates and AGD particularly for boys, using this type of studies. Nevertheless, more studies are needed to confirm these results in girls. However, there are other evidences in experimentation with animal studies.

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9.2.1.2 Hypospadias

In 2010, the Nassar study showed that women exposed to phthalates were more likely to have an affected son with an OR=1.2 and 95% CI: 0.8 to 1.7 (Nassar et al. 2010). A recent review evaluated the association between prenatal phthalate exposure and hypospadias. This review cited a systematic review showing a weak or uncertain association for all six phthalates studied (DEHP, di-isononyl phthalate, DBP, di-isobutyl phthalate, butyl benzyl phthalate, diethyl phthalate). Another article is cited, a case-control study analysing perfluorooctane sulfonate levels and levels of DEHP and DiNP metabolites in amniotic fluid during gestational weeks 13 to 16, showing no association between these chemical levels and hypospadias (Rodprasert et al. 2019).

The link between phthalates and hypospadias is thus still unclear using this type of study.

9.2.1.3 Semen quality

An Indian study showed a significant correlation among 60 male partners between phthalates (DEHP/DBP/DEP) and sperm motility and between concentration and DNA damage. After adjusting for potential confounders, only an association with DEHP was observed (Pant et al. 2014).

The MARCHS (Male-Reproductive-Health-in Chongqing-College-Students) cohort recruited 796 students who experienced a relocation of campuses and a shifting environmental exposure. The semen outcomes were associated with at least one phthalate metabolite. Compared to the lowest quartile of MEP, the highest quartile was associated with 12.5% (95% CI: 1.0%, 24.0%), 10.6% (2.2%, 23.5%) and 5.9% (0.7%, 11.2%) lower sperm concentration, total sperm number and progressive motility. Moreover, MEHP negatively associated with normal morphology and MnBP and ΣLMWP were negatively associated with progressive motility. These effects may only partially revert when exposures decrease (Chen et al. 2017).

A Chinese study composed of 509 reproductive aged men in Wuhan investigates the mediating role of thyroid function on the association between phthalate exposure and semen quality. The analysis showed higher urinary MEP and the proportions of MEHP were associated with decreasing serum thyroid hormones, which in turn were associated with altered semen quality. For instance, after adjustment, significant dose-dependent relationships were found across urinary MEP quartiles with decreasing FT4 (-4.0%; 95% CI: -7.5%, -0.39% for the fourth versus first quartile; p for trend=0.02). Additionally, we found that serum FT4 was associated with decreasing percentage of normal morphology (-3.2%; 95% CI: -5.3%, -1.1% for the third versus first quartile; p for trend=0.04) (Wang et al. 2018).

Another study investigated associations between phthalates exposure, DNA methylation and sperm quality. The results showed that urinary phthalates metabolites were significantly positively associated with sperm motility. Sperm LINE-1 DNA methylation were found to be negatively associated with ΣDEHP exposure and sperm quality (ejaculate volume, total sperm number and motility). Epigenetic modification LINE-1 DNA methylation demonstrated mediating effects in association between DEHP exposure and sperm motility, and 20.7% of the association was mediated by serum LIEN-1 DNA methylation (Tian et al. 2019).

An Italian study evaluated the possible association between chemical exposure and the semen quality of 105 subjects in a fertility clinic. The analysis showed, after adjustment, a positive significant association between MnBP, MnOP and semen volume (p=0.043, p=0.047 respectively) whereas MiNP had a negative significant association with semen volume (p=0.049). Another negative significant association was found between MEP and semen concentration (p=0.010) (Caporossi et al. 2020).

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In a recent review, the articles showed a fairly important impact of phthalates and its metabolites on semen parameters. Two studies have assessed maternal phthalates exposure and subsequent semen quality in their sons. These studies suggest that prenatal exposure to DEHP and DiNP may affect testis development and thus adult testis size (Jensen 2019).

All publications showed that phthalates affect semen quality. However, the biological pathway is still unknown and other studies are needed. Nevertheless, one interesting study showed that it is a reversible mechanism, but more evidence is needed to confirm this result.

9.2.1.4 Sperm DNA damage

A Chinese study investigated the associations of semen phthalate metabolites with sperm apoptosis and DNA damage among 463 men from Wuhan, China. The analysis showed suggestive dose-response relationship between semen mono-(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP) and an increased percentage of Annexin V+/PI- sperm (p for trend of <0.10), a marker of sperm apoptosis. Besides, they observed that semen monomethyl phthalate (MMP) and monoethyl phthalate (MEP) were associated with significant dose-related increases in tail length of the comet (both p for trend of <0.01), which is a marker of sperm DNA damage (You et al. 2015).

Another study investigated the potential effect of phthalate exposures with DNA methylation changes on spermatogenesis (for both the global DNA and some selected imprinting genes) in a cross-sectional male population ($n=118$). The results showed that the Σ DEHP, either as Σ DEHPm or as Σ DEHPm, was significantly associated with the decreased DNA methylation levels of LINE-1 (all $p < 0.05$). The level of LINE-1 methylation declined by -0.46% (95% CI: 0.91, -0.01%) and -0.45% (95% CI: 0.91, 0.00%) with 1-unit increase in ln-transformed concentration of Σ DEHPm and Σ DEHPm, respectively. Additionally, Sperm LINE-1 DNA methylation was found to be negatively associated with Σ DEHP exposure and sperm quality. This study supposed that DEHP exposure might play its action on sperm motility via epigenetic LINE-1 methylation pathway (Tian et al. 2019).

A recent review found that several articles evaluated the association between phthalates and sperm DNA damage. Among these studies, the results showed the same tendency: there was an increase in DNA damage with urinary phthalates metabolites (Zamkowska et al. 2018).

All recent articles have drawn the same conclusion: phthalates exposure may cause sperm DNA damage.

9.2.1.5 Reproductive hormones

A Polish study observed that environmental contaminants have been linked to reproductive hormones. The results showed inverse associations between DiNP metabolites and testosterone with a decrease of 3% and 2%. In addition, a 6% decline in total testosterone with MHiNP was observed (Lenters et al. 2015).

A study investigated the association between phthalate exposure and reproductive hormones in a general population with low phthalate exposure. All metabolites of the DEHP showed a negative association with progesterone (MEHHP, MECPP, MEOHP and MEHP; $P = 0.05, 0.08, 0.004$ and 0.0006 , respectively), as was the molar sum Σ DEHPm and Σ HMWP. Further, MEHHP, MECPP and MEOHP negatively associated with estradiol, and MMP, MiBP, MnBP and Σ LMWP were negatively associated with testosterone. All metabolites except mono (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate declined after relocation ($P < 0.001$ respectively); at the same time, estradiol and luteinising hormone increased (by 34.2% and 10.0%) and testosterone decreased (by 7.0%). The changes in estradiol and testosterone were associated with the changes in the phthalate metabolites, but not the change in luteinising hormone after relocation (Chen et al. 2017).

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A study aimed to explore the relationship between urinary phthalate metabolites and serum AMH level in the general male population. Results showed that the urine concentration of mono (3-carboxypropyl) phthalate (MCP) of 12–20 age group was significantly positively correlated with serum AMH concentration in the model without any covariates ($p < 0.05$). In the 60-year-old group, the monomethyl phthalate (MEP), mono (2-ethyl-5-carboxypentyl) phthalate (MECPP) concentrations were significantly correlated with serum AMH concentrations in models both with and without covariates (all $p < 0.05$). No significant relationships had been observed in either age 20–40 or age 40–60 (Li et al. 2017).

A review summarised data linking non-persistent endocrine-disrupting chemicals exposure, and human, male reproductive hormones levels. The results of studies referring to phthalates and male reproductive hormones are not consistent. Three of the 10 studies did not find any association between the exposure to phthalates and the level of reproductive hormones in the case of men in adjusted models. The rest of the studies revealed that at least one of the phthalate metabolites was associated with a decline in the level of testosterone. Some authors also revealed that exposure to phthalate was inversely associated with E2 and free androgen index (Dziewirska, Hanke, and Jurewicz 2018).

To summarise, most of the articles find an association between phthalates and reproductive hormones, while others do not find any association.

9.2.1.6 Fertility and Fecundity

A control case study measured the level of DEHP among healthy women and women diagnosed with endometriosis. The results showed that higher levels of DEHP in women diagnosed with endometriosis suggest a role of phthalates in the etiology of endometriosis (Nazir et al. 2018).

A Chinese case control study examined the associations between phthalate exposure and premature ovarian failure (POF). After adjustment, the results showed an increase of 38% of ORs of POF for women in the highest quartile of MiBP compared to those in the lowest quartile (OR = 1.38, 95% CI: 0.73 - 2.61, p for trend = 0.01) (Cao et al. 2020).

Another Chinese study evaluated the association between eight phthalate metabolites and pregnancy outcomes like ovarian response and fertilisation. The results showed that the counts of retrieved oocytes were significantly higher in the highest tertile compared with the lowest tertile for MEP (adjusted RR=1.08, 95% CI: 1.03–1.15). However, there was a significant association of MEP with decreased odds of normal fertilisation for the medium tertile compared to the lowest tertile (adjusted OR=0.86, 95% CI: 0.76–0.97). MBP concentration was inversely associated with normal fertilisation odds. Concerning the embryo development, MMP and MEP in the medium tertile respectively reduced 22.4% (95% CI: 0.64–0.94) and 21.9% (95% CI: 0.64–0.95) of the odds to gain good-quality blastocyst compared to the lowest tertile (Deng et al. 2020).

A review investigated the effects of phthalates on female fecundity. The review concludes that there is evidence for potential adverse effects of low-level exposure to some phthalates on female fecundity (Mínguez-Alarcón and Gaskins 2017).

These articles suggest that phthalates may affect fertility and fecundity. However, more studies are needed in particular for fecundity.

To summarise the results of this literature review, phthalates could have an impact on AGD, semen quality, sperm DNA damage, reproductive hormones and fertility & fecundity. However, there is not enough evidence using this type of studies to show that phthalates cause damage to cryptorchidism and hypospadias.

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9.2.2 Pesticides

9.2.2.1 Anogenital distance

The link between pesticides and anogenital distance has been studied for two decades. In 2007, a larger Mexican study among 781 mother and child pairs, of which 29% reported living in Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT)-sprayed homes, indicated no association between p, p'-DDE exposure and AGD, suggesting that even high exposure to p, p'-DDE does not seem to have a significant impact on these outcomes in humans (Longnecker et al. 2007). The next year, a small American study including 37 male offspring indicated reduced AGD at higher p, p'-Dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE) exposure (Torres-Sanchez et al. 2008). These findings are not in accordance with the previous study. Nevertheless, in a recent publication in a Danish mother and child cohort, no consistent association between prenatal exposure to the pesticide metabolites 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3-PBA), 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY), 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D), and dialkyl phosphates (DAPs) and AGD was found (Lind et al. 2017).

The link between AGD and pesticides is thus still unclear.

9.2.2.2 Cryptorchidism

Different studies showed an association between environmental exposure to pesticides and cryptorchidism. In a Spanish study with 963 cases, the risk of cryptorchidism was increased (OR 9.0, 95% CI: 7.9 - 10.2) in areas of high pesticide use compared with areas of low use (García et al. 2017). A meta-analysis of 10 case-control studies evaluating different chemical classes [pesticides, PBB, PCBs, PFCs, phthalates] in different matrices (maternal serum, colostrum, cord blood, amniotic fluid) and countries reported a summary estimate of an odds ratio for congenital cryptorchidism of 1.03 (95% CI: 0.72–1.47) (Bonde et al. 2016). There are still controversial results among scientists and many studies did not find statistically significant associations. Moreover, in Bonde's review these are biological measurements in the general population. If we take into account studies on maternal or paternal occupational exposure to pesticides, many studies are more positive as shown in Virtanen's review (Virtanen and Adamsson 2012). In addition, other results are available in experimental and wild life studies.

9.2.2.3 Hypospadias

A study, published in 2017, researched prevalence rates and risks of birth defects on high or low exposure to pesticides. The results showed that prevalence rates per 100.000 inhabitants for birth defects like hypospadias were significantly greater ($p < 0.001$) in areas of high environmental exposure to pesticides compared to those with low exposure. The risks of hypospadias observed in children of parents who lived in areas of high pesticide exposure was higher with OR = 5.74 (García et al. 2017). An American study analysed total pesticides exposure and birth defects. The results showed a positive association between hypospadias and different pesticides. For example, pendimethalin with OR 50th to 90th = 1.21 [1.01-1.44] or 2,4-D with OR 50th to 90th = 1.39 [1.18-1.64] (Rappazzo et al. 2019).

A review, Bonde et al., mentioned eleven studies about hypospadias. Among it a study examined nine persistent pesticides and observed higher concentrations in serum from cases than controls (Bonde et al. 2016). A recent systematic review cited several articles showing association of pesticides with hypospadias. A French case-control study observed that the presence of pesticides was associated with the risk of hypospadias. For instance, the presence of the phenylurea herbicide isoproturon have an OR =5.9 and CI 95% [1.0-34.1] with moderate exposure. However, the study is composed by 25 cases and 58 controls only. This study is cited in the recent

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systematic review (Rodprasert et al. 2019). In another recent review, the authors cited several studies suggesting association of hypospadias with foetal exposure to pesticides but not all. (Virtanen, Main, and Toppari 2019)

As presented, the association between pesticides and hypospadias does not seem clear at this time. However, more evidences could be found in occupational prenatal exposures.

9.2.2.4 Semen quality

A Japanese study has been assessing the relationship between exposure to pyrethroids insecticides and semen quality in 323 university students recruited in metropolitan Tokyo. In the multiple regression models, urinary concentration of 3-PBA was not selected as significant, indicating that environmental exposure to pyrethroids insecticides did not affect semen quality (Imai et al. 2014).

A study focused on 100 male groundnut farmers aged 18-49 years evaluated reproductive health problems related to organophosphate pesticides (OP) exposure. Analysis revealed statistically significant differences in seminal parameters like motility, morphology and sperm count ($p < 0.05$) in the growing and no growing periods. For instance, the sperm analysis revealed that 74% of the farmers had oligozoospermia in the growing period against 46% in the non growing period (Lwin et al. 2018).

A study investigates associations between exposure to non-persistent chemicals and testicular function in young Danish men with and without FLG mutations. In the FLG mutation carrier group, semen volume was positively associated with urinary levels of 2,4,5-TCP while this association was not seen in the control group (Joensen et al. 2018).

A recent study evaluated the association between environmental exposure to non-persistent insecticides (1-naphthol [1N] and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol [TCPY]) and semen quality. The results identified that urinary TCPY concentration was significantly associated with a decrease in motility and 1N concentration was negatively associated with a percentage of sperm with normal morphology (Dziewirska et al. 2019).

The results are still controversial, but recent publications have shown a link between pesticides and semen quality.

9.2.2.5 Sperm DNA damage

A Polish study evaluated the association between environmental exposure to non-persistent insecticides and sperm DNA damage. The result put in evidence that urinary TPCY concentration in urine greater than the median to 75th percentile was positively associated with DNA fragmentation index ($p = 0.04$). The urinary TPCY concentration in urine greater than the 25th percentile to the median was positively associated with straight-line velocity ($p = 0.02$). 1-naphthol concentration in the category presented as above the median, was positively associated with straight-line velocity ($p = 0.006$), a marker of computer-aided semen analysis parameters. Additionally, 1N was positively associated with straight-line velocity (VSL), both categories of urinary concentrations greater than the median to 75th percentile, and continuous concentrations of 1N ($p = 0.03$ and $p = 0.01$, respectively) (Dziewirska et al. 2019).

A recent review with several articles showed a positive or strong association between pyrethroids and sperm damage, however other studies about this association are needed. Concerning organophosphate pesticides, the review observed a limited number of studies investigating the impact of environmental OPP exposure on human health and concluded that further characterisation of the issue in epidemiological studies is needed (Zamkowska et al. 2018).

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Although recent studies have shown an association between pesticides and sperm DNA damage, more studies are needed.

9.2.2.6 Reproductive hormones

In a Chinese case-control study, stratified analyses showed that each log increase in urinary 3-PBA concentration was significantly associated with an induction in odds of 51.0% being in the highest quartile of FSH and 28.6% being in the highest quartile of LH levels, whereas a 25.9% reduction in odds of being in the highest quartile of AMH levels (All *p* for trend <0.05) (Li et al. 2018).

A cross-sectional study was performed to identify health problems related to organophosphate pesticide (OP) exposure. The results showed statistically significant differences in serum-hormone levels such as FSH and testosterone (*P*<0.05) in the growing and no growing periods (Lwin et al. 2018).

A cross-sectional study assessed the relationship between pesticide exposures and testosterone levels in 133 male Thai farmers. The linear regression analyses revealed significant negative relationships between total testosterone and the herbicide 2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) after controlling for covariates (e.g., age, BMI, smoking status). Positive significant associations were found between some OP pesticides and total testosterone (Panuwet et al. 2018).

A study assessed the association of short- and long-term exposure to pesticides with reproductive hormones in an agricultural population in the South of Brazil. Levels of male testosterone were significantly reduced from the low to high pesticide use season. Moreover, recent use of lambda-cyhalothrin (pyrethroid) or was associate phthalamide (fungicide) with increased male luteinising hormone (LH). They also found associations of lifetime years of agricultural work with increased male testosterone (Santos et al. 2019).

A review published in 2015 cited several articles on the relationship between pesticides and his metabolites and reproductive hormones. The results showed contradictory trends, some articles did not found any association between pesticides and reproductive hormones, whereas some articles found associations such as an increase in FSH levels in serum or an decrease in serum inhibin B concentration or testosterone levels in presence of pesticides (Saillenfait, Ndiaye, and Sabate 2015).

Another review summarised data linking non-persistent endocrine-disrupting chemicals exposure, and human, male reproductive hormones levels. The results of studies analysing the associations between exposure to synthetic pyrethroids and male reproductive hormones have shown some differences in results. The studies concerning the association between organophosphate pesticides and male reproductive hormones levels suggest that environmental exposure to pesticides may interfere with the male endocrine system (Dziewirska, Hanke, and Jurewicz 2018).

9.2.2.7 Fertility and fecundity

A Shanghai birth cohort investigated the effects of preconception exposure to pesticides on time to pregnancy (TTP) and on infertility in a general population of couples planning to become parents. The results showed that women in the highest quartile of DETP had significantly longer TTP (adjusted FOR=0:68 (95 % CI: 0.51, 0.92), *p*=0.012) and increased infertility [adjusted OR=2:17 (95 % CI: 1.19, 3.93), *p* =0.011] compared with women in the lowest quartile. The highest versus lowest quartile of 3PBA was associated with longer TTP and infertility for nulliparous women [adjusted FOR=0:72 (95 % CI: 0.53, 0.98) *p* = 0.034; adjusted OR for infertility=2:03 (95 % CI: 1.10, 3.74), *p* = 0.023] (Hu et al. 2018).

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Another study evaluated the correlation between the concentrations of pesticides in the follicular fluid (FF) obtained during intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) with the ovarian response, endometrial thickness, and embryological and clinical outcomes. There were significant negative correlations between FF concentrations of the eight examined pesticides on the endometrial thickness. However, Pretilachlor, chlorpyrifos, beta-cyfluthrin, and Diazinon were the only toxic agents that negatively correlated with the number of the oocytes retrieved. Fertilisation and early embryo cleavage rates were negatively correlated with Pretilachlor and beta-cyfluthrin. Moreover, high concentrations of Lindane, DDT, Diazinon, and chlorpyrifos were significantly associated with lower implantation rate (Al-Hussaini et al. 2018).

A Chinese case control study explored the association between pyrethroids exposure and women suffering of premature ovarian insufficiency (POI). The results showed that higher urinary levels of 3-PBA were significantly associated with increased risk of POI [adjusted odds ratio (OR) = 2.344, 95 % CI: 1.193-4.607 for the highest vs lowest quartile of 3-PBA, p = 0.013]. (Li et al. 2018.)

Another review explored associations between the female reproductive system and pesticides, however the publications showed contradictory results. Nevertheless, the evidence suggests a potential association with OPs and the disruption of normal female reproductive functions (Sifakis et al. 2017).

Pesticides seem to have more or less impact on all markers of reproductive health, but further studies are needed to confirm these results. Indeed, many studies have shown that pesticides affect reproductive hormones. However, a few articles have found an association between pesticides and other markers such as hypospadias, sperm quality, sperm DNA damage and fertility. Moreover, these associations were often weak or contradictory with other articles. There is not enough evidence to conclude that pesticides can cause damage to AGD or cryptorchidism.

9.2.3 Bisphenols

9.2.3.1 Anogenital distance

In China, the exposure levels of bisphenol are high and many studies conducted there have been found (Jensen 2019). An occupational cohort study from China revealed that maternal exposure to BPA during pregnancy was associated with shortened AGD in male offspring (Miao et al. 2011). In a longitudinal Chinese study with 655 mother and son pairs, mothers with detectable BPA in urine in gestational week 12 & 16 gave birth to boys with shorter AGDap (anus-penis) at age 6 and 12 months (Sun et al. 2018). However, no significant association between maternal BPA and AGD was found in a Chinese study among 137 boys but data were not shown and the measurement method of AGD was not specified (Liu et al. 2016). These findings are in accordance with findings from a Canadian study among 198 boys, where no significant associations between maternal BPA exposure and AGD in offspring were reported (Arbuckle et al. 2018).

A study from Cyprus measured BPA in cord blood and found no significant correlations between cord blood and AGD. Only 72 boys above the 90th percentile of BPA levels in cord blood had shorter AGD AS (anus-scrotum) (Mammadov, Uncu, and Dalkan 2018). Another study measured BPA in cord blood which correlated with AGI ($\rho=0.220$, $p=0.029$) (Sunman et al. 2019).

Among the various studies, the results remain controversial. Further studies are needed to explain the relationship between bisphenol and AGD.

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9.2.3.2 Cryptorchidism and Hypospadias

Virtanen et al. review cited two articles evaluating cryptorchidism and hypospadias together and suggested a positive association with placental levels of pesticides, BPA, and benzophenones (Virtanen, Main, and Toppari 2019).

9.2.3.3 Semen quality

A study has been investigating associations between exposure to non-persistent chemicals and testicular function in young Danish men with and without FLG mutations. Analysis showed that the highest urinary BPA quartile had lower sperm motility than those in the lower quartiles. When the men were split by genotype, a lower percentage of progressively motile spermatozoa was observed with increasing urinary BPA excretion in the group of FLG mutation carriers, but no such association was observed in the control group (Joensen et al. 2018).

A Polish study examined BPA exposure in relation to male fertility. A multiple linear regression analysis identified that urinary concentration of BPA decreased motility ($p = .03$) (Radwan et al. 2018).

A recent study investigated predictors of urinary BPS concentrations and its association with semen parameters among men attending a fertility center. Lower semen parameters were found among men with detectable BPS concentrations, compared to men with non-detectable BPS [2.66 vs. 2.91 mL for volume ($p=0.03$), 30.7 vs. 38.3 mil/mL for concentration ($p=0.03$), 76.8 vs. 90.0 mil for total count ($p=0.09$), 43.7 vs. 47.0% for motility ($p=0.06$), and 5.42 vs. 6.77% for morphologically normal sperm ($p=0.24$)] (Ghayda et al. 2019).

An Italian study evaluated the possible association between chemical exposure and the semen quality of 105 subjects in a fertility clinic. The analysis showed, after adjustment, a positive significant association between BPA and semen volume ($p=0.018$) (Caporossi et al. 2020).

A recent review showed that the relationship between bisphenols exposure and semen parameters is controversial. Some studies found an association between bisphenol exposure and semen parameters, whereas some other studies found no evidence (Jensen 2019).

The results are still controversial, but BPA seems to impact semen quality. However, there are not enough information about BPS and BPF, more studies are necessary on these substances.

9.2.3.4 Sperm DNA damage

A recent study from Poland examined the associations between urinary BPA concentration and male fertility. The study population was recruited in male reproductive health clinic, 315 volunteers under 45 years with normal sperm concentration participated. The analysis revealed a positive association between the urinary concentrations of bisphenol A 25th–50th percentile and total sperm sex chromosome disomy ($p = 0.004$). Also, when modeled as a continuous variable, urinary BPA concentration increased total sperm sex chromosome disomy ($p = 0.01$). Finally, urinary concentration of BPA also increases the percentage of immature sperm (HDS) ($p = 0.018$) (Radwan et al. 2018).

A review cited an American study investigating semen parameters in the general population represented by men from Michigan and Texas, USA. The authors found a negative relationship between BPA and DNA fragmentation, suggesting less sperm DNA damage (Zamkowska et al. 2018).

In a recent review, only one article is cited on association between BPA and sperm DNA damage. This article explored the possible correlation between urinary BPA concentration and sperm DNA

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damage, evaluated by neutral comet assay, in a cohort of 190 subfertile male patients. Urinary BPA concentration was positively associated with sperm DNA damage (De Toni et al. 2020).

The recent studies found an association between sperm DNA damage and bisphenols. More studies could be useful to understand the biological mechanisms.

9.2.3.5 Reproductive hormones

A study investigated associations between exposure to non-persistent chemicals and testicular function in young Danish men with and without FLG mutations. When analysing subjects by genotype (with or without FLG mutations) divided into exposure quartiles, for each FLG genotype group separately, we observed that FLG mutation carriers with urinary BPA concentrations above the lowest quartile had higher testosterone and estradiol serum levels and lower FSH compared to the lowest BPA quartile. These associations were not observed in the control group (Joensen et al. 2018).

A study investigated cord blood BPA levels and determined their association with the development of male reproductive system. The multivariate linear regression analysis demonstrated significant associations between estradiol and BPA levels (β 1.842, 95% CI: 0.358, 3.326; $p=0.016$) after confounding parameters (maternal age, parity, end-of-pregnancy BMI, BPA, DEHP, and MEHP) were adjusted (Sunman et al. 2019).

A review summarised the effects of male exposure to BPA on markers of testicular function and couple reproductive outcomes. The review cited five studies on male BPA exposure and reproductive hormones, all found significant associations with at least one reproductive hormone; however no consistent relations were observed across studies (Mínguez-Alarcón, Hauser, and Gaskins 2016).

One year later, another review cited a few studies but no association between BPA and reproductive hormones were found (Mínguez-Alarcón & Gaskins 2017).

Another review summarised data linking non-persistent endocrine-disrupting chemicals exposure, and human, male reproductive hormones levels. Four papers concerning exposure to BPA and male reproductive hormones levels were identified. The results showed associations such as increasing levels of testosterone, luteinising hormone and estradiol with increasing BPA concentration. A significant positive association was found between follicle-stimulating hormone and BPA urinary concentration whereas an article did not observe any association. (Dziewirska et al., 2018).

The association between reproductive hormones and bisphenols is not clear. Moreover, there are no studies on potential impact of other bisphenol's forms. One article suggests that bisphenols cause mutations and indirectly impact reproductive hormones. More studies are needed about this last point.

9.2.3.6 Fertility and fecundity

An American study explored whether intake of folate and other methyl donors modified the association between urinary BPA concentrations and IVF outcomes among women at an academic fertility medical center. The results showed that high urinary BPA concentrations were associated with a 66% lower probability of implantation ($p=0.007$) and a 58% lower probability of clinical pregnancy ($p=0.03$) among women who consumed <400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ of food folate, but not among women consuming ≥ 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ (21% higher probability of implantation, $p=0.18$) (p interaction = 0.04). However, BPA was unrelated to these outcomes among women who consumed ≥ 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ of folate from foods (Mínguez-Alarcón et al. 2016).

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The aim of an Iranian case-control study was to find the association between urinary concentrations of Bisphenol-A and PCOS. Comparison of BPA level between two groups shows the significantly higher level in PCOS group compared with control group (3.34 ± 2.63 vs. 1.43 ± 1.57 ng/mL, $P < 0.001$). Using logistic regression analysis, BPA as the main dependent variable was significantly associated with PCOS with adjusted Odds Ratio (OR) equal to 1.53 (95 % CI: 1.14-2.05, $P = 0.004$). Further investigations with better design are necessary to confirm this association (Hosseini Rashidi et al. 2017).

Another study tried to understand possible effects of bisphenol A (BPA) exposure on ovarian reserve in women with PCOS. They measured creatinine adjusted urinary BPA (BPA_Cre) concentrations and used regression models to evaluate the association between urinary BPA level and antral follicle count (AFC). The results showed that a unit increase in BPA_Cre was associated with a significant decrease of 0.34 in AFC ($\beta = -0.34$, 95 % CI = -0.60, -0.08; $p = 0.01$). This result suggests that in women with PCOS, BPA may affect ovarian follicles and, therefore, reduce ovarian reserve (Zhou et al. 2017).

A review on BPA found two studies that assessed the association between BPA concentrations and couples reproductive outcomes. No associations were found in the studies using EARTH and LIFE data (Mínguez-Alarcón et al., 2016).

Another review found several publications, however the results are unclear. The review concludes that female exposure to BPA might have adverse effects on markers of fecundity (such as AFC and possibly oocyte quality), however there was no sufficient evidence supporting a link between female exposure to BPA and TTP (Mínguez-Alarcón & Gaskins 2017).

Another recent review on EDCs and female reproductive system found that the data in literature supports that there is some evidence that BPA may contribute to infertility in humans. (Sifakis et al. 2017).

Different markers like PCOS, TTP or AFC measure fertility and fecundity. The results of these studies are unclear, however the trend is that bisphenol could affect these markers of reproductive health.

To conclude, Bisphenols, especially BPA since many studies have investigated this substance, could be associated with an increased risk for reproductive health. Nevertheless, more studies are needed, notably for BPS and BPF, to confirm these results and to explain the biological mechanisms.

9.2.4 Lead

9.2.4.1 Hypospadias

An American study observed associations between hypospadias and prenatal heavy metals hazardous air pollutants. Indeed, lead was significantly associated with hypospadias risk only in the medium-high and high exposure quintiles. Other heavy metals were significantly associated with hypospadias like manganese, cadmium, nickel (White et al. 2019). The Nassar study observed a strong association with potential maternal occupational exposure to heavy metals, such as mercury, lead and cadmium, with an over twofold increased risk of hypospadias (OR 2.6; 95 % CI 1.3 to 5.2) (Buck Louis et al. 2018).

9.2.4.2 Semen quality

An Indian study showed a significant correlation among 60 male partners between lead and sperm motility and between concentration and DNA damage. After adjusting, the association was still observed (Pant et al. 2014). A recent study explored the mediating effect of oxidative stress on the

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relationship between heavy metal exposure and semen quality. Significant or suggestive associations were also found between urinary 8-OHdG levels and the percentage of normal sperm morphology (ptrend < 0.001), between urinary 8-isoPGF2a levels and total motility (ptrend = 0.052), progressive motility (ptrend = 0.050). Moreover, 16.47 % of the relationship between lead exposure and the decreased percentage of normal sperm morphology was mediated by 8-OHdG (He et al. 2020). A Chinese study explored the relationship between low-level lead exposure and semen quality. The authors recruited 751 students in the MARHCS study. The results showed a significant dose response relationship between lead exposure and a decrease in semen quality. Multilinear regression showed that urinary Pb was negatively associated with sperm concentration, total sperm count, progressive motility and total sperm motility (regression coefficient: -0.074, -0.103, -0.024, and -0.014, respectively; p: <0.001, <0.001, 0.007, and <0.001, respectively). In addition, a logistic regression also indicated that the risk of having abnormal semen quality was higher in the high Pb group (OR: 2.501, 95 % CI: 1.411, 4.435, p = 0.002) than in the low Pb group after adjusting for confounders, with a dose-response relationship in the trend test (p = 0.007) (Ren et al. 2020).

9.2.4.3 Reproductive hormones

A Chinese study explored the relationship between low-level lead exposure and reproductive hormone in males. Multilinear regression showed that urinary Pb decreased serum follicle-stimulating hormone, serum testosterone and the testosterone/luteinising hormone ratio (β coefficient: -0.090, -0.082, and -0.020, respectively; p: 0.002, <0.001, and 0.021, respectively), whereas positive associations were found between Pb and estrogen and progesterone (Ren et al. 2020).

An Iranian cross-sectional study investigated the relationship between the concentration of lead fumes and the levels of reproductive hormones among exposed welders. A total of 165 individuals, including 85 welders as an exposure group, and 80 administrative staff as non-exposed group participated. The results showed that the average level of testosterone in the exposure group was significantly lower than that of the control group (p=0.019). In addition, the mean levels of FSH and LH in the exposed group was significantly higher than that of the control group (p = 0.024 and p = 0.013 respectively). They found a strong correlation between the concentration of lead fumes and the blood lead levels (r = 0.82; P = 0.003). Moreover, blood lead levels were inversely related to the testosterone (r=-0.625, p=0.002) levels and directly related to LH (r = 0.72; P = 0.004) and FSH (r = 0.78; P = 0.001) levels (Dehghan, Mehrifar, and Ardalan 2019).

9.2.4.4 Fertility and fecundity

A Spanish study explored the associations between the concentrations of lead in hair and reproductive outcomes. They detected a direct association with Pb concentration and the probability of having mature oocytes (RR = 1.18, 95 % CI: 1.03–1.35) (García-Forte et al. 2018). An American study examined the association between infertility and blood lead among infertile and pregnant women. The number of infertile women showed a statistically significant increasing trend with increasing blood lead tertiles (p = 0.0145). After several adjustment factors, the analysis between metal levels and odds of being infertile showed that a two-fold increase in blood lead concentration was significantly associated with infertility with OR = 2.60 (1,05-6,41). The comparison of tertiles 2 and 3 revealed a dose-response relationship (Lee, Min, and Min 2020).

Even though lead is not associated with all markers of reproductive health, the literature shows that it may have a real impact on reproductive health.

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9.2.5 Flame retardants

The state of the art showed that FRs may be associated with altered hormones levels and decreased semen quality in men.

9.2.5.1 Anogenital distance

A small Mexican study with repeated AGD measurements found an association between maternal polychlorinated biphenyl (PCBS) and AGD in 74 boys, whereas no associations were found for prenatal DDT exposure (Loreto-Gómez et al. 2018).

In a Spanish mother and child cohort, persistent organic pollutants (POP) were measured in pregnant women, and the AGD was recorded in 43 offspring at 18 months and the anogenital index was calculated as AGD divided by weight. The anogenital index was inversely associated with lipid-adjusted concentrations of PBDE-99 and PBDE-153, but not with PCB congeners (García-Villarino et al. 2018).

In Luan et al. study, the levels of flame retardants in blood showed that boys who had neonatal concentration of BDE-47 or Σ 4PBDEs (sum of BDE-47, BDE-99, BDE-100, and BDE-153) in the higher quartile generally had shorter AGDAP and AGDAS than those in the first quartile. These analyses showed that boys with the highest levels of BDE-153 (> median) had longer AGDAP at 6 months of age ($\beta=4.42$, 95% CI: 0.14, 8.69), while those with mid-range level of BDE-153 had longer AGDAP at 48 months of age ($\beta=4.18$, 95% CI: 0.48, 7.88). There are inverse associations between AGDAS and fourth quartile Σ 4PBDEs levels among boys 12 months of age ($\beta=-5.13$, 95% CI: -9.89, -1.25). Besides, boys who were exposed to prenatal BDE-28 at the mid-range level (LOD to the median) had shorter AGDAP than boys with undetected levels at 48 months of age ($\beta=-4.31$, 95% CI: -7.89, -0.73) (Luan et al. 2019).

These recent studies showed that flame-retardants might be associated with shorter AGD.

9.2.5.2 Cryptorchidism

Different studies showed an association between environmental exposure to flame retardants and cryptorchidism. For instance, a study reported an association between prenatal PBDE exposure and congenital cryptorchidism. The concentration of PBDEs in breast milk was significantly higher in boys with cryptorchidism than in controls, whereas there was no association in placenta levels (Main et al. 2007). An American cohort study of sons born from women accidentally exposed to PBBs found an association between cryptorchidism and in utero PBB exposure (Small et al. 2009). A Canadian case-control study examined the association between cryptorchidism and maternal hair levels of PBDEs. The risk of cryptorchidism was positively correlated to maternal hair levels of BDE-99 (OR 2.5, 95 % CI 1.3-5.0), BDE-100 (OR 2.5, 95 % CI 1.3-4.6), and BDE-154 (OR 1.9, 95 % CI 1.1-3.3) for every 10-fold increase in BDE levels (Goodyer et al. 2017).

According to these studies, flame-retardants seem to have an impact on cryptorchidism.

9.2.5.3 Hypospadias

Rodprasert et al. reported three studies evaluating association between hypospadias and flame-retardants. In a case-control from Canada, PBDE levels in maternal hair were significantly higher in boys with hypospadias as compared with the control boys (Rodprasert et al. 2019). However, in another study, maternal serum levels of PBB were not associated with the risk of hypospadias in the sons (Small et al. 2009).

The results for a potential association between hypospadias and flame-retardants are less clear than for the association with cryptorchidism.

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9.2.5.4 Reproductive hormones

An American study examined whether the exposure to polybrominated biphenyls (PBB) had long-term effects on menstrual cycle function. They observed that high (>3.0 parts per billion [ppb]) and medium (>1.0–3.0 ppb) PBB exposure were associated with lower FSH levels during the follicular phase, compared with low PBB exposure (≤ 1.0 ppb) (Howards et al. 2019).

Other previous studies found a possible association between flame-retardants and reproductive hormones. These recent publications confirm these results.

9.2.5.5 Fertility and fecundity

An American study included 211 women enrolled in the EARTH prospective cohort study and recruited from an academic fertility clinic. The main aim was to evaluate associations between urinary concentrations of organophosphate flame-retardants (PFRs) metabolites and outcomes of IVF treatment. The results showed a decrease for several IVF outcomes across increasing quartiles of both summed and individual PFR metabolites in the adjusted multivariable models. Significant declines in adjusted means from the lowest to highest quartile of Σ PFR were observed for the proportion of cycles resulting in successful fertilisation (10%), implantation (31%), clinical pregnancy (41%), and live birth (38%) (Carignan et al. 2017).

Another study from the same author examined associations of paternal urinary concentrations of PFR metabolites and their partner's pregnancy outcomes. The results showed a significant 12% decline in the proportion of fertilised oocytes from the first to second quartile of male urinary Σ PFR and a 47% decline in the number of best quality embryos from the first to third quartile of male urinary BDCIPP in the adjusted models. An 8% decline in fertilisation was observed for the highest compared to lowest quartile of urinary BDCIPP concentrations (95 % CI: 0.01, 0.12, p-trend =0.06) (Carignan et al. 2018).

An American study evaluated association between organophosphate flame retardant (PFR) and pregnancy loss among women conceiving with assisted reproduction. The results showed that high detection frequency of diphenyl phosphate (DPHP) increased the risk of biochemical loss among women with DPHP concentrations in the fourth vs. first quartile (RR= 1.64; 95 % CI 0.61-4.39). An elevated risk of biochemical pregnancy loss was also found among women in the highest quartile of the molar sum of urinary PFR metabolites compared with the lowest (RR = 1.89; 95% CI 0.64-5.58) (Messerlian et al. 2018).

These recent publication showed that flame-retardants can affect human fertility and fecundity.

To conclude, these publications bring new evidence of the deleterious effect of FRs on reproductive health. Previous studies had already suspected an impact on semen quality and reproductive hormones. The literature now shows that FRs may also affect other markers of reproductive health such as fertility, cryptorchidism or anogenital distance.

9.2.6 Air pollutants and Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

There are several air pollutants like carbon monoxide (CO), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), ozone (O₃), particulat

es matter (PM), benzene, (VOCs) and hydrocarbons. Air pollutants may cause several health effects or diseases. However, only hydrocarbons cause possible reproductive disorders, and birth defects. Children are a sensitive population group.

No recent studies on a possible link between Air pollutants or PAHs and anogenital distance, cryptorchidism and hypospadias have been found.

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9.2.6.1 Semen quality

A Taiwanese study investigated whether exposure to PAHs contributes to decreased sperm quality of coke oven workers. Analysis found a significant difference in immotile sperm between the high exposure group and the control ($p=0.036$). The high exposure group had a significantly higher percentage of asthenospermia than the control ($p < 0.01$). The high exposure group and the low exposure group had lower percentages of normal morphology than the control group ($p < 0.01$). Regarding vitality of sperm, there was no significant difference among the three groups ($p = 0.078$) (Jeng et al. 2013).

Another study investigated the associations between air pollutants PM₁₀, PM_{10-2.5}, and PM_{2.5} exposures and semen quality. Mixed models showed that PM₁₀ exposure was negatively associated with sperm normal morphology (95 % CI: -14.13, -24.47) but positively associated with sperm progressive motility (95 % CI: 23.00, 8.49), and PM_{10-2.5} exposure was inversely associated with sperm concentration (95 % CI: -9.06, -27.31) after multiplicity adjustment (Zhou et al. 2018).

A Chinese study enrolled 1081 men to examine the associations of exposures to PM_{2.5} and its constituents with semen quality. Each interquartile range (36.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) increase in PM_{2.5} exposure was significantly associated with 8.5% (95 % CI: 2.3%, 14.4%) and 8.1% (95 % CI: 0.7%, 15.0%) decrease in sperm concentration and total sperm number, respectively (Huang et al. 2019).

A systematic review found thirteen studies examining the association between main semen parameters and environmental outdoor air pollutants. Most studies concluded that outdoor air pollution affects at least one of the assessed semen parameters (sperm concentration, motility, morphology) (Jurewicz et al. 2018).

Semen quality seems affected by air pollutants and PAH. During the last decades, many publications confirm these results.

9.2.6.2 Sperm DNA damage

A Taiwanese study assessed whether exposure to PAHs linked to male reproductive health of coke-oven workers with a non-smoking status by assessing sperm DNA integrity. The results showed that the high exposure group had 37.8% DNA fragmentation in sperm as compared with 32.9% and 27.1% in the low exposure group and the control, respectively. However, there was no significant difference in DNA fragmentation among the three groups ($p = 0.059$). Besides, all 16 PAH compounds and 1-OHP did not significantly correlate with DNA fragmentation. However, concerning the patterns of bulky DNA adducts in sperm, the high exposure group and the low exposure group had 70.45 in 10^9 nucleotides and 68.31 in 10^9 nucleotides bulky DNA adducts in sperm, respectively, which were significantly higher than those of the control (26.01 in 10^9 nucleotides, $p = 0.03$) (Jeng et al. 2013).

Another study explored the relationships between different PM and reproductive health. In the preliminary regression analysis, PM₁₀, PM_{10-2.5}, and PM_{2.5} exposure were all associated with sperm high DNA stainability (HDS). However, in mixed models, no associations were found between PM and sperm DNA damage, after multiplicity adjustment (Zhou et al. 2018).

A recent review collected several articles on the relationships between air pollutants and sperm DNA damage. The authors collected 5 articles assessing CASA parameters, however only one found inverse associations between sperm VCL (curvilinear velocity) and VSL and the PM₁₀, SO₂, NO₂ ($p < 0.001$). The other studies found no significant associations. Besides, there are seven articles about DNA fragmentation. Among these studies a lot find significant associations between air pollutants or PAH and DNA fragmentation such as abnormal chromatin, GSTM1 null genotype

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or immature chromatin. Only one observed no statistically significant relation between air pollutants and DNA integrity and chromatin maturity. This review also investigates the occupational exposure to air pollutants. The results showed that workers had significantly lower CASA parameters and they had a significantly higher percentage of spermatozoa with damaged chromatin and DNA fragmentation (Jurewicz et al. 2018).

The association between air pollutants or PAHs and sperm DNA damage is unclear. The results of different publications are controversial.

9.2.6.3 Reproductive hormones

In a case-control study, the associations of serum levels of PAHs with the reproductive hormones in Chinese women were investigated. The results showed that serum PAHs levels were significantly associated with higher concentrations of FSH (NAP, ACE, ACY, PHE, ANT, FLA, CHR, BbF, BkF and BaP) and LH (NAP, ACE, ANT, CHR, BbF, BkF and BaP) but lower concentrations of AMH (NAP, ACE, ACY, FLO, ANT, FLA, CHR, BbF, BkF and BaP) (Ye et al. 2020).

This recent article showed that reproductive hormones may be affected by PAHs.

9.2.6.4 Fertility and fecundity

A Chinese case control study analysed the associations of serum levels of PAHs with the risk of premature ovarian failure (POF) by recruiting 157 POF patients and 217 healthy women. The results showed a significant positive correlation between risk of POF and PAH congeners and Σ PAH, except FLO and PYR. For instance, Bap was observed to be significantly positively associated with the risk of POF, after adjustment: per one-unit increase in the log transformed BaP concentration was significantly correlated with 2.191-fold increased risk of POF (OR = 2.191, 95 % CI: 1.634-2.938, $p < 0.05$) (Ye et al. 2020).

Air pollutants and PAHs are frequent in the environment. These substances are already known to decrease reproductive health. These recent publications confirm this findings, PAHs and air pollutants affect several markers of reproductive health such as fertility, semen quality or reproductive hormones. However, more studies are needed to prove that PAHs and air pollutants cause sperm DNA damage.

9.2.7 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

9.2.7.1 Anogenital distance

A publication describes prenatal exposure to perfluoroalkyl substances and reduction in anogenital distance in girls at 3 months of age in a Danish mother-child cohort (Lind et al. 2017) whereas the MIREC cohort showed an increase in anocrostral distance of 1.36 mm (95 % CI 0.30, 2.41) for a one-unit increase in natural log transformed PFOA. This study found no clear evidence that maternal plasma concentrations of PFOS, PFOA or PFHxS were associated with shorter infant anogenital distance in males or any change in AGD in females (Arbuckle et al. 2020).

9.2.7.2 Semen quality

In a recent review, the link between PFAS and semen parameters is controverted. For instance, a Danish study showed that prenatal perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) exposure was associated with lower adjusted sperm concentration and total sperm count, whereas no associations were found for perfluorooctanyl sulfonate (PFOS) exposure (Jensen 2019).

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9.2.7.3 Reproductive hormones

A study explored the associations of prenatal exposure to perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) and perfluorooctanoate (PFOA) with cord blood reproductive hormones. In the male infants, PFOS levels were positively correlated with E2, and were inversely correlated with the T/E2 ratio and inhibin B levels. Maternal PFOA levels were positively correlated with male P4 and inhibin B levels. In the female infants, maternal PFOS was inversely correlated with PRL levels. After fully adjusting for the potential confounders, maternal PFOS exhibited significant positive association with E2 in male infants ($\beta = 0.372$; 95 % confidence interval [CI]: 0.057, 0.687; $p = 0.021$), and negative associations with the male infants' values for the T/E2 ratio ($\beta = -0.399$; 95 % CI: $-0.643, -0.156$; $p = 0.008$), P4 ($\beta = -0.344$; 95 % CI: $-0.678, -0.010$; $p = 0.043$), and inhibin B ($\beta = -0.439$; 95 % CI: $-0.620, -0.257$; $p = 0.001$). Among the male infants, maternal PFOA was positively associated with inhibin B ($\beta = 0.197$; 95 % CI: 0.009, 0.384; $p = 0.040$). Similarly, among the female infants, they observed negative associations between maternal PFOS and P4 ($\beta = -0.552$; 95 % CI: $-0.894, -0.210$; $p = 0.002$), and PRL ($\beta = -0.491$; 95 % CI: $-0.764, -0.218$; $p = 0.001$), although PFOA was not significantly associated with any hormone levels (Itoh et al. 2016).

A study explored whether PCBs or PFASs exposure were associated with abnormalities in reproductive hormones in 263 Faroese men. The results showed a significant positive association between the Σ PCB and SHBG, LH, testosterone and the testosterone/estradiol ratio both in the unadjusted and adjusted analyses. Significant positive associations were observed between PFOS, SHBG, and LH. However, after adjustment for Σ PCB, these associations attenuated and became non-significant. Higher PFOA was significantly associated with lower FT/estradiol ratio. Adjusting for Σ PCB had very little effect on the associations with PFOA (Petersen et al. 2018).

9.2.7.4 Fertility and fecundity

A Chinese study examined the association between PFASs and endometriosis related infertility among Chinese reproductive-age women in a case-control study, which comprised 157 surgically confirmed endometriosis cases and 178 controls seeking infertility treatment because of male reproductive dysfunction in 2014 and 2015. Plasma concentrations of perfluorobutane sulfonic acid (PFBS) were associated with an increased risk of endometriosis-related infertility (second vs. lowest tertile: OR = 3.74, 95 % CI: 2.04, 6.84; highest vs. lowest tertile: OR=3.04, 95 % CI: 1.65, 5.57). In contrast, plasma concentrations of PFHpA, PFHxS and PFNA were inversely associated with endometriosis-related infertility. This evidence suggests that exposure to PFBS may increase the risk of female infertility due to endometriosis (Wang, Zhang, et al. 2017).

Another Chinese study investigated the association between PFAS exposure and primary ovarian insufficiency (POI). The results revealed that Levels of perfluorooctanoate (PFOA), perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS), and perfluorohexanesulfonate (PFHxS) were positively associated with the risks of POI (highest vs. lowest tertile, PFOA: OR, 3.80; 95%CI, 1.92–7.49; PFOS: OR, 2.81; 95 % CI, 1.46–5.41; PFHxS: OR, 6.63; 95 % CI, 3.22–13.65) (Zhang et al. 2018).

Another case control study evaluated associations between PFASs concentrations in plasma and PCOS-related infertility. The results showed that only PFDoA concentration in plasma was significantly associated with an increased risk of PCOS-related infertility (medium vs low tertile: OR = 2.36, 95 % CI: 1.12, 4.99, $P = 0.02$; high vs low tertile: OR = 3.04, 95 % CI: 1.19, 7.67, $P = 0.02$) (Wang et al. 2019).

The recent publications showed that PFASs may affect markers of fertility and reproductive hormones. However, the results on AGD and semen quality are controversial and the evidence for cryptorchidism, hypospadias and sperm DNA damage is scarce.

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9.2.8 Cadmium

Cadmium is a potentially toxic metal classified as a human carcinogen (group 1B). Cadmium causes adverse effects at lower environmental exposures on endocrine system and reproductive health.

9.2.8.1 Semen quality

In a Chinese study, the authors evaluated semen quality among 587 men from the general population, aged from 20 to 59 years old without occupational exposure to cadmium. After adjusting, the results showed an inverse association between Cd and semen volume, progressive motility and sperm morphology (Li et al. 2016).

Another study found inverse correlations between cadmium quartiles and progressive and total sperm motility in the multiple element models (Wang, Wang, et al. 2017).

A recent study explored the mediating effect of oxidative stress on the relationship between heavy metal exposure and semen quality. The mediation analysis showed that about 15.35% and 16.49% of the association between cadmium exposure and the decreased total motility/progressive motility was mediated by 8- isoPGF2a, respectively (He et al. 2020).

9.2.8.2 Reproductive hormones

A Chinese study determined whether blood cadmium level (BCL) associates with reproductive hormones in a cross-sectional study. Results showed that in men, BCL was negatively correlated with total testosterone (TT) (Spearman coefficient = -0.057 , $P < 0.01$) and sex hormone-binding globulin (SHBG) (Spearman coefficient = -0.098 , $P < 0.01$), but in postmenopausal women, this correlation was not observed. In linear regression, after full adjustment for blood lead level, age, body mass index, residence area, economic status, and smoking, TT and SHBG were still negatively associated with BCL in men (Chen et al. 2016).

A Polish study observed that environmental contaminants have been linked to reproductive hormones. The results showed positive associations between mercury and inhibin B with an increase of 11%, and between cadmium and testosterone with an increase of 5% (Lenters et al. 2015).

9.2.8.3 Fertility and fecundity

An American study examined the association between infertility and blood cadmium among infertile and pregnant women. There was an increase in the proportion of infertile to pregnant women from the first to second and third blood cadmium tertiles but no statistically significant trend was observed. After several adjustment factors, the analysis between metal levels and odds of being infertile showed that a two-fold increase in blood cadmium concentration was significantly associated with infertility with OR = 1.84 (1,07-3,15). The comparison of tertiles 2 and 3 revealed a dose-response relationship (Lee, Min, and Min 2020).

Cadmium seems to affect semen quality, reproductive hormones and fertility. There are no recent publications on the link between cadmium and others markers of reproductive health. However, more studies are needed, notably on biological mechanism and women population.

9.2.9 Others associations (Anilines, UV filters, Mercury, Arsenic)

Anilines, Mercury, Arsenic and UV filters may cause damages on reproductive health. However, few articles evaluated the link between reproductive markers and these substances. Moreover, the results of publications are still controversial and unclear. Nevertheless, a few results are useful and interesting.

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UV filters may disturb reproductive hormones, fertility and others markers of human reproductive health. Higher exposure has been observed in the female populations, possibly due to its presence in personal care products.

9.2.9.1 Anogenital distance

Data on aniline exposure and AGD are rare. There is an animal study that showed the AGDi significantly decreased for all exposure groups (150 mg/kg/day paracetamol, 31 and 93 mg/kg/day aniline), excepted for the 50 mg/kg/day paracetamol group (Holm et al. 2016). The same year, Fisher et al. study displayed that paracetamol exposure during 8-14 weeks of gestation, was associated with shorter AGD of males by 0.27 SD (95 % CI 0.06-0.48, P = 0.014) from birth to 24 months of age. No association was found for females (Fisher et al. 2016).

Few studies have evaluated the link between anilines and human reproductive health. More studies are needed to understand the impact that aniline can have on reproductive health. For the moment, only animal studies suggest that aniline may have an impact on human reproductive health.

9.2.9.2 Cryptorchidism

Fisher et al. 2016 is the first study investigating the association between paracetamol exposure during masculinisation programming window (weeks 8-14 of gestation) and anogenital distance in boys. This is a small prospective baby cohort study from Cambridge (33 at birth, 62 at any age). It did not find any association between cryptorchidism and exposure to paracetamol during pregnancy (Fisher et al. 2016).

Gurney et al. 2017 is a review of ten studies. A weak evidence of an association between use of analgesia and risk of cryptorchidism was observed (pooled crude OR: 1, 11, 95 % CI: 1, 00-1, 23). They observed weak evidence of a dose-response relationship between increasing weeks of analgesia exposure and risk of cryptorchidism, as well as weak evidence of an effect of timing on analgesia exposure and risk of cryptorchidism (Gurney, Richiardi, et al. 2017).

The link between anilines and cryptorchidism is weak and unclear. Further studies are needed for larger populations, but aniline is rarely taken during pregnancy.

9.2.9.3 Semen quality

The Environment and Reproductive Health (EARTH) study enrolled 129 men contributing 243 semen samples. In unadjusted models, there were positive associations between hair mercury (Hg) levels and sperm concentration, total sperm count, and progressive motility. In adjusted models, semen volume and normal morphology were unrelated to hair Hg levels when the exposure was divided in quartiles. However, when Hg was used as a continuous independent variable, morphologically normal sperm was positively associated with hair Hg levels in models adjusted for age, BMI, smoking status, abstinence time and alcohol time. Nevertheless, this association became attenuated and did not reach statistical significance when the model was further adjusted for fish and total calorie intake. (Mínguez-Alarcón et al. 2018). After adjustments though, the association disappears, so mercury may not cause damage to the quality of the semen.

A Spanish study examined associations between urinary concentrations of BP-type UV filters and semen quality. This is a cross-sectional study with 215 students (18-23 years old). The results showed, after adjustment, that no significant association was found between urinary BP-type UV filters and semen parameters (Adoamnei et al. 2018). According to this publication, UV filters do not appear to affect sperm quality, but there are few studies in this area.

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In a Chinese study, the authors found an inverse dose dependant relationship between arsenic (As) levels and total motility. In multivariate logistic models, As quantities were significantly associated with increased risk of below reference progressive and total sperm motility (Wang, Wang, et al. 2017).

A recent study explored the mediating effect of oxidative stress on the relationship between heavy metal exposure and semen quality. The mediation analysis showed that about 14.59% and 18.06% of the association between arsenic exposure and the decreased total motility/progressive motility was mediated by 8- isoPGF2a, respectively (He et al. 2020). Arsenic appears to cause damage on semen quality, however more studies are needed to understand biological mechanisms involved here.

9.2.9.4 Sperm DNA damage

A Chinese study investigated the relationships between environmental exposure to metals/metalloids and DNA integrity using the metal/metalloids levels in seminal plasma as biomarkers among 401 men recruited from a reproductive medicine center. The results showed positive dose dependent relationship for arsenic (As) and sperm DNA integrity measures. In multiple element models, there were a significant association between Arsenic (As) quartiles and the percentage of tail DNA (ptrend = 0,001), between As and tail extent (ptrend = 0, 01) and between As and tail distributed moment (Ptrend=0.004), after adjustment (Wang, Wang, et al. 2017).

A study examined the association between preconceptional Hg exposure and the alteration of DNA methylation of imprinting genes *H19*, *Meg3*, and *Peg3* in human sperm DNA. Spearman's rank analysis indicated a negative correlation between urinary Hg concentrations and average DNA methylation levels of imprinted genes *H19* ($rs = -0.346$, $p < 0.05$), but there was no such correlation for *Peg3* and *Meg3*. The results showed a negative correlation between urinary Hg concentrations and three out of seven CpG sites on *H19* DMR, namely CpG2 ($rs = -0.137$, $p < 0.05$), CpG4 ($rs = -0.380$, $p < 0.05$) and CpG6 ($rs = -0.228$, $p < 0.05$). After adjusting age, smoking, drinking, intake of aquatic products and education by multivariate regression analysis, the results indicated similar correlations to that above (Lu et al. 2018).

A recent review cited two articles about association between mercury and sperm DNA damage. The first article assessed if Hg exposure affected male reproductive function through sperm DNA integrity. No significant associations between Hg and DNA fragmentation index (DFI) or high DNA stainable (HDS) were found. However, authors found that DFI tends to increase with increasing Hg concentrations, suggesting a prejudicial effect of Hg on sperm chromatin integrity. The second article evaluated the effect of Hg exposure in sperm DNA damage among men recruited from a fertility clinic. Authors showed that urine Hg levels were associated with increasing trends for DNA tail length, suggesting that environmental Hg exposure may result in increased sperm DNA damage. Moreover, authors suggested that Hg-induced sperm DNA damage may be triggered by generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and alteration of the antioxidant defense system (Henriques et al. 2019).

Metals and metalloids such as mercury and arsenic cause several DNA damages particularly on sperm. The recent publications showed that others biological mechanisms can also be involved. More studies are needed to confirm these results.

9.2.9.5 Reproductive hormones

A Spanish cross-sectional study examined associations between urinary concentrations of BP-type UV filters and reproductive hormone levels. After adjustment for important covariates (body mass

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index, smoking status and time of blood sample collection), there was a significant positive association between urinary BP-1 and BP-3 concentrations and serum FSH levels ($\beta=0.08$, 95 % CI: 0.009; 0.15 and $\beta=0.04$, 95 % CI: 0.0002; 0.08, respectively). Urinary BP-1 concentration was also significantly positively associated with T/E2 ($\beta=0.04$, 95 % CI: 0.002; 0.07) and negatively with inhibin b/FSH ($\beta=-0.11$, 95 % CI: -0.21 ; -0.006) ratio (Adoamnei et al. 2018).

A study investigated associations between exposure to non-persistent chemicals and testicular function in young Danish men with and without FLG mutations. The scientists found that urinary levels of 4-HBP and 4-PP were positively associated with serum testosterone and free testosterone (FT) and 4-HBP was furthermore positively associated with serum estradiol.

When analysing subjects by genotype (with or without FLG mutations) divided into exposure quartiles, for each FLG genotype group separately, it was observed that FLG mutation carriers with urinary BP-1 or BP-3 concentrations above the lowest quartile had higher testosterone and estradiol serum levels and lower FSH compared to the lowest BP-1 or BP-3 quartile. Likewise for the group of FLG mutation carriers who excreted 4-HBP compared to those who had no detectable levels of urinary 4-HBP. These associations were not observed in the control group (Joensen et al. 2018). UV filters may cause disruption of reproductive hormones and may have more impact with specific genotype mutations.

An American study evaluated the effect between analgesic medication use and reproductive hormones. The results showed that analgesic users had significantly higher average luteal progesterone ($P = 0.017$) than non-users. Besides, luteal progesterone was higher (% difference = 14.0, 21.6–32.1, $P = 0.08$ adjusted) in cycles with follicular phase analgesic use, but no associations were observed with estradiol, LH or FSH. However, when analgesic use was modeled as a time-varying variable to assess short-term effects of recent medication use, they observed lower estradiol (% difference = 215.5 [220.7, 29.9]; $P = 0.001$) and higher FSH (% difference = 10.0 [4.8, 15.5]; $P = 0.001$) among women who used analgesics during the 5 days prior to the blood draw compared with women who did not use analgesics during this time period. Mid-cycle LH and luteal progesterone were not significantly associated with time-varying analgesic use (Matyas et al. 2015). Aniline may cause disruption on reproductive hormones, however the results are still unclear and more studies are needed to confirm it.

9.2.9.6 Fertility and fecundity

A Spanish study explored the associations between the concentrations of mercury in hair and reproductive outcomes. They detected an inverse association between concentration of Hg in hair and the probability of having mature oocytes (RR = 0.81, 95 % CI: 0.70–0.95) (García-Fortea et al. 2018). A Japanese case control study investigated the associations between female infertility and environmental exposures to metals. The results showed a significant association of infertility with elevated mercury levels. Methylmercury appear to have adverse effects on female fertility (Maeda et al. 2019). A systematic review (1975-2017) explored the mercury influence on human fertility. This review showed that mercury negatively affects human reproduction, affecting the reproductive and endocrine systems in both males and females. However, the results stayed controversial about female fertility, fecundability and longer TTP. There was a significant association between the prevalence of menstrual disorders in Hg-exposed women and the number of years working in the dental professional area (Henriques et al. 2019). Some studies found that mercury cause damage on fertility, however other publications did not find associations with fecundity markers. To conclude, the results are still controversial and unclear for fecundity and more studies are needed.

A study evaluated the impact of low-level arsenic exposure on human fecundity. The aim in this pilot study was a preliminary evaluation of associations between low-level drinking water arsenic

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contamination and female fecundity. The results showed that higher levels of arsenic were associated with a lower probability for pregnancy among women with longer TTPs. For example, 1 µg/L average drinking water arsenic conferred 5%, 8%, and 10% lower likelihoods for pregnancy in the 6th, 9th, and 12th cycles, respectively ($P = 0.01$). More studies are required to confirm these results (Susko et al. 2017).

A Chinese case control study explored the association between the risk of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and the concentrations of several emerging chemicals. The results showed that with stratification according to body mass index one UV filter, octocrylene (OC) was significantly associated with PCOS in women with BMI ≥ 24 (adjusted OR = 1.512, 95 % CI: 1.043, 2.191, $p=0.029$) (Gu et al. 2019). Not all UV filters affected women fertility, only one appears to cause damage on PCOS but only for the women with high BMI. More studies are needed to understand this association and to confirm this result. Moreover, a previous study on exposure to UV filters and fertility, male partners' concentrations BP-2 was associated with reduced fecundity (Buck Louis et al. 2014).

9.3 Highlights

In the previous report (Deliverable 11.3), the literature research has shown that many substances are known or suspected to have health effects on reproductive health (Table 8). The crosses in the last column of Table 8 indicate the associations previously found in the previous deliverable. The other columns with a cross represent each of the reproductive health indicators and their associations with different chemicals found in this work.

Eleven chemical substances potentially affecting reproductive health have been studied. In the course of this literature search, nine substances affecting reproductive health were identified in common with the previous report: lead, mercury, pesticides, UV filters, phthalates, bisphenol, PFASs, flame-retardants and cadmium. Other substances still do not seem to affect reproductive health, as they are not mentioned either in the report or in the literature search. However, some divergent points were noted such as acrylamide and mycotoxins for which the literature review of the last 5 years did not give relevant results even if they are mentioned in the previous version of the report. And conversely with air pollutants, arsenic and anilines.

With this state of the art, it is possible to identify the markers of reproductive health that are most affected by chemicals in general population biomonitoring studies. These are fertility and fecundity, reproductive hormones, sperm quality and damage to sperm DNA. Other markers such as AGD, cryptorchidism and hypospadias appear to be less affected by chemicals. Through this research, it has been shown that pesticides, bisphenol, phthalates and lead are known to affect reproductive health through several markers. Other chemical substances have more contrasting results. However, one can still suspect an impact on reproductive health for air pollutants, flame-retardants, PFASs and cadmium. Some substances require additional studies to confirm or refute their link to reproductive health, such as acrylamide, arsenic, mycotoxines, UV filters, anilines and mercury, although a few studies suggest a potential link. Finally, the literature has not yet shown an association between aprotic solvent, diisocyanates, mixtures or emerging chemicals and reproductive health.

Table 8: Known or suspected chemicals substances of affecting reproductive health

	AGD	Cryptorchidism	Hypospadias	Semen quality	Sperm DNA damage	Reproductive hormones	Fertility & Fecundity	Previous report (D11.3)
Acrylamide								✓
Aprotic solvent								
Arsenic				✓	✓		✓	
Diisocyanates								
Lead			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mercury				✓	✓		✓	✓
Mycotoxines								✓
Pesticides	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
UV filters				✓		✓	✓	✓
Phthalates	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bisphenols	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PFASs	✓			✓		✓	✓	✓
FR	✓	✓	✓			✓	✓	✓
Cadmium				✓		✓	✓	✓
PAH				✓	✓	✓	✓	
Anilines	✓	✓				✓		
Mixtures								
Emerging Chemicals								
Total	6	3	5	10	7	10	11	11

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10 Fetal development

Authors: Rambaud Loïc (ANSP), Riou Margaux (ANSP)

10.1 Measurement of fetal development

Exposure to environmental stressors during the highly sensitive period of embryonic and fetal development can induce later phenotypic variation due to adaptive developmental plasticity, mediated in part by epigenetic changes. It can also increase the risk of chronic diseases later in life. Low birth weight is a non-specific adverse birth outcome, which may reflect prematurity or fetal growth restriction related to a suboptimal intrauterine environment, such as impaired placental function, and other causal risk factors.

For epidemiological studies, information about birth weight can be obtained through questionnaire or birth registers. A Norwegian study found that maternal self-reported information about birth weight is very reliable. On average, -0.03 (sd = 0.20) kg difference was observed between self-reported and register-based data.

Birth weight is considered as the main indicator of fetal growth and development and depends mainly on genetics, maternal nutrition and placenta circulation. It is associated with the health outcome of the newborn, including short-term survival and development of future diseases. Moreover, it has been related to the development of chronic diseases in adulthood, such as cardiovascular disease or cancer (Cabrera-Rodríguez et al. 2019).

According to the International Classification for Diseases 10 (ICD-10) the code which should be used for birth weight is P07 "Disorders related to short gestation and low birth weight, not elsewhere classified". In the ICD-11 coding, similar code is KA21 "Disorders of newborn related to short gestation or low birth weight, not elsewhere classified". In the ICPC-2 there is no code for birth weight, in the ICPC-3 there is a code for premature newborn with index term "low birth weight" coded as AD65.

However, there are other indicators of fetal growth not addressed in this deliverable such as birth length and head circumference. Moreover, the studies selected are focused on general population biomonitoring studies published during the last five years. There are many other relevant studies to explore the link between fetal development and chemicals exposure, such as animal testing studies, which are not discussed here.

10.2 Environmental chemicals associated with fetal development

10.2.1 Pesticides

An American study assessed the association between maternal urinary phenol concentrations in pregnancy and fetal growth. The results showed non-significant associations in generalised linear models. However, in gender stratified analysis, it was showed that maternal diclorophenol (2, 4-DCP and 2, 5-DCP) levels were significantly associated with lower birth weight z-score for males. For instance, 2,4-DCP an IQR difference in average was associated with a 0.18 standard deviation decrease in birth weight z-score (95 % CI=-0.33, -0.02), which corresponds to a 77 g decrease in birth weight. And 2,5-DCP, was associated with a 0.21 standard deviation decrease in birth weight z-score (95% CI= -0.40, -0.03), which corresponds to a 90 g decrease in birth weight (Ferguson et al. 2018).

A South African birth cohort study investigated the associations between DDT and pyrethroids and birth outcomes. The results showed significant associations only among girls for p,p'-DDT and o,p'-

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DDT on the birth weight, β p,p'-DDT = 70.7 g (95 % CI: 11.8, 130.8); β o,p'-DDT = 80.4 g (95% CI: 10.2, 149.9) respectively (Chevrier et al. 2019).

A study from the Netherlands investigated the association between organophosphate pesticide (OP) exposure and reduced birth weight. The results are not consistent. They found that a 10-fold increase in average DAPs was associated with a -0.32 SDS decrease in estimated fetal weight (95 % CI = -0.59, -0.04) at 20 weeks of gestation. However, associations between average DAPs and growth measures at delivery were null for weight (Ferguson et al. 2019).

A Bangladeshi birth cohort evaluated the associations between pesticides exposure and birth outcomes. The results is that women with detectable concentrations of IMPY were at increased risk of having a child born with low birth weight compared to women with non-detectable concentrations - adjusted RR (95 % CI): 2.13 (1.12, 4.08) (Jaacks et al. 2019).

A Spanish cross-sectional study evaluated the potential adverse health effects of twenty organochlorine pesticides on newborns. The results showed a positive association between the cord blood concentration of p,p'-DDE and the birth weight. Regarding the effect of mixtures, boys exhibiting more than 3 OCPs, were at lower risk of having higher birth weight (OR=0.25; 95 % CI=0.07 - 0.89; P=0.032) (Cabrera-Rodríguez et al. 2019).

A French birth cohort explored the relation between maternal hair concentrations of pesticides and birth outcomes. To select variables, the elastic-net approach was used and the following pesticides were selected as predictors of birth weight: β -endosulfan (decrease, i.e., BW decreases with exposure), permethrin (decrease), fipronil sulfone (increase), mecoprop (decrease), bitertanol (increase), DMST (dimethylsulftoluidide, increase), diflufenican (decrease), and imidacloprid (decrease). They observed a significant association between medium level of exposure to fipronil sulfone pesticide and birth weight (β adjusted = +150 g; 44, 255) compared to the group with the lowest exposure level. Moreover, analyses restricted to boys showed eight additional compounds associated with birth weight : 5 were associated with higher birth weight such as 3Me4NP, DCPMU, DMST, fipronil and thiabendazole and three with lower birth weight such as mecoprop, propoxur and fenhexamid (Béranger et al. 2020).

10.2.2 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

A mother-infant pairs study from Taiwan Birth Panel Study investigated the link between perfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and birth outcomes since the evidence in human studies were still inconclusive. Their results showed that at birth, perfluorooctyl sulfonate (PFOS) levels were negatively associated with weight, per ln unit: adjusted β = -0.14 and 95 % confidence interval CI = -0.26, -0.01. Gender stratified analysis: the results are not significant at birth. A significant association was found later in the child's growth. For instance, PFOS levels were negatively associated with weight for girls during the time span of 6 to 12 and 12 to 24 months of age (Chen et al. 2017).

A Scandinavian case-cohort study explored maternal serum levels of perfluoroalkyl substances and organochlorines and indices of fetal growth. In adjusted linear models, the results showed that for the Swedish cohort, birth weight decreased significantly by -359 g (95 % CI: -596, -122; p=0.003) and -292 g (95% CI: -500, -84; p=0.006) per ln-unit increase in PFOA and PFOS, respectively. In Swedish gender stratified analysis, a significant decrease in birth weight (β = -526 g; 95 % CI: -828, -222; p=0.001) was observed for PFOA among male children (Lauritzen et al. 2017).

A Chinese mother-child pairs study investigated the association between PFASs and fetal growth. The results revealed that higher PFOS, PFOA and isomers of PFOS were associated with lower

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birth weight. For instance, per ln-unit (ng/mL) increase in cord serum total branched PFOS isomers was associated with a 126.3 g (95 % CI: -195.9, -56.8; $p < 0.05$) reduction in the weight of infants at birth. After adjustment, an ln-unit (ng/mL) increase of serum linear PFOS isomers (n-PFOS) was associated with a 57.2 g (95 % CI: -103.1, -11.3; $p < 0.05$) reduction in the weight of infants at birth. The association between cord PFAS level and birthweight was more pronounced in male infants (Li et al. 2017).

A Chinese newborns study evaluated the association of perfluoroalkyl substances in cord serum with growth indicators. The results showed that there are non-significant association of PFASs and fetal growth in the study, which may be due to relatively low exposure dose (Shi et al. 2017).

An American study assessed the feasibility and utility of using newborn dried blood spots for quantifying PFOS, PFOA and their associations with selected infant outcomes. The results showed no significant association with birth outcomes (Bell et al. 2018).

A Chinese study explored the associations of PFAS concentrations in umbilical cord blood with gestational and postnatal growth. Infants exposed to PFNA (0.08 – 0.14) and PFUdA (0.06 – 0.11) in the second tertiles showed increased birth weight, whereas PFDoA (0.02 – 0.04 ng/mL) showed decreased birth weight compared to the first tertiles ($\beta = 138.1$ g, 95 % CI: 15.6 to 260.7, $\beta = 142.0$ g, 95 % CI: 19.3 to 264.7 and $\beta = -122.9$ g, 95 % CI: -244.7 to -1.2 respectively). Gender stratified analysis showed that PFDoA decreased birth weight among girls ($\beta = -215.9$ g, 95 % CI: -389.3 to -42.5) (Cao et al. 2018).

Another Chinese study investigated the association between exposure of PFASs and birth outcomes. The results of univariate analyse indicated that an inverse association between birth weight and cord PFOS. After adjustment, a unit increase in logarithmic PFOS was associated with a 417.3 g decline in birth weight ($\beta = -417.3$, 95 % CI: -742.1, -92.4, $p=0.011$) (Xu et al. 2019).

A Canadian cohort study evaluated potential correlations between concentrations of PFAs in maternal plasma and infant cord blood with birth outcomes. They found that only perfluoroundecanoic acid (PFUA) was negatively associated with birth weight: for every unit increase in natural log concentration of PFUA, the birth weight decreased by 76 g (Workman et al. 2019).

A Chinese study investigated the association between PFASs levels in cord samples and birth outcomes. After adjustment, the result showed that a unit increase in logarithmic PFOS was associated with a 417.3 g decline in birth weight ($\beta = -417.3$, 95 % CI: -742.1, -92.4, $p=0.011$). The stratified analysis revealed that effects of PFOS on birth weight were more pronounced in nulliparous than multiparous (Xu et al. 2019).

A recent study on prospective cohort from the Faroe Islands aimed to quantify the associations between maternal serum-PFAS concentrations and birth weight. The results revealed that several PFASs were negatively associated with birth weight (Xiao et al. 2020).

A study investigated the associations between serum persistent organic pollutants (POP) levels of pregnant women in Greenland and their infant's birth weight. They found significant inverse associations between perfluorooctanoic Acid (PFOA) and birth weight (adjusted $\beta = -119$ g, 95% CI: -201; -36; $p=0.005$). Gender stratified analysis showed that PFOA was inversely associated with birth weight ($\beta = -161$ g, $p = 0.010$) among girls (Hjermitslev et al. 2020).

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10.2.3 Cadmium

Cadmium causes adverse effects at lower environmental exposures on endocrine system and reproductive health.

A Chinese study evaluated the association between prenatal Cd exposure and birth outcomes. The results showed that maternal urinary Cd was not significantly associated with low birth weight but with other birth outcomes like gestational age (Yang et al. 2016).

Another study found a significant association between higher cadmium levels and low birth weight, only among the preeclamptic group (Wang et al. 2018).

A Mongolian observational study investigated the relationship between gestational cadmium exposure and fetal growth. The results showed that a doubling of blood cadmium was associated with a 95 g (95 % CI: 34, 155 g) reduction in birth weight among all births in adjusted models (Barn et al. 2019).

A Spanish study examined the association of placental levels of cadmium and other metals with birth outcomes. The results showed that elevated placental Cd levels were associated with reduced birthweight (-111.8 g, 95 % CI=-215.6; -8.06, p-trend=0.01). A 10% increase in Cd was associated with 1.21-fold increased odds (95 % CI=1.01; 1.43) of low birth weight (LBW) in the global sample but with 14% lower odds (95 % CI=0.78; 0.96) of preterm delivery in males (P interaction=0.10) (Freire et al. 2019).

A cross-sectional study including 509 pregnant Inuit women investigated the association between pregnant women's levels of heavy and essential metals and the birth outcomes. The results showed that the maternal blood level of Cd was negatively associated with birth weight $\beta = -75.506 - 95\% \text{ CI: } -122.825; -28.187 - p = 0.002$. Besides, the blood levels of Cd increased the risk of low birth weight with adjusted ORs, $\beta = -78.490 - 95\% \text{ CI: } -136.062; -20.918 - p = 0.008$ (Bank-Nielsen et al., 2019).

An American cohort study found interesting results about cadmium exposure and birth outcomes. The results suggested that the growth of the placenta affected by contaminant element might have a role on birth weight. In multivariable regressions, the placenta weight decreased with every ng/g increase in the Cd concentration of placenta (p-value=0.0009). This association was stronger among females than males. Placental weight would be a mediator in the association between Cd levels during pregnancy and birth weight (Punshon et al., 2019).

10.2.4 Bisphenols

There are still controversies concerning the toxic effects of BPA but there are several cohort studies associating perinatal exposure with bisphenol A. Since 2017, BPA is on the Candidate List of substances of very high concern for Authorisation (SVHC candidates) as it is classified toxic for reproduction. BPA is considered as a threat for pregnant women, foetus and young children. For this reason, young, pregnant or breastfeeding women are at a specific risk.

An American study assessed the feasibility and utility of using newborn dried blood spots for quantifying BPA and their associations with selected infant outcomes. The results showed that among twins, BPA was associated with decreased birthweights (adjusted $\beta = -32.52 \text{ g; } 95\% \text{ CI: } -60.99, -4.05$) (Bell et al., 2018).

An American study examined the association between maternal and paternal preconception urinary BPA or BPS concentrations and birth outcomes. In adjusted models, the results showed that maternal preconception urinary BPA concentrations were inversely associated with birth weight. For each ln-unit, increase was associated with a decrease in birth weight of 119 g (95 %

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CI: -212, -27), $p = 0.01$. Paternal preconception urinary BPA concentrations were not associated with either birth weight. No association was found for BPS concentrations (Mustieles et al., 2018).

A Polish study assessed the impact of maternal exposure to BPA on the exposure of the fetus. The results showed that there was a significant negative correlation between free BPA and fetal birth weight ($R = -0.54$, $p < 0.001$). However, no correlation was found between conjugated and total BPA and the maternal plasma BPA (Zbucka-Krętkowska et al., 2019).

A Chinese study investigated trimester-specific associations of urinary concentrations of BPA, BPF, and BPS with size at birth. The results showed that there were no significant associations between urinary BPA concentrations in different trimesters and birth weight. However, urinary concentration of BPF and BPS were associated with significantly lower birth weight, even after adjustment on other bisphenols. For instance, each IQR increase in urinary BPF and BPS concentration in the first trimester were associated with reduced birth weight $\beta = -27$ (95 % CI: -55, 0g), $\beta = -38$ (95 % CI: -65, -11 g) respectively. For the second-trimester concentrations urinary BPS were significantly associated with reduced birth weight $\beta = -43$ (95 % CI: -71, -15 g) (Hu et al. 2019).

10.2.5 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons & air pollutants

Particulate matter is emitted from a wide range of sources, the most significant primary sources being road transport (20%), homes (20%), construction and mining and quarrying (13%). About 80% of man-made benzene emissions come from petrol-fueled vehicles. PAH and their metabolites may activate estrogen receptors, decreased fertility and semen quality.

An American study examined odds of term low birth weight (LBW) among women exposed to high levels of traffic-related air pollutants during pregnancy. The results estimated a 5% increase in adjusted odds of term LBW per IQR increase in entire pregnancy exposure to several correlated traffic pollutants: LUR measures of NO, NO₂, and NO_x, elemental carbon, and PM_{2.5} from diesel and gasoline combustion and paved road dust (Wilhelm et al. 2012).

A study on a group of healthy, non-smoking pregnant women exposed to eight airborne PAHs investigated the effect of this exposure on birth outcomes. The results showed that one natural-log unit increase in prenatal exposure to the eight summed PAHs during the first trimester was associated with a decrease of birth weight (-105 g, 95 % CI, -188 to -22 g) compared to the units effects of PAHs. This decreasing is most important during the first trimester of pregnancy, therefore it seems to be a window of vulnerability to air pollutants such as PAHs (Choi et al. 2012)

A Polish study assessed the possible impact of coexposure to PAH-containing barbecued meat consumed during pregnancy on birth outcomes. The results showed that barbecued meat consumed in the third trimester of pregnancy was significantly and inversely correlated with birth weight ($z = -1.99$, $P = 0.047$). Moreover, the multivariable regression model showed a significant deficit in birth weight associated with barbecued meat consumption in pregnancy (coeff = -106.0 g; 95 % CI: -293.3, -35.8, $p = 0.004$). The effect of exposure to airborne PAHs was about the same magnitude order (coeff = -164.6 g; 95 % CI: -172.3, -34.7, $p = 0.012$). Combined effect of both sources of exposure amounted to birth weight deficit of 214.3 g (95 % CI: -419.0, -9.6, $p = 0.04$). These results suggested that both sources of PAH have an additive effect on birth weight deficit in newborn (Jedrychowski et al. 2012).

A Chinese study examined the relationship between prenatal exposures to PAH – DNA adducts and birth outcomes in two cohorts of nonsmoking women and their newborns. The results showed no significant association between birth weight and PAH (Tang et al. 2014).

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A study observed effect sizes of prenatal fine particulate matter and polycyclic hydrocarbons exposures on birth outcomes. The results showed that, in the single-pollutant approach, the effect size of prenatal PAH exposure on birth weight was twice that of PM_{2.5}, in terms of standardised coefficients. Nevertheless, in the two-pollutant approach, the negative effect of PM_{2.5} lost its significance, whereas the standardised effect of PAH on birth weight was 10-fold stronger ($\beta = -0.20$, $p = 0.004$) than that estimated for PM_{2.5} ($\beta = -0.02$, $p = 0.757$). These results suggested that the PAH is more biologically relevant to birth outcomes than PM (Jedrychowski et al. 2017).

A Chinese study explored the association between naphthalene (2-OH NAP) and birth outcomes. The results showed a significant association of 2-OH NAP level with low BW (Nie et al. 2018).

A Spanish cross-sectional study evaluated the potential adverse health effects of sixteen polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) on newborns. No association was found for any of the PAHs (Cabrera-Rodríguez et al. 2019).

10.2.6 Phthalates

An American study investigated the relationship between maternal exposure to phthalates in pregnancy and fetal growth. The results showed that MECPP, MEOHP and Σ DEHP were significantly associated with decreases of weight, SD $\Delta = -0.13$ (95 % CI = -0.22, -0.03) $p < 0.01$, SD $\Delta = -0.10$ (95 % CI = -0.20, -0.01) $p = 0.03$ and SD $\Delta = -0.13$ (95 % CI = -0.23, -0.03) $p < 0.01$, respectively (Ferguson et al. 2016).

A Taiwanese study evaluated associations between several endocrine-disrupting compounds (phthalates, bisphenol, pesticides) and birth outcomes. They estimated the effects of separate and correlated exposures. A significant association was found between DEP concentrations and reduced birth weight ($\beta = -111.36$, 95 % CI: -210.52; -12.20, $p < 0.05$) during second trimester. No other association was found with birth weight: after controlling for covariates, prenatal multiple exposures to NP, BPA, MMP, Σ PAEs, DEP and Σ DEPs were not associated with infant birth weight (Huang et al. 2017).

10.2.7 Flame retardants

An American study examined the impacts of organophosphate esters (OPEs) used as flame-retardants on birth weight in the Pregnancy Infection and Nutrition Study (PIN). The results showed that higher ip-PPP levels were associated with lower birth weight, but not after standardising for gestational age (Hoffman et al. 2018).

A recent Chinese case control study explored the prenatal exposure to organophosphate flame-retardants (OPFRs) and an increase in the risk of low birth weight (LBW). The results showed that compared with the lowest tertile of diphenyl phosphate (DPHP) concentrations, pregnant women with the highest tertile of DPHP had a 4.62-fold (95 % confidence interval (CI): 1.72, 12.40). An effect dose-response and sex dependent among female newborns was also found (Luo et al. 2020).

10.2.8 Mixtures

A Belgian mother-child cohort, FLEHS II, estimated the effects of exposure to single pollutants and mixtures on birth weight in 248 mother-child pairs. The results showed that there are stronger effects when analysed as mixtures and by gender. For instance, in girls, the estimated effect was doubled with co-exposure of thallium, PFOS, lead, cadmium, manganese, and mercury (estimate = -235 g, $p = 0.0006$), while in boys, the mixture of MECPP with cadmium showed the strongest association with birth weight (estimate = -129 g, $p = 0.0061$) (Govarts et al. 2016).

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A Spanish study suggested that some inorganic elements in mixtures are associated to a lower fetal development. They observed that mixture of Cr, Ni and Sb appeared as a risk for low birth weight (OR=3.84, 95 % CI=1.42–10.39, p=0.008). (Cabrera-Rodríguez et al. 2018)

10.2.9 Acrylamide

A Norwegian prospective pregnancy cohort assessed associations of prenatal exposure to dietary acrylamide with birth weight. The results showed that acrylamide intake was negatively associated with birth weight OR = -25,7g (95 % CI: -35.9, -15.4) for all women in the fourth quartile compared with women in the first quartile, and similar results were found after exclusion of smokers. Stronger associations were observed among the smokers compared with the overall population OR = -50 g (95 % CI: -86.5, -16.6) (Duarte-Salles et al. 2013).

10.2.10 Arsenic

A Belgian mother-child cohort, FLEHS II, estimated the effects of exposure to single pollutants and mixtures on birth weight in 248 mother-child pairs. The results of single pollutant models showed that arsenic was significantly associated with reduced birth weight (p=0,016). The effect increased with other chemicals such as cadmium (p=0,009) and phthalates (Govarts et al. 2016).

Another study evaluated exposure to As in utero to determine the association between maternal and cord blood of As and birth outcomes in South African populations. In univariate and multivariate analysis, there are no association between maternal blood arsenic levels and birth weight (Röllin et al. 2017).

A Spanish study did not find any association between placental levels of arsenic and birth weight (Freire et al. 2019).

A longitudinal prospective study examined arsenic total exposure and low birth weight. The results showed no significant association (Nyanza et al. 2020).

10.2.11 Mercury

A Japanese study assessed the relationship between birth outcomes and prenatal mercury exposure. The result of multivariate analyse showed a negative correlation between blood mercury and birth weight during the first trimester of pregnancy ($\beta = -0.170$, $t = -2.762$; $p = 0.006$) (Vigeh et al. 2018).

A longitudinal prospective study examined mercury total exposure and low birth weight. The results showed no significant association (Nyanza et al. 2020).

10.2.12 UV filters

UV filters may disturb reproductive hormones, fertility and other markers of human reproductive health.

A French study explored the association between phthalates and phenols with changes and birth weight with the multipollutant ENET model. The results showed a positive association between benzophenone-3 and birth weight (Philippat et al. 2019).

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10.3 Highlights

In the previous report (Deliverable 11.3), the literature research showed that many substances are known or suspected to have effects on the development of the fetus; the crosses in the third column of Table 9 indicate these links. The second column indicates an association found for each chemical with fetal development and its indicator, birth weight.

Seven chemical substances potentially affecting fetal development have been studied in D11.3. In the course of this new literature search, a total of twelve substances affecting fetal development were identified. Acrylamide, arsenic, mercury, pesticides, bisphenol and cadmium are common substances. Other substances like aprotic solvent, diisocyanates, mycotoxins or anilines still do not seem to affect fetal development, as they are not mentioned either in the report or in the literature search. However, a divergent point was noted such as aprotic solvent for which the literature review of the last 5 years did not give relevant results even if they are mentioned in the previous version of the report. Conversely with air pollutants, UV filters, phthalates, PFASs, flame-retardant and mixture.

With this state of the art, it is possible to identify the chemical substances affecting the fetal development such as pesticides, PFASs, cadmium, bisphenol and air pollutants are known to affect fetal development through birth weight change. Other chemical substances have more contrasting effects, an impact on fetal development is suspected for phthalates, flame-retardants and mixtures. Some substances require additional studies to confirm or refute their potential adverse effect on fetal development, such as acrylamide, mercury, arsenic and UV filters, although a few studies suggest a potential link. Finally, the literature has not yet shown an association between diisocyanates, lead, mycotoxins, anilines and emerging chemicals and fetal development and its indicator, birth weight, but maybe because these substances are less studied than others.

However, it is important to note that in all of the articles cited above, birth weight is rarely the only birth outcome analysed. Indeed, it is usually associated with other birth outcomes such as birth length, head circumference and gestational age. A WHO technical report has already pointed out that despite its undisputed value as a public health indicator, birth weight does not capture all aspects of fetal growth and development. Indicators that could be used to measure fetal development according to this paper include maternal BMI, placental weight, maternal weight, and other postnatal indicators that some of the cited articles took into account.

Regarding the methodology for collecting birth weight, most articles do not mention the method used and refer to medical records. Some articles mention the use of pediatric scales without giving any detail about the measurement. The development of a standardised measurement would be an advantage here.

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Table 9: Known or suspected chemicals substances of affecting fetal development

Environmental chemicals	Fetal Development (Actual report D11.4)	Fetal Development (Previous report D11.3)
Acrylamide	✓	✓
Aprotic solvent		✓
Arsenic	✓	✓
Diisocyanates		
Lead		
Mercury	✓	✓
Mycotoxins		
Pesticides	✓	✓
UV filters	✓	
Phthalates	✓	
Bisphenols	✓	✓
PFASs	✓	
FR	✓	
Cadmium	✓	✓
PAH	✓	
Anilines		
Mixtures	✓	
Emerging Chemicals		
Total	12	7

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11 Kidney function

Author: Haverinen Elsi (THL)

Kidney diseases and decreased kidney functions are increasing worldwide, causing significant morbidity and mortality. Kidney health is usually determined by how well the organ is able to filter blood by removing excess metabolic waste and fluids. Additionally, kidneys influence red blood cell formation, mineral metabolism, blood pressure and other endocrine functions (Methods to Estimate and Measure Renal Function (Glomerular Filtration Rate), 2013). The stages and effects of kidney damage can vary, and the mechanisms behind the effects are diverse. Most common kidney diseases include acute kidney injury (AKI), chronic kidney disease (CKD) or end-stage kidney disease (ESKD). In this chapter adverse kidney health effects caused by syndromes or cancer are not discussed.

AKI is a condition which occurs on sudden onset, most often caused by injury or impairment of the kidney (KDIGO, 2012). AKI's renal effects include fluid overload, electrolyte and acid-base derangement, immune dysfunctions and bleeding complications (Hoste et al., 2018). Interestingly, estimates on AKI prevalence range from <1% to 66% due to inconsistent use of standardised classification criteria (Hoste et al., 2018). If untreated, AKI can lead to CKD or even further to ESKD (Hoste et al., 2018). Although, AKI occurs globally, especially low-income countries' environmental factors, such as contaminated water and endemic infections play a role in the morbidity (Couser et al., 2011; Hoste et al., 2018).

In 2017, the global prevalence of CKD was estimated to be 9.1%, meaning 697.5 million patients and 1.2 million deaths (Global Burden of Disease Study, 2020). CKD is defined as abnormal kidney structure or function lasting more than three months with associated health implications. Indicators include albuminuria, urine sediment abnormalities, abnormal findings in renal imaging, serum electrolyte or acid-base derangements, and glomerular filtration rate (GFR) less than 60 mL per minute per 1.73m² (KDIGO, 2013). CKD causes permanent loss of nephrons, leading in structural, functional and molecular changes in the organ (Orr & Bridges, 2017). Environmental chemicals can be an exposure factor for CKD among variety of other risk factors, such as age-related kidney functions' decline, elevated blood pressure, hyperlipidemia, glomerulonephritis, arteriosclerosis, cardiovascular disease and structural diseases (Satarug et al., 2018; Methods to Estimate and Measure Renal Function (Glomerular Filtration Rate), 2013). CKD is also a comorbidity of diabetes, obesity, hypertension and other renal disorders (Satarug et al., 2017; Satarug et al., 2018).

The most severe form of kidney malfunction, ESKD, is defined as a stage in which the renal failure is chronic and irreversible and requires renal replacement therapy (RRT) i.e. dialysis or transplantation (Sommar et al., 2013). 1.9 million people are estimated to undergo RRT worldwide, however the estimation is based on register data and excludes people who are not able to access such treatment (Anand et al., 2013). At global level, ESKD causes 1.2 million premature deaths each year due to lack of access to RRT as a result of diabetes and elevated blood pressure and as many as 3.2 million premature deaths due to all causes of ESKD (Anand et al., 2013). At individual level, ESKD carries significant physical and psychological impact, and increases significantly the risk for hospitalisation and mortality.

The challenge of detecting possible renal diseases lies on kidneys' asymptomatic nature. Kidney functions can be maintained until only 25 % of the nephrons are viable; however after this stage it can no longer withhold sufficient fluid homeostasis and proper renal function (Orr & Bridges, 2017; Hoste et al., 2018). Economic costs of kidney diseases are significant, as Levey et al. (2007)

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concluded that developed nations spend 2-3 % of their annual health care budget on treatment of ESKD patients, while they comprise only 0.02-0.03% of the total population. It is vital to also to understand the effects of environmental chemicals to poor kidney health, as it is a major public health concern, and a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases. According to Shiue & Hristova (2014), Arsenic and Lead exposure are estimated to count for 7% and 5% respectively for the population attributable risk for high blood pressure, one of the main risk factors for kidney health.

Medical records may provide useful information on kidney function (Anandarajah et al. 2005). For identifying patients with decreased kidney functions from public records ICD-10 codes and ICPC – codes can be used (Table 10). The ICD-11 coding, which will be adapted in use by 2022, will have more specific coding for AKI (WONCA, 2016; WHO ICD-11, 2020; WHO ICD-10, 2019).

Table 10: ICD-10, ICD-11 and ICPC coding for acute and chronic kidney function diagnoses

Condition	ICD-10 code	ICD-11 code and sub-codes	ICPC
Acute renal failure (AKI)	N17	GB60 GB60.0 Acute kidney failure, stage 1 GB60.1 Acute kidney failure, stage 2 GB60.2 Acute kidney failure, stage 3 JB44.4 Postpartum acute renal failure GB60.Y Other specified acute kidney failure GB60.Z Acute kidney failure, stage unspecified	
Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	N18	GB61	
CKD with stage 1 (eGFR ≥90)	N18.1	GB61.0	
CKD with stage 2 (eGFR 60-89)	N18.2	GB61.1	
CKD with stage 3 (eGFR 30-59)	N18.3	GB61.2 stage 3a/ GB61.3 stage 3b	
CKD with stage 4 (eGFR 15-29)	N18.4	GB61.4	
CKD with stage 5 (eGFR <15)	N18.5	GB61.5	
ESKD End stage renal disease	N18.6	-	
Chronic kidney disease unspecified	N18.9	GB61.Z	
Unspecified renal failure	N19	GB62	
Endocrine/metabolic/nutritional Limited function/disability (t)			T28

For retrieving information on kidney function by questionnaire, HBM4EU and EHIS standardised questions can be used (Appendix 22.2).

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11.1 Measurement methods and standardisation of criteria

Kidneys' capacity to function can be estimated by using several different measurement methods and data collection means. Health information surveys collect self-reported health information by questionnaires. The HBM4EU initiative has provided a standard questionnaire which includes a question on kidney disease or dysfunction diagnosed by a medical doctor including the time and age of the diagnosis (HBM4EU Basic questionnaire for 1st priority substances) (see Appendix 22.2). However, it must be acknowledged that self-reported data and/or register data may provide less accurate data in comparison to biological measurements due to misclassification of over- or under reporting.

In Human Biomonitoring studies in addition to register and questionnaire data, also biological sample collection is often used. For chronic kidney diseases several different measurement methods currently exist. In this chapter, the most commonly used measurement methods are presented including; measured and estimated glomerular filtration, serum creatinine, cystatin-C, albumin- and proteinuria-creatinine-ratios.

The process of kidneys' filtering is called glomerular filtration (GFR). Unfortunately, measuring GFR is complicated in clinical practice requiring substantial time and resources; hence estimation (eGFR) is considered equally effective measure to assess kidney function (Methods to Estimate and Measure Renal Function (Glomerular Filtration Rate), 2013). Estimated GFR (eGFR) is based on person's age, gender, ethnicity, measured level of creatinine and/or cystatin C in serum (Jain, 2019). Notably, it is suggested to use both measures when possible in estimating GFR, as it is more cost-effective and gives more accurate reference values than either marker used alone (Inker et al., 2012; Methods to Estimate and Measure Renal Function (Glomerular Filtration Rate), 2013). In comparison, Yashiro et al. (2009) compared cystatin-C and creatinine for evaluation in chronic kidney diseases, and suggested Cys-C to be used as marker for GFR due to its un-relatedness to age or gender. However, inflammation, use of cortisone and diabetes caused deviation in Cys-C to deviate higher than expected from GFR.

Serum creatinine (SCr) is the most common and accessible biomarker of kidney function. SCr can be used in the calculation of GFR, in analysing the state of CKD and as main criteria when assessing AKI (Kashani, Rosner & Ostermann, 2020). Cystatin C (CysC) is a cysteine protease inhibitor that is present in all tissue and produced at a constant rate, filtered freely, and neither secreted into the renal tubules nor absorbed into the blood stream from the renal tubules (Methods to Estimate and Measure Renal Function (Glomerular Filtration Rate), 2013). In addition to these biomarkers, other cardio-renal function methods can be used to assess kidneys' function, e.g. blood samples assessing albumin, urea or serum uric acid concentrations (Kataria, Trasande & Trachtman, 2015).

In CKD diagnostics, urine and blood samples are used as parameters for the disease. As CKD is comprised of two components, renal function decline and kidney damage, both aspects should be considered in the diagnostics and estimation of the stage of the disease. Measured GFR is considered as a gold standard for diagnoses, however due to its complexity and high cost, eGFR is more feasible measurement method in most clinical settings. Table 11, the different kidney function and kidney damage measurement methods are presented shortly. In addition to the measurement method chosen to assess kidney function also technical considerations such as preservation and analytical methods should be considered. Jaffe and enzymatic methods are the most commonly used measuring methods for serum creatinine. Jaffe method is less expensive than the enzymatic method; however it is also suggested to be more sensitive for errors, which can lead to misclassification and even misdiagnosis (Schmidt et al., 2015).

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Table 11: Kidney function measurement methods

Kidney function tests	Methods	Pathology
Measured GFR (mGFR)	Renal insulin clearance (gold standard) Renal or plasma clearance of diethylene-triamine-penta-acetic acid Renal or plasma clearance of radioactively tagged ethylenedia-minetetra-acetic acid Iohoxol Iothalamate	renal function
Estimated GFR (eGFR)	Serum Creatinine and/or Cystatin C. If SCr used for estimation background information on muscle mass, age, sex, ethnicity, weight, height are needed. CysC does not require background information for the calculation.	renal function
Serum creatinine (SCr)	Jaffe method Enzymatic method	renal function
Cystatin C (Cys-C)	Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA)	renal function
Albumin-creatinine-ratio (ACR)	Measurement of albumin should be done preferably from a morning urine specimen.	kidney damage
Proteinuria-creatinine-ratio (PCR)	Measurement of total protein should be done from a morning urine specimen.	kidney damage

When examining pre-analytical stages and its effects on standardisation of measurements and results, also technical issues such as preservation and analytical methods should be considered. Ford and Berg (2008) argue that as eGFR is used mainly in primary health care, a significant delay between sample collection, separation and analysis may occur. In their study, creatinine measurement using Jaffe method and delayed sample separation (24 hours), 32% of the samples were misclassified or changed stages in the CKD categorisation (1-5). An average of 11% increase in the creatinine values were observed after 24 hour delay in the separation (Ford & Berg, 2008). In a study comparing serum creatinine levels using Jaffe method and enzymatic assay, good concordance in healthy adult population was revealed among the two methods. However, among diabetics, the enzymatic method performed slightly better (Cheuiche et al., 2013).

A global approach to standardise kidney diseases have been made by the National Kidney Foundation – Kidney Disease Outcomes Quality Initiative -guidelines (Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes, 2013; Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes, 2012). The classification of AKI includes three stages measuring the severity of the condition (KDIGO, 2012). The definition of AKI is fulfilled if there is an increase in SCr by ≥ 0.3 mg/dl within 48 hours or increase in SCr to ≥ 1.5 times from the baseline, which is known or presumed to have occurred within the prior 7 days, or urine volume < 0.5 ml/kg/h for 6 hours. CKD classification is divided into five categories, describing the severity of the condition using eGFR thresholds and proteinuria. Stage 1 and 2 include stages of reduced eGFR levels, as stage 5 is defined as kidney failure (ESKD). 90% of the population with CKD is estimated to comprise of stage 3 patients with mild to severely increased eGFR levels (KDIGO, 2013). For ESKD renal functions are non-existent and require immediate health care intervention, in other words RRT or kidney transplant (KDIGO, 2009; Couser et al., 2011).

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Daily consumer products, food and outside environment expose general public to wide range of chemicals in daily life. Prolonged environmental exposure, in conjunction with other risk factors such as age-associated decline in kidney functions and other comorbidities, can accelerate progression of CKD (Kataria et al., 2015). For children, exposure to chemicals can be especially harmful, as during in utero-phase and in early childhood organs, pathways and connections are still being established. Exposure to chemicals during this time can alter cell signaling and development (Zheng et al., 2017) and furthermore affect the blood-brain barrier which is not fully developed until 36 months of life (Sly & Flack, 2008).

The epidemiological evidence between chronic kidney diseases and environmental chemical exposure is still incoherent and used measurement methods and standardisation in the studies are inconsistent. In the next chapters, some evidence of the environmental chemicals and related adverse kidney functions are presented.

11.2 Environmental chemicals associated with chronic kidney disease

11.2.1 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

In a scoping review by Stanifer et al. (2018), 21 epidemiological studies investigating PFAS exposure and kidney health were identified between years 2003-2017. Eleven of these studies assessed exposure through serum concentrations or prevalent CKD. Perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctane sulfonate (PFOS) were most often examined, and in addition four studies also included analysis on perfluorohexane sulfonate (PFHxS) and two studies on perfluorononanoic acid (PFNA). Five studies, three being cross-sectional NHANES-studies, found association between decreased eGFR or prevalent CKD and PFAS exposure among both children and adults (Dhingra et al., 2017; Kataria et al., 2015; Shankar et al., 2011; Vearrier et al., 2013; Watkins et al., 2013) as six studies examining eGFR, serum creatinine or prevalent CKD observed no association (Conway et al., 2017; Emmett et al., 2006; Olsen et al., 2003; Olsen et al., 2012; Steenland et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2014). Notably, the studies with no association focused mainly on adult populations. Moreover, the focus was mainly on occupational studies and communities located near surrounding manufactories. In addition to the epidemiological studies, the authors presented current knowledge on pharmacokinetic studies (n=13) and toxicology studies (n=40). From the animal studies, most studies indicated small changes in blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and/or creatinine concentrations across different exposure levels.

Rappazzo et al. (2017) investigated in their systematic review PFAS exposure on children, and identified four studies. Watkins et al., (2013) and Kataria et al. (2015) examining children from US were also included in the review by Stanifer et al. (2018), however two new studies from Taiwan; Lin et al. (2013) and Qin et al. (2016) were also added. Lin et al. (2013) observed that PFUA levels were higher in children with chronic renal failure and Qin et al. (2016) noticed that increasing PFOA was associated with increased odds of high uric acid level (≥ 6 mg/dL), having potentially higher odds in boys than girls.

One study outside the review by Stanifer et al. (2018) and Rappazzo et al. (2017) was identified to focus on children, hyperuricemia and PFOA and PFOS levels. Although, hyperuricemia is not necessarily a direct indicator of kidney function, it can give indication of decreased kidney elimination. The study concluded that PFOA and PFOS were significantly associated with hyperuricemia when comparing first quartile (1 referents) and quartile 4, multivariable-adjusted OR of 1.62 (95% CI 1.10-2.37) for PFOA and 1.65 (95% CI 1.10-2.49) for PFOS (Geiger et al., 2013).

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Studies published since the Stanifer et al.'s (2018) scoping review have provided more evidence suggesting association between PFAS exposure and adverse kidney health (Blake et al., 2018; Jain and Ducatman, 2019a; Lin et al., 2021).

11.2.2 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

PAH substance group composes of over hundred components (Kataria et al., 2015). Different PAH components are metabolised in the liver and kidneys as hydroxylated metabolites in hours or days and excreted in urine (Farzan et al., 2016). Notably, very limited amount of studies have yet focused on PAHs and kidney health, hence more monitoring among different subpopulations are needed.

In a NHANES study examining adolescents' ten urinary PAH metabolites and kidney function, some evidence of association was found with serum increased uric acid, GGT, CRP and decreased eGFR (Farzan et al., 2016).

In a recent NHANES study using data between 2003-2014, urinary PAH metabolites (OH-PAHs) were associated with increased albumin-creatinine-ratio (ACR) between lowest and highest quartiles (Li et al., 2020).

In a Korean population survey, three urinary PAH components (1-Phenanthrene, 2-Phenanthrene and 1-Pyrene) were linked to development of CKD (Lee et al., 2020).

In Taiwan, geographical exposure and adverse kidney health were examined showing urinary 1-hydroxypyrene (1-OHP) concentration to be associated with living close to petrochemical industry. A decrease in eGFR, higher ORs for CKD and high-intermediate risk of CKD were observed (Yuan et al., 2020).

11.2.3 Heavy metals Cadmium, Lead, Mercury and Arsenic

Environmental heavy metals are widespread and their effects on human health through food and diet are unavoidable. In the past years, several studies have focused on individual and joint effects of heavy metals and their possible association in development and progression of chronic kidney diseases. Some evidence on the individual and mixed effects have been able to be presented in the general population, however causal relationships are still difficult to prove. In Table 12 studies among different populations globally and in different age groups are presented.

Table 12: Individual and joint effects of heavy metals to kidney disease

Authors and year	Heavy metals	Outcome measured	Population studied	Results
Sanders et al. (2019)	As, Pb, Cd, Hg	eGFR, serum uric acid (SUA), urine albumin, blood urea nitrogen (BUN), systolic blood pressure (SBP) and Umix (As, Cd, Pb, Hg) and Ublood (Cd, Pb, Hg)	Adolescents 12-19 yrs, NHANES	The mixed and individual effects of As, Pb, Cd, Hg were measured using WQS regression analysis. Umix showed evidence of association with BUN, e GFR and urinary albumin. Hg, As, Cd and Pb measured in urine were associated with higher eGFR. In single-metal analyses urine Pb and Cd were associated with increased urine albumin. No association was observed between Bmix (Cd, Pb, Hg) and eGFR, urine albumin, BUN or SBP. No significant association between urine Hg and albumin levels.

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Authors and year	Heavy metals	Outcome measured	Population studied	Results
Kim et al. (2015)	Pb, Hg, Cd	CKD serum creatinine, urine albumin	KNHANES, adults	No association was found after adjusting for age, sex, BMI, smoking, hyperlipidaemia, hypertension and diabetes when using multivariate logistic regression models. Cd was associated with CKD among adults with hypertension or diabetes (OR 1.52, 95% CI 1.05-2.19, p= 0.026). No similar effect with Hg or Pb.
Sommar et al., (2013)	Cd, Pb, Hg	End stage kidney disease	population-based case-referent study, Swedish adult population	Pb in erythrocytes and blood showed association with end-stage kidney disease at low levels (OR 1.54, 95% CI 1.18-2.0). Hg was negatively associated (OR 0.75, 95% CI 0.56-0.99). Cd showed some evidence of association (OR 1.15, 95% CI 0.99-1.34). Notably, gender-specific analyses suggest that men carried most of the Pb and Pb associated risk.
Zhu et al., (2019)	Cd, Pb, Hg	Albuminuria, albumin-creatinine-ratio (ACR)	NHANES, adults	Urinary ACR was significantly higher among participants with blood Cd level in quartile 3 than in quartile 1. Urinary Cd levels were associated with albuminuria. Pb and Hg showed no association.
Navas-Acien et al. (2009)	Cd, Pb	CKD urinary albumin, urinary creatinine, serum creatinine, eGFR	NHANES, adults	Blood Cd and Pb levels were higher among older participants, with lower education level, and current or previous smoking history. Blood Pb was also higher among men, alcohol drinkers and participants with hypertension. For reduced eGFR, fully adjusted odds ratios comparing the highest versus the lowest blood cadmium and lead quartiles were 1.32 (95% CI 1.04- 1.68) and 1.56 (95% CI, 1.17- 2.08) respectively. Increased blood Cd and Pb levels were independent factors for albuminuria, reduced eGFR and both outcomes together.
Pollack et al. (2014)	Pb, Hg, Cd	blood Pb, Hg, Cd	Premenopausal women	Median levels of Cd, Pb, and Hg were 0.31 µg/L, 0.88 µg/dl, and 1.1 µg/L, respectively. One-third of women had diminished glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) (<90 ml/min/1.73 m ²). Each twofold increase in Cd was associated with a negative 4.9% change in blood urea nitrogen (BUN) and bilirubin. Each twofold rise in Pb was associated with decreased eGFR and increased creatinine. A twofold elevation in Hg was associated with higher protein and reduced alkaline phosphatase.

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11.2.4 Cadmium

A small amount of Cd is excreted in the urine, but mostly it's accumulated in the kidney cortex (Satarug et al., 2002). Accumulation of Cd in the kidneys leads to reduced GFR, polyuria and generalised tubular dysfunction (Nordberg et al., 1992). One of the earliest signs of kidney injury is seen in urinary biomarkers; changes in kidney injury molecule-1, β_2 -microglobulin, N-acetyl- β -D-glucosamidase and cystatin-C (Nordberg et al., 1992).

Although, liver is the main site for acute Cd exposure, chronic exposure to high levels of Cd are also distributed to kidneys, where it accumulates on tubular epithelial cells (Prozialeck & Edwards, 2012). For certain groups, such as elderly, diabetics, patients with hypertension and smokers, blood sampling may be more suitable matrix, as their kidney function may be affected from these health outcomes. Interestingly, sex differences and Cd levels seem to be significant. It is suggested that lower serum ferritin levels might affect the uptake of Cd through the divalent metal transporter (DMT1) and increase body burden (Jayatilake et al., 2013).

Among heavy metal exposure Cd seems to indicate strongest association of exposure and adverse kidney effects among general population in different age groups (See Table 12 for joint heavy metal exposure studies assessing individual and joint effects) (Zhu et al., 2019; Sommar et al., 2009; Kim et al., 2015; Sanders et al., 2019; Ferraro et al., 2010; Navas-Acien et al., 2009).

In an individual study examining Cd exposure among US adult population (NHANES between years 1999-2006) higher Cd blood levels were associated with CKD and kidney damage (Ferraro et al., 2010).

In Zheng et al.'s (2017) systematic review on children's kidney effects and Cd exposure revealed incoherent results among the seven studies identified. Most studies revealed some evidence of associations, however did not often reach level of significance. For this, the evidence was considered to be suggestive among children. The authors also conducted a quality analysis of the studies and found two large studies (over 500 participants) which adjusted for confounders and concluded that they provide reasonable evidence on the association among early life Cd exposure (Weaver et al., 2014; Swaddiwudhipong et al., 2015).

11.2.5 Lead

Harari et al. (2018) suggested Pb to affect renal functions by entering the kidney's proximal tubule by endocytosis after binding to low-molecular-weight proteins. In the cells, it inhibits renal mitochondrial respiratory function, causing oxidative stress, reactive oxidative species, intracellular depletion of glutathione apoptosis (Harari et al., 2018).

In a large Swedish prospective population-based cohort, association between low-level Pb exposure and decreased kidney function were examined. Blood sampling was used as a measurement method. In this study, participants in the highest quartiles (3rd and 4th) had higher eGFR changes in the follow-up in comparison to the participants in the lower quartiles. Interestingly, association of blood Pb levels and lowered eGFRs were seen already in the second quartile, suggesting low level exposure to be a concern. Hypertension and age also increased the suspected risk of nephrotoxicity. (Harari et al., 2018.) In another Swedish population-based prospective cohort, erythrocyte lead was associated with end-stage renal disease, especially present among men (Sommar et al., 2013).

Another recent study revealed that Pb exposure was associated with reduced eGFR among general population in Republic of Korea between years 1999-2016 (Lee et al., 2020). According to Kim & Lee (2012) Pb exposure and decreased eGFR were associated among South Korean general population, as the difference in eGFR levels comparing participants in the highest versus

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the lowest quartiles of blood lead was -3.835 mL/min per 1.73 m² (95% CI, -5.730 to -1.939). In another joint analysis of Cd and Pb, for the highest quartile of blood lead, the participants were 19% more likely to have albuminuria, 56% more likely to have reduces eGFR, and twice as likely to have both outcomes compared to the participants in the lowest quartile (Navas-Acien et al., 2009). Among adolescents, similar results have also been found, as NHANES study revealed an association with lower Cys-C, estimated GFR and highest quartile of Pb in the blood (Fadrowski et al., 2010).

In a systematic review by Zheng et al. (2017) 16 studies of paediatric Pb exposure and kidney health were identified published between 1985 and 2016. 12 of these studies were cross-sectional, two prospective cohorts and two case-control studies. The authors note that the studies published before 1999 had small sample sizes and did not adjust for possible confounders. Nine of the studies indicated significant association. Zheng et al., (2017) claim in their quality analysis that the studies adjusted for different confounders, making direct comparisons between the studies difficult. Seven studies reported null results or found no association. Similarly to the studies with association methodological choices, used matrices and strength of the studies varied.

As a conclusion, Pb exposure and kidney disease among children and adults indicate some evidence of association.

11.2.6 Mercury

Mercury exists in elemental (metallic), inorganic and organic forms. Kidney is the main organ for mercury accumulation and exposure to conjugates of Hg²⁺ can lead to severe nephropathy (Orr & Bridges, 2017).

Several studies have so far reported no or modest association between Hg exposure and kidney effects among adult populations (Table 12). However, for children more evidence was gathered in the systematic review by Zheng et al. (2017), presented below.

Among children, several publications were identified in Zheng et al.'s (2017) systematic review. Two were clinical trials examining dental amalgam fillings containing mercury or composites; the Children's Amalgam Trial in USA (Barregard et al., 2008; Bellinger et al., 2006) and the Casa Pia study in Portugal (Geier et al., 2013; Woods et al. 2008), one individual study was a cross-sectional study conducted in France, Poland and Czech Republic (De Burbure et al., 2006). Both of the trials indicated incoherent evidence, demonstrating some positive association. However, Zheng et al. (2017) highlighted several questions on the study methodologies in both of the studies, which might affect the interpretation of the study results. De Burbure et al. (2006) reported statistically significant association with urine Hg levels and increased serum Beta-2-microglobulin, a marker for proximal tubular injury and glomerular filtration and urinary N-acetyl-β-d-glucosaminidase, an early marker of tubular damage. A recent study not included in the Zheng et al.'s review, examined As, Pb, Hg, Cd and their combinations in cross-sectional study among 12-19 year olds. The findings suggested increase in the kidney parameters (eGFR, serum uric acid, urine albumin, blood urea nitrogen and systolic blood pressure), implying that early life low-level exposure to multiple metals may have far-reaching consequences later in life in the development of increased blood pressure, kidney disease and dysfunction (Sanders et al., 2019).

11.2.7 Arsenic

Zheng et al. (2014) conducted a systematic review on arsenic exposure and CKD. Overall, 25 papers (24 studies) were identified between years 1966 and 2014. Two of the studies were occupational and 22 were conducted among general population. 12 studies focused on low to moderate level As exposure. CKD outcome was measured in several ways in the studies; five

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studies focused on albuminuria or proteinuria, eight on eGFR, several studies on the biomarkers β -2-microglobulin (β 2MG), N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG) and retinol binding protein (RBP), lastly five studies evaluated kidney status on ICD9-codes. The authors concluded that there was generally a positive association between As and albuminuria and proteinuria outcomes. Furthermore, there was inconclusive evidence between As exposure and CKD, β -2-microglobulin (β 2MG), and N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG) outcomes. Additionally, there was evidence of positive association between As exposure and kidney disease mortality. Overall, Zheng et al. (2014) concluded that eight of the included studies lacked adjustment for possible confounders and two had small study populations.

A NHANES study published after the Zheng et al.'s (2014) systematic review by Sanders et al., (2019) is presented in the Table 12: Individual and joint effects of heavy metals to kidney disease focusing on children's As exposure and adverse kidney health.

11.2.8 Pesticides

Valcke et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review on CKD and pesticide exposure finding 21 studies (23 articles) to be included in the analysis. The studies included were conducted around the world, 13 were cross-sectional, five case-control studies and three longitudinal designs. All studies focused on pesticide exposures in occupational settings and in the majority, the exposure assessment was extremely crude; 11 studies only had a dichotomous yes/no exposure variable of pesticide use without any specification of pesticides examined or any quantification of duration and/or intensity of exposure. As a result, the authors reported 13 studies to have a positive association between exposure indicator and CKD (four showing relatively low association, five middle and four relatively strong explanation value). Notably, eight studies showed no association. The authors concluded that several of the reviewed studies had insufficient control of potential confounding factors, selection bias related to volunteer participation or high non-participation was not addressed. In addition, use of inadequate case or control groups, possible recall bias and deficient description of statistical analyses was observed.

After the publication of the systematic review by Valcke et al. (2017) one study on pesticide exposure and CKD were found. Hassanin et al. (2018) examined in a case-control study pesticide exposure and kidney function in male agricultural workers (n=200). Serum urea and creatinine levels were used as indicators for kidney health. A significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in urea among exposed group was observed in comparison to the control group. Also, there was a significant increase ($p < 0.01$) in creatinine among exposed group in comparison to the controls.

11.2.9 Mycotoxins

In a recent pilot study, Aflatoxin-B₁ exposure and early stage renal damage was estimated among Mexican indigenous women. Exposure was measured through biomarker AFB₁-lysine and renal damage through kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1), neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL) and cystatin-C (Cys-C). Statistically significant correlations between AFB₁-Lys and KIM-1 ratio ($p=0.007$) and AFB₁-Lys and Cys-C ($p=0.014$) were detected. This may indicate high renal toxicity (Díaz de Leon-Martinez et al., 2019). In an animal study, mice were exposed 28 days to aflatoxin B1 (AFB1), aflatoxin M1 (AFB2) and combination of the two. Results showed that exposure of AFB1 (0.5mg/kg), AFM1 (3.5 mg/kg) and their combination (AFB1 0.5 mg/kg + AFM1 3.5mg/kg) activated oxidative stress and renal damage through altering expression of proline dehydrogenase and L-proline levels, which then led to apoptosis (Li et al., 2018). Another study examined lactating mothers and their infants' serum concentration in regards to aflatoxin exposure. 48% of the mothers were exposed, however no association between renal or hepatic dysfunction was discovered on either the mothers or infants (Hassan et al., 2006a).

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Animal trials show an association between kidney damage and Patulin exposure. De Melo et al. (2011) observed DNA strand breakage in the kidneys of mice treated with intraperitoneal one single dose. El-Sawi et al. (2015) injected subcutaneously mice with Patulin; control group was injected subcutaneously daily with aqua; test groups one and two were injected with Patulin (0.2 mg/kg/day) for one and two weeks respectively. Group three received the same dose of patulin for two weeks and after that they received subcutaneous injection of Goji extract (2ml/kg /day) for next fortnight. Group four received Goji for two weeks and after that they received the same dose of patulin for the following two weeks. Increase in the levels of antioxidant stress, blood urea nitrogen and pyruvate kinase were observed, implying renal toxicity.

Ochratoxin A (OTA) has been shown to be highly nephrotoxic, causing several different adverse kidney effects. Ozçelik et al. (2001) observed significantly higher OTA concentrations in blood samples of patients with renal stones, cysts and bladder cancer. Additionally, there have been some suggestions that Balkan endemic nephropathy (BEN) could be associated with higher OTA blood concentrations (Fuchs & Peraica, 2005). However, inconsistent results remain still on the subject. In Egypt, lactating mothers and their infants were examined, revealing 72 % of the mothers to have OTA in their serum and milk, and moreover passing it to their infants' serum samples. Multivariate analysis showed an association of higher OTA level in infants' sera and the degree of microalbuminuria (Hassan et al., 2006b). Scott (2005) suggests in his review the use of urine sample as better indicator and biomarker for OTA exposure, albeit plasma has been thus far the most commonly used matrix. The need to relate concentrations and total amount excreted to exposure still need to be validated.

No human studies on adverse kidney effects and Zearalenone (ZEA) or Deoxynivalenol (DON) were found. However, animal studies suggest ZEA to adversely affect hormonal balance and kidney health, mainly due to its similarity to naturally-occurring estrogens and oxidative stress (Kowalska et al., 2016; Jia et al., 2014). In a study on new-born rats, with four different exposure amounts (0.3, 48.5, 97.6 or 146 mg/kg) for days 0 to 7 and following normal diet between days 8-20, the results showed that ZEN induced kidney dysfunction through oxidative damage, caused pathological changes in kidneys in dose-dependent manner (Jia et al., 2014). Another study focused on combined effects of DON and ZEA on mouse's kidneys using intraperitoneal injections (DON, ZEA or DON+ZEA) for 12 days in nine different dose categories. Apoptosis, serum creatinine and blood urea nitrogen increased in the kidney by ZEA and/or DON. The observed changes were dose and time dependent (Liang et al., 2015).

11.2.10 UV filters

Exposure to UV filters, and especially benzophenones have been studied among different population groups however, very few studies have focused on the association of kidney effects and the chemicals. For the first time Kang et al. (2019) assessed benzophenone-3 metabolites (BP-3) levels and kidney function markers among healthy Korean women. A significant association was detected between urinary metabolite benzophenone-1 (BP-1) and ACR (albumin-to-creatinine-ratio). It is noteworthy that BP-1 is considered a major metabolic compound of BP-3, and the authors suggest that BP-1 may even be a better biomarker to BP-3 than BP-3 itself due to demethylation in humans. Among US population, urinary BP-3 did not show a significant association with eGFR, however this study group did not assess the presence of BP-1 in urine samples (You et al., 2011). No other human studies on kidney effects and UV filters were found. In animal studies, liver and kidney have been identified as target organs of benzophenone toxicity. In a study concerning rats and mice, increased kidney weights and other renal changes were associated with the exposure (Chhabra, 2000). Rhodes et al. (2007) on the other hand exposed

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rats and mice for oral administration of BP for 105 weeks and observed increased kidney nephropathy among the exposed groups.

11.3 Highlights

- Kidney health is a major public health challenge however the contribution of environmental chemicals to the disease burden is still unclear.
- In Human Biomonitoring as part of public health surveys, methodological and pre-analytical stages should be considered carefully to minimise misclassification and over/under estimations.
- To measure kidney function, either SCr or CycC can be used to estimate GFR, however the eGFR based on both SCr and CycC gives the most accurate values.
- Control of hypertension is one of the most effective interventions for CKD, hence focus should be placed on environmental chemicals affecting the elevation of blood pressure.
- More standardised data on the prevalence of kidney diseases are needed.

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12 Liver function

Author: Haverinen Elsi (THL)

Liver is human body's largest discrete organ having four major functions in metabolism. These include synthesis, production and exportation of many lipids and proteins in the bloodstream, excretion of excess waste, storage of vital substances and detoxification of poisons (Blann, 2014). Liver diseases can vary greatly, and also the exposure risk factors are diverse. For instance, viral infections can cause hepatitis, parasitic exposure liver flukes, metabolic exposure fatty liver disease, bacterial infections tuberculosis, autoimmune disease primary biliary cirrhosis and anatomical and vascular changes expose to gallstones and biliary atresia (Blann, 2014). In addition, to the diverse disease spectrum, also stages and symptoms are versatile. It is estimated that 29 million people in Europe are affected by chronic liver diseases, causing 170 000 deaths from cirrhosis and 47 000 deaths from liver cancer (Blachier et al., 2013).

Furthermore, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), the most common liver disease, has been estimated to affect between 2-44% of the European general population, and 42.6-69.5% among people with type 2 diabetes (Blachier et al., 2013). Notably, country variation is large. NAFLD is closely linked to obesity and metabolic syndrome, which both have presented to be associated with exposure to certain chemicals. The more advanced level of NAFLD is non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH), which has been estimated to progress to cirrhosis among 10-20% of the population (Moore & Aithal, 2006). Indeed, the economic toll of liver diseases is significant in Europe and has not shown any signs of decreasing in the upcoming years (Blachier et al., 2013). Due to the large functional reserve of the liver, diagnoses might come at a late stage of a liver disease. It was noted in a study by Scaglione et al. (2015) that 70% of the patients with non-diagnosed liver disease were asymptomatic and unaware of their liver disease.

Epidemiologic evidence on interaction between environmental chemicals and liver functions has so far been limited, as very few studies have focused on the possible association. However, decreased liver function is a major public health concern and identifying environmental chemicals causing exposure and adverse health effects is a priority within different study populations. For drawing register data from liver diseases several ICD and ICPC –codes can be used. In Table 13 the most common and adaptable codes for biomonitoring are presented. In the ICD-10 and ICD-11 codings, several sub-codes for the classes exist. (WONCA, 2016; WHO ICD-11, 2020; WHO ICD-10, 2019).

Table 13: ICD-10, ICD-11 and ICPC coding for chronic liver function diagnoses

Condition	ICD-10 code	ICD-11 code	ICPC
Alcoholic liver disease	K70 (K70.0-K70.9)	DB94 (DB94.0-DB94.Z)	
Toxic liver disease	K71 (K71.0-K71.9)	named: Drug-induced or toxic liver disease DB95 (DB95.0-DB95.Z)	
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified	K72 (K72.0-K72.9)	named: acute or subacute hepatic failure DB91 (DB91.0-DB91.Z) or hepatic failure whether acute or chronic DB99.7 or Chronic hepatic failure DB 99.8	
Chronic hepatitis, not elsewhere classified	K73 (K73.0-73.9)	DB97.2	

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Condition	ICD-10 code	ICD-11 code	ICPC
Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver	K74 (K74.0-K74.6)	named: hepatic fibrosis or cirrhosis DB93 (DB93.0-DB93.Z)	
Other inflammatory liver diseases	K75 (K75.0-K75.9)	named: infectious liver disease DB90 (DB90.0-DB90.Z)	
Other diseases of liver	K76 (K76.0-K76.9)	DB99.Y	
Liver disorders in diseases classified elsewhere	K77	DB9Z	
Non-alcoholic liver disease		DB92 (DB92.0-DB92.Z)	
Liver disease NOS			D97

For retrieving information on liver function by questionnaire, HBM4EU and EHIS standardised questions on cirrhosis can be used (Appendix 22.2).

12.1 Liver function tests

Liver function tests (LFTs) are blood tests investigating suspected liver disease or monitoring disease activity (Hall & Cash, 2012). Consequently, only bilirubin and albumin give information regarding the functional capacity of the liver, whereas liver enzymes are important on the assessment of the primary disorder to decide if it's hepatic or cholestatic nature (Hall & Cash, 2012). As liver functions are diverse and complex, no single test can provide adequate information of the condition of the liver on its own. It is suggested that at least five different tests are required for the assessment (Blann, 2014). Enzymes that are produced in the liver, and in other organs, can be used to assess liver function, however they are not necessarily sensitive or specific on their own to make a diagnosis (Hall & Cash, 2012; Blann, 2014). In Table 14 the most commonly used LFTs are presented. Few notable marks have been added to the side column, adapted from Hall and Cash (2012) and Blann (2014).

Table 14: Liver function measurement methods adapted from Hall & Cash (2012) and Blann (2014)

Liver function tests	Things to consider when choosing methods	Pathology
Bilirubin	Decreased liver function causes bilirubin to build up in the bloodstream as a result of weakened ability to remove it.	Hepatocyte damage
Albumin	Reduced albumin levels in the blood may indicate damage to the liver.	Hepatocyte damage
Alanine Transaminase (ALT)	Relatively low concentrations in other tissues, indicated to be the most specific. Levels fluctuate during the day. Specific marker to hepatocellular injury. Certain drugs or strenuous exercise may increase the levels.	Hepatocyte damage

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Liver function tests	Things to consider when choosing methods	Pathology
Aspartate Transaminase (AST)	Cytosolic isoenzyme is present in skeletal and heart muscles and kidney tissue. Caution must be used when used it to evaluate hepatocellular damage. Usually increases in conjunction with ALT to indicate hepatocellular injury.	Hepatocyte damage
Alkaline Phosphatase (ALP)	Released in the response to the accumulation of bile salts or cholestasis. Non-hepatic production is present in kidney, intestine, leukocytes, placenta and bone. Pathological rise in certain disease (renal disease and bone metastases).	Biliary damage, cholestasis
Gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT)	Present in liver, kidney, pancreas and intestine Elevation of GGT simultaneously with a rise in ALP suggests biliary tract obstruction, indicating cholestatic problem. Certain drugs and alcohol use may increase the levels.	Biliary damage, cholestasis

Liver function tests can be used to measure a variety of different conditions. Exposure of environmental chemicals do not straightforward target liver as an organ but can expose to fatty liver disease and cirrhosis. Notably, increased ALT and GGT levels have been shown to be associated with NAFLD and effect later development of diabetes, hypertension, hyperlipidemia and coronary atherothrombosis (Hall & Cash, 2012). In a study by Ahmed et al. (2018) 771 liver biopsies and LFTs were examined from study participants, revealing significant number of patients diagnosed by biopsy to have CLD, however LFTs (AST, ALT, INR, BUN, SCr, platelets, alkaline phosphatase, bilirubin and albumin) remained normal or showed only slightly increased laboratory values. Based on their study AST showed some progressive increase and was statistically significant in advanced liver disease, whereas ALT, which is more liver specific, did not show correlation. Liver biopsy has been considered a golden standard for evaluating liver injury and staging of the disease (Ahmed et al., 2018).

When conducting Human Biomonitoring studies including liver function tests, preanalytic considerations should be paid close attention. It is suggested that 31-75% of laboratory errors could be primarily caused to preanalytic causes; mainly being hemolytic samples, insufficient sample, incorrect samples, clotted samples and incorrect identification (Bonini et al., 2002). According to Seeling (2008), storage and transportation times are regarded as main factors altering sample stability and especially in field studies several hours delay can occur in preanalytical processing. For liver function tests, bilirubin samples maintain their stability for 4 hours in room temperature, however the samples must be covered from light. Other LFTs maintain their stability for 24 hours in room temperature when stored in heparin plasma (Seeling, 2008).

12.2 Environmental chemicals associated with adverse liver health

12.2.1 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

The liver is a primary target organ for long-chain PFAS storage. A recent review by Fenton et al. (2021) combined the current studies on long-chain PFASs (over 6 fluorinated carbons) and higher liver enzymes. Eight studies were identified examining adults and adolescents (six cross-sectional and two longitudinal studies) (Sakr et al. 2007a; Gallo et al. 2012; Yamaguchi et al. 2013; Gleason

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et al. 2015; Attanasio 2019; Nian et al. 2019; Sakr et al. 2007b; Darrow et al. 2016). The results in these studies were inconsistent. As a summary; ALT levels were positively associated with increased PFOA levels (Darrow et al., 2016; Gallo et al., 2012; Sakr et al., 2007). However, direct bilirubin was negatively associated with PFOA concentrations and GGT showed inconsistent results (Gallo et al., 2012; Sakr et al., 2007). Interestingly, Gallo et al. (2012) noticed bilirubin to rise at low level of PFOA exposure and decrease again at higher exposure level.

A study from the Fenton et al.'s review was discovered to study mother-child exposure. Mora et al. (2018) examined 682 mother-child pairs for PFAS exposure and lipid homeostasis (lipid panel) and liver function (ALT) on two onsets, in pregnancy and in mid-childhood. The results concluded that among both boys and girls in mid-childhood (median age 7.7 years) that higher PFOA and PFNA concentrations were associated with slightly lower ALT levels, which might indicate better liver function. In addition, prenatal PFAS concentrations were also modestly associated with improved childhood ALT levels. So far, this study seems to be the only one assessing childhood and prenatal PFAS exposure and liver enzymes.

12.2.2 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Most of the PAH exposure and liver enzyme studies so far have been conducted among occupational workers having higher exposure levels in comparison to general population. For instance, 288 workers at a petrochemical plant were measured for urinary PAH metabolites and serum AST and ALT levels. Urine 2-naphthol levels were positively correlated with serum AST (OR 4.1, 95% CI 1.6-10.2) and for ALT (OR 2.4, 95% CI 1-2-4.9). (Min et al., 2015.)

Another study examined dose-response relationship between coke oven workers with higher exposure and non-occupational PAH exposed workers. ALT, AST, GGT and ALP were measured from serum, and urine samples were collected to assess PAH metabolites. The coke oven workers had significantly higher exposure levels of PAH and increased serum liver enzymes in all four liver tests (Chen et al., 2006).

12.2.3 Anilines

Although the high number of production and ubiquitous presence worldwide, surprisingly low number of epidemiological studies assessing aniline exposure and liver diseases have been conducted.

A significant contributor to acute liver failure is a metabolite of aniline, N-acetyl-4-aminophenol (APAP), commonly known as paracetamol. It causes severe liver toxicity if used at high amounts (Scoping Document for Anilines, 2018). Although Paracetamol is the most common analgesic and antipyretic drug worldwide, it is also the leading cause of drug-induced liver injury in the developed world, contributing to over 70 000 hospitalisations annually in the US (Budnitz et al., 2011). Unfortunately, no biomonitoring studies yet have focused on the long term effects of APAP use, or its presence in the general population.

12.2.4 Aprotic solvents

Only one human and one animal study on aprotic solvents and liver effects were found.

Haufroid et al.'s (2014) epidemiological study examined workers exposed to N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), revealing inconsistent results and no conclusion of possible liver health effects were detected.

Saillenfait et al. (2016) evaluated solvent N-ethyl-2-pyrrolidone (NEP) in a 4-week trial on rats. NEP was orally served to the rats daily in different dosage levels (0, 5, 50 and 250 mg/kg/day).

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After the trial hepatocellular centrilobular hypertrophy in the liver of male rats receiving 250 mg/kg/daily increased. The study demonstrated mild to no liver effects on the mice.

12.2.5 Mercury

In a NHANES study 2003-2004, whole blood total mercury was present in 92.5% of the study subjects, and was dose-dependently associated with ALT elevation and suspected NAFLD among adult USA population (Cave et al., 2010). A NHANES study by Lin et al. (2014) researched on most suitable matrix for assessing Hg exposure and liver function status. The hepatic function was examined by using ALT, AST and GGT enzymes from 3769 participants aged over 20 years in three different NHANES study cycles (2003-2004, 2005-2006, 2007-2008). Both urinary and serum samples were examined for Hg and MeHg. The study identified association between liver function, serum Hg and urinary Hg. However, urinary analysis was concluded by the authors not to be the optimal matrix to assess the elimination of Hg, as it is excreted through enterohepatic system e.g. feces. Another study focusing on elderly population, observed a significant association between blood Hg concentrations and increased AST, ALT and GGT after adjusting for potential confounders when comparing lowest and highest quartiles ($p < 0.05$) (Lee et al., 2017). Similar results have been reported also among other study populations (Choi et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2014).

Lin et al. (2017) conducted a retrospective cross sectional study in Taiwan focusing on soil heavy metals and fatty liver disease among adult population. Their study has been thus far the first to assess chromium, nickel, arsenic, mercury, cadmium, copper, lead and zinc. The prevalence of fatty liver disease among the population was 26.5%. In univariate and multivariate analysis the presence of soil heavy metals was a significant risk factor among men, revealing an OR 1.83 (95% CI 1.61 to 2.89, $p = 0.009$). By stratifying to BMI and gender, lean men with BMI under 24 kg/m² were the most susceptible for soil heavy metals (OR 5.059, 95% CI 1.62 to 15.78, $p = 0.05$).

12.2.6 Mycotoxins

Exposure to Mycotoxins occur worldwide, highest exposure areas being in tropical and subtropical regions. Aflatoxin, a form of Mycotoxin, is considered the most potent naturally occurring human hepatocarcinogen. In the areas where aflatoxin is most highly detected in the nature, also prevalence of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is generally high. Several studies have focused on aflatoxin exposure combined with HBV infection, and concluded an exponential increase in the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC, liver cancer) (Kirk et al., 2005; Omer et al., 2004; Liu et al., 2012). Liu et al. (2012) examined current and previous evidence on aflatoxin exposure and people carrying HBV and calculated in their meta-analysis 14-19% population attributable risk for HCC.

In a study examining intraperitoneal exposure to Patulin in male mice, a dose-dependent effect of DNA strand breaks in the liver was observed. A statistically significant dose-dependent increase was detected at 2.5 mg/kg at single dose ($p < 0.01$) indicating high liver genotoxicity (de Melo et al., 2011). A recently published review focusing on liver defects and Patulin exposure identified eight different animal studies with clear indication of exposure and adverse liver effects (Ramalingam et al., 2019).

Ochratoxin A (OTA) was discussed in a review article focusing on liver health (Capraro & Rossi, 2012). The authors summarised the main effects found in literature, concluding liver biomarkers AST, ALT, GGT and ALP to rise in association with intake, whereas albumin decreased linearly with OTA exposure. Other observed indicators for hepatic damage in the review were oxidative damage and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, showing no consensus of the specific effect of OTA toxicity. Additionally, liver cell apoptosis was observed in several studies and

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exposure to OTA was also shown to increase liver weight. Notably, the animal studies in this review used relatively high dosages in comparison to the human weekly tolerable intake. In a case-control study examining subjects with chronic liver disease (case group) and healthy volunteers (control group) OTA intake was observed and the genesis of chronic liver disease and HCC were investigated. The OTA intake was low (0.039 ng/kg bw/day – 0.065 ng/kg bw/day), resulting 49 % of the participants to have OTA levels lower than the limit of detection (25 ng/l). In the study, no affect was detected between prevalence of liver disease and OTA, however among the participants with cirrhosis the prevalence of HCC was higher in participants with OTA than participants without detection ($p < 0.05$) (Prati et al., 2012).

12.2.7 UV filters

Benzophenones are common additives in cosmetics, sunscreens and other consumer products worldwide, however studies focusing on liver effects and exposure to UV filters seems to be scarce. A few animal studies have focused on benzophenone exposure and liver effects, however the studies have mainly focused on oral administration rather than dermal absorption. One study examined benzophenone-3 (BP-3) exposure in *Carassius auratus* fish indicating an association of exposure and hepatic oxidative stress (Liu et al., 2015). According to Chhabra (2000) BP exposure on rats and mice increased liver weights, and attributed to hypertrophy and/or cytoplasmic vacuolisation of hepatocytes. In an experiment observing rats and mice, oral administration of BP was maintained for 105 weeks. The study group observed significantly increased incidence of liver lesions in rats and hepatocellular adenoma in mice in groups with higher exposure (625 and 1,250 ppm) (Rhodes et al., 2007). No epidemiological studies were found on UV filters and liver effects.

12.3 Highlights

- Very few observational studies have so far focused on adverse liver effects and possible association with environmental chemicals.
- Determining the best LFTs to be used in biomonitoring studies is challenging. So far, ALT has been the most used measurement method for liver function in biomonitoring studies as it is the most liver specific enzyme and possibly projects hepatocyte damage most accurately.
- For collecting register data it is notable that there are several ICD-10 and ICD-11 codes concerning chronic liver diseases.

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13 Osteoporosis

Author: Elonheimo Hanna (THL)

The World Health Organisation (WHO, 1994) defines osteoporosis as a disease characterised by reduced bone mass and microarchitectural deterioration of bone tissue, leading to enhanced bone fragility and increase in fracture risk. These criteria are defined only for women, since men have larger bones with thicker cortices even though their bone density and trabecular architecture is similar to that of women (WHO, 2001). WHO's operational definition among women is based on the following general diagnostic categories: a normal value for bone mineral density (BMD) or bone mineral content (BMC) is within 1 standard deviation (SD) of the young adult reference mean. Low bone mass (osteopenia) is a value for BMD or BMC more than 1 SD below the young adult mean but less than 2.5 SDs below this value.

Osteoporosis is a value for BMD or BMC with 2.5 SDs or more below the young adult means (WHO, 1994). Osteoporosis weakens bones and therefore makes them fragile and more likely to break. A fall or sudden impact, which causes a bone to break and fracture to occur, can lead to diagnosing of slowly over the years developing disease. The risk of fractures is markedly increased with osteoporosis (NHS, 2019; IOF, 2017a). Risks of osteoporosis and susceptibility to fractures include e.g. female sex, white race, advanced age, estrogen deficiency, early menopause, family history of osteoporosis, a maternal history of hip fracture, a prior fracture and a fracture after 40 years of age, low body weight and body mass index (BMI) and smoking (NIH, 2001; Reginster & Burlet, 2006). In order to maintain healthy bones adults should ensure a nutritious diet and avoid under-nutrition. Adequate calcium intake and supply of vitamin D as well as avoiding smoking and heavy drinking and engaging in regular weight-bearing activity are the cornerstones of building and maintaining healthy bone mass (Reginster & Burlet, 2006; IOF, 2017b; NIH, 2001).

It is estimated that over 200 million people (most of them women) worldwide have osteoporosis and osteoporosis causes more than 8.9 million fractures annually (Cooper, 1999; Johnell & Kanis, 2006). In the European Union (EU) (based on the number of 27 countries) 22 million women and 5.6 million men were estimated to have osteoporosis in 2010 (Hernlund et al., 2013). In so called EU6 countries (France, Germany, Italy, Spain, Sweden and UK) the estimated number of people over 50 years of age having osteoporosis was 20 million in 2015; of them 16 million were women and 4 million men (IOF, 2017c; Hernlund et al., 2013; Looker et al., 1998; Ström et al., 2011; UN, 2017). Of all postmenopausal women, approximately 30 % have osteoporosis in the United States and Europe, and according to the estimation, 40 % of these women may encounter one or more fragility fractures during their lifetimes (Melton et al., 1992).

Globally, 1 in 3 women and 1 in 5 men over the age of 50 will encounter an osteoporotic fracture (Melton et al., 1998; Melton et al., 1992). The lifetime risk of hip fragility fractures in European women aged 50 years is from 9.8% to 22.8% and in the same aged men from 6.1% to 13.7% (Borgström et al., 2020). Altogether in Europe, 3.5 million new fragility fractures were sustained in 2010 and this annual figure is expected to rise to 4.5 million in 2025 indicating an increase of 28% (Hernlund et al., 2013). A baseline fracture is shown to be a very powerful predictor of further fractures; according to an analysis based on the data from four large 3-year-long osteoporosis treatment trials, 20% of patients encountered a second fracture within the first year (Lindsay et al., 2001). A major complication of osteoporosis is an increase in fragility fractures leading to significant morbidity, increased mortality and decreased quality of life (NIH, 2001).

In the EU the economic burden of osteoporosis and prior fragility fractures was estimated at €37 billion in 2010. Incident fractures accounted for 66%, long-term fracture care 29% and

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pharmacological prevention 5 % of this cost. Previous and incident fractures accounted for 1,180,000 quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) lost during 2010. The costs are predicted to increase by 25% in 2025 (Hernlund et al., 2013).

Fracture related costs occur mostly in the first year following a fracture, differ between the fracture sites and tend to be highest with hip fractures (IOF, 2017c; Roux & Briot, 2017; Bonafede et al., 2016). The amount of sick days taken by working individuals due to fragility fractures in EU6 countries was 7.6 million in the year 2017 (Borgström et al., 2020). According to the systematic search of 62 articles conducted by Ballane et al. (2017), the prevalence of morphometric vertebral fractures in European women was highest in Scandinavia (26 %) and lowest in Eastern Europe (18 %). The prevalence of osteoporosis is continuing to escalate as the amount of elderly population is increasing. The costs of osteoporosis to health care services are already significant, and these costs are estimated to double by the year 2050. The direct costs of osteoporosis-related fractures to the health services in the EU were approximately €32 billion € in 2000, and the estimation of the direct osteoporosis-related fracture costs by the year 2050 is €77 billion (Reginster & Burlet, 2006; Kanis & Johnell, 2004).

13.1 Measurement methods

The ICD-10 (International Classification for Diseases) code for osteoporosis is M80 for osteoporosis with pathological fracture under disorders of bone density and structure (M80-M85) (WHO ICD-10, 2019). The ICD-11 code for osteoporosis is FB83.1 and FB83.0 for osteopenia under low bone mass disorders (FB83) (WHO ICD-11, 2020). The International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC 2) - code for osteoporosis is L95 (WONCA, 2016).

For osteoporosis, HBM4EU standardised question can be found in Appendix 22.2.

The golden standard for diagnosing osteoporosis is dual energy/photon X-ray absorptiometry (DXA), which is defined as BMD >2.5 SDs below the mean of young reference populations (Schousboe et al., 2013). X-rays of two different energy levels are applied in DXA-scanners for the imaging and measuring of BMC and bone density (Grados et al., 2009). The scanned bone area, the proximal femur, is placed under the scanner arm; the greater trochanter area permits accurate calculation of bone density. Only the bones are imaged and measured, and the soft tissues are subtracted from the scan ensuring the accuracy of the results (HBM4EU, 2019). The disadvantages of the DXA method are its high costs and limited availability; it is usually located in hospital-based facilities only. Therefore applying this method can be restricted in prevention campaigns and public health interventions (Villa et al., 2016; Frost et al., 2000; HBM4EU, 2019).

In comparison to DXA, quantitative ultrasound (QUS) is introduced as a possible noninvasive alternative or complementary examination in fracture risk assessment (Njeh et al., 1997). QUS-device produces high frequency ultrasound (US) waves to determine bone health status in humans; the US has a frequency exceeding the normal auditory range of humans (>20 kHz). QUS-devices have typically two probes: the emission and receiver probes (Guglielmi & de Terlizzi, 2009). Two types of QUS exist depending on the axis of the US waves in relation to bone. Horizontal transmission measures the speed of sound (SOS) on the cortical layer of the bone at a fixed distance. The measured bone areas are the forearm, tibia and radius. Longitudinal transmission is mostly applied with calcaneus being the bone segment measured (Laugier, 2004). Two parameters of the QUS are SOS and the broadband ultrasound attenuation (BUA). Nowadays, there are also more defined QUS variations derived from the two basic measurements of SOS and BUA, such as amplitude-depend SOS (AD-SOS), stiffness index (SI), quantitative ultrasound index (QUI) and estimated BMD (eBMD) (Guglielmi & de Terlizzi, 2009; Glüer, 1997).

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QUS has become an easy and widely used screening tool for osteoporosis, and compared to DXA, QUS is more conveniently applied due to its portability, easiness to maneuver, lowness of costs and absence of ionising radiation (Chin & Ima-Nirwana, 2013; Laugier, 2004; Villa et al., 2016). Thus, QUS can be useful for public health studies where measurement of bone health is needed.

13.1.1 QUS advantages, disadvantages and recommendations

Calcaneal QUS is potentially useful as a prescreening tool for assessment of osteoporosis (Thomsen et al., 2015), and a large compatibility between the two methods (DXA and QUS) in the comparative studies has been assessed (Flöter et al., 2011). Therefore, it can be applied to exclude healthy individuals from further examinations (Hans & Krieg, 2009; Camozzi et al., 2007; Flöter et al., 2011). The ability of QUS to predict fractures and to serve as a screening tool for osteoporosis has been validated in several epidemiological cohort and cross-sectional studies. Additionally, QUS provides information on bone microarchitectures and BMD (Chin & Ima-Nirwana, 2013).

QUS could replace DXA as an examination tool due to its lower cost and portability of devices. Furthermore, QUS could be applied to reduce the number of needed DXA examinations for fracture prediction, it could be used for risk assessment, and patients with intermediate risk of future fractures could be subdivided in low- and high-risk individuals. When using together with DXA, QUS may add value to the formal evaluation conducted with DXA (Høiberg et al., 2016).

However, a large heterogeneity between studies, and uncertainty about cutoff, device and measured variable regarding calcaneal QUS has been detected. Furthermore, there is insufficient evidence for recommending a specific cutoff for calcaneal QUS to be used for osteoporosis assessment (Thomsen et al., 2015). Also, there are no established diagnostic threshold values for QUS, and therefore it cannot be used as a diagnostic method for osteoporosis. There are various QUS devices available without adequate standardisation and cross-calibration performed (Kauppi, 2015). Finally, different QUS devices have different optimum T-score thresholds for diagnosing osteoporosis. Therefore, the current WHO criteria for the diagnosis of osteoporosis in postmenopausal women cannot be applied to calcaneal QUS measurements (Frost et al., 2000).

In order to use QUS for assessing skeletal status, the WHO threshold of $T = -2.5$ for diagnosing osteoporosis requires modification (Hartl et al., 2002; Frost et al., 2000). Furthermore, using of calcaneal QUS in prescreening method must be based on device-specific cut-offs and parameters that are validated in the populations for which they are intended to be used (Thomsen et al., 2015; Villa et al., 2016).

Further studies, e.g. clinical trials, are called upon to determine criteria and a reliable correlation between QUS and DXA (Flöter et al., 2011; Moayyeri et al., 2012; Nayak et al., 2006). To conclude, it is possible to improve the QUS devices to be used at the clinical treatment of osteoporosis (Hans & Krieg, 2009), for the method has good assessment of the quality of the bone and high correlation with the clinical fracture risks (Camozzi et al., 2007).

13.2 Environmental chemicals associated with osteoporosis

According to the current search, osteoporosis is possibly associated with environmental chemicals and metals such as cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), phthalates, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and arsenic (As). Somewhat weaker and unclear associations are established between osteoporosis and bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and mercury (Hg) (Elonheimo et al., 2021).

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13.2.1 Cadmium

Åkesson et al. (2014) reviewed available information on the health effects of Cd exposure with respect to human health risk assessment including a chapter on toxic effects of Cd on bone. It has been recognised for long that excessive exposure to Cd may cause itai-itai disease occurring after manifestation of kidney damage leading to osteomalacia and/or osteoporosis with multiple fractures. Cross-sectional and prospective studies on different populations (e.g. Belgium, Sweden and US), some of them very large, have clearly demonstrated the associations between Cd exposure and low mineral density, as well as increased risk of osteoporosis. Most of these studies have applied DXA and Z- or T-score for defining low bone mass/osteoporosis. There are varying exposure levels of Cd associated with decreased BMD and increased risk of osteoporosis and fractures. Cross-sectional and prospective studies have suggested associations at U-Cd values of 0.5-2 µg/g cr. Growing evidence suggests that Cd has a direct toxic effect on bone. Interestingly, the bone cells breaking down bone tissue called osteoclasts are particularly sensitive to low Cd concentrations. The effects of Cd on the skeleton are especially harmful due to the irreversible nature of exposure; even after the exposure is ceased, the effects remain.

Lv et al. (2017) explored the association between osteoporosis and long-term environmental Cd exposure through diet in southern China. More than 1000 persons from either Cd-polluted or non-Cd-polluted area were investigated, and according to the results urinary Cd concentrations were positively associated with osteoporosis and there was a significant negative association with BMD. The study subjects in the second, third and fourth quartiles of urinary Cd concentration had greater odds of osteoporosis compared with the subjects in the first quartile. The study showed an inverse association between the body burden of Cd and osteoporosis. The toxic effect of Cd on bone may happen together with nephrotoxicity.

Callan et al. (2015) conducted a cross-sectional study of the relationship between metals exposure and renal and bone health in 77 women aged 50 years and above. Both urinary and whole blood samples were collected to detect the levels of different metals including Cd. Despite low concentrations of Cd in both matrices, urinary Cd was a significant predictor of BMD at whole body, lumbar spine, total hip and femoral neck; increasing urinary Cd concentrations were associated with decreased bone density. Urinary Cd concentrations were positively correlated with the process of osteoclasts breaking down the bone tissue. Similar results were reported by Engström et al. (2011) who surveyed a cohort of nearly 2700 women, aged 60-69 years. There was an inverse relationship between urinary Cd and BMD of the whole body, femoral neck, total hip, lumbar spine and volumetric femoral neck. The results on risk of fractures were aligned with the conclusion of the BMD results. The association between U-Cd and BMD appeared to be independent of former smoking status, and the adjusted urinary Cd concentrations were not higher in ever smokers compared with never smokers (Callan et al., 2015), and also in the study by Engström et al. (2011) the observed associations were independent of tobacco smoking. Engström et al. (2011) suggested that Cd exposure from diet alone (mainly from cereals, potatoes, and vegetables) may contribute to the risk of osteoporosis and fractures.

Alfvén et al. (2002) examined nearly 1000 women and men environmentally or occupationally exposed to Cd and Pb, and according to their findings, the relationship between blood-Cd and tubular proteinuria was strong even when occupationally exposed participant were excluded. In the age group > 60 years, the risk of low BMD for the subgroup with highest blood-Cd levels was almost 3-folded compared to the group with lowest blood-Cd levels. Cd exposure was associated with both BMD and kidney function.

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The combined effects of chemicals are scarcely studied, but Chen et al. (2014) investigated the interactive effects of Cd and Pb on BMD in a Chinese population (N=321; 202 women and 119 men, aged 27 years and older). The Cd and Pb levels of populations living in the polluted area were markedly higher than those living in the control area ($p < 0.05$). The BMD of women living in the polluted area was significantly lower than that of women living in the control area ($p < 0.05$), and the BMD decreased with increasing of B-Cd, B-Pb and U-Pb in women. The likelihood of low BMD was associated with higher B-Cd in women (OR=2.5, 95 % CI: 1.11-5.43) and B-Pb in men (OR=4.49, 95 % CI: 1.37-14.6). The relative extra risk index of low BMD for female and male subjects with both high levels of B-Cd and B-Pb was 0.45 and 1.16, respectively. The results strengthened the previous evidence that Cd and Pb may affect the bone and also showed that Cd and Pb may have interactive effects on BMD.

13.2.2 Lead

Exposure to Pb may be a risk factor for the development of osteoporosis, even though human studies on this association are limited and inconsistent. Campbell & Auinger (2007) mentioned that animal studies have been able to show that increased Pb exposure is linked to a decrease in bone density and bone strength, and according to in vitro studies exposure to Pb inhibits the function of chondrocytes and osteoblasts, i.e. the cells manufacturing bone.

Human skeleton is known to be a repository for Pb in those individuals who have been exposed to high levels of this environmental toxin in their childhood; this storage mechanism has previously thought to be benign. More recently, however, research has shown that actually the opposite is true: Pb in bone sets off a chain reaction first accelerating bone growth and then eventually limiting it so that a high peak bone mass is not achieved. The prevention of high peak bone mass will predispose a young person to osteoporosis later in life (University of Rochester Medical Center, 2006).

A few decades ago the researchers using database of nearly 3000 black and white women examined Pb status before and after menopause. There was a highly significant increase in both whole blood and calculated plasma Pb concentrations after menopause. The results confirmed the findings of the previous experimental data by showing, that Pb in bone can be released in conditions of demineralisation such as pregnancy and lactation, and bone-Pb is not an inert storage site for absorbed Pb. Pb may aggravate postmenopausal osteoporosis, since it inhibits activation of vitamin D, uptake of dietary calcium and various regulatory factors of bone cell function (Silbergeld et al., 1988).

Campbell and Auinger (2007) used data from a national database (NHANES III incl. personal interviews and physical examinations of nearly 40 000 people \geq 2 months of age, between 1988 and 1994) to explore the association between Pb exposure and osteoporosis. A significant inverse association between Pb exposure and BMD was detected, but only among white subjects. However, due to the cross-sectional study design of NHANES, temporal sequence of this association could not be formed. Alfvén et al. (2002) examined nearly 1000 women and men environmentally or occupationally exposed to Cd and Pb, but were unable to find association between Pb exposure and BMD. However, the mean blood-Pb level was low among the study subjects (0.16 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in men and 0.11 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ in women) referring to the fact that the lack of an association may have been caused by low exposure. Thus, it is possible that bone effects from Pb exposure can take place at higher levels. The threshold for proximal tubular injury according to both animal and human studies has been set at around 3 $\mu\text{mol/L}$ (Loghman-Adham, 1997).

Sun et al. (2008) explored whether occupational Pb exposure was linked to low bone mass among population working in a storage battery plant. Pb concentrations of urine and blood were

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determined in a cohort of 249 workers (191 males and 58 females). BMD was markedly decreased in the groups of the high urinary-Pb (UPb) level compared to the low UPb-level with a significant difference in both genders. However, no significant difference was found in the relationship between blood-Pb (BPb) and BMD. There was also a dose-response relationship between Pb exposure and prevalence of osteoporosis either measured by UPb or BPb. Occupational Pb exposure was associated with osteoporosis. Nash et al. (2004) used the NHANES III survey interview of nearly 3000 women (aged 40-59 years) to examine cross-sectional associations of bone density-related factors with blood-Pb levels. They found that BMD was significantly inversely associated with blood-Pb level after adjustment for other factors traditionally associated with blood Pb. A low BMD measurement may result from either recent decline in BMD or longstanding bone mineral status, and it is possible that Pb may affect BMD rather than BMD's affecting Pb.

Wong et al. (2015) examined how bone Pb-content at mid-tibia and calcaneus is related to bone microstructure and volumetric density at the distal tibia in a random sample of women above 50 years of age. However, the study population included only 38 postmenopausal women. High amounts of bone-Pb at the tibia were associated with thinner distal tibia cortices and volumetric BMD. A higher blood-Pb was associated with larger trabecular separation and lower trabecular volumetric BMD. Therefore, Pb accumulated in bone can have mild effect on bone structure.

13.2.3 Arsenic

The effect of As on apoptosis (cell death) of osteoblasts is widely unknown and scarcely studied on humans. Tang et al. (2009) found that As caused cell apoptosis in the human osteoblast-like cell lines and dysfunction of mitochondria in osteoblasts; the study was conducted with mouse osteoblasts and bone marrow cells. Also, As triggered endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, which was indicated by changes in cytosolic-calcium levels. The results indicated that the risk of osteoporosis is increased with As exposure, since As increased cell apoptosis in cultured osteoblasts and chondrocytes. In vivo studies conducted with mice showed that As reduced BMD and BMC. In vitro studies the effects and mechanism of As on osteoblast differentiation by evaluating BMD and bone microstructure in rats have been examined. Wu et al. (2014) used As doses corresponding to human exposure from drinking water, and they were able to show that As was capable of inhibiting osteoblast differentiation. Akbal et al. (2014) investigated the effect of As on BMD in men (n=254), and concluded that As exposure was associated with bone metabolism. However, no significant correlations between hair As levels and BMD measurements could be detected. According to the study, exposure to As may be a possible cause of osteopenia.

13.2.4 Mercury

Hg has a contradictory connection to BMD and osteoporosis. Researchers have examined the effects of heavy metals such as Hg on calcium homeostasis. Suzuki et al. (2004) examined the effects of Cd and Hg on calcium homeostasis, plasma calcium and calcitonin. Fish scales were examined, since they are similar to mammalian membrane bone having both osteoclasts and osteoblasts. While Cd suppressed the tartrate-resistant acid phosphatase (TRAP) and alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity in both cell types, Hg acted directly on bone cells and influenced calcium homeostasis and induced hypercalcemia. Both metals adversely influenced the growth factor and estrogen receptor participating in osteoblastic growth and differentiation. Both Cd and Hg influenced osteoclastic activities first and inhibited osteoblastic activities in the long term exposure.

In the cross-sectional study of nearly 500 postmenopausal women by Cho et al. (2012) it was found that high blood Hg levels were associated with a lower risk of osteoporosis. However, the blood sample reflects the recent exposure, and long-term exposure should be examined from hair

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or fingernails. Pollack et al. (2013) investigated the effects of metals in blood, i.e. Cd, Pb and Hg, on BMD among nearly 250 premenopausal women. According to the results Hg was linked to the reduced odds of decreased lumbar spine BMD in the sample of younger and reproductive-aged women (0.66, CI 95 % 0.44-0.99). Overall, metals were not associated with reduced BMD in the premenopausal women at environmentally relevant levels of exposure. Similar results were reported by Callan et al. (2015), who examined the relationship between metal exposure and renal and bone health in 77 women aged 50 years and above: blood Hg levels were found to be negatively associated with bone resorption. Kim et al. (2016) conducted a nationwide cross-sectional study using data from the 2008 to 2010 Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. The relationship between blood Hg and BMD and the prevalence of osteopenia or osteoporosis in 1190 men over 50 years of age was evaluated. After adjusting for the traditional factors associated with osteoporosis such as age, BMI, calcium intake, vitamin D levels, fish consumption, alcohol consumption, smoking and exercise habits, high blood Hg levels were associated with reduced odds of decreased femur neck BMD. However, the subgroup analysis was unable to reveal a significant protective effect of blood Hg on osteoporotic fractures.

13.2.5 Phthalates and Bisphenol A

Experimental animal studies have shown that some phthalates hamper skeletal formation and the maintenance of bone homeostasis (Ema et al., 1994; McKee et al., 2006; Saillenfait et al., 2009). The association of phthalates to human bone health is still widely unknown. Min and Min (2014) analysed data from the national database (NHANES 2005-2008) of nearly 400 postmenopausal women (≥ 50 years old) and evaluated whether urinary phthalate metabolites were associated with total hip and femur neck BMD and osteoporosis. 11 phthalate metabolites were included and divided into quartiles. Increments in the urinary mono-n-butyl phthalate (metabolite of DnBP), mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate (metabolite of DnBP and DnOP) and monobenzyl phthalate (metabolite of BBzP) quartiles were significantly associated with reduced total hip or femur neck BMD. The women with the highest levels of mono-(3-carboxypropyl) phthalate, mono(carboxyoctyl) phthalate, and the sum of the three di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate metabolites were more likely to have an increased risk for total hip and femur neck osteoporosis than the women with the lowest levels of these metabolites. The results suggested that phthalate exposure may adversely affect bone homeostasis, osteoporosis risk and BMD in humans. DeFlorio-Barker and Turyk (2016) investigated the data of the NHANES 2005-2010 including nearly 500 post-menopausal women, and according to the results, different phthalate metabolites such as MEP, MNBP, MIBP and MBZP and an estrogen equivalency factor were negatively associated with spinal BMD.

According to various studies the exposure of BPA and phthalates leads to adverse health outcomes, including bone loss. Environmental pollutants disrupting endocrine system by their estrogen-like activity can affect the modeling and remodeling of bone. BPA can influence bone health by decreasing the plasma calcium level and inhibiting calcitonin secretion (Fossi et al., 2018; Vitku et al., 2018). Only few studies have been conducted on the association between endocrine disruptor chemicals (EDCs) and BMD or bone metabolism in humans (DeFlorio-Barker & Turyk, 2016; Min & Min, 2014). BPA has been mostly reported not to be associated with BMD in women with osteoporosis or in premenopausal women (Kim et al., 2012; Zhao et al., 2012). Chin et al. (2018) reviewed the evidence on the relationship between BPA and BMD/bone health from cellular, animal and human studies. Two cross-sectional human studies presented trivial association. In conclusion, BPA and its derivatives could have effect on bone health and there was a possible gender effect in animal studies. More comprehensive longitudinal human studies are warranted to gain verification of the bone health effects of BPA.

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13.2.6 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

Khalil et al. (2016) used a sample of nearly 2000 participants of the National Health and Nutritional Examination Survey (NHANES) 2009-2010. Serum PFAS concentrations were associated with lower BMD, which however varied according to specific PFAS and bone sites measured. Most of the associations were detected only in women. In women, osteoporosis was also associated with PFAS exposure in small number of cases. Lin et al. (2014) investigated the data of nearly 2500 study subjects of NHANES 2005-2006 and 2007-2008. They found that 1-U increase in the serum PFOS level was associated with a decrease in total lumbar spine BMD by 0.022 g/cm² (CI 95 % - 0.038 to -0.007, p = 0.006) in women not in menopause. However, there was no association in PFOA or PFOS concentrations and self-reported fractures.

13.2.7 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

There is a contradictory connection detected between PAHs and the risk of osteoporosis. PAHs are environmental endocrine disruptors, which may also affect the bone mineralisation (Guo et al., 2018). EDCs such as PAHs interfere with the homeostasis of the organisms by mimicking endogenous hormones, expressing estrogenic or anti-estrogenic activities (Zhang et al., 2016). Mounting epidemiological evidence implies that EDCs are significantly related to the levels of BMD (Glynn et al., 2000; Hodgson et al., 2008; Khalil et al., 2016; Min & Min, 2014). Guo et al. (2018) conducted a study in human population exploring the associations of PAHs with BMD and osteoporosis by using data from the NHANES 2005-2010 of general U.S. population. The impacts of single and multiple U-PAHs were analysed. The associations of U-PAHs with BMD and osteoporosis varied depending on specific U-PAHs and bone sites measured among adult women: compared with women at the first tertiles, those at the third tertiles had significantly decreased BMD levels or increased likelihoods of osteoporosis at different bone sites. The dose-response relationships between U-PAHs mixtures and BMD were inverted U-shaped in femur and negatively correlated in lumbar spine. In addition, associations of U-PAHs with BMD and osteoporosis varied in relation to the menopausal status and gender: associations were stronger for postmenopausal women. The results implied that even relatively low levels of PAHs exposure might affect BMD.

Duan et al. (2018) used the NHANES survey (2005-2014) in order to examine the relationship between PAHs and osteoporosis. Eight different PAH metabolites were investigated to represent the exposure in the human body by using the sample of 3053 people: intervention group consisted of 577 persons with osteoporosis and there were 2476 persons without osteoporosis in the control group. The results showed that 3-hydroxyfluorene metabolite was associated with decreased odds of osteoporosis in ≤ 50-years old postmenopausal women and ≤ 50-years old men even after controlling for factors traditionally associated with osteoporosis. 2-hydroxyfluorene was associated with increased odds of osteoporosis. In the non-smoking group, the association with osteoporosis regarding both of these metabolites existed.

13.3 Highlights

- In addition to the traditional risk factors of osteoporosis such as female sex, early menopause, low BMI, inadequate physical activity and smoking, heavy metals and environmental chemicals may affect the bone health and may be associated with the development of osteoporosis.
- Osteoporosis is possibly associated with environmental chemicals and metals such as cadmium (Cd), lead (Pb), phthalates, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and arsenic (As). Somewhat weaker and unclear associations are established between osteoporosis and bisphenols, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and mercury (Hg).

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- Adverse effects on bone metabolism seem to be especially profound among peri- and postmenopausal women.
- Although there is some evidence that environmental substances have an adverse effect on bone health, more high-quality research is needed, and especially epidemiological long-term studies are warranted.

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14 Cancer

Authors: Elonheimo Hanna (THL), Haverinen Elsi (THL), Paalanen Laura (THL)

Cancer is a general term for a vast group of diseases affecting any part of the body. In addition to the term cancer also terms malignant tumours and neoplasms are used. In cancer, there is a rapid creation of abnormal cells growing beyond their usual boundaries. These cells can invade adjoining body parts by spreading to other organs as metastasis, and these metastases are the primary cause of cancer deaths (WHO, 2021a).

Cancer is one of the main types of noncommunicable diseases (NCDs). NCDs are regarded as chronic diseases of long duration, which are resulting from a combination of genetic, physiological, environmental and behavioural factors. Cancerous diseases are the second most common cause of NCD deaths after cardiovascular diseases with 9.3 million deaths occurring yearly worldwide (WHO, 2021b). The most common cancers in 2020 were breast cancer (2.26 million cases), lung (2.21 million cases), colon and rectum cancer (1.93 million cases), prostate cancer (1.41 million cases) and skin cancer (1.20 million cases). Mortality from cancer was in 2020 highest among lung cancer patients (1.80 million deaths and colon and rectum cancers (935 000 deaths). (WHO, 2021a.)

Environmental chemical's carcinogenicity has been examined and regulated through different agencies and institutes. The specialised cancer agency of the WHO, the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), promotes international collaboration in cancer research (IARC, 2021a). IARC has identified carcinogenic hazards to humans by classifying the carcinogens into different groups according to their hazardous properties.

- Group 1 includes 121 agents, which are carcinogenic to humans.
- Group 2A consists of 89 agents, which are probably carcinogenic to humans and group 2B of 318 agents, which are possibly carcinogenic to humans.
- Furthermore, group 3 includes 499 agents, which are not classifiable as carcinogenic to humans (IARC, 2021b).

In the EU level, the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation (EC No 1272/2008), based on the United Nations' Globally Harmonised System (GHS), aims to safeguard a high level of protection of health and the environment, as well as the free movement of substances, mixtures and articles (ECHA, 2021a). Furthermore, in the EU, the registration, evaluation, authorisation and restriction of chemicals-regulation (REACH) (EC 1907/2006) seeks to improve the protection of human health and the environment by better and earlier identification of the intrinsic properties of chemical substances (European Commission, 2021). The Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive (CMD) (Directive 2004/37/EC) identifies the minimum requirements for protecting workers against risks to their health and safety, which are arising or are likely to arise from exposure to carcinogens and mutagens at work. The directive sets preventive and protective measures as well as exposure limits (ECHA, 2021b).

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14.1 Measurement methods

Cancers are divided to different stages and grades to describe the size, spread and appearance of cancerous cells (NHS, 2021). Different staging methods can be used for different cancers, however the below presented is an example of commonly used staging and grading (Table 15 and Table 16).

Table 15: Cancer stages according to NHS (2021)

Stage	Definition
stage 0	indicates that the cancer is where it started (in situ) and hasn't spread
stage I	the cancer is small and hasn't spread anywhere else
stage II	the cancer has grown, but hasn't spread
stage III	the cancer is larger and may have spread to the surrounding tissues and/or the lymph nodes (part of the lymphatic system)
stage IV	the cancer has spread from where it started to at least one other body organ; also known as "secondary" or "metastatic" cancer

Cancer grades are defined under microscopic examination, and lower grade indicates a slower growing cells.

Table 16: Cancer grading according to NHS (2021)

Grade	Definition
grade I	cancer cells that resemble normal cells and aren't growing rapidly
grade II	cancer cells that don't look like normal cells and are growing faster than normal cells
grade III	cancer cells that look abnormal and may grow or spread more aggressively

In the ICD-10 coding neoplasms (cancer) are categorised under C00-C97 including several sub-categories for each code. Below the main categories for most common cancers are presented. (WHO ICD-10, 2019.)

- C00-C75 Malignant neoplasms, stated or presumed to be primary, of specified sites, except of lymphoid, haematopoietic and related tissue
- C00-C14 Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx
- C15-C26 Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs
- C30-C39 Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs
- C40-C41 Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage
- C43-C44 Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin
- C45-C49 Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue
- C50-C50 Malignant neoplasm of breast
- C51-C58 Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs
- C60-C63 Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs
- C64-C68 Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract

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- C69-C72 Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system
- C73-C75 Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands
- C76-C80 Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, secondary and unspecified sites
- C81-C96 Malignant neoplasms, stated or presumed to be primary, of lymphoid, haematopoietic and related tissue
- C97-C97 Malignant neoplasms of independent (primary) multiple sites

For the ICD 11-coding the cancer coding is much more detailed and possibly somewhat challenging for the purposes of HBM data collection. The main subgroups are under the code 02 Neoplasms. (WHO ICD-11, 2020.)

For ICPC2-codes cancer codings are spreaded out under the main categories. Below the main categories are presented (WONCA, 2016).

- A79 malignancy NOS
- B72 Hodgkin's disease/lymphoma, B73 leukaemia, B74 malignant neoplasm blood other, B75 benign/unspec. neoplasm blood
- D74 malignant neoplasm stomach, D75 malignant neoplasm colon/rectum, D76 malignant neoplasm pancreas, D77 malignant neoplasm digest other/NOS and D78 neoplasm digest benign/uncertain
- F74 neoplasm of eye/adrexa
- H75 neoplasm of ear
- K72 neoplasm cardiovascular
- L97 neoplasm benign/unspec. musculo.
- N74 malignant neoplasm nervous system, N75 benign neoplasm nervous system, N76 neoplasm nervous system unspec.
- R84 malignant neoplasm bronchus/lung, R85 malignant neoplasm respiratory/other, R86 benign neoplasm respiratory, R92 neoplasm respiratory unspec.
- S77 malignant neoplasm of skin, S78 lipoma, S79 neoplasm skin benign/unspec., S80 solar keratosis/sunburn
- T71 malignant neoplasm of thyroid, T72 benign neoplasm thyroid, T73 neoplasm endocrine other/unspec.
- U75 malignant neoplasm of kidney, U76 malignant neoplasm of bladder, U77 malignant neoplasm urinary other, U78 benign urinary tract, U79 neoplasm urinary tract NOS
- W72 malignant neoplasm relate to pregnancy, W73 benign/unspec. neoplasm/pregnancy
- Y77 malignant neoplasm prostate, Y78 malignant neoplasm male genital other, Y79 benign/unspec. neoplasm genital (M)
- X75 malignant neoplasm cervix, X76 malignant neoplasm breast female, X77 malignant neoplasm genital other (f), X78 fibromyoma uterus, X79 benign neoplasm breast female, X80 benign neoplasm female genital, X81 genital neoplasm other/unspec.

For cancer, HBM4EU standardised questions can be found in Appendix 22.2.

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14.2 Environmental chemicals associated with cancer

In this chapter, reviews, systematic reviews and meta-analysis on environmental chemicals association to different cancers are presented. The search was restricted on studies among humans. A great variety of studies on different cancers with inconclusive results were found. The strongest evidence of an association was detected between heavy metals (except for mercury), plasticisers (BPA, phthalates, PFASs), pesticides, mycotoxins and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. See Appendix 22.3. tables 2-12.

Chemicals which presented inconclusive or only few studies were identified not been compiled in Appendix tables, but are shortly presented below. For aprotic solvents, mercury, anilines, diisocyanates and flame retardants only individual or inconclusive evidence was available. For UV filters no studies on cancer were identified.

There was only one systematic review detected regarding the association between solvents and breast cancer (Leso et al., 2019). In this study, including 10 studies (five different solvents) inconclusive results were observed. Searching with the sub-groups of aprotic solvents such as acetone, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide did not yield relevant results.

The evidence on the association of mercury exposure and cancers is scarce. From the US, a study using the NHANES data found that higher blood total Hg and methylmercury levels were associated with a higher prevalence of nonmelanoma skin cancer (Rhee et al., 2020). In Slovenia, mercury miners have been seen to have excess of incidence of total cancer, of oral and pharyngeal cancers and of lung cancer (Zadnik et al., 2007). However, the increased risk of miners could not be proved to be a result of mercury exposure but was possibly related to their smoking and alcohol drinking habits.

For anilines, the association to bladder cancer was detected in few epidemiological individual studies with inconclusive results (Ward et al., 1991; Tannenbaum, 1991; Freudenthal et al., 1994; Ward et al., 1994).

For diisocyanates, two reviews were identified. In the study of Prueitt et al. (2017) animal and epidemiological studies on respiratory cancer among occupational exposure was examined. The authors concluded inconclusive results in the human studies. The other review by Bolognesi et al. (2001) investigated the association between non-Hodgkins's lymphoma, Hodgkin's disease, pancreatic cancer and lung cancer. The few epidemiological studies available (n=5) were based on young cohorts, short follow-up and yielded no conclusive results. (Bolognesi et al., 2001.)

There is an evident lack of epidemiological studies of the association between different cancer types and FRs. Some evidence of increased risk of digestive system cancers, lymphoma and thyroid cancer was detected in relation to FRs exposure (Alsen et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2014).

14.2.1 Acrylamide

Most of the evidence regarding acrylamide exposure and cancer risk was related to women's gynecological/hormonal cancers. There was evidence of the association between acrylamide exposure and ovarian and endometrial cancers, especially in never smoking women (Adani et al., 2020; Je, 2015; Pelucchi et al., 2015). Furthermore, some evidence was detected of breast cancer in premenopausal women with rising amounts of acrylamide intake (Adani et al., 2020). A borderline significance was detected between acrylamide association and kidney cancer (Pelucchi et al., 2015). According to the search, the evidence regarding other cancers was rather weak. (Appendix table 2.)

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14.2.2 Cadmium and Chromium (VI)

In the identified Cd-studies, both general population and occupational exposure groups were represented. In Cr(VI)-studies only occupational exposure routes were identified. The studies on the association between Cd and various different cancer types are vast, whereas there is a scarcity of studies on Cr(VI). Both Cd and Cr(VI) exposure is tentatively associated with different cancer types (See Appendix table 3 and Appendix table 4).

The exposure to Cd was associated with the following cancer types: breast, lung, prostate, endometrial, renal and pancreatic cancers (Larsson et al., 2015; Rahim et al., 2013; Cho et al., 2013; Lin et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2016; Nawrot et al., 2015; Ju-Kun et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2016; Song et al. 2015; Chen et al., 2015). Furthermore, Cd exposure was associated with cancer mortality (Larsson et al., 2016) and total cancer risk (Cho et al., 2013; Nawrot et al., 2015). Finally, the role of Cd on pathophysiology of cancer and the carcinogenic effects of Cd have been highlighted in recent studies (Ebrahimi et al., 2020). However, some of the results were contradictory, and the studies within meta-analyses were occasionally heterogenic. Furthermore, cultural and gender related differences as well as differences between occupational and general exposure levels and hazards emerged in relation to cancer risk.

Cr exposure was associated with stomach and sinonasal (SNC) cancers (Welling et al., 2015; Binazzi et al. 2015). Some heterogeneity within the studies was detected.

14.2.3 Lead

There is a scarcity of systematic reviews and/or meta-analyses regarding the association between Pb and cancer. Tentative evidence is found, but overall evidence is inconclusive. Furthermore, the lack of epidemiological studies on the subjects hinders making of thorough conclusions.

Pb exposure was associated with malignant brain tumors, brain cancer, gliomas and meningiomas (Ahn et al., 2020; Meng et al., 2020). Furthermore, parents' exposure to Pb might be a risk factor for brain tumors in children (Meng et al., 2020). The role of Pb on pathophysiology of cancer and the carcinogenic effects of Pb have been strengthening in recent studies (Ebrahimi et al., 2020). Some of the results are contradictory, and the results/conclusions vary e.g. between different study designs (Appendix table 5).

14.2.4 Arsenic

The exposure to arsenic in drinking water is associated with the following cancer types based on systematic reviews and/or meta-analyses: urothelial cancer, bladder cancer, liver cancer, lung cancer and skin cancer (Appendix table 6). However, as expected, the risk depends on the arsenic concentration. For breast cancer the evidence is currently less conclusive.

14.2.5 Pesticides

The relation of different types of pesticides and cancers has been quite extensively examined (Appendix table 7). Findings from systematic reviews and meta-analyses point to positive associations of pesticide exposure with bladder cancer, non-hodgkin lymphoma, prostate cancer and thyroid cancer. For breast cancer, the studies do not currently show a consistent link with pesticides. Furthermore, the exposure to herbicides was seen to be associated with cutaneous melanoma. The risk of childhood cancers (lymphoma and leukemia) has also been found to be higher among children with residential pesticide exposure or prenatal parental occupational exposure.

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14.2.6 Mycotoxins

A positive association between the consumption of aflatoxin-contaminated foods and primary liver cancer risk was verified in a systematic review (Claeys et al., 2020) (Appendix table 8). The associations of mycotoxins and breast cancer or hepatocellular carcinoma remained unclear based on the review. Furthermore, the association between aflatoxin and gallbladder cancer has been examined in individual studies, which point to a possible association (Koshiol et al., 2017; Nogueira et al., 2015).

14.2.7 Phthalates and Hexamoll® DINCH

Phthalate exposure's association to breast cancer was examined in several systematic reviews and in one meta-analysis (n=4). Notably, the number of studies included in the analysis was small (n between three and six studies). The identified literature concluded inconclusive results between the different phthalate metabolites (Zuccarello et al., 2018; Wan et al., 2021; Rocha et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021). One review was identified to examine thyroid cancer and phthalate exposure, revealing a positive association between exposure and thyroid cancer in all three included studies (Alsen et al., 2021). (Appendix table 9).

14.2.8 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

The occupational exposure is especially high among certain occupations. Therefore, major part of studies on the association of PAH exposure and cancers have been conducted among occupational groups (Appendix table 10). Systematic reviews and meta-analyses point to associations between PAHs and lung cancer and larynx cancer and with somewhat less extensive evidence for cancer in the oral cavity and urinary tract. For breast cancer, the evidence is currently suggestive of an association.

Furthermore, in one independent study, the risk of bladder cancer was observed to be higher among chimney sweeps, nurses and waiters, aluminum workers, seamen, and oil/petroleum workers, which represent occupations with PAH exposure (Cumberbatch et al., 2015).

14.2.9 Bisphenol A

Evidence from human studies on the association of BPA and cancers is scarce (Appendix table 11). Systematic reviews or meta-analyses looking into the association of BPA and breast cancer did not provide evidence of a significant association (Liu et al., 2021; Wan et al., 2021). Significant association of BPA and BPAF and thyroid cancer was observed in two independent cross-sectional studies compiled in a recent review (Alsen et al., 2021).

14.2.10 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

Five systematic reviews were identified on PFAS exposure and different cancers. Two studies focused on breast cancer (Wan et al., 2021; Zeinomar et al., 2020), one on thyroid cancer (Alsen et al., 2021), one on liver cancer (Fenton et al., 2021) and one on kidney cancer (Stanifer et al., 2018). For breast cancer, inconclusive results were detected. For thyroid cancer the evidence was scarce, and the number of studies included was small (n=4). For liver cancer the results were also inconclusive. PFAS exposure and kidney cancer showed that in the eight included studies long-chain PFAS exposure was associated with kidney cancer or kidney cancer mortality. (See Appendix table 12).

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14.3 Highlights

In this literature search, the focus was placed on systematic reviews and meta-analysis to gain an overview of the possible associations between cancer and HBM4EU priority substances.

Cancer is causing one of the highest global health burdens, however the effects of environmental chemical exposure are not yet sufficiently known. In the table below, the summary of our findings and the findings from the previous report (Deliverable11.3) are presented.

Table 17: Summary of HBM4EU priority substance chemicals associated with cancer identified in the epidemiological literature search

	Breast/ other female cancer (indicated b or o)	Prostate cancer	Childhood cancers	Lymphoma/ Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	Bladder/ urothelial cancer	Lung cancer/ respiratory/ cancers	Thyroid cancer	Stomach cancer/ colon cancer	Kidney/ liver/ pancreatic cancer (indicated k, l or p)	Skin cancer	Brain cancer	Other*	Previous report (D11.3)
Acrylamide	√b,o								√k				√
Aprotic solvent	√b3												
As					√	√			√l	√			√
Diisocyanates						√3							√
Pb			√1								√	√*	√
Hg													√
Mycotoxins									√l				√
Pesticides	√b3	√	√2	√	√		√			√			√
UV filters													√
Phthalates	√b3						√						
BPA	√b3												√
PFASs									√ k				√
FR				√			√	√					√
Cd	√b,o	√				√			√k, p			√*	√
Cr								√				√**	√
PAH	√b					√						√** *	√
Anilines					√3								√

¹childhood brain tumor, ² childhood leukemia and lymphoma, ³The association remains unclear but suggestive results of an association were found, *total cancer, pathophysiology of cancer or carcinogenic effects, **sinonasal cancer, ***larynx cancer

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15 Hematological system

Authors: Virgolino Ana (FMUL), Capitão Carolina (FMUL), Martins Raquel (FMUL), Bicho Manuel (FMUL), Santos Osvaldo (FMUL)

The development of blood cells (hematopoiesis) starts early in embryonic and fetal life. During the prenatal period, hematopoiesis takes place, at different stages, in the yolk sac, liver, spleen, and bone marrow. At birth, this skeletal marrow becomes the exclusive site of blood cell formation (Kawthalkar, 2012).

While during infancy all the bone marrow (practically all bones) is hemopoietic, during childhood hemopoietic marrow becomes confined to the flat bones, namely the skull, vertebrae, ribs, sternum, sacrum, pelvis, and proximal ends of the femur and there is a progressive replacement of several skeletal sites by fat cells (in adulthood, nearly 50% of the marrow in these areas are composed of fat). Notwithstanding, when there is an increased need for blood cell production, the remaining yellow fatty inactive marrow can reverse to hemopoiesis and, if necessary, can expand hemopoiesis to the long bones. Also, in severe cases of disease, the liver and spleen can resume their fetal hemopoietic activity (Kawthalkar, 2012; Hoffbrand & Steensma, 2019).

Hematological diseases are pathological conditions that primarily affect blood or organs responsible for the production of blood (Pyszal et al., 2005). These pathological conditions include disorders of red blood cells (namely anemias), disorders of white blood cells, and disorders of hemostasis. Some examples of the most frequent diseases analysed in this deliverable are presented in Table 18. In this section, blood cancers will not be presented.

Table 18: Hematological diseases/health conditions and definitions under study (Mehta & Hoffbrand, 2009; Kawthalkar, 2012; Hoffbrand & Steensma, 2019; Karakus et al., 2020)

Disease/health condition	Definition	ICD-10	ICD-11	ICPC-3
Anemia	Reduction in circulating hemoglobin concentration below the expected range for healthy persons of the same age and sex, in the same environment, due to red blood cell loss, destruction, underproduction, or a combination of them	D60-D64; D50-D53	3A00-3A03; 3A20-3A4Z; 3A70.1- 3A70.Z; 3A9Z	BD66-BD67; BD77
Basophilic stippling	Basophilic granules in the cytoplasm of erythrocytes in peripheral blood smear	-	-	-
Cytopenia	Reduction above the normal range of the number of blood cells	-	-	-
Hemolysis	Rupture of erythrocytes and release of its content into surrounding fluid	-	MA16.00	-
Leukocytosis	An increase in the level of white cell in the peripheral blood above the normal range	D72.8	MA16.11	BS51

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Disease/health condition	Definition	ICD-10	ICD-11	ICPC-3
Methemoglobinemia		D74	3A93; 3A9Y	BD99
Monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance	Dyscrasia of the plasma cell, which can lead to multiple myeloma	D47.2	2A83.0; XH1NV1	-
Neutropenia	Low concentration of neutrophils in the blood	D70	4B00.0	BS51
Thrombocytopenia	A decrease in the level of platelets in peripheral blood below the normal range	D69.4-D69.6	3B64	BD78
Thrombotic thrombocytopenic purpura	Presence of microangiopathic hemolytic anemia and thrombocytopenia, as a result of a congenital or acquired decrease of enzymatic activity degrading unusual large vWF multimers	M31.1	3B64.14	BD78

In the last years, remarkable advances in understanding the pathogenesis of blood diseases and associated risk factors have been achieved (Hoffbrand & Steensma, 2019). It is now known that the hematopoietic system is susceptible to the influence of several environmental chemicals, including lead, cadmium, pesticides, arsenic, mercury, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), among others, ought to intensive proliferation of blood cells. Exposure to these chemical substances may take place in different settings, such as the workplace or residential areas (Pyszel et al., 2005).

This work aimed to review and summarise the existing literature of human studies exploring the association between hematological outcomes and environmental chemicals considered as a priority within the HBM4EU initiative. (Table 19)

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Table 19: List of HBM4EU priority substances and hematological outcomes key terms

Chemical substances	Hematological development
Acrylamide	Anemia
Aniline family	Hemoglobinopathies
Aprotic solvents	Thalassemia
Arsenic	Polycythemia
Benzophenones	Erythrocytoses
Bisphenols	Cytopenia
Cadmium	Lymphopenia
Chromium VI	Macrophage disorders
Chemical mixtures	Platelet dysfunction
Diisocyanates	Thrombocytopenia
Emerging substances	Plasma cell dyscrasias
Flame retardants	Monoclonal gammopathies
Lead	Paraimmunoglobulinemia
Mercury	
Mycotoxins	
Per-and polyfluorinated substances	
Pesticides	
Phthalates and hexamol® DINCH	
Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons	

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15.1 Environmental chemicals associated with hematological diseases

The associations between HBM4EU priority substances and hematological outcomes explored in the literature identified are presented in Table 20.

Table 20: List of the associations between HBM4EU priority substances and hematological outcomes under study in the identified literature

Substances	Hematological outcome	Papers (n)
Lead	Anemia	37
	Hemoglobin levels	14
	Basophilic stippling	3
	Gestational thrombocytopenia	1
Cadmium	Anemia	11
	Hemoglobin levels	2
	Gestational thrombocytopenia	1
Cadmium and lead	Hemoglobin levels	1
Arsenic	Anemia	10
	Hemoglobin levels	4
	Gestational thrombocytopenia	1
Mercury	Anemia	7
	Hemoglobin levels	3
Chromium	Anemia	3
	Hemoglobin levels	1
	Red blood cells count	1
	Hematocrit	1
	Eosinophilia	1
	Gestational thrombocytopenia	1
Pesticides	Hematological cells number alterations	2
	Hemolysis	1
	Monoclonal gammopathy	1
Phthalates	Anemia	2
	Hemoglobin levels	2
Aniline family	Methemoglobinemia	1
	Hemolytic anemia	1
PAHs	Hemoglobin levels	1
	Hematocrit	1
Perfluoroalkyl acids	Hemoglobin levels	1

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The appendix tables compiling the studies on environmental chemicals and hematological outcomes are presented at the end of Part C (Appendix 22.4).

15.1.1 Lead

In the blood, Pb produces its effect by interfering with the biosynthesis of heme, along with inducing oxidative damage, to which the erythrocyte membranes are more vulnerable, resulting in altered membrane integrity, permeability, and function (Jan et al., 2015). Additionally, Pb exposure long-term may also affect the kidney's capacity of hyper-production of erythropoietin to compensate for the Pb effect on hemoglobin levels (Camaj et al., 2020).

In total, 47 studies exploring the relationship between Pb and hematological outcomes were identified.

15.1.1.1 Lead and anemia

Out of the 47 studies identified, 37 explored the relationship between Pb and anemia (1 cohort, 3 case-control studies, 18 cross-sectional, 3 case series, and 12 case reports), comprising a sum of 18 219 participants. These studies are summarised in the Appendix table 13.

Two case-control studies conducted with children found a positive association between Pb levels and anemia, where anemic participants had higher Pb levels than healthy controls (one study investigated specifically iron deficiency anemia (Nassef et al., 2014), and the other, aplastic anemia (Ahamed et al., 2011)). On the contrary, the other case-control study, also conducted with children, did not find an association (Shah et al., 2011).

Similarly, the cohort study identified did not find a significant association between elevated BLLs and anemia, in children (Mohan et al., 2014).

Of the 18 cross-sectional studies, 7 did not find associations between anemia and Pb levels (3 studies with children and/or adolescents (Anticono et al., 2014; Gaman et al., 2020; Shah et al., 2011), 2 with adult participants (Meltzer et al., 2016; Plante et al., 2011), and 2 conducted with both populations (Suh et al., 2016; Kordas et al., 2011)), while 8 found higher BLLs in anemic participants in comparison to non-anemic (5 conducted with children and/or adolescents (Martins et al., 2016; Swaddiwudhipong et al., 2014; Thebo et al., 2019; Choi et al., 2017; Geltman et al., 2019) and 3 conducted with adults (Hsieh et al., 2017; Ahmad et al., 2014; Basit et al., 2015)). Still, 1 of these 9 studies also investigated the association between BLLs of children above 5 µg/dL and the presence of anemia, but it did not reach statistical significance (Martins et al., 2016). A cross-sectional study conducted by Örün, et al. (2011) concluded that mothers with a history of anemia had higher breast milk Pb levels than those without anemia. The last 2 studies described anemia prevalence of children with BLLs ≥100µg/L (36.8%) (Bouftini et al., 2015) and adults diagnosed with Pb poisoning (85.4%) (Dadpour et al., 2018).

All 12 case reports identified presented cases where patients were diagnosed with high BLLs and anemia (3 simply classified as anemia (Breeher et al., 2013; Kute et al., 2013; Breyre et al., 2016), 1 normocytic anemia (Kaneko et al., 2020), 1 normocytic normochromic anemia (Gunturu et al., 2011), 1 normocytic hypochromic anemia (Chambial et al., 2017), 4 microcytic hypochromic anemias (Akshatha et al., 2014; Toto et al., 2012; Gupta et al., 2011; Nazma et al., 2017), 1 sideroblastic anemia (Nicolli et al., 2020), and 1 hemolytic anemia (Muller et al., 2013)). One case series presented 4 cases of Pb toxicity, of which, 3 presented normocytic normochromic anemia (Petraicca et al., 2013), the other described two cases with simultaneous high serum Pb levels and anemia (Qasim et al., 2014), and one of the cases presented on the last one had high BLL and microcytic anemia (Wu et al., 2013).

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15.1.1.2 Lead and hemoglobin levels

Overall, 14 studies exploring the association between Pb levels and hemoglobin levels were found, of which, 3 were case-control studies and 11 cross-sectional, comprising a total of 8 720 participants (Appendix table 14).

All case-controls identified found a negative correlation between blood/serum Pb levels and hemoglobin levels (Nassef et al., 2014; Goel et al., 2019; Mitchell et al., 2012).

Regarding cross-sectional studies conducted with children and/or adolescents, 2 did not find a correlation between BLLs and hemoglobin levels (Srinivasa Reddy et al., 2011; Counter et al., 2012), and 4 reported a negative association between the two variables (Abdel Rasoul et al., 2012; Rondó et al., 2011; Kordas et al., 2011; Moawad et al., 2016). One of the studies conducted with children also assessed their mothers, and it did not find a correlation (Kordas et al., 2011). Likewise, Örün, et al. (2011) did not find a correlation between breast milk Pb levels and maternal hemoglobin levels. In contrast, 4 cross-sectional studies conducted with adults found an association between Pb levels and hemoglobin (Chen et al., 2015; Kim & Lee, 2013; Dadpour et al., 2018; Ahmad et al., 2014). Chen, et al. (2015) besides finding a correlation between Pb levels and hemoglobin, also compared hemoglobin levels of groups according to BLLs (>100g/L), but only observed a statistically significant difference in women, not in men.

15.1.1.3 Lead and basophilic stippling

Three studies addressing basophilic stippling were identified. One cross-sectional study mentioned that of the 118 workers of a Pb acid battery industry, with a mean BLLs of 65.25 ± 26.66 µg/dL, blood samples of three participants showed red blood cells with basophilic stippling (Ahmad et al., 2014). Additionally, one case report, presenting a case of a woman with high blood and urinary Pb levels, reported that a blood smear showed basophilic stippling (Muller et al., 2013) and a case series presenting two cases of Pb occupational toxicity reported that both patients did not exhibit basophilic stippling (Qasim & Baloch, 2014).

15.1.1.4 Lead and gestational thrombocytopenia

One cohort study, following 3911 pregnant women from China, did not find an association between gestational thrombocytopenia and a 10-fold increase in urinary Pb in multiple-metal models (Bao et al., 2020).

Chronic Cd toxicity may result in several adverse health-related effects (Rehman et al., 2017) including damages in the hematopoietic system (e.g. anemia through hemolysis, iron deficiency, and insufficient erythropoietin production) (Horiguchi et al., 2011).

15.1.1.5 Cadmium and anemia

A total of 11 studies (7 cross-sectional, 3 case-controls, and 1 case-report) exploring the association between Cd and anemia (including iron deficiency anemia, and hemolytic anemia) were identified, which included 22 094 participants.

Out of the seven cross-sectional studies, three observed higher serum levels of Cd among individuals with iron deficiency anemia (Ahn et al., 2017; Suh et al., 2016; Silver et al., 2013). On the other hand, three cross-sectional studies did not find an association between Cd levels and anemia (López-Rodríguez et al., 2017; Wai et al., 2020; Choi et al., 2017) (one of the studies assessed specifically iron deficiency anemia). Muller et al. (2011) found that all anemic workers had normal urine and blood Cd levels.

All case-controls found consistent results. In Pakistan, Shah et al. (2011) compared the levels of toxic elements between anemic and non-anemic children and showed that the mean levels of Cd

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were significantly higher in the anemic group. Ikeda et al. (2013) observed a higher urine concentration of Cd among the anemic participants, in comparison to controls and Nassef, et al. (2014) concluded that the concentrations of Cd were significantly higher in iron deficiency anemic participants than healthy controls.

Lastly, a case report of a 51-year-old man mentioned that the patient was diagnosed with hemolytic anemia, and his laboratory results showed a high blood Cd concentration (Raval et al., 2011).

15.1.1.6 Cadmium and hemoglobin levels

In total, 2 cross-sectional studies exploring the relationship between Cd and hemoglobin levels were identified, comprising a sum of 452 participants. These studies are presented in Appendix table 18.

The two studies found opposite results. Örün et al. (2011) evaluated serum hemoglobin levels in a sample of 144 mothers two months postpartum and did not find an association with breast milk Cd level, and the analysis conducted by Chen et al. (2015) in a sample of 308 Chinese adults revealed a negative correlation between hemoglobin and blood Cd levels.

15.1.1.7 Cadmium and gestational thrombocytopenia

Only one study addressing the association between Cd and thrombocytopenia was identified. This cohort study followed 3911 Chinese pregnant women and found that a 10-fold increase in urinary Cd was significantly associated with increased odds for gestational thrombocytopenia in different trimesters (Bao et al., 2020).

15.1.1.8 Cadmium and lead and hemoglobin levels

Chen et al. (2015) also evaluated the combined association of two heavy metals (Cd and Pb) and the hemoglobin levels and concluded that the participants with higher Pb levels had a lower hemoglobin concentration, regardless of the Cd level.

15.1.2 Arsenic

As toxicity can have a major impact on human health, with blood being an important target. Chronic As exposure has been associated with disorders in the hematopoietic system (Prasad et al., 2020; Taheri et al., 2016), and particularly anemia (Heck et al., 2008; Prasad et al., 2020; Hopenhayn et al., 2006), with inhibition of erythropoiesis in the hematopoietic system (Prasad et al., 2020).

15.1.2.1 Arsenic and anemia

Two cross-sectional studies focused on the association between As and anemia (Appendix table 21).

While one concluded that exposure to this chemical could be linked to this condition, especially in pregnant women (Surdu et al., 2015) the other suggested that additional factors could have played a role in the development of anemia (Choi et al., 2017).

Likewise, the two case-control studies found inconsistent evidence on the association between As and anemia. Taj et al. (2016) through adjusted logistic regression models, did not find an association between exposure to As and aplastic anemia cases. On the other hand, López-Rodríguez et al. (2017) found that As concentration was higher in the anemic group.

Results from case reports are consistent with the ones from the previous studies, suggesting anemia resulting from As poisoning by exposure in the workplace (Yoshimura et al., 2011)

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exposure throughout life nearby the residence (Dani, 2013), or ingestion of contaminated water (Laskar et al., 2016) or herbal mixtures (Wu et al., 2013; Shumy et al., 2016).

15.1.2.2 Arsenic and hemoglobin levels

López-Rodríguez et al. (2017) through a case-control study, found an association between hemoglobin and As concentration. Additionally, four cross-sectional studies also analysed the association of exposure to As and overall levels of hemoglobin. Except for one, which did not find a significant relationship (Taheri et al., 2016) the others found a reduction in the hemoglobin levels (Parvez et al., 2017; Ameer et al., 2015; Prasad et al., 2020).

15.1.2.3 Arsenic and gestational thrombocytopenia

The only study found which analysed the association between As and thrombocytopenia had a longitudinal design and was conducted with pregnant women (Appendix table 23).

The results revealed that this metal was in higher concentrations in urine in the third trimester of pregnancy than in the first and/or second trimester. Only during the 2nd trimester, a 10-fold increase of urinary As was associated with reduced odds of gestational thrombocytopenia (OR=0.58, 95% CI: 0.38-0.88) (Bao et al., 2020).

15.1.3 Mercury

Regarding laboratory assessment of Hg exposure, blood levels are a useful biomarker for short-term and high levels of exposure. However, since the levels decrease within days, urine Hg concentration is the indicated biomarker for long-term exposure to both elemental and inorganic Hg, and a good indicator of body burden (Park & Zheng, 2012). Exposure to Hg is a global concern due to its consequences on health. Based on a systematic review of the literature, human exposure to Hg has been linked to several adverse effects on the hematopoietic system, especially anemia, lymphopenia, neutrophilia, and basophilia (Vianna et al., 2019).

15.1.3.1 Mercury and anemia

In total, 7 studies (1 case-control, 3 cross-sectional, 1 case report, and 2 case series) exploring the association between Hg and anemia were identified, comprising a sum of 966 participants. These studies are summarised in Appendix table 24.

A case-control study found that the median of Hg hair and nail in anemic exposed dental staff was higher than the non-anemic in the same group but without significant difference (Al-Amodi et al., 2018).

Plante, et al. (2011) in a cross-sectional study, observed that the prevalence of anemia in subjects with high Hg levels was not higher, in comparison to the rest of the sample. Similarly, Choi et al. (2017) did not find an association between Hg levels and iron deficiency anemia and Örün et al. (2012) did not find an association between Hg level in breast milk and postpartum anemia.

Both case series, as well as the case report, presented cases where patients were diagnosed with high blood Hg levels and anemia (Wu et al., 2013; Yıldırım et al., 2012) aplastic anemia (Priya et al., 2012) neutropenia and/or thrombocytopenia (Yıldırım et al., 2012).

15.1.3.2 Mercury and hemoglobin levels

A total of 3 cross-sectional studies were identified addressing the association between Hg and hemoglobin levels (Appendix table 25).

Weinhouse et al. (2017) concluded that, in the total sample of 1387 participants, the association between total hair Hg and hemoglobin was not statistically significant, and remained nonsignificant after adjustment for age, sex, and BMI. However, when examined the same association in the sub-

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sample (that had a higher proportion of anemic children), the authors observed an inverse relationship between total hair Hg and hemoglobin and this association remained significant in the model adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and vitamin B12. Regarding the study conducted by Marques et al. (2020) it was observed a significant correlation between hemoglobin and hair Hg concentrations in traditional villagers. Lastly, Örün et al. (2012) did not find a correlation between hemoglobin concentration and breast-milk Hg level.

15.1.4 Chromium (VI)

Though high levels of Cr are always toxic, the toxicity level depends on its oxidation state (Jobby et al. 2018). The main mechanism of Cr(VI) toxicity is related to its easy diffusion across the cell membrane, followed by reduction of Cr(VI) in cells giving rise to free radicals that may directly cause DNA alterations and other toxic effects (Jobby et al., 2018; Younan et al., 2016).

Through the literature search, 5 papers exploring the relationship between Cr exposure and hematological outcomes were identified (1 cohort (Bao et al. 2020), 3 cross-sectional (Shah et al., 2011; Muller et al., 2011; López-Rodriguez et al., 2017) and 1 case report (Stepien et al., 2018).

15.1.4.1 Chromium and anemia

Three cross-sectionals were identified, exploring the relationship between Cr exposure and anemia (Appendix table 26). The two studies conducted with children reported conflicting findings, where one study reported that concentrations of Cr in scalp hair, blood, and urine were found to be significantly lower in anemic patients in comparison to control subjects of matched age groups (Shah et al., 2011) while the other did not find a difference of wt% of Cr between anemic and non-anemic children (Shah et al., 2011). The last cross-sectional study that included navy military aircraft maintenance repair facility workers reported that out of the 15 participants with Cr(VI) > 5 µg/m³, only one presented anemia (Muller et al., 2011).

15.1.4.2 Chromium and hemoglobin levels, red blood cells, hematocrit, and eosinophilia

Stepien, et al. (2018) reported a case of a 57-year-old adult with levels of chromium and cobalt markedly elevated, along with elevated red blood cells, hemoglobin, and hematocrit. Blood film also showed mild persistent eosinophilia with degranulation.

15.1.4.3 Chromium and gestational thrombocytopenia

A prospective cohort study conducted with pregnant women that investigated the associations of repeated measures of 13 urinary metals with platelet levels during pregnancy, did not find an association between gestational thrombocytopenia and a 10-fold increase in urinary Cr in multiple-metal models (Bao et al., 2020).

15.1.5 Pesticides

The vast array of adverse effects that pesticides have on human health (e.g., respiratory, immunological, neurological, endocrine, and hematological conditions) suggests that they act through different mechanisms of action. Experimental studies point out the hematotoxic properties of this group of substances which can lead to depressed hematopoiesis (Chatterjee et al., 2014; Chattopadhyay et al., 2015). Accordingly, pesticides can affect the hematopoietic system by causing oxidative stress and influencing immunological mechanisms, potentially inducing apoptosis of mononuclear cells from peripheral blood (Chatterjee et al., 2014; Luschak et al., 2018).

In total, 4 studies regarding pesticide exposure and hematological outcomes were found in the literature (1 cohort, 2 cross-sectional and 1 case series).

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15.1.5.1 Pesticides and hematological cells number alterations

A cross-sectional study showed that chronic exposure to pesticides abandoned on the outdoor may be associated with some hematological alterations, namely reduced counts of white blood cells, particularly eosinophils (Freire et al., 2015). Additionally, the use of pesticides in the workplace also seems to be associated with hematological alterations. For instance, a study assessing agricultural workers in contact with several pesticides found that serum levels of several organochlorine pesticides were associated with lower numbers of white blood cells, particularly monocytes, eosinophils, lymphocytes, neutrophils, as well as hemoglobin levels (Piccoli et al., 2019).

15.1.5.2 Pesticides and hemolysis

Bălăeț et al. (2018) presented three cases of repeated exposure to copper-calcium fungicides, at the occupational setting, and although there was no anemia, constant hemolysis was observed. According to the authors, this does not exclude the possible toxicity of the fungicides induced through ineffective erythropoiesis.

15.1.5.3 Pesticides and monoclonal gammopathy

Lastly, a cohort study following 958 Vietnam veterans found that those with higher TCDD levels had increased odds ratios for having monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance (a dyscrasia of the plasma cell which can lead to multiple myeloma), although after adjusting for covariates, the TCDD >10.92 ppt level effect did not reach statistical significance (Landgren et al., 2015).

15.1.6 Phthalates

Human exposure to phthalates occurs mainly through diet, inhalation, and dermal contact (Wang et al., 2019). This poses a concern due to its adverse health effects, for example, on the reproductive and endocrine systems, as well as hepatotoxic and genotoxic effects (Erkekoglu & Kocer-Gumusel, 2016).

Two studies (1 cross-sectional and 1 cohort) analysed the association between phthalates exposure and anemia as well as hemoglobin levels.

15.1.6.1 Phthalates and anemia and hemoglobin levels

In a cross-sectional study with 1482 pregnant women, Jiang et al. (2018) concluded that higher urinary phthalate metabolites were associated with an increased likelihood of anemia and a decreased hemoglobin concentration.

Similarly, the results from a cohort study, that followed 3269 pregnant women from China, showed a higher concentration of urinary phthalate metabolites among participants with persistent anemia, in comparison to the group without persistent anemia. Additionally, a significant inverse relationship was also found between phthalate metabolites concentration and hemoglobin levels (Zhu et al., 2018).

15.1.7 Anilines

Aniline is an aromatic amine used in the manufacture of antioxidants, antidegradants, and vulcanisation accelerators. Human contact with this substance occurs via inhalation, ingestion, and dermal absorption. The health effects of acute exposure to aniline result in the oxidation of hemoglobin present in the red blood cells, which leads to the formation of methemoglobin (National Research Council, 2000).

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Only one case report describing the exposure to aniline metabolites and hematological outcomes (namely, methemoglobinemia and hemolytic anemia) were found.

15.1.7.1 Aniline and methemoglobinemia and hemolytic anemia

Kusin et al. in CDC paper presented a case of a patient with methemoglobinemia and hemolytic anemia and his results of toxicology screening of urine were positive for p-aminophenol, another aniline metabolite (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2012).

15.1.8 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

15.1.8.1 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and hemoglobin levels and hematocrit

Only one cross-sectional study was found in the literature, exploring data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2003-2004 (see Appendix table 35). It showed that, after adjusting for age, gender, race, education, and smoking, there was a positive association between 1-hydroxynaphthalene urinary metabolite (NAP1) and hemoglobin as well as hematocrit. In contrast, 2-hydroxynaphthalene urinary metabolite (NAP2) was not significantly associated with hemoglobin or hematocrit (Sudakin et al., 2013).

15.1.9 Perfluoroalkyl acids

15.1.9.1 Perfluoroalkyl acids and hemoglobin levels

Jain analysed data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2003-2004, that included US adults aged ≥ 20 years and concluded that independently of anemic status, the adjusted associations between whole blood hemoglobin levels and every PFAA were positive and statistically significant, for the exception of PFNA among both non-anemic male and female participants, and PFHxS for anemic participants (see Appendix table 36). In this study, the impact of deteriorating kidney function on these associations was also addressed. However, these findings are not discussed since it is not within the scope of the present document.

15.2 Highlights

To date, several human studies have focused on the association between hematological development and exposure to environmental chemicals identified as HBM4EU priority substances.

Overall, considering the number of selected papers in this systematic review focusing on the abovementioned association, Pb is the most studied substance, followed by Cd and As.

Regarding hematological outcomes, anemia and hemoglobin levels are the ones with the most evidence available.

However, findings regarding the association between substances and hematological outcomes are not consistent, or enough evidence is not available.

Notwithstanding, Pb, Cd, and As seem to be associated with anemia and hemoglobin levels, as summarised in Table 21 The association between UV filters and hematological development in animal studies described in the deliverable report 11.3 was not found in human studies.

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Table 21: Associations between human exposure to substances and hematological outcomes supported by the literature

	Anilines	Arsenic	Cadmium	Chromium VI	Lead	Mercury	PFAS	Pesticides	Phthalates	PAH
Anemia		✓	✓		✓				✓*	
Hemoglobin levels		✓			✓	✓	✓*		✓*	
Basophilic stippling										
Gestational thrombocytopenia			✓*							
Lower count of leukocytes								✓*		
Eosinophilia										
Hematocrit										
Hemolysis										
Monoclonal gammopathy										

✓, association between substance and hematological outcome supported by the literature identified.

✓*, association only supported by ≤ 2 papers identified.

A meta-analysis should be performed (which surpasses the scope of this deliverable). However, the available studies are very heterogeneous in terms of aims, methods used to assess exposure to substances, and outcomes, which would impair this quantitative approach. Efforts to standardise practices among biomonitoring studies are needed to enable comparison between human studies – an identified need that is in accordance with HBM4EU efforts.

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16 Asthma

Author: Mattila Tiina (THL)

Below we report the association between the HBM4EU priority chemicals which are having or possibly having an association with asthma. Of these diisocyanates, hexavalent chromium Cr(VI) and possibly p-phenylenediamine (p-PDA) are considered to cause asthma through specific sensitisation (ECHA, 2020) and polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) and organophosphate insecticides are associated with asthma in epidemiological data. While phthalates, polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), pyrethroid insecticides, mercury, arsenic and lead are only potentially associated with asthma in epidemiological data (Mattila et al., 2021).

16.1 Measurement of asthma

According to international GINA guidelines clinical diagnosis of asthma includes various respiratory symptoms (wheezing, shortness of breath, cough and chest tightness) and confirmed reversible expiratory airflow limitation. Usually airway limitation is measured by spirometry. There are also other determined diagnostic methods which include such as daily diurnal PEF variability and increase in FEV1 in spirometry after anti-inflammatory treatment. However, in survey spirometry is the only reasonable method for measurement for diagnosing new asthma. Bronchial obstruction in asthma is normally reversible and after adequate inhaled anti-inflammatory treatment spirometry in subject with asthma is often normal (Reddel et al., 2019).

According to the International Classification for Diseases 10 (ICD-10) codes for asthma are J45 and J46, ICD-11 code is CA23 and ICPC-2 code R96. Countries have various administrative records. If asthma is diagnosed according to GINA criteria recorded administrative data should be reliably in scientific use. In clinical practice international diagnostic criteria are not always followed and the reliability of unspecified asthma diagnosis ("doctor's diagnosis") in records might be weak (Pekkanen & Pearce, 1999; GINA, 2019; Kavanagh et al., 2019).

Performing spirometry is the golden standard for diagnosing new asthma in surveys. However, performing spirometry takes time and resources, and therefore, despite diagnostic problems asthma is often diagnosed in epidemiological surveys by standardised questionnaires (Pekkanen & Pearce, 1999; Lim et al., 2014). Standardised protocol for spirometry has been presented in HBM4EU deliverable D11.3 <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>.

In addition, for asthma, the HBM4EU and EHIS standardised questions are presented in Appendix 22.2.

16.2 Environmental chemicals associated with asthma

16.2.1 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Many PAHs associated with fine particles enter in the lungs, cause inflammation and affect respiratory health. According to epidemiological data there is an association between exposure to PAHs and concentration of air pollutants and development of allergic and non-allergic asthma, increased symptoms of asthma, risk of asthma exacerbation and lung function decrease (Delfino, 2002; Pope, 2000; Jenerowicz et al., 2012; Karimi et al., 2015). Additionally, airborne PAHs, especially small sized particles, such as air pollution, burning coal inside and tobacco smoke, associate with childhood asthma (Pope, 2000; Jenerowicz et al., 2012;). Risk for asthma increase while the duration and amount of exposure to PAHs increases (Delfino, 2002; Pope, 2000). There are multiple pathophysiologic mechanisms suspected to lie behind this process including immunoglobulin E (IgE), mast cells', eosinophils' and epithelial cells' mediated reactions (Delfino,

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2002; Pope, 2000; Jenerowicz et al., 2012; Karimi et al., 2015; Klingbeil et al., 2014; Leem et al., 2005). However, generally PAHs are one of many other airborne chemicals (mixed exposure) and determining the role of each particulate PAH for the risk of asthma is difficult (Kim et al., 2013).

16.2.2 Diisocyanates

In addition to other respiratory symptoms, specific sensitisation for diisocyanates causes asthma. Diisocyanates are one of the most commonly identified causes for occupational asthma while even a very low exposure to diisocyanates may cause sensitisation and asthma. Prevalence of asthma in workers exposed to diisocyanates without appropriate protections is from 5 to 15%, and asthma often persists after removal of the exposure. Asthma induced by isocyanates is sometimes IgE mediated, yet, the specific mechanism for sensitisation stays undetermined. Specific sensitisation is often observed in specific bronchial challenge tests (no specific IgE). Diisocyanates may also cause asthma by irritating mechanisms (reactive airways dysfunction syndrome, RADS) (Tarlo et al., 2002; Tarlo et al., 2008; Collins et al., 2017; Wisnewski et al., 2001; Health Council of Netherlands, 2020).

Subjects producing and working with diisocyanates have increased risk for exposure and this associate with the risk of occupational asthma (Tarlo et al., 2002; Tarlo et al., 2008; Collins et al., 2017; Wisnewski et al., 2001).

Occupational groups who have a specific risk for asthma and other health harms caused by diisocyanates include subjects working with and producing diisocyanates (HBM4EU, Tarlo et al., 2002; Collins et al., 2017; Wisnewski et al., 2001).

MDI, TDI and HDI are used in multiple various applications, such as foams, sealants, coatings, plastic and medicinal utensils including for instance polyurethane. Specific sensitisation occurs through inhalation or trans-dermally (HBM4EU, 2020; Tarlo et al., 2002; Tarlo et al., 2008; Collins et al., 2017; Wisnewski et al., 2001).

Exposure to diisocyanates is measured in urine and sensitisation by skin tests (Prick), blood tests (IgE sensitisation), serial peak expiratory flow (PEF) measurement at work place or controlled inhalation challenge to diisocyanates (HBM4EU; Tarlo et al., 2002; Collins et al., 2017; Wisnewski et al., 2001).

16.2.3 Chromium (VI)

There is an association between exposure to Cr(VI) and asthma (Schneider et al., 2012; Huang et al., 2016; Zeng et al., 2016). Several national and international bodies, such as the NIOSH, WHO and HSE in the UK have recognised Cr(VI) as an airway sensitiser which may cause occupational asthma. Due to the widespread use of Cr(VI) in various industrial sectors, workers are the vulnerable population in developing asthma. Numerous case studies have revealed a link between occupational asthma, allergy and inhalation of certain particulate salts of Cr(VI) (Fernandez-Nieto et al., 2006; Walters et al., 2012; Hannu et al., 2007; Lockman, 2002; Park et al., 1994). Additionally, exposure to Cr(VI) may influence pulmonary function and cause asthma related symptoms in childhood (27). One study suggested that asthma prevalence was positively associated with the urinary concentration of chromium (Huang et al., 2016).

The underlying mechanism involved in occupational asthma caused by Cr(VI) has not yet been fully elucidated. Cr(VI) does not usually induce specific IgE response but causes, still, asthmatic reactions in sensitised workers in a specific inhalation challenge test at the concentrations which do not cause irritation (Fernandez-Nieto et al., 2006).

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Subjects working with Cr(VI) are specifically in risk and occupational exposure associate with asthma (Costa & Klein, 2006; Fernandez-Nieto et al., 2006; Walters et al., 2012; Hannu et al., 2005; Lockman et al., 2002; Santonen et al., 2019).

Occupational groups in risk for asthma include people breathing contaminated air while working with Cr(VI). This include workers in producing metal electroplatings, performing cement activities, construction workers (the risk of asthma being highest in these three previous) and stainless steel refractory products and clean glass ware factories and those who expose to various chemical syntheses (Rahman & Singh, 2019; Costa & Klein, 2006; Fernandez-Nieto et al., 2006; Walters et al., 2012; Hannu et al., 2007; Lockman, 2002; Park et al., 1994).

16.2.4 Pesticides

Acute high exposure to pyrethroids causes such symptoms as dyspnea, coughing, bronchospasm, nausea, vomiting, dermal effects and peripheral neural symptoms. Some pyrethroids have showed immunotoxic properties in experimental studies and some are classified as skin sensitisers (HBM4EU, 2020; Koureas et al., 2012; Mostafalou et al., 2017).

There are multiple studies showing an association between pesticides and asthma. Most of the evidence comes from occupational studies among farmers and pesticide applicators, and the strongest evidence was seen with organophosphate insecticides. Use of insecticides has also been related to exacerbation of asthma among subjects with allergies (HBM4EU, 2020; Ratanachina et al., 2019). Only a few studies are made about the potential impact of pesticides on asthma in the general population and the results are conflicting. A large Canadian cohort study, using urinary metabolites of organophosphates and pyrethroids as biomarkers of exposure, found an association between exposure to organophosphates and reduced lung function in the adult general population (Ye et al., 2016a) and to pyrethroids and reduced lung function in children and adolescents (Ye et al., 2016b).

Subjects producing and using pesticides have a risk for occupational exposure and this associate with a risk for asthma (HBM4EU, 2020; Esteban & Castano, 2009; Koureas et al., 2012; Mostafalou et al., 2017).

16.2.5 Phthalates and Hexamoll® DINCH

Epidemiological studies have showed a possible correlation between exposure to phthalates and asthma, and exposure to phthalates might exacerbate already existing respiratory symptoms (Kimber & Dearman, 2010; North et al., 2014; Jaakkola & Knight, 2008). In children exposure at home is associated with asthma and allergies, and in adults heated PVC fumes possibly associated with asthma (Jaakkola et al., 2008; Bornehag & Nanberg, 2010). In the U.S. National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) was found that HMW phthalates may cause allergy, allergic symptoms and sensitisation in adults but not in children (aged below 17 years) (Hoppin et al., 2013). A Danish study for children in preschool age with asthma, atopic dermatitis and rhino-conjunctivitis found a significant association between exposure to phthalates and allergic sensitisation (Beko et al., 2013). Experimental studies in vitro and in mice have reported that several phthalates may modulate the murine immune response to co-allergen and act as adjuvants in atopy and allergic reaction (Jaakkola & Knight, 2008; North et al., 2014).

Children, particularly early in life and in the prenatal period, are specifically sensitive for the immunotoxicity of phthalates (North et al., 2014; Bornehag & Nanberg, 2010). However, no data was found about the association between phthalates and a risk for asthma in these specifically sensitive population groups.

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Workers in the plastic industry, firefighters and meat wrappers might have an increased risk for exposure of phthalates; however, the amount of data is limited. No data about occupational exposure to phthalates and an increased risk for asthma was found (North et al., 2014; Jaakkola & Knight, 2008).

16.2.6 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

There is no data in adults and only limitedly studies in children and adolescents with no consistent results about the association between PFASs and asthma. Some studies for children and adolescents reported no association between PFASs and asthma (Rappazzo et al., 2017; Smit et al., 2015; Gaylord et al., 2019), allergies and IgE levels (Rappazzo et al., 2017; Gaylord et al., 2019). In another study exposure for some PFASs increased risk for asthma in children (Rappazzo et al., 2017). Among 981 mother-child pairs within the Odense Child Cohort in Denmark a significant association for PFNA with self-reported asthma was reported (Dalsager et al., 2016). A very recent study examined associations between childhood PFAS exposure and immune related outcomes. A statistically significant positive association mostly found in cross-sectional studies was seen between PFHpA and asthma in girls (Kvalem et al., 2020). In a study from Taiwan, serum concentrations of PFASs were associated with asthma, markers and severity for asthma (Dong et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2016). A study from Norway shows also a positive association of PFAS exposure with asthma and clinically severe asthma in adolescents (Averina et al., 2019). Animal models have shown that exposure PFASs cause airway hyperresponsiveness and inflammation (Humblet et al., 2014).

The scientific opinion of the EFSA CONTAM-panel, which has been published for public consultation recently, summarises that there are no or inconsistent associations with asthma and allergies for prenatal and postnatal PFASs exposures. However, the risk characterisation is based on effects on the immune system in humans at very low exposure concentrations, which is also supported by effects in laboratory animals (EFSA, 2020). Ongoing work in the HBM4EU shall provide further insight on PFASs related effects on the immune system including asthma and allergies.

Children have a higher body burden for PFASs compared to adults and also race and ethnicity affect exposure to various PFASs (Park et al., 2019). There is no shown association that these groups would have increased risk for asthma.

Data about the association between exposure to PFASs and occupation is limited. Yet, a high cumulative exposure to PFASs in workplace associated with higher measured PFASs levels. Risk works include such occupations as laborer in construction industry, prepress technicians and workers in printing industry (Tanner et al., 2018). There is no data about asthma or other diseases caused by this occupational exposure to PFASs.

16.2.7 p-phenylenediamine

p-PDA is a derivative of aromatic amines and a common contact allergen causing skin sensitisation (contact dermatitis) (HBM4EU, 2020; SCOEL, 2017; Malvestio et al., 2011; Richter, 2015; Helakoski et al., 2014). Some anilines and their derivatives are restricted in the EU and under the REACH regulation (HBM4EU, 2020; Malvestio et al., 2011).

p-PDA seem to associate with occupational asthma, rhinitis and contact dermatitis in hairdressers using p-PDA and related compounds (Baur & Bakehe, 2014; Malvestio et al., 2011; Helakoski et al., 2014).

Hairdressers working with p-PDA might have increased risk for asthma (Baur & Bakehe, 2014; SCOEL, 2017; Malvestio et al., 2011; Helakoski et al., 2014).

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16.2.8 Mercury

There are limited studies about association between exposure to mercury and asthma and no final conclusion can be made. In child the blood concentration of mercury is showed to associate (Kim et al., 2015) and not associate with asthma (Wu et al., 2019; Heinrich et al., 2017). Body burden of mercury might associate with acute atopic eczema and measured total IgE in children (Weidinger et al., 2004).

Specifically vulnerable populations include fetuses, newborn babies, young child and heavy seafood consumers (HBM4EU, 2020; Ha et al., 2017), yet, there is no shown association in these groups between exposure to mercury and asthma. Occupational groups in risk include workers refining of mercuric sulphide cinnabar ore, exposing to fossil fuels, incinerating solid waste, working in mining, smelting, restoration and artisanal works and dentists using amalgam (HBM4EU, 2020; Esteban & Castano, 2009; Ha et al., 2017). No data about association between an occupational exposure to mercury and asthma was found.

16.2.9 Cadmium

Inhaled exposure to cadmium affect respiratory system and might associate with asthma. However, smoking confound this association while cigarettes include cadmium, increase the blood concentration of cadmium and also associate with asthma (Zeng et al., 2016, Tinkov et al., 2017; Yang et al., 2019; Zeng et al., 2016). In children in China urinary concentration of cadmium associated with asthma (Huang et al., 2016) and blood concentration with cough but not with asthma (Zeng et al., 2016). In the U.S. the blood concentration of cadmium associated with wheeze and asthma in smoking adults and with lower forced expiratory volume in 1 s (FEV1) per forced vital capacity (FVC) and fractional exhaled nitric oxide (FeNO) in all participants (Yang et al., 2019).

The occupational groups having an increased risk for cadmium exposure include subjects protecting steel for corrosion, soldering and welding metal in alloys, incinerating waste and those working with color pigments and stabilisers in polyvinyl chloride plastics, in mining and battery industry (HBM4EU, 2020; Rahman et al., 2019; Tinkov et al., 2017). No data about an association between occupational exposure to cadmium and asthma was found.

16.2.10 Arsenic

There are a limited number of studies about the association between exposure to inorganic arsenic and its methylated forms and asthma and, therefore, the association is undetermined. Chronic exposure to arsenic was associated with various respiratory symptoms, decrease in lung functions, dyspnea and asthma (Das et al., 2014; von Ehrenstein et al., 2005) and respiratory symptoms in children in China (Zeng et al., 2016). Arsenic associated with obstructive lung diseases (Ratnaike, 2003).

Occupations where workers have a risk to expose for arsenic include gold mining, smelting, glass workers, wood preservation and handling of arsenic-containing agricultural products such as pesticides and herbicides (HBM4EU, 2020; Rahman et al., 2019; Ratnaike, 2003). No data about association between occupational exposure to arsenic and asthma was found.

16.2.11 Lead

There are quite a few studies about the association between exposure to lead and asthma, and therefore, no definite conclusion can be made. Generally, the effect of lead on lungs depend on the size and state of lead, for instance small inhaled particles are deposited in alveolar level and absorbed (HBM4EU, 2020). In child increased exposure to lead and blood level of lead associated

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with asthma and IgE production (Zeng et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2017), yet, not with current wheezing or whistling in one of these previous studies (Wu et al., 2019). In adults the results were not conclusive. In some studies the blood concentration of lead associated with lower FEV1%, decrease in FEV1 and FVC, bronchial hyperresponsiveness and increased total IgE level while in some not with wheeze and asthma (Yang et al., 2019; 4, Min et al., 2015; Min et al., 2008; Pak et al., 2012; Joseph et al., 2005.)

No data about association between occupational exposure to lead and asthma was found.

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17 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Authors: Elonheimo Hanna (THL), Haverinen Elsi (THL), Mattila Tiina (THL)

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is a progressive, life-threatening and under diagnosed disease which cause various respiratory symptoms. COPD is characterised by various irreversible pathophysiological changes causing chronic bronchus obstruction, chronic bronchitis (CB), and emphysema. The most common symptoms of COPD include breathlessness, sputum production and / or cough (WHO, 2021; NHS, 2019).

Etiology of COPD is suspected to be chronic inflammation caused by smoking in most of the cases (NHS, 2019; WHO, 2017; Delzell, 2013; WHO, 2021) but also by air pollutants and occupational exposure.

The most important risk factor for COPD is smoking. In addition to active smoking, also exposure to passive tobacco smoke and childhood exposure are critical risk factors. Other risk factors for COPD are exposure to fumes and smoke from carbon-based cooking and heating fuels (such as charcoal and gas), and occupational hazards (such as exposure to pollutants and chemicals). In addition to this inhalation risk factors also poor nutrition, low socioeconomic status, pneumonias or childhood respiratory infections may increase the likelihood of developing COPD. Other non-modifiable risk factors include increasing age, asthma and genetic predispositions. In some cases, correct diagnosis is missed or delayed causing the pulmonary impairment to advance (WHO, 2017; Koblizek et al., 2016).

COPD symptoms vary individually, and the symptoms increase during time if the exposure continues. Progressive COPD usually includes diverse respiratory symptoms and quite often people suffer from comorbidities and face exacerbations of the disease. As the disease progresses, the need for care also increases and the patient will decay with time.

Based on the data from the Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors Study in 2017 (GBD, 2018), there were 545 million people worldwide having a chronic respiratory disease; 50 % of the cases being COPD and 50 % asthma. Chronic respiratory disease prevalence was the highest in high-income regions among both women and men, and the lowest prevalence was detected in sub-Saharan Africa and South-Asia. Chronic respiratory diseases were the third leading cause of death; there were nearly 4 million deaths due to these diseases with an increase of 18 % compared to 1990. Total DALYs increased by 13.3 %. In both females and males, most chronic respiratory disease-attributable deaths and DALYs were due to COPD (GBD, 2018; GBD, 2020).

The total cost of respiratory diseases in the European Union (EU) (based on the former amount of 28 countries) is more than €380 billion annually. The annual costs of healthcare and lost productivity due to COPD are estimated to €48.4 billion, of which €23.3 billion are direct and €25.1 billion indirect costs. The monetised value of DALYs lost is €93.0 billion. Together these costs of COPD contribute to total costs of €141.4 billion (European Respiratory Society, 2021).

17.1 Measurement methods

COPD diagnosis includes symptoms typical for COPD and persistent (postbrochodilation) airflow obstruction in spirometry. Spirometry measures airflow in bronchus and can be used to categorise the severity of the obstruction. Standardised protocol for spirometry can be found from Deliverable 11.3 <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>. Measured values for COPD include the maximal volume of air exhaled in the first second of a forced expiration from a position of full inspiration (FEV1) and the maximal volume of air exhaled with maximally forced effort from a maximal

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inspiration (FVC) (Miller et al., 2005). COPD is diagnosed when a patient at risk is having respiratory symptoms and irreversible airway obstruction evidenced by FEV1/FVC ratio less than 0.7 (Delzell, 2013). Availability of diagnostic and treatment options vary across different resource settings.

In order to understand the severity of COPD and its influence on patients' lives, a categorisation of different stages of COPD can be used. The most common way for determining the stages of COPD consists of the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD Staging System) and the BODE Index. The GOLD categorisation includes four different stages using the FEV1 measurement ranging from mild to severe disease description (GOLD Report, 2021). The BODE Index includes investigation of body mass, obstruction of airflow, dyspnea (difficulty of breathing) and exercise capacity. The Index is used to understand prognosis (Lung Health Institute, 2018).

The treatment of COPD is based on the symptoms and possible exacerbations of the disease. Smoke-free life is the most crucial part of COPD treatment, following pulmonary rehabilitation and healthy lifestyle habits. Medical treatment is based on various inhalations and treating comorbidities. COPD, as being a progressive disease usually requires more treatment as time passes and includes increased risk of mortality. More than 90% of COPD deaths occur in low- and middle-income countries partly due to bad air quality and higher smoking status. (NHS, 2019; WHO, 2017; GOLD Report, 2021).

The ICD-codes (International Classification for Diseases) morbidity statistics of COPD are the following:

The ICD-10:

Chronic lower respiratory diseases (J40-J47), more specifically J44 Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease subdivided into:

- J44.0 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute lower respiratory infection
- J44.1 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute exacerbation, unspecified
- J44.8 Other specified chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
- J44.9 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, unspecified (WHO ICD-10, 2019).

The ICD-11:

Diseases of the respiratory system (12). The ICD-11 code is CA22 divided into:

- CA22.0 Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease with acute exacerbation, unspecified
- CA22.1 Certain specified chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
- CA22.Z Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, unspecified (WHO ICD-11, 2020).

The International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2) – code for COPD is R95 (WONCA, 2016).

For COPD, the HBM4EU and EHIS standardised questions are presented in Appendix 22.2.

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17.2 Environmental chemicals associated with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

17.2.1 Pesticides

Abundance of evidence seems to be linked with the association between pesticides and COPD. Pourhassan et al. (2019) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis including nine studies in occupational settings (8 cohort- and 1 case-control study; total n= 101 353) aiming to estimate the relationship between occupational exposure to pesticides and risk of obstructive pulmonary diseases. A direct relationship between exposure to pesticides and obstructive pulmonary diseases (OR 1.27, CI 95% 1.23-1.31) and an increased risk of COPD (OR 1.44, 1.14-1.81) was detected.

In another systematic review, 23 case-control or cross-sectional studies, of which six were agricultural occupational studies on airway obstruction (asthma and COPD), bronchitis or wheezing were investigated (Doust et al, 2014). According to the results exposure to pesticides might be associated with COPD, but the evidence was weaker than for asthma. Lytras et al. (2019) examined the effect of occupational exposures on CB incidence in the European Community Respiratory Health Survey. A cohort study in occupational settings investigating pesticides (and metals and solvents) was performed. The cohort consisted of randomly selected population samples aged 20-44 (n=8 794) in 1991-1993, which were followed up twice over 20 years. In women, exposure to pesticides increased the incidence of chronic phlegm. Occupational exposures were associated with chronic phlegm and CB, however there were differences among women and men warranting further research.

Fontana et al. (2017) conducted a systematic review to identify epidemiological studies investigating COPD prevalence in farmers/in occupational settings. The review consisted of 14 case-control or cohort studies, of which three studies focused on pesticides. In one of the case-control studies the prevalence of COPD was significantly higher among farmers compared to controls (18.1% vs. 6.9%). As well, the severity of the disease was greater in farmers (9.0% vs. 4.0% for mild, 5.0% vs. 2.3% for moderate and 2.9% vs. 0.5% for severe COPD forms). A positive association between red blood cell acetylcholinesterase inhibition and COPD prevalence was observed, which suggested a causative role of pesticide exposures. Among farmers there was a significantly increased risk of COPD (adjusted OR 1.59, CI 95% 1.32-2.28). In one of the cohort studies higher risks of airway obstruction was observed among those exposed to high levels of herbicides compared to controls (adjusted OR 2.11, CI 95% 1.03-4.30).

Similar findings were detected in another cohort; workers exposed to pesticides had an almost two times higher prevalence of airway obstruction compared to non-exposed subjects. However, one of the cohort studies assessed COPD with the GOLD criteria. The findings showed a significant exposure-response relationship with restrictive ventilator defects, but after adjusting for several confounding factors, including e.g. the number of years and the lifetime days of application, there was no significant association between paraquat exposure and COPD.

Ye et al. (2013) conducted a review including case-control or cross-sectional studies to identify respiratory symptoms and diseases associated with occupational pesticide exposures. There was suggestive evidence for an association between occupational pesticides exposure and CB or COPD. Furthermore, Mostafalou et al. (2013) investigated the relationship between pesticides and human chronic diseases by conducting a review including 8 studies of COPD (2 case-control, 4 cohort and 2 with other designs) in occupational settings. Tentative evidence on the association between exposure to pesticides and respiratory problems, including COPD was detected. Mamane et al. (2014) conducted a review regarding occupational exposure to pesticides by including 41

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cross-sectional, case-control, longitudinal and cohort studies. Of 15 cross-sectional studies focusing on respiratory symptoms and agricultural pesticide exposure, 12 found significant associations with chronic cough, wheeze, dyspnea, breathlessness or chest tightness. The three identified cross-sectional studies on CB found a relationship with occupational exposure and the four cross-sectional studies applying spirometry reported impaired respiratory function associated with pesticide exposure. All cohort studies on COPD (n=3) found a significant relationship with increased risk of COPD. Workers employed in pesticide production had an elevated risk of COPD (2 out of 3 cohort studies) and impaired respiratory function suggestive of an obstructive syndrome (2 out of 2 cohort studies).

More agricultural occupational reviews were found in the literature search (Nordgren & Bailey, 2016; Poole, 2012; Silver et al., 2021; Tarmure et al., 2020). Nordgren and Bailey (2016) reviewed studies investigating the harmful effects of occupational exposures in the agricultural industry. Occupational exposures to numerous agricultural environment aerosols including pesticides were associated with impaired respiratory function and disease, including COPD. Poole (2012) reviewed important farming related environmental exposures with impact on atopic and non-atopic upper and lower respiratory diseases. Upper and lower respiratory diseases were prevalent in the farming community, and important mediators included e.g. pesticides. Upper and lower respiratory adverse health effects, particularly non-IgE (immunoglobulin E) mediated, were common among agriculture workers.

Moreover, Silver et al. (2021) followed the 1992 Health and Retirement Study (HRS) cohort (n=7 907) not diagnosed with COPD in the beginning of the study. The study was conducted in farming/occupational settings. Subhazard ratios (SHRs) for COPD were significantly increased for several industries including farming. SHR for farming, forestry and fishing was 0.94 (CI 95% 0.68-1.28) and SHR ever vs. never exposed regarding pesticides 1.31 (0.97-1.76), which was heightened but not statistically significant. Significantly heightened COPD SHRs were detected to certain industry and occupation (I/O) pairs such as farmworkers and pesticide exposures; farmworkers exposed to pesticides had a significantly heightened SHR for COPD (3.40, CI 95% 1.40-8.23, N of COPD cases=5). Lastly, Tarmure et al. (2020) conducted an occupational literature review on the influence of pesticides on respiratory pathology. Exposure to pesticides was highly correlated with respiratory pathologies such as COPD, well-documented evidence was detected regarding the occupational exposure to pesticides and COPD.

In three individual studies, two cohorts and one case-control study some evidence of pesticide exposure was detected. Alif et al. (2017) followed a large cohort (n=1 335) within the Tasmanian Longitudinal Health Study (TAHS) from 2002 to 2008 in occupational settings. Ever exposure to pesticides (RR 1.74, CI 95% 1.00-3.07) was associated with fixed airflow obstruction. As well cumulative EU-years to all pesticides (RR 1.11, 1.00-1.25) and herbicides (RR 1.15, 1.00-1.32) were associated with fixed airflow obstruction. Furthermore, all pesticides exposure was consistently associated with CB and symptoms consistent with airflow obstruction. De Jong et al. (2014) investigated occupational exposure to pesticides within a large LifeLines cohort study (n= 11 851) aged 18-89 years. Second general population cohort (n=2 364) was used to verify the findings.

Occupational exposure to pesticides was associated with a lower level of lung function (prebronchodilator FEV1, FEV1/FVC) and with a higher prevalence of mild and moderate/severe airway obstruction in the two general populations. The results were adjusted for sex, age, height, weight, current/ex-smoking and pack-years. Lastly, Chakraborty et al. (2009) conducted a case-control study of agricultural and non-agricultural workers including 376 nonsmoking agricultural workers and 348 non-agricultural workers. Agricultural workers (cases) had greater prevalences of

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upper and lower respiratory symptoms and noticeable reduction in spirometry measurements. Lung function reduction was prevalent in 48.9% of agricultural workers compared to 22.7% of controls. A restrictive type of deficit was predominant. COPD was diagnosed in 10.9% of agricultural workers compared with 3.4% of controls ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the severity of the disease was greater in agricultural workers.

17.2.2 Bisphenol A

A scarcity of evidence regarding the association between BPA and COPD was found on the literature search. Drummond (2014) reviewed the epidemiology, risk factors and interventions regarding obstructive lung disease (OLD) in urban populations. Postnatal BPA exposure contributed to increased OLD prevalence and symptom manifestations. Erden et al. (2014) conducted a case-control study of COPD-patients ($n=50$) and controls from general population ($n=33$). BPA levels were significantly higher in COPD patients than in control subjects (3.04 ± 3.30 and 0.57 ± 0.19 ng/mL, respectively) ($p < 0.001$), and high serum BPA levels were associated with COPD. Cases (COPD-patients) had statistically lower FEV1 (% predicted), FVC (% predicted) and FEV1/FVC ratio compared to controls ($p < 0.001$). BPA might have an influence on the etiopathogenesis of COPD.

17.2.3 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Some studies regarding the association between exposure to PAHs and COPD were identified. Most of the studies regarding PAHs have been conducted in connection with air pollution and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) (e.g. Che et al., 2020). PM_{2.5} is consisted of PAHs and other inorganic elements. However, air pollution as such is outside the scope of this report, and therefore only a few studies of PAHs were included. In case PAHs were investigated in connection with air pollution, only studies where Human Biomonitoring was applied were selected for this report.

In a review, Låg et al. (2020) assessed epidemiological studies on associations between gas phase and particle-bound PAHs in ambient air and non-malignant respiratory diseases or related psychological processes. 30 epidemiological, experimental and mechanistic studies within case-control, panel, cross-sectional, birth cohort and cohort settings were included, and the study subjects were either occupational, children or patients. Exposure to PAHs in adults was associated with respiratory functions and increased morbidity/mortality of OLD. However, the studies were few and weak. PAHs may trigger many processes linked to non-malignant respiratory diseases.

Che et al. (2020) conducted a sample study ($n=54$) among COPD-patients to investigate the composition characteristics of atmospheric fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) and bronchoalveolar lavage fluid (BALF) samples. PAHs and other inorganic elements in PM_{2.5} were studied, and there were 16 PAHs detected in 32 BALF samples. The main components of BALF and atmospheric PM_{2.5} were the high molecular weight PAHs, and the species and concentration of PAHs in BALF and atmospheric PM_{2.5} were highly consistent in COPD patients. The enduring high concentrations of PAHs in BALF of COPD patients may have long-term adverse effects on patients; PAHs in lungs may cause or worsen COPD.

Shiue (2016) conducted a cohort study ($n=5\ 560$, aged 20-80) to examine the relationships of urinary PAHs and adult respiratory conditions. The data was derived from the United States National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES) representing a sample of the civilian, non-institutionalised US population. Urinary 2-hydroxyfluorene and 3-hydroxyfluorene were positively associated with emphysema (OR 1.60, 95% CI 1.26-2.03, $p=0.001$ and OR 1.42, 1.15-1.77, $p=0.003$, respectively), while 2-hydroxynaphthalene (2-naphthol) was borderline associated with

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emphysema. Urinary PAHs were associated with adult respiratory health conditions, although the causality was not confirmed.

17.2.4 Flame retardants

Evidence regarding the association between FRs and COPD is inconclusive. Hulin et al. (2012) conducted a systematic review in which 12 studies focused on FRs. The aim was to investigate population-based studies evaluating the respiratory effects (incl. COPD and CB) of quantitatively measured indoor air pollutants in industrialised countries. The evidence regarding the role of FRs in respiratory diseases including COPD was not confirmed.

In a systematic review by Baur et al. (2012) 474 studies of cohort or case-control settings were included; 20 studies investigated occupational COPD. The focus of the studies was mostly occupational asthma, and occupational COPD was only incidentally included. Chlorine, one type of synthetic organic FRs, was associated with COPD as an individual agent with strong evidence. Irritant-induced occupational COPD was significantly underreported. Campos-Obando et al. (2018) conducted a cohort study (two cohorts from the Rotterdam study, n=3731) to investigate the association between phosphate (P) (one type of synthetic organic FRs) levels and all-cause and cause-specific mortality. A significant positive association was detected between phosphate and all-cause mortality in men (pooled HR 1.46, 95% CI 1.26-1.69) but not in women (0.90, 0.77-1.05). In men, higher phosphate levels increased the risk of chronic lung disease mortality (1.94, 1.02-3.72) driven by mortality due to COPD (4.44, 2.08-9.49). Serum phosphate was associated with increased all-cause and COPD mortality in men but not in women.

17.2.5 Heavy metals

Thus far most of the epidemiological and biomonitoring studies on COPD and heavy metal exposure have focused on occupational settings at certain risk industries. The mechanisms behind heavy metal toxicity are not yet fully known, however some evidence of antioxidant-oxidant mechanisms have shed light to the pathogenesis of decreased pulmonary functions and heavy metal exposure.

A few studies were found to focus on these mechanisms in relation to COPD. Glutathione-S-transferase (GST) and glutathione (GSH) are antioxidants of the lung and have been identified as having antioxidant effects and detoxification mechanisms of the cells by converting endogenous and exogenous electrophilic compounds to less reactive metabolites (Gogoi et al., 2019). GSH levels in the human airways are naturally high in comparison to blood or other body fluids, describing the possibly high oxidative pressure on the lung surface (Cantin et al., 1985). Furthermore, GSH levels may be influenced by both environmental and genetic factors (Wisniewski et al., 2005). Genetic alteration of GST (GSTM1, GSTT1 and GSTP1) has been identified as potential risk factor for COPD development (Shukla et al., 2011; Gogoi et al., 2019; Skalny et al., 2020). In a study by Gogoi et al. (2019) Cd, Pb, Hg and Cr were inversely correlated with pulmonary function (FEV1/FVC ratio), GST activity and GSH levels among COPD patients working at a coal mine site in comparison to healthy controls (p<0.05).

In a study by Elmasry et al. (2015) GSH levels were discovered to be significantly higher in healthy population (non-smokers) in comparison to COPD patients (smokers). The authors concluded that GSH has a significant role in antioxidant protection of the lungs, and furthermore oxidant-antioxidant imbalance may play a role in the severity of the disease and that it may have shown some signs of pathogenesis of the disease.

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17.2.6 Cadmium

There is quite solid evidence regarding the association between Cd and COPD. Skalny et al. (2020) conducted a review to explore data on the role of heavy metal exposure in development of respiratory dysfunction. Cd exposure, among other heavy metals, was associated with respiratory dysfunction and respiratory diseases (COPD, bronchitis). Torén et al. (2019) observed an association between blood-Cd and emphysema based on lung computed tomography in a random population sample. There was an association between blood-Cd and emphysema and the results were assessed with detailed control for smoking habits. Cullinan (2012) used data from reviews of occupational COPD in specific occupations and industries in general populations to investigate the role between occupation and COPD. There was a good evidence for an increased risk of COPD from Cd fume. Certain occupations augment the risk of COPD independently or together with smoking; the evidence was the most uniform for coal mining and work including exposure to Cd fume among other fumes (silica, cotton dust).

Two case-control studies were identified (Gogoi et al., 2019; Hassan et al., 2014). The first case-control study by Gogoi et al. (2019) among COPD patients of coal mine site consisted of 93 nonsmoking cases and 85 nonsmoking controls. The hypothesis that circulatory heavy metals may be associated with lung function decline and lower plasma GST activity and GSH level in COPD patients was investigated. Blood (plasma) levels of heavy metals, including Cd, were significantly higher ($p < .05$) in COPD patients than in healthy controls at coal mine site. The blood-Cd level increase in cases was 0.0207 ± 0.003 and in controls 0.0025 ± 0.001 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

A statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) inverse correlation between the circulating levels of heavy metals including Cd and lung function (FEV1/FVC %, predicted) was detected. Furthermore, the levels of blood heavy metals including Cd were significantly ($p < .001$) and negatively correlated with plasma GST activity and GSH level in COPD patients. In comparison, in controls, a weak and statistically non-significant ($p > .05$) inverse correlations were detected between the levels of blood heavy metals (incl. Cd) and lung function, GST activity and GSH level. In conclusion, the heavy metal levels in COPD patients were significantly and negatively correlated with lung function and antioxidant activity in plasma.

Secondly, Hassan et al. (2014) conducted a small case-control study among COPD patients (GOLD 4) ($n=11$) and healthy controls (GOLD 0) ($n=9$) to assess expression of the Cystic Fibrosis Transmembrane conductance Regulator (CFTR) and the cigarette smoke metal content in lung samples. All the participants had a history of smoking except one person in the control group. However, they all had quit smoking before the sample collection except one person in GOLD 4 group, who was a current smoker. CFTR is a chloride channel in airway epithelial cells. Decreased CFTR expression and function causes impairment of airway surface liquid (ASL) volume homeostasis, which results in accumulation of mucus, reduced clearance of bacteria and chronic infection and inflammation. CFTR was reduced in the lungs of GOLD 4 COPD patients. Based on the assessment of metals present in lung samples, Cd was significantly higher in GOLD 4 COPD patients when compared to control smokers ($p=0.007$).

Oh et al. (2014) conducted a study by using cross-sectional data from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey from 2008 to 2011 ($n=3\ 622$) among general population. The aim was to investigate the relationship between Cd and COPD according to gender and smoking status. A higher blood-Cd level, but within the normal range, was associated with COPD in males including those who had never smoked (p for trend < 0.001 and p for trend $= 0.008$). On the other hand, higher blood-Cd was not significantly associated with COPD in females, including those who had never smoked (p for trend $= 0.39$ and p for trend $= 0.43$). Rokadia and Agarwal (2013) used

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cross-sectional data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2007-2010 to evaluate the association between serum Cd concentration and OLD. The prevalence of OLD was 12.4 % (95% CI 10.2 - 13.6 %). The mean (SE) Cd levels in the OLD group were significantly higher in comparison with normal control subjects (0.51 [1.04] vs. 0.33 [1.02], $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the association between OLD and smoking was significantly suppressed after adjusting for serum Cd concentration.

There was also a progressive increase in serum Cd concentrations with worsening FEV1 % predicted values among smokers in the study population. Leem et al. (2015) followed cross-sectional data from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2008-2012 ($n=5972$) to assess the relations between blood levels of heavy metals and lung function. Adjusted means for age, sex, BMI, and smoking status in blood Cd levels increased with age and were higher in men and current smokers. The FEV1/FVC ratio was lower in the highest quartile group of Cd concentrations (78.3 % vs. 79.2%, $p < 0.001$) in comparison to those in the lowest quartile groups. There was an inverse relationship between the FEV1/FVC ratio and concentrations of Cd (estimated -0.005 , $p=0.001$). In current smokers the risk of obstructive lung function (OLF) was higher in subjects in the highest quartile group of Cd concentration compared to those in the lowest quartile group (OR 1.94, 95% CI 1.06-3.57). In conclusion, there was a significant association between the FEV1/FVC ratio and blood Cd concentrations in population, and the OLF risk was heightened with increasing concentrations of Cd among current smokers.

Two cross-sectional studies focused on children's exposure to heavy metals, with inconclusive results (Pan et al., 2020; Zeng et al., 2017). Pan et al. (2020) included 221 healthy children in the cross-sectional study aiming to investigate the associations between metal concentration and pulmonary function. The geometric mean of the blood-Cd levels was 0.28 (0.06-0.40) $\mu\text{g/L}$. There was a significantly positive interaction of blood-Cd on pulmonary function: FVC ($\beta = 13.11$, $p= 0.03$), percent-predicted FVC ($\beta = 15.18$, $p= 0.04$), and percent-predicted FEV1 ($\beta = 3.90$, $p= 0.03$). Causal relationships could not be confirmed, however. Zeng et al. (2017) scrutinised the contribution of blood heavy metals and lung function levels. The relationship between living area and blood parameter and lung function levels were investigated in 206 children between the ages of 5-7 years old. Of the children 100 lived in electronic waste (e-waste) exposed recycling areas (cases) and 106 in reference areas (controls). There was no significant difference in blood-Cd level between the cases and controls ($p>0.05$). However, living in the exposed area was positively associated with blood Cd levels ($\beta = 0.186$, $p<0.05$). Furthermore, lower lung function levels were detected in children residing in the exposed area.

17.2.7 Chromium (VI)

Some evidence exists also for Cr and its association with COPD. One of the studies was on fine particulate matter (PM2.5) including Cr. The earlier mentioned case-control study by Gogoi et al. (2019) showed that blood levels of heavy metals, including Cr, were significantly higher in COPD patients than in healthy controls. Blood (plasma) levels of heavy metals, including Cr, were significantly higher ($p<.05$) in COPD patients than in healthy controls at coal mine site. The blood-Cr levels were 0.0086 +- 0.001 and 0.0023 +- 0.001 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ in COPD patients and controls, respectively. There was also a statistically significant ($p<0.001$) inverse correlation between the circulating levels of heavy metals including Cr and lung function (FEV1/FVC %, predicted). As well, the levels of blood heavy metals including Cr were significantly ($p<.001$) and negatively correlated with plasma GST activity and GSH level in COPD patients. Valdés et al. (2012) collected air pollution in a residential area of Santiago, Chile, and obtained daily mortality counts from the National Institute of Statistic. The associations between PM2.5 and cause-specific mortality were studied. Significant effects of PM2.5 on all the causes were found. The strongest effects were

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detected for the two-day average and all respiratory mortality with a 1.75 % increase (95 % CI 1.01-2.49) and for COPD mortality with 1.94 % increase (0.63-3.27) per 10 μ g/m³ increase in PM_{2.5}. Particles with high content of Cr showed strong associations with respiratory and COPD mortality. Cr modified the association between PM_{2.5} and death from all respiratory diseases. A 10 μ g/m³ increase in the two-day average of PM_{2.5} and an interquartile range (IQR) increase in monthly average of Cr concentration/PM_{2.5} was associated with increases of 3.35 % (95 % CI 1.90-4.83) in all respiratory mortality.

17.2.8 Mercury

For Hg exposure and development of decreased pulmonary function or COPD the results seem to be highly controversial and not widely enough researched. In a study by Gogoi et al. (2019) lung function (FEV₁/FVC% predicted) and blood Hg level showed statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) inverse correlation among coal mine workers already diagnosed with COPD. Furthermore, the GST activity and GSH levels were negatively correlated ($p < 0.01$) among the COPD patients. In a review by Skalny et al. (2020), inconclusive evidence on the Hg exposure to respiratory diseases were presented, however the studies focused mainly on asthma rather than COPD. The authors concluded that data on Hg exposure and pulmonary function is clearly insufficient.

Heo et al. (2017) examined 152 adult participants living in a dusty area in Korea, and the possible association between Hg, Cd and Cr exposure from inhalation and COPD. From the 152 participants, 111 were diagnosed to have obstructive lung disease during the follow-up time of one year. The authors concluded that there was significant association between post-bronchodilator FEV₁ and Hg concentration after adjusting for age, gender and smoking status ($p = 0.03$).

However, there was no significant association between post-bronchodilator FEV₁/FVC ratio and Hg level. In an Indonesian case-control study artisanal- and small-scale gold mining workers were examined for lung function (FEV₁ and FVC) and measured for the level of Hg in nasal and scalp hair samples. In the areas with high occupational exposure and higher atmospheric Hg, the Hg levels were significantly higher in cases in comparison to the control group. However, against the hypothesis, a negative correlation was revealed between the lung function and Hg exposure levels (Pateda et al., 2018). For children no association was found between the Hg exposure and development of COPD (Pan et al., 2020), or wheezing (Miyake et al., 2011).

17.2.9 Arsenic

Arsenic exposure has been identified to have several different kinds of lung effects, such as bronchiectasis (Mazumder et al., 2005), cough, (Guo et al., 2003) and declined pulmonary functions (De et al., 2004; Parvez et al., 2013). A study by Smith et al. (2006) investigated two distinct periods of high arsenic exposure in Chile in young adults and after exposure in utero and early childhood. COPD mortality, bronchiectasis standardised mortality ratio, increased for both men and women, especially for those born in the high-exposure period, 1958–1970 (women: SMR = 50.1, 95% CI, 20.0–103, $p < 0.001$; men: SMR = 36.4, 95% CI, 4.1–132; $p = 0.001$). In animal studies, in utero and postnatal exposure of As has been linked to altered pulmonary structure and functions (Lantz et al., 2009).

Another study revealed chronic As poisoning from drinking water to decrease pulmonary functions, mainly causing obstructive symptoms, and worsened with the increase of the exposure (De et al., 2004). A large cohort ($n = 20\,033$) examined As exposure from drinking water, revealing lower levels of FEV₁ and FVC measurements discovered by every standard deviation increase in baseline with As exposure (-46.5 ml, $p < 0.0005$ and -53.1 ml, $p < 0.01$). A dose-related decrease in

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pulmonary functions was related to increasing levels of baseline water and urinary As (Parvez et al., 2013).

In a NHANES study 2003-2006, 5 365 participants were examined for their urinary As level and examined for association of COPD prevalence. Male sex, age and non-white race were associated with increased urinary As, however association between urinary As and COPD was not demonstrated in this study (Amster et al., 2011). In the next cycle of NHANES studies, 2007-2012, Shih et al. (2019) investigated exposure by assessing urinary total As and dimethylarsonic acid (DMA) and pulmonary functions (FEV1 and FVC). The authors concluded that As exposure was related to increased risk of airway inflammation, however there was limited evidence of an association in relation to lung function (Shih et al., 2019).

Children's exposure to As was examined a cohort study in Bangladesh. As exposure was measured from urine during mother's early pregnancy, at 4.5 years of age and at 9 years. At the 9-year check-up point spirometry was conducted to assess lung function and airway inflammation was measured by NIOX MINO system. Additionally, blood samples of CRP and Clara cell secretory protein (CC16) were collected. The urinary levels at 9 years old were lower than at prenatal stage from mother's urine sample (median 53 micrograms/l vs 76 micrograms/l). Decreased FEV1 and FVC measurements were found in relation to increased urinary arsenic levels, suggesting that prenatal and early childhood exposure may reduce lung function in children (Ahmed et al., 2017). In a prospective cohort study, high exposure group (in utero and early life exposure to As through drinking water) was examined in comparison to group with low exposure. At the age of 14 to 26 years, the young adults were examined for lung function (FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio) and interviewed for respiratory symptoms. Male participants from the exposure group showed significant declined respiratory FVC results (-95 ml, p=0.04). All exposed participants showed increased dry cough and asthma symptoms (Khan et al., 2020).

According to a systematic review by Sanchez et al. (2016) 29 studies were identified focusing on inorganic As and different respiratory outcomes (lung function, symptoms, acute respiratory infections, chronic non-malignant lung diseases, and non-malignant lung disease mortality). The review concluded that there is consistent evidence of InAs exposure and its association with decrease in lung function (most commonly FVC) and increase in coughing and breathing problems. For infancy and childhood, in utero exposure was associated with increased number and severity of respiratory tract infections, and in childhood also respiratory symptoms seem to increase (Sanchez et al., 2016). In a meta-analysis of As exposure and lung functions, Sanchez et al. (2018) aimed to assess exposure-relationship, however a meta-analysis was not possible to conduct due to wide range of As exposure levels and differences in cut off points between the studies. The authors concluded that according to the nine studies included, As exposure was associated with restrictive impairments based on inverse associations between As FEV1 and FVC, whilst not with FEV1/FVC ratio.

17.2.10 Lead

In a large cross-sectional KNHANES study (n=53 829) COPD, blood Pb levels, smoking status and other risk factors were evaluated. Smoking status, occupation, education level, older age and male sex were independently associated with higher Pb levels, whilst COPD was discovered not to be related after adjusting for all confounding factors, suggesting that higher Pb levels in COPD can be attributed to smoking status, education level and occupation, rather than COPD itself (Lee et al., 2020). In a NHANES study between 2007 and 2010, pooled cross-sectional data was gathered to assess obstructive lung disease using FEV1/FVC ratio (<0.7 by spirometry) and adjusting for smoking. Pb concentration was significantly higher among participants with obstructive lung

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disease in comparison to the control group (1.73 vs. 1.18, $p < 0.01$) (Rokadia & Agarwal, 2013). In a similar pooled cross-sectional KNHANES study, 5 972 subjects between 2008 and 2012 were examined by using the FEV1/FVC ratio. The ratio was lower in the highest quartile group of Pb in comparison to the lowest quartile (78.4% vs 79.0%, $p=0.025$). FEV1 and FVC was higher in the three higher quartiles (2, 3 and 4) compared to the lowest group (quartile 1), however there was no significant dose-relationship. The Pb concentration were adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and smoking. (Leem et al., 2015). Interestingly, Ibrahimou et al. (2019) further examined the interaction of blood Pb level and COPD on risk of heart attack or stroke. The authors discovered a significant interaction between both COPD and the level of Pb on the occurrence of heart attack (OR= 0.26, 95% CI 0.12-0.56) and stroke (OR= 0.44, 95% CI 0.12-1.0) (Ibrahimou et al., 2019).

A few studies were found to focus on children, Pb exposure and pulmonary functions. The outcomes in the studies varied. One study found focused on children, and the possible effects of Pb, Hg and Cd on healthy children's pulmonary functions. FEV1 and FVC measurements and questionnaire data were acquired, and blood samples were drawn from the participants. The results revealed only blood Pb level to have a negative association with the pulmonary functions (Pan et al., 2020). In China, preschool age children's blood Pb and Cd levels were measured and compared to lung function (FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio) in area exposed to high amounts of e-waste as well as a control area. The Pb levels were higher among the children living in the exposed area ($p<0.05$), and blood hemoglobin and hematocrit levels were lower in comparison to the control area. Notably, children exposed to the Pb e-waste had lower FEV1 (92 ml) and FVC (86ml) lung function levels in comparison to the control area ($p<0.05$) (Zeng et al., 2017). In a NHANES study, 1234 6-17 year-olds' urine and blood samples were investigated for Cd, cobalt (Co), manganese (Mn) and Pb exposure and pulmonary function measures (FEV1, FVC and FEV1/FVC ratio).

Exposures were categorised into quartiles based on the concentrations. Urinary Pb was inversely associated with pulmonary function tests (mid-exhalation forced expiratory flow rate 25-75% millilitres per second, $p=0.01$) (Madrigal et al., 2018). Little et al. (2017) from Poland used shuttle run test to investigate pulmonary function and agility, revealing blood Pb to be inversely associated with FVC. These contradictory findings could be since studies on children's pulmonary diseases have mainly focused on asthma, and rarely thus far in pulmonary function measurements. Additionally, cut-off points, outcomes and measurement methods have varied between the studies. In Table 22 joint heavy metal studies focusing on COPD and declined lung function are presented.

Table 22: Joint heavy metal studies focusing on COPD and declined lung function

Authors and year	Heavy metal	Outcome measured	Population studied	Results
Skalny et al., 2020	As, Cd, Hg, Pb	Review article, outcomes varied	Review article, study designs and populations varied	As, Cd, Hg and Pb exposure was associated with respiratory dysfunction and respiratory diseases (COPD, bronchitis).
Gogoi et al., 2019	Cd, Pb, Hg, Cr	FEV1/FVC ratio, plasma GST activity and GSH level	COPD patients of coal mine site (N=93) and healthy controls (N=85)	The blood levels of heavy metals (Cd, Pb, Hg, Cr) were significantly higher in COPD patients of coal mine site compared to the healthy controls. The levels of these heavy metals in COPD patients were

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Authors and year	Heavy metal	Outcome measured	Population studied	Results
				significantly and negatively correlated with lung function, plasma GST activity, and GSH level. (GST and GSH are two primary antioxidant molecules playing an important role in the reduction of cellular oxidative stress).
Heo et al., 2017	Hg, Cd, Cr	FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio	152 subjects from a cohort study, of which 111 COPD-patients and 41 healthy controls	A significant association between post-bronchodilator FEV1 and serum Hg level after adjusting for age, gender and smoking status (p=0.03). Following the adjustment, a significant higher prevalence of OLD in subjects in the highest Hg concentration tertile (p=0.03). The risk of OLD was significantly higher for subjects in the higher Hg concentration (OR 3.62, CI 95% 1.29-10.18) than in those in the lowest tertile. No statistically significant associations between the OLD subjects and controls regarding Cd or Cr levels.
Pan et al., 2020	Pb, Hg, Cd	FEV1, FVC, percent-predicted FEV1/FVC	221 healthy children	A significant positive interaction found between the blood Pb and Cd levels on FVC ($\beta = 13.11$, $P = 0.03$), percent-predicted FVC ($\beta = 15.18$, $P = 0.04$), and percent-predicted FEV1 ($\beta = 3.90$, $P = 0.03$). Meanwhile, a borderline statistically significant positive interaction was also observed between the blood Pb and Hg levels on FEV1 ($\beta = 12.07$, $P = 0.09$). Although causal relationship was not confirmed, at least higher levels of Pb in blood were associated with decreased pulmonary parameters in children.
Leem et al., 2015	Cd, Pb	FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio	Cross-sectional data from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2008-2012 (N=5 972) among general population	The forced expiratory volume in 1 second/forced vital capacity (FEV1/FVC) ratio lower in the highest quartile group of Pb (78.4% vs. 79.0%; $P=0.025$) and Cd (78.3% vs. 79.2%; $P < 0.001$) concentrations, compared with those in the lowest quartile groups. An inverse relationship between the FEV1/FVC ratio and

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Authors and year	Heavy metal	Outcome measured	Population studied	Results
				concentrations of Pb (estimated - 0.002; P=0.007) and Cd (estimated -0.005; P=0.001). Among current smokers, the risk of obstructive lung function (OLF) higher in subjects in the highest quartile group of Cd concentration than in those in the lowest quartile group (OR 1.94; 95% CI 1.06-3.57).
Rokadia & Agarwal, 2013	Cd, Pb	Full information not available	Cross-sectional data from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2007-2010	Mean (SE) Cd levels in the obstructive lung disease (OLD) group significantly higher in comparison with normal control subjects (0.51 [1.04] vs. 0.33 [1.02], P < .001). Mean (SE) serum Pb concentration significantly higher in the OLD group compared with the control population (1.73 [1.02] vs. 1.18 [1.0], P < .001). The association between OLD and smoking significantly attenuated after adjusting for serum Cd concentration.
Madrigal et al., 2018	Cd, Co, Mn, Pb	FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio, FEF	NHANES 2011-2012 survey cycle of 6-17 years old (N=1 234).	Urinary Pb was inversely associated with FEF 25–75% (p for trend = 0.01).
Zeng et al., 2017	Pb, Cd	FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio	Cross-sectional study design, a case-control study. 5-7 year-old children (N=206; 100 cases, 106 controls)	Preschool children living in electronic waste (e-waste) exposed areas had 1.37 µg/dL increase in blood Pb and 1.18 µg/L increase in blood Cd. 92 mL decrease in FVC and 86 mL decrease in FEV1. Each unit of hemoglobin (1 g/L) decline was associated with 5 mL decrease in FVC and 4 mL decrease in FEV1. In conclusion the children living in e-waste exposed area had higher levels of blood-Pb and -Cd and lower levels of lung function.

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17.2.11 Diisocyanates

Diisocyanate exposure to (occupational) asthma has been widely recognised global challenge (Baur et al., 2012; Latza et al., 2005). However, thus far less focus has been placed on COPD or relating symptoms (bronchitis, emphysema, obstructive ventilation patterns/functions). Most of the studies identified from the literature examined diisocyanate exposure and COPD on occupational settings. Vandenplas et al. (1999) examined short-term and low exposure pulmonary effects of toluene diisocyanate (TDI) on asymptomatic adults. The results revealed short-term exposure to possibly cause noticeable changes in airway calibre and epithelial permeability.

Among occupational workers in cushion manufactory a two-year cohort study was conducted to assess long-term exposure to TDI. The study population was divided into three different exposure subgroups (≤ 0.0015 ; $0.0020-0.0030$ and ≥ 0.0035 ppm), revealing the workers with exposure to TDI over 0.003 pm to possibly be in danger of chronic pulmonary dysfunction loss (Wegman et al., 1977). For spray-painting workers, hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) was assessed for respiratory symptoms such as chest tightness, asthma-like symptoms and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease-like symptoms. The authors provided evidence of exposure to HDI and respiratory symptoms revealing an exposure-response relationship (prevalence ratios for interquartile range increased in exposure for chest-tightness 2.0, asthma-like symptoms 1.2 and obstructive pulmonary disease-like symptoms 1.3, $p \leq 0.05$) (Pronk et al., 2007). Similar results were found also among other spray-painters (Glindmeyer et al., 2004). Another occupational risk group has been identified to be cork workers, as a significant correlation ($p \leq 0.05$) was found between lengths of exposure and decreased pulmonary function (Alegre et al., 1990).

A long cohort study (1971-1999) was conducted to assess occupational exposure to inorganic dust, gases (including isocyanates), irritants, fumes, diesel exhaust and wood dust and incidence and increased mortality from COPD. An increased mortality from COPD was discovered with any airborne exposures (RR 1.12 (95% CI 1.03-1.22)). All the analyses were adjusted for age and smoking, which further revealed an increases mortality of COPD even among non-smokers (Bergdahl et al., 2004). Another cohort study examining foam manufacturing workers concluded that high exposure level of TDI (over 30 ppb peak exposure) showed larger average annual losses of pulmonary function and might be contributing to obstructive pulmonary function changes in the workers (Omae et al., 1992). As presented, all the studies found focused on occupational exposure rather than general population. In addition, GSH has been shown to protect the lung tissue against hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) exposure (Wisnewski et al., 2005).

One systematic review was found focusing on occupational asthma and COPD and environmental chemicals including diisocyanates (Baur et al., 2012). Notably, the authors stated that the most studies found did not straight forwardly focus on COPD, but on CB and emphysema which may be indicative of COPD. Nonetheless, isocyanate exposure was seen to be associated with occupational COPD symptoms, however currently still underreported.

17.3 Highlights

Respiratory irritants are major causes of occupational obstructive airway diseases. Of the HBM4EU priority substances especially pesticides and heavy metals of cadmium, arsenic and lead were shown to have adverse health effects on pulmonary function.

Environmental chemical exposure studies and their association to COPD among general population have thus far focused mainly on certain chemicals, such as heavy metal exposure. For occupational studies more literature was available among different chemicals, however certain substances such as heavy metals and pesticides were more examined than others. All of the

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studies identified used spirometry in the examination of the pulmonary outcomes (FEV1, FVC, FEV1/FVC ratio) and some studies even provided further details about the methodology and examination settings. In several studies, COPD was not set as a primary health outcome per se, but rather the focus was on symptoms of COPD (cough, decreased pulmonary function), from which the authors concluded the possible association to decreased pulmonary function and furthermore into COPD. Additionally, most studies had analysed the results taking into consideration the possible confounding factors, such as smoking and age. Studies focusing on heavy metals tend to be joined evaluations, however the possible effects of mixed chemical exposure risks are not addressed. Although some chemicals showed strong association of exposure and COPD, more research in wider perspective is required in order to raise awareness of the putative harmful effects of the environmental substances in relation to pulmonary function and respiratory diseases.

The evidence provided in this chapter highlights the need for further examination of both general and occupational exposures and their association to chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.

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18 Skin irritation and inflammation

Author: Haverinen Elsi (THL)

The skin is the body's largest organ, accounting for over 10% of the total body mass. Skin diseases are major medical conditions globally and cause significant burden to patients, their families and to the societies (Seth et al. 2017). In 2013, skin and subcutaneous diseases were responsible for 41.6 million disability-adjusted life years (DALY) (1.8%) and 39 million years lived with disability (YLD) (Karimkhani et al., 2017). The most influencing skin diseases were atopic, contact and seborrheic dermatitis, acne vulgaris and urticaria. Dermatitis resulted in greatest burden, causing 9.3 million disability-adjusted life years (Karimkhani et al., 2017). At global level, skin diseases were the fourth leading causes of nonfatal disease burden resulting to have enormous disease burden in both low- and high-income countries (Hay et al., 2014; Karimkhani et al., 2017).

Inflammation is defined as a continuation of protective and regenerative responses of the skin (Dainichi et al., 2014). Skin inflammations are caused by several different factors, such as pathogens (bacteria, viruses or fungi), external injuries (scrapes, puncture wound of foreign object), and effects of chemicals or radiation. According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (2020) chemical agents are commonly divided into irritants and sensitisers. Irritants act directly on the skin through chemical reactions, as sensitisers might not cause immediate reaction, but during continuous exposure can cause allergic reactions (CDC, 2020). In Table 23 different factors contributing to development of skin irritation by Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety (2021) are presented.

Skin diseases and chemical exposure affects mostly certain industries and occupational workers, thus most of the chemical exposure and dermal studies have been conducted in the field of occupational health. Dermal exposure at work places can occur through direct contact, deposition of aerosols, immersion or splashes on the skin (Anderson & Meade, 2014).

Table 23: Different factors contributing to development of skin irritation by Canadian Centre for Occupational Health and Safety (2021).

Related to chemical	Related to person	Related to environment
Properties of the chemical solubility form (gas, liquid, solid) concentration length of the exposure frequency of the exposure	Skin location (hands, arms, face etc.) skin condition (intact, rashes, abrasions) dryness sweating age genetic background	temperature humidity and moisture barometric pressure friction contamination

18.1 Atopic and contact dermatitis

Atopic dermatitis (AD) is the most common type of eczema, usually starting as early as from six months of age but can occur at any life stage. AD causes strong and visible skin inflammation and epidermal barrier disruption, is chronic and tends to flare periodically (Wong et al., 2017). It may be accompanied by asthma or hay fever. Association between the prevalence of contact dermatitis and both age and sex has been observed (Rubins et al., 2020).

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Contact dermatitis is an inflammation of the skin, caused by external agents. The two main types are irritant contact dermatitis (ICD) and allergic contact dermatitis (ACD). ICD is caused by direct damage to the skin by chemicals or other irritant agents and does not require prior sensitisation (Tan et al., 2014). In contrary, allergic contact dermatitis is caused by sensitisation to a certain chemical, causing allergic reaction on the skin which has been already previously sensitised (CDC, 2020; Tan et al., 2014). Notably, airborne contact dermatitis can result in both ICD and ACD, and is most often seen in occupational chemical exposures (Tan et al., 2014). For occupational exposure, contact dermatitis is the most common type of skin disorder, accounting in the USA for over 90% of all occupational skin defects (Anderson & Meade, 2014). According to Rubins et al. (2020) rubber gloves are a major cause of occupational ACD in healthcare workers and occupations involving frequent handwashing have shown an increased incidence in cumulative ICD. The prevalence of occupational hand dermatitis among workers that reported handwashing frequency over 35 times per shift was 69.7% (Rubins et al., 2020).

18.2 Urticaria

The World Allergy Organisation has defined urticaria as *“a transient erythematous swelling of the skin, associated with itching, which usually resolves within 24 hours. It is caused by degranulation of histamine containing cells (mast cells) in the superficial dermis.”* Urticaria is commonly classified according to the symptom duration into acute or chronic. Acute urticaria should be present for less than six weeks as chronic form is everything over six weeks. Acute condition is highly prevalent among children and adults and is most commonly caused by an allergic reaction of ingested food or contact on the skin. There are several other forms of urticaria, from non-specific stimuli to cold-dependent disorders, pressure-induced urticaria, solar urticaria and chronic spontaneous urticaria. (World Allergy Organisation, 2019). The symptoms between urticaria and ACD can be very similar, affecting the diagnoses between these two conditions (Anderson & Meade, 2014).

18.3 Measurement methods

Skin diseases are challenging to diagnose and different scoring systems are used to evaluate the severity of the disease. There has been discussion about the accuracy of detecting skin conditions by using different scoring systems; however no conclusive scale has yet been adopted. Most often clinicians and researchers use the Simple Scoring System (SSS), the Scoring Atopic Dermatitis (SCORAD) index, Eczema Area and Severity Index (EASI), the Basic Clinical Scoring System (BCSS), and the patient-oriented SCORAD index (Sprickelman et al., 1997; Stalder et al., 2011; Schmitt et al., 2013). The European Task Force on Atopic Dermatitis has suggested the use of SCORAD index (Kunz et al., 1997; Severity scoring of atopic dermatitis: the SCORAD index, 1993) which provides a cumulative index combining objective and subjective criteria.

The SCORAD scores the extent, six intensity criteria, and subjective symptoms of AD. The extent is assessed by using a front-back drawing of inflammatory lesions. The intensity criteria are assessed from absent to severe on erythema, edema/papulation, oozing/crust, excoriation, lichenification, and dryness. Subjective symptoms such as pruritus and sleep loss are evaluated from the last 3 days and nights, and all are scored by the patients or in case of children less than 7 years of age, by the parent. Finally, the total score for the severity of the atopic dermatitis is mathematically assessed as the sum of the scores for extent, intensity, and subjective symptoms concluding at the maximum score at 100.

Patch testing is used on patients with dermatitis to conclude whether the skin condition may be caused by contact allergy, hypersensitivity or mucosal conditions. According to the European Society of Contact Dermatitis guidelines (2015) diagnostic patch testing should be done in cases of

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suspected contact dermatitis, acute or chronic, other types of dermatitis and skin and mucous membrane eruptions (Johansen et al., 2015).

ICD-codes can be used to retrieve information on skin irritation and inflammatory diseases. The codes for ICD-10 are presented in Table 24.

Table 24: ICD-10 codes for skin diseases (WHO, 2019, ICD-10)

ICD-10 codes for skin diseases	More detailed ICD-10 codes for dermatitis and eczema	More detailed ICD-10 codes for urticaria and erythema
L00-L08 Infections of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	L20 Atopic dermatitis	L49 Exfoliation due to erythematous conditions according to extent of body surface involved
L10-L14 Bullous disorders	L21 Seborrheic dermatitis	L50 Urticaria
L20-L30 Dermatitis and eczema	L22 Diaper dermatitis	L51 Erythema multiforme
L40-L45 Papulosquamous disorders	L23 Allergic contact dermatitis	L52 Erythema nodosum
L49-L54 Urticaria and erythema	L24 Irritant contact dermatitis	L53 Other erythematous conditions
L55-L59 Radiation-related disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	L25 Unspecified contact dermatitis	L54 Erythema in diseases classified elsewhere
L60-L75 Disorders of skin appendages	L26 Exfoliative dermatitis	
L76-L76 Intraoperative and postprocedural complications of skin and subcutaneous tissue	L27 Dermatitis due to substances taken internally	
L80-L99 Other disorders of the skin and subcutaneous tissue	L28 Lichen simplex chronicus and prurigo	
	L29 Pruritus	
	L30 Other and unspecified dermatitis	

The upcoming ICD-11 codes for skin disorders provoked by external factors are (WHO ICD-11, 2020):

- EK00 Allergic contact dermatitis
- EK01 Photo-allergic contact dermatitis
- EK02 Irritant contact dermatitis
- EK10 Allergic contact urticaria
- EK11 Protein contact dermatitis
- EK12 Allergic contact sensitisation
- EH90 Pressure ulceration
- EH92 Dermatoses provoked by friction or mechanical stress
- EH93 Dermatoses due to foreign bodies
- Dermatoses provoked or exacerbated by exposure to cold
- Dermatoses provoked by heat or electricity
- Dermatoses provoked by light or UV radiation
- Dermatoses due to ionising radiation

For ICPC, the codes for skin diseases and disorders are between S01 and S99. The most relevant concerning HBM studies are S87 dermatitis/atopic eczema, S88 dermatitis contact/allergic and S98 urticaria (WONCA, 2016).

HBM4EU standardised questions on skin irritation can be found in Appendix 22.2.

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18.4 Environmental chemicals associated with skin irritation/inflammation

Environmental chemical exposure is one of the most common exposure sources for skin irritation and inflammation, and especially industrial occupational workers not wearing sufficient Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) might be exposed. There is a substantial risk for skin exposure in many work settings, but such exposure is challenging to quantify and continues to be underappreciated (Bello et al., 2007).

18.4.1 Chromium (VI)

Chromium has been considered one of the most important contact allergens among general population, concluding in a prevalence of 1-3% (Thyssen & Menné, 2010; Hedberg, 2020). Previously one of the most apparent exposers to chromium has been cement, however after the legislation restrictions (European Legislation on chromium (VI) in cement 82003/53/EC) the number of exposure has decreased, and currently, leather products are one of the main sources of chromium (Thyssen et al., 2009). In 2015, European Union set a new directive on Cr VI and leather application (Commission regulation (EU) No.301/2014). Additionally, the presence of Cr VI in tattoo inks has been associated to ACD (Bocca et al., 2018).

Among Danish population, a total of 13379 adults between years 2002-2017 were patch tested for chromium allergy, revealing a prevalence of 2.2%. The temporal decrease between the study years was explained by the implementation of the EU directive on Cr VI leather goods (Alinaghi et al., 2019). A case-study from Sweden, described 4 out of 24 workers working on plant manufacturing concrete wall panels and beams, to have contact allergy, despite the chromate regulation on cement (Mowitz et al., 2016).

In Sweden, 6482 participants were patch tested towards Cr VI, resulting with 233 positive patch tests (3.6%). The Cr VI allergy increased with age, as participants over 40 years of age had higher prevalence of allergy in comparison to under 40 year olds ($p=0.006$). Additionally, ACD was significantly higher among Cr VI allergic patients. (Lejding et al., 2018). In Israel, occupational ACD was analysed among 4846 patients, revealing 146 (3%) of the participants to suffer from Cr VI sensitivity. The participants showed most signs on the hands, and the symptoms seemed to be highly persistent even after a change of occupation (Kridin et al., 2016).

A few case-studies have reported different occupational and leisure time exposures to Cr VI, one case-study reported an electroplating worker's dermal exposure to chromium to cause chemical burn of the skin (15% of body surface) and multiple organ failure (Lin et al., 2009). Another case-study reported outbreak of papules and vesicles at both hands and feet discovering the exposure route to be Cr VI used on leather shoes (Hedberg et al., 2020).

18.4.2 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) have been shown to cause both short- and long-term effects on the skin. Especially, anthracene, benzo(a)pyrene and naphthalene have been reported as skin irritants, and anthracene and benzo(a)pyrene have been reported also as skin sensitizers (Unwin et al., 2006; ICPS, 2010; Kim et al., 2013). Naphthalene has been shown to cause redness and inflammation on the skin (Srogi, 2007). Dermal contact most often happens indoors through use of mothballs and outdoors from car exhaust, food and fossil fuel combustion (Preuss et al., 2003). According to NIH (2021) benzo(a)pyrene can cause a skin rash, a burning feeling, skin color changes and warts.

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Increased inhalation and dermal occupational exposure to PAHs have been shown in professions working in different industries, such as asphalt workers (Fustinoni et al., 2010; Väänänen et al., 2005), coke- (VanRooij et al., 1993), oil-, wood-, rubber- and foundry-workers (Unwin et al., 2006). The level of dermal absorption differed between the locations, occupations and industries. Additionally, Qiao et al. (2017) discovered in a reasonably new study PAH compound SRM1649b, a well-known air pollutant, to induce cell aging on the skin. Väänänen et al. (2005) point out that one of the challenges of occupational dermal investigations is the lack of standardised techniques for assessing skin exposure. Most commonly three techniques are used; surrogate skin techniques (pads and patch testing), removal techniques (such as handwashing) and fluorescent tracer techniques.

18.4.3 Anilines

The European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) has classified 4,4'-methylenedianiline to be skin sensitising (ECHA, 2021). Two studies were found to examine 4,4'-methylenedianiline (TGMDA) and dermal exposure among different populations. In a study by Uter et al. (2006) 25 out of 1119 patients showed patch test reaction to aniline. From the 25 positive patch tests, 18 had been diagnosed previously with ACD. Most commonly the participants showed signs of ACD in hands, legs and face. Another study examined occupational exposure to Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-methylenedianiline (TGMDA) among aircraft industry workers, revealing all 9 participants to show allergic contact dermatitis on patch testing to TGMDA (Pesonen et al., 2015).

P- phenylenediamine (PPD) is an irritant causing frequently symptoms in hair dressers and people handling temporary tattoos (Rubins et al., 2020). According to estimation, the average prevalence of dermatitis due to PPD was found to be 4.0% among Europeans (Thyssen et al., 2008).

18.4.4 Acrylamide

According to the European Commission's report on Recommendation from the Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits for acrylamide (2012) case-reports have reported skin effects such as rashes, peeling and acne-like dermatitis from acrylamide exposure. Peeling has been most commonly detected in the palms of the hands. In a case study by Kim et al. (2017) two Korean grouting workers were exposed to acrylamide during construction work, leading to severe dermal absorption and further to neurological symptoms. Hagmar et al. (2001) conducted a study on acrylamide exposure on 210 tunnel workers, exposed for over 2 months for acrylamide and N-methylolacrylamide while grouting. Ten of the workers showed dermatitis on their hands, 8 having ICD and 2 ACD. One worker showed skin sensitisation to N-methylolacrylamide. The workers who were highly exposed reported a high prevalence of symptoms, such as eye irritation and respiratory tract irritation.

18.4.5 Aprotic Solvents

Dermal exposure to solvents is the most common exposure route. Solvents may also enhance the penetration of other chemicals by disrupting the protective lipid layer of the skin (Anderson & Meade, 2014). Research on occupational and general population have focused on N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP), N-ethylpyrrolidin-2-one (NEP), N,N-dimethylacetamide (DMAC), and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF).

Studies show that skin absorption of NMP may contribute significantly to the overall uptake of NMP (Bader et al., 2005; Ligocka et al., 2003). In a Norwegian factory 10 out of 12 workers showed ACD after two days of working with NMP (Leira et al., 1992). No other studies on aprotic solvents and skin effects were found.

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18.4.6 Arsenic

Arsenic is widely used as an ingredient in variety of products in manufacturing industries, i.e. wood preservatives, herbicides, insecticides, pesticides, fungicides and semi-conductors and thus making especially industrial workplaces a source of inhalation and dermal exposure to arsenic. In addition to occupational exposure, even bigger exposure source remains on ground water, exposing people globally (Petrusevski et al., 2007).

Skin is a sensitive organ towards arsenic intake, and skin lesions are one of the most common and earliest signs of chronic As exposure (Yoshida et al., 2004) Among 752 participants in Kurdistan province in Iran the total lifetime intake of arsenic from drinking water was calculated, revealing 49 persons (6.5%) suffered from skin condition called hyperkeratosis and 20 persons (2.7%) from hyperpigmentation ($R=0.325$, $p<0.01$) (Mosaferi et al., 2008). A review by Yoshida et al. (2004) investigated dose-response relationship and skin effects among exposed populations. In their review they concluded several non-malignant skin conditions such as lesions, hyperpigmentation, Keratosis, skin signs and unexplained skin rashes to be related with As exposure (Borgono et al., 1977; Valentine et al., 1992; Valentine et al., 1992; Tsuda et al., 1995; Mazumder et al., 1998; Tondel et al., 1999; Guo et al., 2001).

18.4.7 Diisocyanates

Diisocyanates are used in polyurethane production and are usually divided into two types, aromatic diisocyanates and aliphatic diisocyanates. The aromatic diisocyanates are toluene diisocyanate (TDI) used for production of flexible foams, and methylenediphenyl diisocyanate (MDI) used in polyurethane products like coatings, adhesives and water resistant materials (American Chemistry Council, 2021). Diisocyanate exposure has been previously linked to asthma, and Bello et al. (2007) note that skin exposure in addition to inhalation might be a potential exposure source to develop isocyanate asthma.

A study by Kieć-Świerczyńska et al. (2014) assessed chemical sensitisation and outbreak of contact dermatitis among vehicle equipment factory workers to polyurethane foam based on 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI). From 300 workers, 21 persons showed signs of ACD, ICD or a combination of ACD and ICD.

In another study, over a 13-year period, patients were tested from different occupations to react to diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI), 2,4-toluene diisocyanate (TDI), isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) and the metabolite 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA). The most affected occupational groups were motor vehicle-, electronic-, paint- and construction workers. The numbers of tested people varied between the substances from 124 to 780. In total, 53 participants reacted to some of the substances tested for, in more detail, 44 to MDA, 12 to MDI, 9 to IPDI, 6 to TDI, and 1 to HDI (Aalto-Korte et al., 2012.).

A study in Sweden and Belgium investigated 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate (MDI), its corresponding amine 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (MDA) among 6190 company workers. Only a small number of participants (5 in Sweden and none in Belgium) showed positive patch testing towards MDI, however 18 Belgian participants showed positive reaction towards MDA, and 5 from the Swedish participants (Engfeldt et al., 2012).

Additionally, in a case-study of Militello et al. (2004) ACD was detected among sculptors to diphenylmethane diisocyanate and isophorone diisocyanate and a second case report of a 40-year old housewife reported severe pruritic erythema and per-orbital oedema in the upper body after 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate exposure (Morgan & Haworth, 2003).

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18.4.8 Pesticides

According to Arcury et al. (2007) inflammatory skin diseases are highly prevalent among farmworkers. The most common skin defects detected were infectious diseases, inflammatory diseases, pigmentary disorders and skin traumas. The number of inflammatory cases decreased with age, while infectious diseases increased with higher age. Another study examined 366 banana plantation workers, from which 37 participants were identified as possibly having a work related dermatoses by using a questionnaire, and further 15 of the 37 workers showed positive patch test results to different pesticides (5 carbaryl positive patch tests, 4 benomyl, 3 ethoprophos, 2 chlorothalonil, 2 imazalil, 2 glyphosate, 2 thiabendazole, 1 chlorpyrifos, 1 oxyfluorfen, 1 propiconazole, and 1 tridemorph) (Penagos et al., 2004). Another study among similar population revealed 27.8% positive patch tests among the workers (Penagos, 2002). For other occupational exposure, a case-study reports contact dermatitis among tobacco farmworkers (Abraham et al., 2007), fruit and vegetable farmers (Verma et al., 2007) and agricultural workers (Sharma et al., 2018). Gamsky et al. (1992) studied Californian farmers and estimated the prevalence of contact dermatitis to be 2% and for lichenified hand dermatitis 13%.

18.5 Highlights

Literature on skin irritation and inflammation has mainly focused on occupational exposure and reporting of case-studies, thus very limited data was found on general population. Another interesting observation is that most of the dermal studies have focused on skin cancer, not on inflammation or irritation and therefore are not included in this review.

19 Cognitive development and neurological disorders

Authors: Elonheimo Hanna (THL), Paalanen Laura (THL)

The human nervous system can be divided into the central nervous system (CNS) and the peripheral nervous system (PNS) (Figure 10). The central nervous system consists of the brain and the spinal cord while the peripheral nervous system connects the central nervous system with receptors and effectors. A vital component of the nervous system is the neuron, a specialised nerve cell for quick transferring of signals over long distances with a highly accurate manner. Together these organs control all the systems of the body. The nervous system receives huge amount of information from a person's surroundings and body. When some or all of the nervous system organs fail, troubles await in moving, speaking, swallowing, breathing or learning. Alterations and problems in memory, senses or mood can follow as well. More than 600 neurologic diseases exist (Brodal, 2004; U.S. National Library of Medicine, 2019).

(Picture Wikipedia, licenced under OpenStax/CC BY (http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0))
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:1201_Overview_of_Nervous_System.jpg. Date last accessed: 2020-06-24

(Picture Wikipedia, under public domain)
https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Nervous_system_diagram.png. Date last accessed: 2020-06-24

Figure 10: Human nervous system

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Brain development is the basis of the neurological development: human brain development is a longstanding process beginning at the third gestational week with the differentiation of the neural progenitor cells. Neural development includes proliferation, migration, differentiation, synaptogenesis, myelination, and apoptosis of the cells. The brain development continues at least until late adolescence, but the most likely scenario is that this process takes place throughout the lifespan. Brain development is influenced by the processes ranging from the molecular events of gene expression to environmental input (Stiles & Jernigan, 2010; Rice & Barone, 2000).

Cognition is a wide term referring to cognitive performance and to mental functioning involved in gaining knowledge and comprehension (Esteban-Cornejo, 2015). Cognition comprises a range of mental processes regarding acquisition, storage, manipulation and retrieval of information. Knowledge and understanding are gained through thought, experience and senses. Cognition entails the mental processes linked with the input and storage of information and how that information is applied in guiding one's behaviour. Having adequate cognitive abilities is essential for everyday functioning and in defining our thoughts and actions; cognition is needed in order to understand the information and world around us and to separate the important messages and cues from the unimportant ones. Cognition derives from the brain and is regulated by distinct brain circuits. A number of brain chemicals are included in regulating cognitive processes including dopamine, noradrenaline (norepinephrine), serotonin, acetylcholine, glutamate and γ -amino-butyric acid (GABA) (Cambridge Cognition, 2015).

Cognitive development is the construction of cognitive abilities, and it includes thought processes, remembering, problem solving and decision-making; all of them developing from childhood through adolescence to adulthood. Areas of cognitive development are e.g. information processing, intelligence, reasoning, language development and memory (Encyclopedia of Children's Health, 2021). Furthermore, psychomotor development is a term covering the changes in a child's cognitive, emotional, motor, and social capacities starting from the beginning of life encompassing fetal and neonatal periods, infancy, childhood, and adolescence (Cioni & Sgandurra, 2013).

19.1 Neurological disorders and associated neurotoxic substances

Neurodevelopmental disorders are manifested as impaired brain development and behavioural, cognitive, and/or physical abnormalities. Behavioural abnormalities in sociability, communication, and/or compulsive activity are sometimes presented (Hsiao et al., 2013). Neurological disorders are characterised as diseases of the central and peripheral nervous system including disorders of the brain, spinal cord, cranial nerves, peripheral nerves, nerve roots, autonomic nervous system, neuromuscular junction and muscles. Common disorders are autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), epilepsy, Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other dementias, cerebrovascular diseases including stroke, migraine and other headache disorders, multiple sclerosis (MS), Parkinson's disease (PD), neuro-infections, brain tumours, traumatic disorders of the nervous system due to head trauma and neurological disorders due to malnutrition (WHO, 2016).

The term brain diseases consist of all neurological, psychiatric and neurosurgical diseases. The origins of the diseases are located in the central or peripheral nervous system and are caused mainly by environmental or psychological factors (Olesen & Leonardi, 2003).

Neurotoxic substances can change the normal activity of the nervous system (ILO, 2011). Strong evidence exists that industrial chemicals spread in the environment are significant contributors behind the neurodevelopmental toxicity (Grandjean & Landrigan, 2006; 2014). The developing human brain is vulnerable to toxic chemical exposure, and significant windows of developmental vulnerability occur in utero, during infancy and early childhood. During these sensitive development

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phases chemicals are more apt to cause permanent brain injury even at low levels of exposure compared to adult brain (Grandjean & Landrigan, 2006; 2014; Rice & Barone, 2000). The various aspects of cognitive development can be adversely influenced by the chemical exposure occurring early in life (Dzwilewski et al., 2015; Freire et al., 2010).

A few industrial chemicals, e.g. lead (Pb), methylmercury (Hg), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), arsenic (As), ethanol and toluene, have been linked with the neurodevelopmental disorders and subclinical brain dysfunction. Another 200 chemicals are identified as causes behind the clinical neurotoxic effects in adults. Many neuro-toxicants are still to be recognised, and systematic testing and tracking of the chemicals seem to be lacking. These neurotoxic chemicals are widely used and spread out in the environment (Grandjean & Landrigan, 2006; 2014).

In adults, neuro-toxicology evaluations concentrate on the nervous system structure and function whereas in children the focus is on the development of the nervous system (Landrigan et al., 2000). Thus, we have divided the structure of the texts so, that neurological disorders are connected to adults and neurological developmental disorders to children. The disorders which usually develop during childhood are introduced first followed by the disorders more common among adults.

To give an overview of the economic impact of the large spectrum of disorders of the brain in Europe, it has been calculated that the total costs of these disorders were €798 billion in 2010; this estimation included 19 major groups of brain disorders. Direct costs constituted the majority of these costs as 37 % of these costs were direct healthcare costs and 23 % of the costs were direct non-medical costs. 40 % of the costs were identified as indirect costs associated with patients' production losses. The estimated costs per person with a disorder from brain varied from €285 for headache to €30 000 for neuromuscular disorder. The European per capita cost of disorders of the brain was €1550 on average, but there were variations between the countries. The overall costs in Europe (and most likely worldwide) are increasing since the estimated total costs of these disorders were €477 billion in 2004 (Gustavsson et al., 2011). In Europe, 23 % of the years of healthy life are lost and 50 % of years lived with disability (YLDs) are caused by brain diseases. Considering the key summary measure of lost health, disability adjusted life years (DALYs), 35 % are due to brain diseases (Olesen & Leonardi, 2003). However, as mentioned, the overarching term of brain disorders includes various disorders summing up to the total cost estimation. Declining trend for burden of disease and DALYs has been observed in neonatal disorders in all ages between the years 1990 and 2019 (percentage change in number of DALYs -32.3 and percentage change in age-standardised DALY rate -32.6), and in children of 0-9 years (-36.2 and -35.4). Conduct disorders in children and adolescents aged 10 to 24 years have increased in their prevalence (24.7 and 4.4). In 75 years and older, both AD (180.0 and 2.6) and PD (153.7 and 6.0) have become more prevalent (GBD 2019 Disease and Injuries Collaborators, 2020).

The neurological disorders introduced in this review are chosen according to the solidity of the evidence based on the literature search conducted.

19.2 Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder

Attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is characterised by a persistent pattern (at least 6 months) of inattention and/or hyperactivity-impulsivity (World Health Organisation, 2019a; World Health Organisation, 2019b). The onset of the disorder is during the developmental period, typically early to mid-childhood.

ADHD is a chronic behavioural disorder with onset in childhood that often persists into adulthood (Ramos-Quiroga, et al., 2013). There are three different types of ADHD: 1) predominantly

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hyperactive/impulsive type, 2) predominantly inattentive type and 3) combined type. ADHD also shows increased comorbidity with other neurodevelopmental disorders and behavioural problems.

Many genetic and environmental factors have been identified as contributing to the risk of ADHD, and the vast majority of cases are multifactorial in origin (Thapar et al., 2016). Certain rare syndromes with genetic origin, however, are characterised by ADHD-like features. Environmental factors, which have been found to be associated with ADHD, include prenatal and perinatal factors such as low birthweight and prematurity, environmental toxins, dietary factors, e.g. deficiency of certain nutrients, and psychosocial factors such as exposure to very severe, early social deprivation.

Assessment of ADHD relies primarily on a clinical interview, including medical and social history, along with the aid of objective measures (Austerman, 2015). The diagnosis is made by a health care provider such as a psychologist, psychiatrist or a pediatrician. A prerequisite for an ADHD diagnosis is that symptoms must be present in at least two settings. The most frequent sources of information are the parents and the school teachers in addition to a patient interview, although the patient interview may not be very reliable among very young children. Diagnostic tools for ADHD assessment, such as the Vanderbilt ADHD Diagnostic Teacher Rating Scale, the Vanderbilt ADHD Diagnostic Parent Rating Scale, Diagnostic Interview for Children and Adolescents (DICA-IV) and the Conners' ADHD Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM)-IV Scales are also available to be used as a part of the diagnosis process. A list of tests and tools for evaluation of cognitive and psychomotor development is available in a previous deliverable (HBM4EU 2019 Deliverable Report D 11.3). The tools based on parents' rating might be the most feasible in Human Biomonitoring studies and/or information on diagnosed ADHD.

The definition of the disorder was added in the 11th revision of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) with diagnosis code 6A05 (World Health Organisation, 2019a). The code used for ADHD in ICD-10 classification is F90.0 (disturbance of activity and attention) (World Health Organisation, 2019c). Regarding the ICPC-2 codes, at least code P81 "hyperkinetic disorder" has been used for ADHD (WONCA, 2016).

For HBM4EU standardised questionnaire includes questions on ADHD, which can be useful in HBM studies (see Appendix 22.2).

Both nonpharmacological and pharmacological treatment is used for ADHD (Caye et al., 2019). Most guidelines recommend behavioral interventions, such as behavioral parent training and social skills training for ADHD, either alone or in combination with medication treatment. However, pharmacological treatment remains the mainstay of ADHD treatment, and a vast majority of children with ADHD receive medication for the disorder at least at some stage.

The global ADHD prevalence has been estimated to be between 2% and 7%, with an average around 5%, based on systematic reviews (Sayal et al., 2018). ADHD is more common in males than females with a ratio of 2–3:1. However, relative under-recognition of ADHD among females may partly explain this sex difference.

In the European Union, the economic burden of ADHD has not been estimated. However, a review including seven studies suggested that ADHD imposes a significant economic burden on multiple public sectors in Europe (Le et al., 2014). The largest cost category was education and was followed by health care costs. The average estimated total costs ranged from €9,860 to €14,483 per child/adolescent with ADHD.

Globally, ADHD was responsible for 491,500 disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) in 2010 (0.02% of total all-cause DALYs) (Erskine et al., 2014). The DALYs consisted solely of years lived with

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disability (YLD) as no evidence of deaths resulting directly from ADHD was found. The global age-standardised DALY rate per 100,000 of the population due to ADHD was 7.1. In Europe, the DALYs for ADHD were 96,625 in 2019 and the rate per 100,000 was 11.4 (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2020).

19.3 Environmental chemicals associated with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder

Studies on the association of ADHD and environmental chemicals have most often been performed in the United States but studies from the European countries and elsewhere also exist.

Reviews and meta-analyses collecting data from the individual studies point to associations of ADHD and several environmental chemicals. The research suggests moderate to high evidence for an association of lead (Pb), phthalates and bisphenol A (BPA) and ADHD. For the association between polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), flame retardants and mercury (Hg) with ADHD the evidence is limited, and the findings can be interpreted as only suggestive of an association. Furthermore, for pesticides, cadmium (Cd) and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs), the evidence for an association with ADHD is low, but justifies further research.

19.3.1 Lead

Two recent reviews have analysed studies on the associations of lead and ADHD. A systematic review which identified 17 studies published between July 2013 and 30 June 2018 (Donzelli et al., 2019) and a systematic review and meta-analysis with 14 studies from years 1980–2017 (Nilsen et al., 2020). The conclusion of both reviews was that there is evidence for an association between Pb exposure and ADHD (Table 25).

Table 25: Studies on Pb and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Donzelli et al., (2019)	Mexico, China, USA, South Korea, Germany, Spain, Belgium, Taiwan, Turkey	N of studies: 17 Setting: 2 cross-sectional, 5 birth cohort studies, 10 case-control studies Target group: exposure assessment to Pb performed during pregnancy or early childhood	12 studies showed positive associations between Pb exposure and ADHD whereas the remaining 5 studies found no association. The conclusion: There is an association between Pb and ADHD and even low levels of Pb raise the risk.
Nilsen & Tulve, (2020)	Countries not indicated in the article.	N of studies: 13 studies on lead Setting: - Target group: Infants, children and adolescents (for lead the participant ages ranged from 3 to 12 years)	The overall OR for Pb exposure being associated with an ADHD diagnosis was 3.39 (90%CI 2.66–4.12, $p < 0.001$). The OR for specific ADHD diagnoses was 4.06 (2.89–5.23, $p < 0.001$). The certainty of the evidence in the ADHD specific and all-symptom meta-analysis was determined to be 'moderate'.

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19.3.2 Phthalates

The association of phthalate/plasticiser exposure and ADHD has been examined in a meta-analysis including five studies and the age range of the participants was 6–18 years (Table 26) (Nilsen et al., 2020). The certainty of the evidence for an association between phthalate/plasticiser exposure and ADHD was moderate. Thereby, the findings suggest that phthalate/plasticiser exposures will likely result in an increase in all ADHD outcomes across both sexes, whether analysed together or separately.

Table 26: Studies on phthalates and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Nilsen & Tulve, (2020)	Countries not indicated in the article.	<p>N of studies: 8 studies on phthalates/plasticisers</p> <p>Setting: -</p> <p>Target group: Infants, children and adolescents (for phthalates/plasticisers the participant ages ranged from 6 to 18 years years)</p>	<p>The OR for an ADHD diagnosis (all subtypes) being associated with phthalates/plasticiser exposure in both sexes was 3.31 (2.59–4.02, $p < 0.0001$). When males and females were evaluated separately, the odds ratio was 3.54 (2.23–4.86, $p < 0.0001$) for males and 3.12 (2.54–3.70, $p < 0.0001$) for females. The certainty of the evidence included in the phthalates/plasticiser meta-analysis when both sexes were combined and when the sexes were separated was 'moderate'. These findings suggest that phthalates/plasticiser exposures will likely result in an increase in all ADHD outcomes.</p>

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19.3.3 Bisphenol A

Three human studies were included in a systematic review on the relationship between early life exposure to bisphenol A (BPA) and hyperactivity, a key diagnostic criterion of ADHD (Table 27) (Rochester et al., 2018). The studies were published between 2016–2010. In addition to the three human studies, the review also included animal studies among which also a meta-analysis was performed. The confidence rating for the evidence of the human studies was moderate. The conclusion based on the integration of animal and human literature was that early exposure to BPA is a presumed health hazard linked to hyperactive behaviors in humans.

Table 27: Studies on BPA and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Rochester et al., (2018)	Spain and USA	N of studies: 3 Setting: - Target group: Exposure during gestation or childhood	The systematic review among human studies found that early BPA exposure is associated with a presumed hazard of hyperactivity in humans. In humans, all three studies showed significant effects of BPA on increased hyperactivity, although there were differences in the sexes and windows of exposure. The meta-analysis part was conducted for animal studies.

19.3.4 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

The association of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and ADHD has been examined in two systematic reviews, one of which also included a meta-analysis (Table 28) (Aghaei et al., 2019; Rezaei et al., 2020).

The meta-analysis consisted of studies, which comprised altogether 2557 children aged 5–15 years (Rezaei et al., 2020). The exposure measurement varied: maternal adduct, cord adduct and metabolite concentration in urine were used. Also the evaluation of the outcome, i.e. ADHD, varied between the studies. The overall OR was 1.99 (0.96–4.11). The authors concluded that the meta-analysis demonstrated a significant positive association, and that PAH has a vital role in child ADHD.

The conclusion of the systematic review was somewhat more prudent (Aghaei et al., 2019) on the association of PAH and ADHD. The authors concluded that there is more evidence suggesting the detrimental effects of the other studied air pollutants on ADHD compared to PAH in particulate pollutants category. The matrices used for the assessment of PAF exposure included maternal blood, umbilical cord white blood cells, urine samples, complemented with other measurements such as 48-hour personal air monitoring.

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Table 28: Studies on PAHs and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Rezaei Kalantary et al., (2020)	Spain and USA	<p>N of studies: 6 in the systematic review and 5 in the meta-analysis</p> <p>Setting: cohort and cross-sectional studies</p> <p>Target group: children</p>	<p>There was no significant association between PAH exposure and ADHD for children when all studies were combined (overall odds ratio = 1.99, 95% CI = 0.96-4.11) with low heterogeneity ($I^2 = 28.73\%$; P value < 0.001). However, the authors concluded that PAH has a vital role in child ADHD.</p>
Aghaei et al., (2019)	Spain and USA	<p>N of studies: 7</p> <p>Setting: cohort and cross-sectional studies</p> <p>Target group: children</p>	<p>Eleven associations were investigated in seven studies related to PAH in which 5 significant associations were observed. On the other hand, no associations were found in six investigations. Although limited evidence of detrimental effects of PAH on ADHD was found in this review, moderate-quality studies in terms of exposure assessment showed positive associations.</p>

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19.3.5 Flame retardants

One systematic review assessing the association of polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and ADHD or intelligence was identified (Table 29) (Lam et al., 2017). Nine studies met the inclusion criteria for studies on attention-related behavioural conditions. The results of the studies were inconsistent, and the possibility of publication bias could not be confidently eliminated. The overall strength of the evidence was limited for the outcome of ADHD and attention-related behaviors.

A review on organophosphate esters (OPEs) and children's health also considered hyperactivity or attention problems (Table 29) (Doherty et al., 2019). Only two studies with hyperactivity or attention problems were included. The studies suggested that exposure to OPEs may be positively associated with hyperactivity.

Table 29: Studies on FR and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Lam et al., (2017)	USA, Spain, the Netherlands	N of studies: 9 Setting: cohort and cross-sectional studies Target group: mother-child pairs	A systematic review regarding developmental exposure to polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and intelligence or Attention Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and attention-related behavioral conditions in humans. The body of evidence was of moderate quality for ADHD with "limited" evidence for an association with PBDEs.
Doherty, (2019)	USA	N of studies: 2 Setting: prospective pregnancy cohorts Target group: mother-child pairs	The conclusion was that greater hyperactivity was associated with organophosphate ester metabolites. However, the available studies have notable limitations. The authors of the review concluded that reproduction of the results in other study populations, ideally with repeated measures of OPE exposure, is necessary to make stronger inference about the potential cognitive and behavioral effects of early life OPE exposures.

19.3.6 Heavy metals Mercury and Cadmium

The relationship of mercury (Hg) and ADHD has been examined in a recent systematic review and meta-analysis (Table 30) (Nilsen et al., 2020). Three studies with an age range of 5–15 years of the participants were included in the analyses. Hg was assessed from blood samples in all included studies.

In an earlier meta-analysis, the association of environmental sources of Hg with ADHD was assessed (Table 30) (Yoshimasu et al., 2014). Environmental exposure showed moderate adverse effects. However, the meta-analysis only included two studies.

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A review, which assessed the association of perinatal and childhood exposure to cadmium (Cd) and ADHD, collected studies published between January 2009 and March 2015 (Sanders et al., 2015) (Table 30). Five of the included studies examined the association between cadmium and ADHD or ADHD-like behavior. None of the five studies that examined the association between early life Cd and ADHD reported significant associations.

However, results from two studies published after the review suggest an association (Lee et al., 2018, Kim et al., 2020) A study from Taiwan recruited 29 patients with ADHD inattentive type (ADHD-I), 47 patients with ADHD hyperactivity/impulsivity type (ADHD-H/I), and 46 healthy control children. The age range of the participants was 6–16 years. ADHD-I patients demonstrated the highest Cd levels in urine ($p = 0.034$). The authors concluded that Cd was associated with susceptibility to ADHD and symptom severity in school-age children. Another study examined the effect of prenatal Cd exposure on ADHD in Korea (Kim et al., 2020). Blood Cd concentration of the mothers was assessed during pregnancy. ADHD symptoms among the children were assessed at the age of six. The results of the study suggested a significant dose-dependent relationship between prenatal Cd concentrations and ADHD scores at the age of 6 years among girls but not among boys.

Table 30: Studies on Hg, Cd and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Nilsen & Tulve, (2020)	Countries not indicated in the article.	N of studies: 3 studies on Hg Setting: observational Target group: the age range 5–15 years	The OR for Hg exposure and all ADHD outcomes was 2.68 (2.16–3.19, $p < 0.0001$). The authors conclude that despite the significant results, the small number of studies cannot be overlooked, and a relationship could not be proven.
Yoshimasu et al., (2014)	Canada, USA, South Korea	N of studies: 2 studies with 3 data sets Setting: case-control, cross-sectional and cohort studies Target group: children and mother-child pairs	Environmental Hg exposure showed moderate adverse effects on ADHD (OR 1.60, 95% CI 1.10-2.33). Only two studies with environmental Hg exposure were included. According to the authors, the results should be interpreted with caution because of the limited number of studies.
Sanders et al., (2015)	Spain, USA, Poland, United Arab Emirates	N of studies: 5 studies on Cd and ADHD Setting: prospective cohort, cross-sectional and case-control studies Target group: Age range 2–18 years	None of the five studies reported significant associations between early life Cd and ADHD.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Lee et al., (2018)	Taiwan	<p>N of studies: 1</p> <p>Setting: cross-sectional case-control study</p> <p>Target group: 6–10-year-old children: 29 with ADHD inattentive type (ADHD-I), 47 with ADHD hyperactivity/impulsivity type (ADHD-H/I), and 46 healthy control children</p>	ADHD-I patients demonstrated the highest Cd levels ($p=0.034$).
Kim et al., (2020)	Korea	<p>N of studies: 1</p> <p>Setting: cohort study</p> <p>Target group: 6-year-old children</p>	Increased prenatal maternal blood Cd concentrations were associated with increased scores for ADHD for girls, but not for boys, at age 6. A 2-fold increase in the prenatal Cd level was significantly associated with a 22.3% (95% CI, 11.6 to 34.1) increase in ADHD in girls at 6 years of age.

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19.3.7 Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

No meta-analyses on the association of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFASs) and ADHD were found. A qualitative assessment for perfluoroalkyl compounds (PFCs) and ADHD was performed in a systematic review, however (Nilsen et al., 2020). The review included two studies on PFCs, both of which with sample sizes >1000 participants (Table 31). The results of the two studies were somewhat discordant: One study reported no significant relationship between increasing PFC exposures and ADHD outcomes in children aged 6–12 years but observed a sex-based relationship. In the other study, a significant relationship between increasing PFC exposures and ADHD outcomes in children aged 12-15 years was observed, whereas sex-based differences were not discussed.

In another review, several studies suggesting a positive association for prenatal exposure to PFCs and ADHD or related behavioral problems were identified (Lee, 2018). However, all studies did not observe an association.

Overall, more research is needed to draw a more conclusive conclusion on the association between PFASs and ADHD.

Table 31: Studies on PFASs and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Nilsen et al., (2020)	USA	N of studies: 2 Setting: cohort study and cross-sectional study Target group: 6–15-year-old children	The findings on the association of perfluoroalkyl compounds (PFCs) and ADHD were inconsistent.
Lee, (2018)	Taiwan, USA, Greenland, Ukraine, Poland, Denmark, Sweden	N of studies: 5 Setting: cohort, cross-sectional and case-control study Target group: children / mother-child pairs	Several but not all studies find association for some PFC substances and ADHD. The outcome varied and in addition to ADHD diagnosis, hyperactivity assessed with a questionnaire was used.

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19.3.8 Pesticides

Two recent reviews have examined the association of pesticides and ADHD (Table 32). Pesticides were included in the group of organic contaminants (OCs) in a systematic review and meta-analysis (Nilsen et al., 2020). The odds ratio for OCs exposures coinciding with an ADHD outcome was 0.99 (0.96–1.02). Thereby, practically no effect could be ascertained. The certainty of the evidence used in this meta-analysis was considered ‘very low’ by GRADE standards, and the authors recommended that in future studies, OCs should be narrowed to single OC classes for a more precise conclusion.

The other review included twelve epidemiological studies among humans (Roberts et al., 2019). In most of the included studies the outcome was ADHD, but also hand tremor, as an example, was used as a sign of ADHD. The level of pesticide exposure in the studies was generally low. The authors conclude that a growing body of literature provides evidence that pesticides may have a role in the development of ADHD, and that it is likely that there are gene–environment interactions. The epidemiological data provided supporting evidence for human outcomes beginning in the earliest stages of childhood development and at exposures well below those resulting in acute toxicity. However, the evidence could not be considered conclusive.

Table 32: Studies on pesticides and ADHD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Nilsen et al., (2020)	USA, Taiwan	N of studies: 6 Setting: cross-sectional and case-control studies Target group: children aged 4–17 years	Based on the meta-analysis, organic contaminant exposure may or may not result in an increase in ADHD diagnosis (OR 0.99, 95% CI 0.96–1.02). However, the certainty of the evidence was considered ‘very low’ by GRADE standards.
Roberts et al., (2019)	USA, Costa Rica, Taiwan, Spain, Belgium	N of studies: 12 Setting: cross-sectional, case-control and cohort studies Target group: children or mother-child pairs	Some kind of association between pesticides and ADHD or measures of attention was found in the majority of studies.

19.4 Autism spectrum disorder

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is described in ICD-11 revision as follows: ASD is characterised by persistent deficits in the ability to initiate and to sustain reciprocal social interaction and social communication, and by a range of restricted, repetitive, and inflexible patterns of behaviour and interests (World Health Organisation, 2020). The onset of the disorder occurs during the developmental period, typically in early childhood, but symptoms may not become fully manifest until later, when social demands exceed limited capacities (World Health Organisation, 2020; Lord et al., 2018).

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There are several sub-types of ASD and individuals along the spectrum exhibit a full range of intellectual functioning and language abilities. ADHD is the most common comorbidity in people with ASD and occurs among almost 30% of persons with ASD (Simonoff et al., 2008). In addition, anxiety, irritability and aggression also occur more frequently in ASD than in other developmental disorders (Lau et al., 2019; Simonoff et al., 2008; Hill et al., 2014).

The diagnosis of ASD is made on the basis of behavior as no reliable biomarkers exist (Lord et al., 2018). To be diagnosed with ASD, a person must show evidence of difficulties in each of three social communication subdomains: 1) deficits in social–emotional reciprocity, 2) deficits in non-verbal communicative behaviours and 3) deficits in developing, maintaining, and understanding relationships. Furthermore, the person must have difficulty in restricted, repetitive sensory–motor behaviours. ASD can be diagnosed by various professionals such as paediatricians, psychiatrists or psychologists. Various diagnostic instruments or scales such as the Childhood Asperger Syndrome Test (CAST) (Scott et al., 2002) are available which allow the clinician to observe and characterise the behaviours of a person suspected to have ASD. A list of tests and tools for evaluation of cognitive and psychomotor development is available in a previous deliverable (HBM4EU 2019 Deliverable Report D 11.3). Information on diagnosed ASD and/or a parent-completed short checklist feasible for the country in question might be most feasible method for assessing ASD in Human Biomonitoring studies. The tool should be selected based on the age of the children in the study.

The ICD-10 code for autistic disorder is F84.0. The code for Asperger’s syndrome is F84.5 (WHO 2019, ICD-10). The ICD-11 code for ASD is 6A02 (WHO 2020, ICD-11). Among ICPC-2 codes, P99 “Psychological disorders, other” has been used as well as ICPC-2 PLUS codes P99010, P99005, P99006, P99013 (WONCA, 2016, Birch et al., 2018).

For HBM studies, recommended questions on ASD can be found in Appendix 22.2.

The treatment strategy depends on the sub-type and symptoms of each individual affected with ASD (Howes et al., 2018). Non-pharmacological treatments include social-communication interventions, which were recommended by consensus guidelines on from the British Association for Psychopharmacology, and behavioral interventions based on high-intensity applied behavioral analysis (Howes et al., 2018).

It has been estimated that 64–91% of ASD risk is heritable (Tick et al., 2016). The environmental factors that have shown association with ASD include advanced maternal age (≥ 40 years) and paternal age (≥ 50 years), short interpregnancy intervals (< 24 months), preterm birth (< 32 weeks) and environmental chemicals, among others (Idring et al., 2014; Zerbo et al., 2015; Lampi et al., 2012; Bölte et al., 2019).

The population prevalence of ASD is estimated at around 1.5% in developed countries (Lyall et al., 2017). More males than females are affected with ASD.

The economic costs of ASD are distributed to several sectors and are complex to estimate. In a literature review, the types of ASD related costs were categorised in six classes: 1) medical and healthcare related service costs, 2) therapeutic costs, 3) (special) education costs, 4) costs of production loss for adults with ASD, 5) costs of informal care and lost productivity for family/caregivers, and 6) costs of accommodation, respite care, and out-of-pocket expenses (Rogge et al., 2019). The review included 48 papers from several countries including the European countries the UK, Sweden and the Netherlands. The distribution of the costs varied considerably between countries, and the authors stated that it was not straightforward to compare the cost estimates across studies. However, they presented an estimate of the overall lifetime costs of ASD

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for an average individual with ASD (or family with a child with ASD) in the UK was about £ 1.5 million in 2011.

The economic burden of ASD in the European Union has also been estimated by the programme 'Autism Spectrum Disorders in the European Union – ASDEU' (ASDEU, 2018). Their report included 14 EU countries. The results suggested that the range of direct costs per individual ranged considerably between the countries, and that special education services were the costliest resources per individual. However, the authors alert that the surveys carried out in the framework of the ASDEU programme by a questionnaire for individuals with ASD and their families do not represent the whole population of the countries.

Globally, autistic disorders accounted for more than 58 DALYs per 100 000 population and other ASDs accounted for 53 DALYs per 100 000 in 2010 (Baxter et al., 2015). In Europe, the DALYs for ASD were 567,560 in 2019 and the rate per 100,000 was 66.8 (Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation, 2020).

19.5 Environmental chemicals associated with autism

Based on reviews and meta-analyses there is evidence for association of ASD and several environmental chemicals. The exposure of lead and mercury and their association with ASD has been examined most extensively. For the association between phthalates and ASD the evidence is less abundant, but the findings can be interpreted as suggestive of an association. Furthermore, for pesticides and mycotoxins, the published results justify further research.

19.5.1 Heavy metals Lead and Mercury

The association of lead (Pb) and ASD has been examined in a systematic review and meta-analysis (Table 33) (Saghazadeh et al., 2017). The meta-analysis included 32 studies, which were published between 1982 and 2016 (Saghazadeh et al., 2017). The meta-analysis could be performed for studies which had measured erythrocyte, blood, urine and hair Pb levels. ASD patients had higher erythrocyte, blood and hair Pb levels than control subjects. However, regarding the results on hair Pb levels, sensitivity analyses showed that ASD patients in developing but not in developed countries had higher hair concentrations of Pb in comparison with control subjects.

In addition, a descriptive review with basically part of the same studies included in the meta-analysis has been published but is reported in more detail here because the meta-analysis included more comprehensive information (Ye et al., 2017).

The association of mercury (Hg) and ASD has been examined in two recent meta-analyses (Table 33)(Saghazadeh et al., 2017, Jafari et al., 2017).

A meta-analysis of 38 studies with data considering hair, blood, urine, and erythrocyte measures of Hg found significantly higher erythrocyte concentration among ASD patients than among control subjects (Saghazadeh et al., 2017). In another recent meta-analysis with 44 studies significantly higher blood, erythrocyte and brain concentrations of Hg in ASD patients compared to healthy subjects were found (Jafari et al., 2017).

A third meta-analysis on the associations between environmental mercury exposure and ASD (Yoshimasu et al., 2014) was also found. However, this meta-analysis is not covered in more detail here as it was published before the two more recent meta-analyses and only included 5 studies.

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Table 33: Studies on Pb, Hg and ASD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Saghazadeh & Rezaei, (2017)	USA, Italy, Russia, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Korea, Spain, Egypt, Turkey, Slovenia, India, Kuwait	N of studies: altogether 32 studies, e.g. 19 studies with hair as specimen, 6 studies with blood as specimen Setting: observational studies Target group: Mostly children but adults were not excluded	ASD patients had higher erythrocyte, blood and hair Pb levels than control subjects. The blood Pb levels in ASD patients were significantly higher than in control subjects (SMD=0.43, CI: 0.02 to 0.85). ASD patients had also higher erythrocyte Pb levels than control subjects with a summary effect size of 1.55 (Z = 2.26, p = 0.024). No differences in urine Pb levels between cases and controls were seen.
Saghazadeh & Rezaei, (2017)	Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Russia, Slovenia, USA, Oman, Italy, UK, India, Poland, Korea, Kuwait, Japan	N of studies: 38 Setting: observational Target group: children or infants and one study with working-age adults	Significantly higher erythrocyte concentration among ASD patients than among control subjects. Blood, urine and hair Hg levels did not differ significantly between ASD patients and controls.
Jafari et al., (2017)	USA, Hong Kong, Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Egypt, Poland, India, Italy, U.K., Jamaica, Oman, Mexico, Slovenia, China, Russia	N of studies: 44 Setting: case-control studies Target group: children	The Hg level in blood (Hedges =0.43, 95% CI: 0.12, 0.74, P =0.007), red blood cells (Hedges =1.61, 95% CI: 0.83, 2.38, P<0.001), and brain (0.61 ng/g, 95% CI, 0.02, 1.19, P =0.043) was significantly higher in ASD patients than healthy subjects, whereas Hg level in hair was significantly lower in ASD patients than healthy subjects. The Hg level in urine was not significantly different between ASD patients and healthy subjects. The authors concluded that Hg is a causal factor in the etiology of ASD.

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19.5.2 Phthalates

The systematic review (Jeddi et al. 2016) identified five studies and observed the association between prenatal and/or childhood exposure to phthalate and ASD (Table 34) (Jeddi et al., 2016). Three of the studies showed a positive association between exposure to phthalates and ASD.

In another review, the observed associations were less clear (Ye et al., 2017).

Table 34: Studies on phthalates and ASD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Jeddi et al., (2016)	USA, Italy, Turkey	N of studies: 5 Setting: cohort studies, case control studies Target group: children	Out of the five studies, two were cohort studies (one with positive results and another one with not clear association). Among the three case control studies, two of them showed a significant relation between exposure to phthalate and ASD and the last case control study had negative results. This review reveals evidence showing a connection between exposure to phthalates and ASD.
Ye et al., (2017)	USA	N of studies: 5 (not strictly on ASD) Setting: not indicated Target group: children and mother-child pairs	The authors concluded that the results from two included studies suggested that prenatal exposure to low molecular weight phthalate may induce autism-like behaviors and affect neurodevelopment in children. Here, however, the measured outcome was wider than ASD.

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19.5.3 Pesticides and Mycotoxins

The association of pesticides and ASD or deficits in social functioning has been reviewed based on 11 studies (Table 35) (Roberts et al., 2019). A positive association was seen in most studies. The conclusion of the authors was that the evidence cannot be considered conclusive, but the existing data justifies further research.

A review examining the effects of mycotoxins on neuropsychiatric symptoms also looked into the effect on ASD (Ratnaseelan et al., 2018). Two studies including children with ASD and healthy controls provided strong evidence of an association between exposure to mycotoxins and ASD. The biomarker in the first study was ochratoxin A in urine and serum and in the other study aflatoxin M1, ochratoxin A and fumonisin B1 in serum and urine.

Table 35: Studies on pesticides, mycotoxins and ASD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Roberts et al., (2019)	USA, Finland	N of studies: 11 Setting: case-control and cohort studies Target group: children and mother-child pairs	A growing body of literature provides evidence that pesticides may have a role in the development of ASD and ADHD.
Ratnaseelan et al., (2018)	Italy	N of studies: 2 Setting: case-control studies Target group: children	Both studies included in the review provided strong evidence of an association between exposure to mycotoxins and ASD.

19.6 Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) is a motor neuron disease characterised by progressive muscular paralysis and degeneration of motor neurons in the primary motor cortex, corticospinal tracts, brainstem and spinal cord. It is the most common neuro-generative disorder of motor neurons including both upper and lower motor neuron signs (Figure 11). The symptoms of the disease typically involve weakness starting in the hands and legs or slurred speech and dysphagia. The disease is progressive, and there is no available therapy or cure leaving the patients with the mean survival time of three to five years (Wijesekera & Leigh, 2009; Rowland & Schneider, 2001; Armon, 2003). However, the symptoms can be relieved with appropriate physical therapy and other therapy modes such as occupational and speech therapy.

Two different types of ALS exist: sporadic and familial. Sporadic form is the most common affecting 90 to 95 % of the patients. Familial ALS (FALS) is hereditary and it is prevalent in 5 to 10 % of the cases (ALS Association, 2020; Kiernan et al., 2011). There are at least 13 genes identified behind the FALS form of the disease, and also there are several susceptibility genes detected regarding the sporadic form. However, the complex genetic basis for the sporadic form has not been established (Kiernan et al., 2011; Beleza-Meireles & Al-Chalabi, 2009).

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The risk factors of ALS are older age, male sex and family history of ALS (Armon, 2003; Ingre et al., 2015). Identification of especially non-genetic risk factors for ALS is difficult (Ingre et al., 2015).

To diagnose ALS is not an easy task. No specific test or procedure exists to end up with a diagnosis. Diagnosis is predominantly based on a clinical examination and series of diagnostic tests including ruling out other diseases causing similar symptoms. Diagnostics include mainly the following procedures: electromyography (EMG), nerve conduction velocity (NCV), blood and urine tests including high resolution serum protein electrophoresis, thyroid and parathyroid hormone levels and 24-hour urine collection for heavy metals, spinal tap, X-rays including magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), myelogram of cervical spine, muscle and/or nerve biopsy and comprehensive neurological examination (ALS Association, 2020). Paganoni et al. (2014) illustrated the diagnostic timelines by including over 300 ALS patients in their analysis. Median total diagnostic time was 11.5 months, and older age (> 60 years), sporadic disease and limb onset delayed the diagnostics. Interestingly, 52% of the patients received an alternative diagnosis, and each patient met an average of three different physicians before the confirmation of ALS diagnosis. The authors concluded that diagnostic timelines in ALS are long.

Figure 11: ALS involves neurons in the brain and in the spinal cord. (Picture Wikipedia. License under Rccchang16 / CC BY-SA (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>). https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:UMN_vs_LMN.png.)

Nevertheless, there are specific criteria established by the El Escorial World Federation of Neurology. According to these criteria, the diagnosis of ALS requires the following features: 1) signs of lower motor neuron (LMN) degeneration by clinical, electrophysiological or neuro pathologic examination, 2) signs of upper motor neuron (UMN) degeneration by clinical examination and 3) progressive spread of signs within a region or to other regions, together with the absence of electrophysiological evidence of other disease processes that might explain the signs of LMN and/or UMN degenerations and neuroimaging evidence of other disease processes that might explain the observed clinical and electrophysiological signs (Brooks, 1994).

The ICD-10 code for ALS is G12.2 under diseases of the nervous system (G00-G99), spinal muscular atrophy and related syndromes G12 and motor neuron disease G12.2 (WHO ICD-10, 2019). The ICD-11 code for ALS is 8B60.0 under motor neuron diseases or related disorders and motor neuron disease 8B60 (WHO ICD-11, 2020).

Longinetti and Fang (2019) provided an update of recent literature concerning the incidence and risk factors of ALS. They conducted a summary of epidemiological studies, which were published during the previous 18 months. According to these studies, the incidence of ALS was between 0.6 and 3.8 per 100 000 person-years. However, in Europe the incidence was higher: between 2.1 to 3.8 per 100 000 person-years. Recent population-based studies indicated a prevalence of ALS between 4.1 and 8.4 per 100 000 persons. Worldwide incidence and prevalence numbers seem to be increasing. Logroscino et al. (2010) investigated the incidence rate of ALS in the general European population based on 1,028 identified incident cases in three countries (Ireland, UK, Italy)

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between the years 1998-1999. They found that the rough annual incidence rate was 2.16 per 100 000 person-years (95 % CI 2.0-2.3). The incidence in men was higher (3.0 per 100 000 person-years, 2.8-3.3) than in women (2.4 per 100 000 person-years, 2.2-2.6). The incidence rate of ALS seemed to be homogenous all over Europe.

The socioeconomic importance of ALS is significant. Arthur et al. (2016) conducted a study to estimate the worldwide number of people with ALS in the year 2015 and 2040. They based their estimation on the previously published data on ALS incidence. The estimation was that the cases of ALS will increase by 69 % by the year 2040, and the increase is mainly because of aging of the population. There seems to be a change of the projected number of ALS cases from the developed countries to the developing nations.

Universal and up-to-date costs of ALS are quite difficult to find. Schepelmann et al. (2010) conducted an evaluation of the socioeconomic impact of three neuromuscular diseases including ALS. The patients were German (n=107), and costs were evaluated from the societal perspective in 2009. Total annual costs were 36,380 € (95 % CI 27,090-47,970) per patient. The costs consisted mainly of health insurance and the productivity loss of patients and their caretakers.

19.7 Environmental chemicals associated with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis

Based on the supplementary literature search there seems to be extensive amount of systematic reviews conducted on the association between ALS and environmental substances, and the most solid and vast evidence concerns pesticides and Pb. The amount of evidence regarding Cd, solvents and Hg is more limited, but regardless the association of these substances and the disease is carefully supported.

19.7.1 Pesticides

Pesticides seem to have a possible association with the risk of ALS according to the evidence, and the strongest and vastest evidence is linked with occupational exposure. Of the studies selected, only one study concluded that the association between pesticides exposure and ALS is weak and insignificant. However, the authors concluded that the lack of statistically significant association between occupational exposure and ALS was mainly caused by the methodological diversity of the studies and the lack of prospective studies at the workplace (Capozzella et al., 2014). The results are presented in Table 36.

Table 36: Studies on pesticides and ALS

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 31, of which 5 on ALS Setting: 4 case-control and 1 prospective cohort study Target group: occupational	Pesticides increased the risk of ALS by at least 50 % (RR 1.35, 95 % CI: 1.02-1.79).

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2018)	Not specified	N of studies: 37, of which 5 on pesticides (10 studies on chemicals altogether) Setting: 4 case-control and 1 prospective cohort study Target group: occupational	Exposure to all the selected chemicals increased the risk of ALS with RR 1.19 (95 % CI 1.07-1.33). Pesticides alone increased the risk of ALS with RR 1.35 (1.02-1.79) (Gunnarsson & Bodin, 2019).
Krewski et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting:- Target group: - Studies exploring the risk factors associated with the onset and progression of 14 neurological conditions including ALS	Exposure to pesticides associated with an increased risk of ALS with sufficient evidence, meaning that at least one systematic review rated of moderate/high quality has reviewed the available evidence and published a peer-reviewed report showing that a credible relationship exists.
Sutedja et al., (2009)	Not specified	N of studies: 38, of which 7 on chemicals Setting: - Target group: - Studies exploring exposure to chemicals and its association with ALS	In two studies, a significant association found with increased ALS risk and exposure to pesticides.
Kang et al., (2014)	Italy, USA, France, India, Sweden, Greece, Netherlands, Scotland, Australia	N of studies: 22 Setting: 19 case-control and 3 cohort studies Target group: rural residence and farming occupation	The risk of ALS significantly increased with pesticide exposure (OR 1.44, 95% CI 1.22-1.70) and with farmers (1.42, 1.17-1.73), but not markedly with rural residence (1.25, 0.84-1.87). A positive association with men (OR 1.96) in pesticide exposure and ALS. In the studies using the EI Escorial criteria for ALS definition the association positive (OR 1.63) as well as in expert judgement for pesticide exposure (OR 2.04). The association of exposure to

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
			pesticides and risk of ALS supported.
Kamel et al., (2012)	USA	<p>N of studies: A cohort data of nearly 84,739 persons. Mortality data of 41 individuals (ALS patients) compared to the remaining cohort (controls). 8 studies included in the meta-analysis.</p> <p>Setting: The current study both cohort- and case- control study and in the meta-analysis 1 cohort- and 7 case-control studies</p> <p>Target group: pesticide applicators and their spouses from the Agricultural Health Study (AHS) /occupational</p>	In the meta-analysis, ALS linked with the use of pesticides as a group (1.9, 95 % CI 1.1-3.1), and in the analysis of AHS data, the association with OCs (organochlorine insecticides) particularly important.
Malek et al., (2012)	Italy, USA, Scotland, Sweden	<p>N of studies: 6 of men incl. 1,517 ALS deaths and 589 ALS or motor neuron disease cases</p> <p>Setting: 1 retrospective cohort and 5 case-control studies</p> <p>Target group: occupational</p>	Evidence found for an association of exposure to pesticides and risk of ALS in male cases compared to controls (OR 1.88, 95% CI 1.36–2.61), but the chemical or class of pesticide not specified in most of the studies. The relationship of exposure to pesticides and development of ALS supported.
Capozzella et al., (2014)	Not specified	<p>N of studies: 750</p> <p>Setting: cohort- or case-control studies</p> <p>Target group: occupational, individuals with clinical diagnosis of sporadic ALS or sporadic ALS on the death certificate</p>	The association between exposure to pesticides and ALS as a whole weak and non-significant. Regarding the products of agricultural pesticides in general, an association found with ALS in men but not in women, with a dose-response relationship.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Mostafalou & Abdollahi, (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 448, of which 18 studies on ALS Setting: 15 case-control- and 3 cohort studies Target group: occupational, overall, general, war field	A vast amount of evidence regarding the possible role of pesticides exposure and elevated incidences of ALS. The harmful effects in relation to provoking different diseases linked mostly to insecticides and herbicides, especially organophosphorus, organochlorines, phenoxyacetic acids, and triazine compounds.

19.7.2 Lead

The possibility of Pb contributing to the risk of ALS seems to be supported by the findings. According to the epidemiological studies, of the heavy metals, particularly Pb is associated with the adverse health effects. As with pesticides, also with Pb, occupational exposure is prominent when scrutinising the human health effects. The results are presented in Table 37.

Table 37: Studies on Pb and ALS

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 14 on metals, of which 5 on Pb Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational, 1 on veterans	An elevated risk for ALS only in exposure to Pb (RR 1.57, 95% CI 1.11–2.20). At least 50 % increased risk for ALS in exposure to Pb.
Cicero et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: case-control and ecological studies Target group: occupational	Possible association between Pb exposure and ALS consistently supported by some occupational cohort studies, several retrospective case-control studies and in a recent meta-analysis (Wang et al. 2014).
Wang et al., (2014)	Not specified	N of studies: 9 in the meta-analysis and 4 additional articles on heavy metals incl. Pb in the sensitivity analyses	ALS risk among people with a history of exposure to Pb almost doubled (OR 1.81, 95% CI 1.39-2.36). A 5 % risk of developing ALS in exposure to Pb.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
		Setting: case-control studies with specific Pb exposure information Target group: occupational	
Wang et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 7 on Pb Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational	Increased risk for ALS in occupational history of exposure to heavy metals, particularly Pb. The OR of having a history of exposure to Pb markedly heightened for ALS patients compared to controls (OR 1.72, 95% CI 1.33-2.23).
Capozzella et al., (2014)	Not specified	N of studies: 750 Setting: cohort- or case-control studies Target group: people with clinical diagnosis of sporadic ALS or sporadic ALS on the death certificate, occupational	Regarding the metals, a stronger association in women than in men in some of the cases. For individual metals, the association apparent with chromium and Pb.
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2018)	Not specified	N of studies: 37, of which 6 on metals and 3 on Pb Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational, US veterans	The weighted RRs for the occupational exposures 1.45 (95% CI 1.07–1.96) for metals. The weighted RR for the exposure to Pb 1.51 (0.96-2.38). The risk of ALS statistically significantly heightened for occupational exposure to metals, especially to Pb.
Hersi et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 9 on Pb Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational	The results of the previous studies confirmed by highlighting the heightened risk of ALS in relation to occupational exposure to Pb and other heavy metals.

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19.7.3 Cadmium

The epidemiological evidence supports the role of Cd in the risk of ALS and mostly the conclusions of the different studies show consistency. However, the limited number of systematic reviews and meta-analyses identified hinders the solidity of the conclusions and makes the overall evidence somewhat weaker compared to pesticides and Pb. Furthermore, the case-control study by Vinceti et al. (1997) was able to show only limited evidence of Cd in the etiology of sporadic ALS. The results are introduced in Table 38.

Table 38: Studies on Cd and ALS

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Cicero et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 8 on Cd Setting: observational case-control and ecological studies Target group: occupational	Some evidence found for Cd; positive associations in two case-control studies (Roos et al. 2013 & Vinceti et al. 1997).
Roos et al., (2013)	Norway	N of studies: 1 Setting: Case-control study; a cohort of ALS patients (n=17) vs. controls (n=10) Target group: ALS patients	Statistically significant higher concentrations of Cd in ALS CSF compared to controls (median value in ALS 0.156 and in controls 0.062; p-value not reported). The metal concentrations higher in CSF compared to blood plasma. Neurotoxic metals associated with the pathogenesis of ALS.
Vinceti et al., (1997)	Italy	N of studies: 1 Setting: Case-control; ALS patients/cases (n=16) and controls (n=39) Target group: ALS patients	Higher Cd concentrations in the patients with limited disability compared to the controls. Mean Cd-levels of these patients (n=15) 1.25 (+/- SD 0.42) and in the controls (n=36) 0.98 (+/- SD 0.31), and the p-value statistically significant (p=0.025). A limited support for the involvement of Cd in the etiology of sporadic ALS.
Wang et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 10 on heavy metals, of which 3 incl. Cd Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational	Previous exposure to Cd may be associated with an increased risk of developing ALS.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Preciados et al., (2016)	Not specified	N of studies: 25 Setting: 11 case-control, 6 cohort and 5 cross-sectional studies, 2 clinical trials and 1 mortality study Target group: -	The association of Cd with ALS supported according to cross-sectional, cohort and case-control studies.

19.7.4 Mercury

The evidence regarding Hg in association with risk of ALS is inconsistent and scarce. Occupational exposure is putatively the most contributing factor regarding Hg and the public health, as with other heavy metals. The results are found in Table 39.

Table 39: Studies on Hg and ALS

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Cicero et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 7 on Hg Setting: case-control and ecological studies Target group: occupational	In a few case reports a possible connection between ALS and Hg. In some retrospective case-control studies no association, or even markedly lower concentrations of Hg in ALS patients or then again the opposite (Roos et al. 2013).
Roos et al., (2013)	Norway	N of studies: 1 Setting: Case-control study; a cohort of ALS patients (n=17) vs. controls (n=10) Target group: ALS patients	Slightly elevated Hg concentrations in ALS patients blood plasma compared to controls (ALS: median 0.827, min. 0.195, max. 1.623 and controls: median 0.510, min. 0.075, max. 0.914).
Wang et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 10 on heavy metals, of which 3 incl. Hg Setting: case-control studies Target group: occupational	The second most common heavy metal associated with ALS after Pb is Hg. Case reports of ALS or ALS-like symptoms associated with exposure to Hg presented, but epidemiological investigation for the association not thoroughly implemented.

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19.7.5 Solvents

There is evidence of solvents contributing to the risk of ALS, but the amount of studies is limited. The literature search was hindered by the fact that there are many types of solvents; the search term “aprotic solvents” wasn’t particularly useful, so the term “solvents” was applied instead. The type of solvent was not specified in the search making the specification and elaboration of the detailed results difficult. However, in many studies, the types of solvents were introduced in detail and in association with the disease yielding more specified results. Also, with the solvents the occupational exposure is evidently the most important issue to consider when protecting public health. The results are introduced in Table 40.

Table 40: Studies on solvents and ALS

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Wang et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 11 studies on solvents Setting: 8 case-control and 2 cohort studies, 1 other type of study (undefined) Target group: e.g. occupational	The OR of having ALS 40 % higher in individuals exposed to solvents (OR 1.43, 95 % CI 1.10-1.86). In these studies the nature of solvents identified as detectable polychlorinated biphenyls and aromatic solvent.
Capozzella et al., (2014)	Not specified	N of studies: 750 incl. studies on solvents, heavy metals and pesticides Setting: cohort or case-control studies Target group: occupational	A slightly increased risk of ALS in association of solvents in some studies, particularly in women, and in others a slight but significant linear association observed.
Krewski et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting:- Target group: - Studies exploring the risk factors associated with the onset and progression of 14 neurological conditions including ALS	A limited evidence of the interrelation between exposure to solvents and ALS; evidence suggestive of an association between the agent and the outcome and in at least one high-quality study a positive association observed, but the results of other studies inconsistent.

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19.8 Parkinson's disease

Parkinson's disease (PD) is classified as a neurodegenerative disorder affecting dopamine-producing neurons in the brain, in the area called substantia nigra. It is the second most common neurodegenerative disorder after AD. Symptoms of the disease develop slowly and with individual variation. Some common symptoms include tremor, bradykinesia (slowness of movement), limb rigidity as well as gait and balance problems. The disease is not curable neither fatal. However, the complications of the disease can be serious. Treatment involves medication and surgery (Parkinson's Foundation, 2020; de Lau & Breteler, 2006). Physical therapy and other therapy modes such as speech and occupational therapy are often included in the treatment protocol.

The exact pathogenesis regarding the selective dopaminergic cell loss in PD is not fully understood. Etiology and pathogenesis of PD emphasises a multifactorial approach with both genetic predispositions and environmental factors interacting. Non-genetic factors and susceptibility genes are thought to intertwine, but which of them are more relevant, is not exactly known. Various causative monogenetic mutations have been discovered, but these mutations probably explain only a small proportion of all PD-cases since about 90 % of cases are estimated to be sporadic. The role of heredity and genes are supported with the introducing of at least 11 forms of genetic PD sharing clinical features and pathogenetic mechanisms with the more common sporadic form of PD. In the sporadic form of PD non-genetic factors play a bigger role. Most PD cases derive from primary Lewy body PD, and so-called Parkinsonism-plus syndromes and secondary Parkinsonism exist with lesser extent. The risk factors of PD are gathered based on the epidemiological evidence. The risk of developing the disease increases with age and male sex is a risk factor. Based on the various epidemiological studies there is evidence, that PD is rare in the age groups below 50 years and increasing prevalence is seen with age. Dietary habits, infections, environmental toxins and trauma are also considered as risk factors (de Lau & Breteler, 2006; WHO, 2006; Bonifati, 2005; Logroscino, 2005).

Diagnosing of PD is performed through strict clinical criteria such as the one developed by the Brain Bank of the Parkinson's Disease Society in the UK (Hughes et al., 2001). These criteria used worldwide provide accurate diagnostic methods, and at least two of the following symptoms need to be present for diagnosis: resting tremor, bradykinesia, rigidity or postural imbalance. Although clinical diagnosing is mostly used, there are diagnostic tools to confirm the presence of dopaminergic denervation including fluorodopa positron emission tomography (FDOPA PET) and dopamine transporter imaging with radionuclide tracers by means of single photon emission tomography (DAT-SPECT). They are not used for the routine diagnostics, and their use is purely investigational. Although these techniques are available, their use for population-based epidemiological research is still limited (de Lau & Breteler, 2006; WHO, 2006).

The ICD-10 code for PD is G20 under diseases of the nervous system (G00-G99) and extrapyramidal and movement disorders (G20-G26). Secondary Parkinsonism is labelled as G21 including seven different forms numbered from G21.0 to G21.9 (WHO ICD-10, 2019). The ICD-11 code for PD is 8A00.0 under diseases of the nervous system (08), movement disorders and Parkinsonism 8A00 (WHO ICD-11, 2020). The International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC 2) - code for Parkinsonism is N87 (WONCA, 2016).

The HBM4EU standardised questionnaire includes recommended questions on PD (Appendix 22.2).

The prevalence of PD is estimated at about 0.3 % of the whole population and 1.0% among people over 60 years of age in the industrialised countries (Nussbaum & Ellis, 2003). Cross-cultural variations in prevalence are potential results of differences in environmental exposures or

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distribution of susceptibility genes. PD might be less common in black and Asian people compared to white people, but the results are contradictory (Van den Eeden et al., 2003). Reported standardised incidence rates are 8-18 per 100 000 person-years with increasing rates after 60 years of age (de Lau and Breteler, 2006). Von Campenhausen et al. (2005) conducted an overview of the prevalence and incidence rates of PD in selected European countries (namely Austria, the Czech Republic, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and UK) based on the 39 studies. Prevalence rate estimates varied from 66 to 12 500 per 100 000 persons while annual incidence estimates varied from 5 to 346 per 100 000 persons (excluding Austria and the Czech Republic). Lindgren et al. (2005) included five European countries in their systematic review (namely Germany, France, UK, Finland and Sweden). They came up with the prevalence and incidence rates of approximately 108-257/100 000 and 11-19/100 000 per year, respectively. The corresponding rates regarding older people (> 60 years) were 1280-1500/100 000 and 346/100 000, respectively. The variations in both the prevalence and incidence rates might result from potential environmental and genetic factors (von Campenhausen et al., 2005; Lindgren et al., 2005).

Another study by von Campenhausen et al. (2011) evaluated the costs of PD among nearly 500 patients in six countries (namely Austria, the Czech Republic, Germany, Portugal, Italy and Russia). Survey-based economic data was collected during a 6-month-period and it was presented from the societal perspective. The total mean costs per patient varied from EUR 2620 to EUR 9820 consisting of 60-70 % of direct and 30-40 % of indirect costs. Although the proportions of cost components vary among countries, inpatient care, long-term care and medication were contributing to the major expenditures. The total costs of PD in Europe were estimated at €13.9 billion in 2010 (Gustavsson et al., 2011).

19.9 Environmental chemicals associated with Parkinson's disease

According to the literature search, the amount of studies regarding the association between pesticides and PD is vast, and the evidence derived from these studies mainly strengthens the hypothesis of pesticides contributing to the risk of PD. Exposure to solvents, Pb and Hg has been less studied - only a few studies exist of each. In spite of the limited number of evidence solvents, Pb and Hg all have possible associations with the risk of disease.

19.9.1 Pesticides

The evidence regarding pesticides exposure and increased risk of PD is quite solid with some variations and heterogeneity in the study results. Furthermore, high class studies, especially cohort studies are warranted, in order to be able to detect causal relationships. The pesticide exposure seems to cause most of its adverse effects, logically, in rural areas and among the workers in the agriculture sector. The results are presented in Table 41.

Table 41: Studies on pesticides and PD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 31, of which 24 on PD Setting: cohort or case-control studies	The risk of PD increased by at least 50 % (RR 1.66, 95 % CI 1.42–1.94) with exposure to pesticides. The weighted RR for six PD studies published before 2005 was 1.98 (1.41-2.77) and 1.57 (1.33-1.85) for 18 studies published in or after 2005.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
		Target group: occupational	
Freire & Koifman, (2012)	Taiwan, France, Australia, South Korea, Italy, USA, Taiwan, Scotland, Sweden, Romania, Malta, Brazil, UK, India, Canada, Denmark, Greenland, Finland, Serbia	N of studies: 50 Setting: ecological, cross-sectional, prospective and case-control studies Target group: occupational, residential, lifetime exposure, environmental	Increased PD risk in 13 out of 23 case-control studies (risk estimates of 1.1–2.4) and in 10 out of 12 studies with other research designs (risk estimates 2 or higher). Stronger associations in genetically susceptible study subjects found in various studies. Increased PD risk with insecticides, especially chlorpyrifos and organochlorines, in six studies (OR 1.8-4.4), and with the herbicide paraquat, the fungicide maneb or the combination of both in studies on exposure to specific pesticides (n=20).
van Den Mark et al., (2012)	Hong Kong, USA, Canada, Spain, Germany, Taiwan, Italy, Australia, Brazil, Sweden, Finland, France, Israel, India, Turkey, Scotland, Romania, Malta, Faroe islands, Serbia	N of studies: 46 Setting: 39 case-control, 4 cohort and 3 cross-sectional studies Target group: occupational and non-occupational	A summary risk ratio (sRR) of 1.62 (95% CI 1.40-1.88) for pesticide exposure (ever vs. never). In the summary estimates for subclasses of pesticides a positive association with herbicides and insecticides and risk of PD, but not with fungicides. In job title-based exposure assignment a higher sRR (2.5, 95% CI 1.5-4.1) than in assignment based on self-reported exposure (e.g. for self-reported ever/never exposure sRR = 1.5, 1.3-1.8).
Breckenridge et al., (2016)	Not specified	N of studies: 105 Setting: 88 % of the studies based on self-reported pesticide use, 22 % population-based and 29 % case-control studies using population- or cohort-based controls Target group: occupational, residential, smokers vs. non-smokers	In quantitative assessment less consistent associations between PD and the use of pesticides, herbicides, insecticides, fungicides or paraquat than in qualitative assessment. Causally related risk factors with rural living, farming, pesticide use or well-water consumption may exist, but such factors not extensively studied yet.
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 23 Setting: case-control, cohort or cross-sectional studies	The weighted relative risk estimate was 1.67 (95% CI 1.42-1.97). A ≥50% increased PD risk with exposure to any pesticide. Higher estimates found when heredity or onset below age 60 was concerned.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
		Target group: occupational	
Martino et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 11 meta-analyses, and 93 primary articles, of which 89 on PD onset and 4 on PD progression Setting: case-control, cohort or cross-sectional studies Target group: occupational, environmental	A positive association of onset of PD with pesticide exposure, rural living, well-water drinking, and farming occupation. Important factors incl. also family history and polymorphisms to key genes.
Krewski et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: - Target group: - Studies exploring the risk factors associated with the onset and progression of 14 neurological conditions including PD	Exposure to pesticides connected to an increased risk of having PD with sufficient evidence; at least one systematic review rated of moderate/high quality reviewed the available evidence and published a peer-reviewed report showing that a credible relationship exists.
Pezzoli & Cereda, (2013)	Not specified	N of studies: 104 Setting: cohort and case-control studies Target group: occupational, residential, environmental	PD linked with farming and the association with pesticides highly significant in self-reported diagnoses. Increased risk of PD with exposure to any type of pesticides and herbicides in case-control studies. The risk about two-folded with exposure to paraquat or maneb/mancozeb. The rural living was a risk factor for PD.
Ahmed et al., (2017)	France, Israel, USA, Canada, Korea, Italy, Turkey, Taiwan, Serbia, Australia, Portugal, India, Germany, China, Japan, Denmark, Norway, West Wales (UK), Brazil	N of studies: 64 Setting: 45 observational case-control studies on the relationship between pesticide exposure and PD, 3 on alterations of PD-related genes and 16 on both	The risk of PD increased with exposure to pesticides (OR 1.46, 95% CI 1.21-1.77). The risk of alterations in different PD pathogenesis-related genes increased with exposure to pesticides. The genes involved in alterations incl. GST (OR 1.97, 1.41-2.76), PON-1 (OR 1.32, 1.09-1.6), MDR1 (OR 2.06, 1.58-2.68) and SNCA (OR 1.28, 1.02-1.37).

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
		Target group: residential, environmental	
Yan. et al., (2018)	France, Serbia, China, Italy, USA, Germany, France, Netherlands	N of studies: 10 articles with 13 reports Setting: observational cohort and case-control studies (3 for cumulative and 10 for duration exposure) Target group:-	A nonlinearity association in duration exposure and PD risk found ($p=0.01$ for nonlinearity). The summary ORs of getting PD for 5 and 10 years of duration exposure was 1.05 (95% CI 1.02-1.09) and 1.11 (1.05-1.18), respectively. Pesticide duration exposure for 5 and 10 years linked with a 5 % and 11 % increase in the risk of PD, respectively
Tangamornsuksan, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 13 Setting: 12 case-control studies and 1 prospective cohort-study Target group: -	A statistically significant association between PD and paraquat exposure (OR = 1.64, 95% CI 1.27-2.13; the quantity of heterogeneity $I^2 = 24.8\%$).
Allen & Levy, (2013)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: case-control studies with a very few cohort studies Target group: occupational and non-occupational	Based on the summary effect sizes (ES), a significantly positive association between PD and overall pesticide use (non-occupational and/or occupational pesticide use) (1.42, 95% CI 1.32-1.5) as well as between PD and occupational pesticide exposure (1.49, 1.34-1.66). A significant association with both occupational herbicide and occupational insecticide exposure.
Mostafalou & Abdollahi, (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: 448, of which 33 on PD Setting: 26 case-control, 5 cohort and 2 cross-sectional studies Target group: occupational, environmental, residential, parental and maternal	A vast amount of evidence of the possible role of pesticides exposure and elevated incidence of PD. Harmful effects mostly related to insecticides and herbicides, especially organophosphorus, organochlorines, phenoxyacetic acids, and triazine compounds.

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19.9.2 Solvents

The results regarding the association between exposure of solvents and risk of PD are limited and weak and based on small study numbers and study subjects. Furthermore, in the study by Lock et al. (2013) both epidemiological and animal/toxicological evidence was introduced, but only epidemiological evidence is taken into account in this review. As already earlier mentioned, the search term “aprotic solvents” was most often replaced by the generic term of “solvents” in order to find relevant studies. There are various types of solvents, but in the search the different types of solvents were not specified. Often, however, the detailed results of different types of solvents were introduced in the studies selected. According to this limited research evidence, solvents may be associated with the risk of PD, but the results show some inconsistency, and the number of study subjects and relevant studies are mostly limited. Also, the study quality was sometimes regarded as a source of heterogeneity. The results are introduced in Table 42.

Table 42: Studies on solvents and PD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Lock et al., (2013)	Sweden, Germany, Italy, UK, USA, Scotland, Malta, Romania, Faroe Islands, Canada	N of studies: 15 epidemiological studies Setting: case-control or cohort studies Target group: occupational, residential	Weak results in various epidemiological studies regarding potential associations between solvents and PD; most of the RR estimates were in the range of 1.0-1.5. The most suggestive possible etiological results identified for TCE, PCE and carbon tetrachloride in the US twins study. A possible dose–response gradient with years of exposure observed in the UK Rolls Royce cohort, but little validate evidence from other studies. No consistent evidence of either the toxicological or epidemiological exposure mechanism of solvents in relation to PD.
Pezzoli & Cereda, (2013)	Not specified	N of studies: 104 Setting: cohort and case-control studies Target group: occupational, residential, environmental	Increased risk of PD found with exposure to solvents in case-control studies.

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19.9.3 Heavy metals Lead and Mercury

The evidence of Pb contributing to the increased risk of PD is limited, but despite the association between Pb and PD is suggested. Occupational exposure is the most common exposure pathway to consider in relation to Pb- induced diseases. The evidence regarding Hg exposure and risk of PD is limited and weak, but in spite a possible association exists according to the epidemiological studies investigated. The causal pathways are difficult to detect, however. The results are introduced in Table 43.

Table 43: Studies on heavy metals Pb, Hg and PD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 14, of which 5 on Pb Setting: case-control and cohort studies Target group: occupational	50 % (RR=1.57, 95 % CI 1.11-2.20) increased risk for PD with exposure to Pb.
Cicero et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: various on PD, and 6 on Hg Setting: case-control and ecological studies Target group: occupational	A possible positive association between Hg and PD according to 4 epidemiological studies.

19.10 Alzheimer's disease

In order to understand AD, one needs to get familiar with the concept of dementia. Dementia is an umbrella term for several diseases that are progressive and memory-affecting and interfere with cognitive abilities, behavior and daily living of persons affected (WHO, 2017). More specifically, dementia is a syndrome manifesting in deterioration of cognitive function; in greater extent compared to what might be expected from normal ageing. It influences the processes of memory, thinking, orientation, comprehension, learning and language capacity as well as judgement. Deterioration in emotional control, social behavior and motivation are often accompanied. Consciousness remains intact, however. Dementia, progressive cognitive impairment hindering the activities of daily living, causes a lot of dependence, disability and mortality. AD is regarded as the most common form of dementia, prevalent in approximately 50-75 % of the dementia cases, affecting mostly older people with the doubling amount of diagnoses every 5 years after the age of 65 years (WHO, 2019 Dementia; Lane et al., 2018; Prince et al., 2014). AD is a progressive disease, and often persons having the disease for longest are also in the need of higher level of care (Brookmeyer et al., 2007). According to the Consortium to Establish a Registry for Alzheimer's

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disease (CERAD), 6 years is suggested as a mean time of disease progression from mild to severe case by using the Clinical Dementia Rating Scale (CDR) (Neumann et al., 2001).

The neuropathological changes of AD consist of both positive and negative features. The pathology of AD is manifested mainly as amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs). Amyloid plaques are extracellular accumulations mainly consisting of abnormally folded A β with 40 or 42 amino acids (A β 40 and A β 42), the by-products of amyloid precursor protein (APP) metabolism. Neurofibrillary tangles, on the other hand, are mostly helical filaments consisting of hyperphosphorylated tau. Tau is a microtubule-associated protein, and in AD it is exposed to hyperphosphorylation, misfolding and aggregation, which gives rise to neurofibrillary tangles and neuropil threads. Positive lesions include abundant amyloid plaques and NFTs, neuropil threads and dystrophic neurites containing hyperphosphorylated tau accompanied by astrogliosis and microglial cell activation. Characteristic losses of neurons, neuropil and synaptic elements are basic negative features of AD (Lane et al., 2018; Serrano-Pozo et al., 2011 referring to various authors).

AD occurs mostly in a so-called sporadic form, but mutations in three genes – amyloid precursor protein (APP), presenilin 1 (PSEN1) and presenilin 2 (PSEN2) contribute to a rare (<0.5%), familial form of AD (fAD). In the rare form of AD, symptoms are detected earlier than in the sporadic form, namely between the ages of 30-50 years (Bateman et al., 2011). The common start of late onset AD is supposed to take place due to the combination of both genetic and environmental factors. The common perception is that approximately 70 % of AD risk is caused by genetic factors (Lane et al., 2018). The evidence from epidemiological studies has shown that the level of education and physical activity may protect from AD. Hypertension in the middle-age and diabetes may be factors increasing the risk for disease (Xu et al., 2015). Hersi and Irvine et al. (2017) identified risk factors for the onset and progression of AD including factors such as head injuries in males, age, diabetes mellitus, current smoking, depression, mild cognitive impairment, lower social engagement and exposure to pesticides. Regarding the genetic factors, the APOE gene, including the variants ϵ 2, ϵ 3 and ϵ 4, is the strongest predictor of AD; especially the APOE ϵ 4 has been shown to contribute strongly to the disease. Compared to non- ϵ 4 carriers, ϵ 4 heterozygotes cause an OR of approximately 3, which rise to 12 in homozygotes (Hersi & Irvine et al., 2017; Verghese et al., 2011). The protective factors include e.g. light-to-moderate alcohol consumption, a Mediterranean diet, education as well as regular physical and cognitive activities. Regarding genetics, the APOE ϵ 2-gene seems to have a protective effect for AD (Hersi & Irvine et al., 2017).

Diagnosis is based on the clinical assessment focused specifically on the clinical interview with the patient and a possible accompanying person, namely someone concerned about the functioning capabilities of a patient. Cognitive and focused physical examination is in order. The examination includes neuropsychological test in order to evaluate the magnitude of cognitive deficits against age-related values. Full blood tests are run to exclude conditions causing cognitive deficits, as well as structural imaging with computed tomography or MRI is applied to exclude structural abnormalities and provide help in diagnostics (Lane et al., 2018; Hort et al., 2010). MRI findings showing symmetrical medial temporal atrophy can be classified as a predictive marker of AD (Frisoni et al., 2010).

The ICD-10 code for AD is G30 under diseases of the nervous system (G00-G99) and other degenerative diseases of the nervous system (G30-G32) including senile and pre-senile forms. AD with early onset is labelled as G30.0 (onset typically before the age of 65) and AD with late onset as G30.1 (onset after the age of 65). Other AD is specified as G30.8 and unspecified AD as G30.9 (WHO, 2019 ICD-10). The ICD-11 code for AD is 8A20 under diseases of the nervous system (08)

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and disorders with neurocognitive impairment as a major feature (WHO, 2020 ICD-11). The International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC 2) - code for dementia is P70 (WONCA, 2016).

The exact and up-to-date data of dementia and AD is not easily separated, since the umbrella term of dementia is more common. The overall figures presented here derive mostly from the reports published by the Alzheimer`s Disease International (ADI), and the umbrella term dementia is used. ADI published global prevalence data on dementia in the World Alzheimer Report in 2009 (ADI 2009), and they based their data on a systematic review of 154 studies conducted worldwide as well as on population projections of United Nations (UN) through to the year 2050. In the updated reports published later on by the ADI and the WHO, the ADI 2009-report has been referred to, and figures have been revised based on the increased and current knowledge of the data. In 2015, there were 47 million people affected by dementia worldwide, and the figure was estimated to increase to 75 million in 2030 and to 132 million by 2050. Approximately 10 million new incidents of dementia develop every year (ADI, 2013; WHO, 2015; Prince et al., 2016). In 2015, there were roughly 10.5 million people living with dementia in Europe, and the expected numbers for 2030 and 2050 are 13.4 and 18.7 million, respectively. 58 % of all the people with dementia live in the low- or middle-income countries, and this number is predicted to rise to 63 % in 2030 and to 68 % in 2050 (Prince et al., 2015).

Estimated in 2015, the dementia prevalence was 5.2% worldwide, and the regional prevalence estimate for Europeans was 5.9%. The prevalence calculations were based on a systematic review of nearly 300 studies, and the numbers included people over 60 years of age. The incidence rates of dementia were derived from the same systematic review, and the incidence increases exponentially with increasing age. The incidence doubles with every 6.3-year increase in age, from 3.9/1000 person-years at age 60-64 to 104.8/1000 person-years at age ≥ 90 . The incidence rate seems to be slightly higher in the high-income countries compared to the low- or middle-income countries. Interestingly, the incidence rates have been on a rise in Asia, the Americas and Africa while the rates have decreased in Europe, and this tendency is expected to continue. The age- and gender-standardised incidence for people aged ≥ 60 in Western Europe was 17.29, and the regional distribution of new dementia cases in Europe was 2.5 million (25% of the worldwide total) in Europe. The estimated total costs of dementia were 818 billion US\$ (890.6 billion €) worldwide in 2015, and the costs were expected to rise to a trillion dollars by 2018 and to two trillion dollars by 2030. Of the total costs direct medical care costs make roughly 20 %, while direct social sector costs and informal care costs account both for approximately 40 % (Prince et al., 2015).

19.11 Environmental chemicals associated with Alzheimer`s disease

According to the literature search, most of the studies identified are related to pesticides. Exposure to pesticides seems to be associated with the risk of AD rather strongly. The evidence regarding Hg is slightly inconsistent and the amount of studies limited, but associations are possible. The associations between AD and Cd and As are less studied, and the results are inconsistent and contradictory to some extent. However, the evidence regarding Cd and As seem to be inclined towards the possible association between the substances and the disease, while the evidence regarding Pb is contradictory and weak. In the search terms both “dementia” and “Alzheimer`s disease” were used in order to cover the full spectrum of the disease.

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19.11.1 Pesticides

The evidence regarding the association between exposure to pesticides and risk of AD is rather solid. Occupational exposure plays a prominent role in the adverse health effects, and according to Yan et. al (2016) high-class cohort studies with prospective design are the most trustworthy in showing the associations between the exposure and the disease. The results are presented in Table 44.

Table 44: Studies on pesticides and AD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Gunnarsson & Bodin, (2019)	Not specified	N of studies: 31, of which 4 on AD Setting: at least one case-control study Target group: occupational	The weighted RR for AD was 1.50 (95% CI 0.98–2.29). Exposure to pesticides increased the risk of AD by at least 50 %.
Yan et al., (2016)	Canada, France, USA, Australia	N of studies: 7 Setting: 3 cohort and 4 case-control studies Target group: occupational	A positive association between pesticide exposure and AD: OR 1.34 (95% CI 1.08-1.67). The summary ORs from the crude and adjusted effect size studies: 1.14 (0.94-1.38, n=7) and 1.37 (1.09-1.71, n=5), respectively. Significant relationships in high-quality studies, but only half with statistical significance. A significantly increased risk in cohort studies (OR=1.37, 1.08-1.75), but not in case-control studies (OR=1.24, 0.78-1.97).
Killin et al., (2016)	Canada, USA, France, Netherlands, UK	N of studies: 60, of which 10 on pesticides Setting: 4 cohort, 2 cross-sectional (case-control), 2 review and 2 prospective longitudinal studies Target group: occupational, environmental, regional	An association between pesticides and increased risk of dementia found according to the reviews. An association between occupational exposure and dementia was rather weak. The strongest evidence found for exposure to pesticides, but findings were mixed.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Krewski et al., (2017)	Not specified	<p>N of studies: -</p> <p>Setting:-</p> <p>Target group: -</p> <p>Studies exploring the risk factors associated with the onset and progression of 14 neurological conditions including AD</p>	An increased risk with exposure to pesticides and AD with sufficient evidence, meaning that at least one systematic review rated of moderate/high quality has reviewed the available evidence and published a peer-reviewed report showing that a credible relationship exists.
Mostafalou & Abdollahi, (2017)	Not specified	<p>N of studies: 448, of which 6 on AD</p> <p>Setting: 2 case-control, 3 cohort and 1 ecological studies</p> <p>Target group: occupational, environmental</p>	In cohort studies, 1.4- and 2.4- times higher risk for the disease in people occupationally exposed to any pesticides and 1.5 increased risk of AD with exposure to organophosphorus and organochlorine compounds. Fumigants and defoliants linked to AD with RR of about 4.3. The prevalence of AD in people living in the areas using more pesticides two times higher than in others. In one study an OR of about 1.1 for the risk of AD in relation to pesticides and fertilisers, and in another study the blood level of DDE positively linked with the risk of disease with an OR of about 4.2. Most of the disorders investigated provoked by insecticides and herbicides, especially organophosphorus, organochlorines, phenoxyacetic acids and triazine compounds.
Santibáñez et al., (2007)	Not specified	<p>N of studies: 24, of which 6 on pesticides</p> <p>Setting: 21 case-control and 3 cohort studies</p> <p>Target group: occupational</p>	In the good quality and prospective design studies, increased and statistically significant associations between AD/dementia and pesticides exposure found.

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19.11.2 Heavy metals Cadmium, Arsenic, Lead and Mercury

The findings regarding heavy metals are inconsistent and limited, but nevertheless possible and tentative associations exist. In the review by Sharma et al. (2020) neurotoxic metals such as Pb, Hg, Cd and As as well as some pesticides were associated with AD. Also Xu et al. (2018) were able to show associations regarding Cd and Hg. Epidemiological data is limited in order to come up with an extensive conclusion on the role of Cd in relation to the disease. The role of As in the risk of AD is unclear, and based on this literature search forming a thorough conclusion is not possible. The review by Gong and O'Bryant (2010) introduced a mere hypothesis of As exposure instead of making a real synthesis of available evidence. Furthermore, they included both animal and epidemiological studies in their review. In the systematic review by Cicero et al. (2017) contradictory evidence was introduced; higher soil As-levels were associated with AD, but no such association was detected when measuring As-levels from biological samples. Regarding Pb the evidence is conflicting and weak. In the study by Xu et al. (2018) blood-Pb levels were reduced in AD patients compared to controls, and in the study by Santibáñez et al. (2007) there was no evidence between the association of professional exposure to Pb and AD/dementia. Based on the results, no conclusive statements of the associations between the heavy metals and risk of AD can be formed. The results are presented in Table 45.

Table 45: Studies on heavy metals Cd, As, Pb, Hg and AD

Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Xu et al., (2018)	Not specified	N of studies: 8 on Cd, 10 on Pb and 7 on Hg Setting: case-control Target group: AD patients and healthy subjects	Significantly more elevated circulatory levels of Cd (SMD=0.62, 95% CI 0.12-1.11) and Hg (SMD=0.55, 0.15-0.95) in AD patients than in controls. Reduced circulatory levels of Pb in AD patients compared to controls (SMD=-0.23, -0.38 - -0.07), Elevated Cd- and Hg-levels in the circulation, especially in serum, may contribute to the progression of AD.
Cicero et al., (2017)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: case-control and ecological studies Target group: -	As: Some evidence from epidemiological studies of an association between higher soil As-levels and higher rates of AD in European countries. No evidence from biological samples. Cd: Data on Cd brief and inconclusive. Pb: A possible association between blood-Pb levels and AD in several case-control studies, but a significant increase of Pb-concentration in only one study. In two studies of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) contradictory results found; one showed no difference and another reduced concentration of Pb. In one study reduced Pb concentration in

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
			hair, but no difference in nail samples. Hg: An inverse relation between Hg excretion and cognitive functions in exposed workers. In 4 case-control studies higher Hg levels in AD cases compared to controls. In other studies lower concentrations of Hg or no difference. No differences in CSF Hg concentration. Nail-Hg concentrations lower in AD patients and inconsistent findings in the hair-Hg.
Gong & O`Bryant, (2010)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: - Target group: - Both animal and epidemiological studies included	As-exposure hypothesis suggesting a simple mechanism for AD development and progression in certain AD patients. As linked to reduced memory and intellectual abilities.
Santibáñez et al., (2007)	Not specified	N of studies: 24, of which 6 on Pb Setting: 21 case-control and 3 cohort studies Target group: occupational	No evidence of association of Pb.
Mutter et al., (2010)	Not specified	N of studies: 88 Setting: mainly case-control or comparative cohort studies (8 animal studies) Target group: occupational	Significant memory deficits found in individuals exposed to inorganic Hg in 32 out of 40 studies. In some autopsy studies showed elevated Hg-levels in brain tissues of AD patients. Inorganic Hg may have a role in the development of AD, and it may increase the pathological influence of other metals and promote neurodegenerative disorders. Measurements of Hg-levels in blood, urine, hair, nails, and CSF showed inconsistencies. In epidemiological studies weaker influence of inorganic Hg on the nervous system found than in animal and in vitro-studies.

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Author and year	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group	Main findings and conclusions
Sharma et al., (2020)	Not specified	N of studies: - Setting: - Target group: - Collects the available data for human neurotoxicity caused by toxic chemicals.	Neurotoxic metals such as Pb, Hg, Cd and As as well as some pesticides have been associated with AD due to their ability to produce senile/amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles (NFTs).

19.12 Highlights

Exposure to environmental substances may be associated with an increased risk of ADHD and ASD. However, the body of evidence varies markedly between the substances and there are inconsistencies between the individual studies.

Among the substances covered here, the substances with most conclusive evidence of an association with ADHD are lead (Pb), phthalates and bisphenol A (BPA). For ASD, the respective substances are lead and mercury. For the association between polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs) and mercury (Hg) with ADHD as well as for phthalates and ASD the evidence is less abundant, but the findings can be interpreted as suggestive of an association. Further research is needed to draw a more decisive conclusion regarding the relevance of these as well as other potential substances in the etiology of ADHD and ASD.

Regarding the risk of ALS, the most solid and vast evidence was detected regarding pesticides and Pb. The amount of evidence of Cd, solvents and Hg was less consistent and scarce. However, even for Cd and solvents, the evidence was inclined to support the association between chemical exposure and risk of disease, whereas for Hg the evidence was less coherent.

The increased risk of getting PD was mostly associated to pesticides, from which the vastest amount of literature and the strongest evidence was detected. In spite of the limited number of studies regarding exposure to solvents, Pb and Hg, they all seemed to indicate possible associations with the risk of PD.

Considering the risk of AD, exposure to pesticides seemed to be the strongest contributor among the substances selected. With Hg, associations are possible, but inconsistent. Also, with Cd and As the results are incomplete, but in spite, inclined towards the possible association between the substances and the risk of disease. Instead, the evidence regarding Pb is weak, and a possible association between the substance and the disease cannot be established.

For all the diseases, the most convincing evidence was found in pesticides. Regarding the other substances selected, Cd, solvents, Pb, As, and Hg, the evidence of the risk of the specific neurological disorders was limited and contradictory. However, there is a possibility of the association between these substances and the neurological diseases in question.

Furthermore, one evident finding from this review was that in most of the studies investigated, the harmful chemicals exposures were connected to the occupational settings. Thus, close attention

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should be paid on the health effects of certain occupation groups, such as farmers, since e.g. pesticides exposure seems to be associated with increased disease rates of all the selected neurological diseases. There are indications that also heavy metal exposures are most harmful at the occupational exposure levels in relation to the diseases.

Occasionally, gene relations were discussed in connection with chemicals and neurological disorders. Regarding exposure to pesticides and PD, Ahmed et al. (2017) found, that in addition to pesticides being linked to PD, exposure to pesticides affects various PD pathogenesis-related genes by increasing alterations in the certain genes such as GST, PON-1, MDR1 and SNCA, but no statistically significant alterations were detected in genes CYP2D6, SLC6A3, MnSOD, NQO1 or PON-2. Therefore, pesticides exposure was substantially associated with both the risk of PD and alterations in PD pathogenesis-involved genes.

The scope of the epidemiological studies regarding environmental substances and neurological diseases is still limited and there are inconsistencies in results between the studies. Further and extensive multidisciplinary epidemiological research is strongly warranted in order to learn more about the association between the substances and neurological disorders and protect the public health.

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20 Conclusions

This deliverable compiled the current knowledge on the association of the HBM4EU rounds 1 and 2 priority substances and selected health outcomes. The level of evidence ranged substantially between the substances and outcomes, and more research is needed to confirm the partly suggestive findings.

This report updates and extends the information about known associations between health outcomes and HBM4EU priority substances (see Table 46). It is evident that individual health outcomes are affected by several environmental substances. Medical doctors and public health professionals should be better informed about these environmental risk factors in addition to traditional risk factors especially among diseases which have high disease burden and thereby generate high direct and indirect health care costs.

The current literature on the association between health outcomes and environmental exposures is based on observational studies, as experimental studies would not be ethically approved. Observational studies cannot be used to show causal effects, only associations. They are also known to be prone for bias and confounders. For example, because of possible non-response bias, the survey participants may not represent the original study population. Furthermore, the effect of confounding factors, such as smoking, may not have been fully eliminated and discussed in the biomonitoring studies.

When observational studies are based on survey data, where information about health outcome is based on self-reported information or possibly objective measurement, we have to keep in mind the possible biases related to the measurements. Self-reported information easily suffers from reporting, recall and awareness bias. People may not know what to report their illnesses, they don't remember that they have been diagnosed for some health condition or they are unaware of their existing health condition. A simple example about awareness is hypertension which is asymptomatic for a long time and if a person does not have his/her blood pressure measured regularly, he/she may not know about existing hypertension. Survey data is also prone for non-response bias when those who participate don't necessarily represent the target population in respect to some health outcomes. For example, obese people are known to be more often non-respondents than people with normal weight.

The methods of the reviewed HBM studies varied substantially and the results may often not be generalised to other populations. Especially for some chemicals, such as pesticides and flame retardants, the exposure and thereby also the respective biomonitoring studies have focused on specific occupational groups instead of the general population. Among occupational groups, exposure times are often longer and exposure levels substantially higher than among the general population. Further studies are needed to confirm the causal relationship between many of the environmental substances and health outcomes.

To achieve possibly comparable results in future biomonitoring studies, the use of standardised measurement methods is essential both in regards to measures of chemical exposure as well as measures of health outcomes.

Thus far, Human Biomonitoring studies have not been widely included in health examination surveys. However, this might be a feasible and cost-effective way to conduct biomonitoring studies. Combining HBM and health studies would provide extensive data regarding environmental chemical exposure and different health outcomes.

In countries where record linkage is possible by existing legislation and required identifiers in the data sets, information about health outcomes could be obtained by linking HBM data to

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administrative registers such as primary care, out-patient and hospitalisation registers. This is a very cost-effective way to obtain information on the disease history of individuals. Moreover, administrative registers can provide follow-up information on health outcomes and disease incidence. Through record linkage a cross-sectional HBM study could be transformed into a cohort study.

Table 46: Observed associations between health outcomes and HBM4EU priority substances

Health outcome		HBM4EU priority substances																
		Acrylamide	Aniline family	Aprotic solvents	Arsenic	Bisphenols	Cadmium	Chromium VI	Diisocyanates	Flame retardants	Lead	Mercury	Mycotoxins	Pesticides	PAHs	PFAS	Phthalates + DINCH	UV-filters
Cardiovas-cular disease (CVD)	CVD overall				x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Hypertension				x	x	x				x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Ischemic heart disease (IHD)				x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Stroke				x	x	x				x			x		x	x	
Metabolic syndrome (MetS)	Metabolic syndrome overall					x					x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Obesity				x	x	x							x	x	x		
	Glucose metabolism/ Diabetes				x	x	x					x		x	x			
	Lipid metabolism				x	x	x							x		x	x	
Reproductive health	AGD		x			x				x				x		x	x	
	Cryptorchidism		x							x				x				
	Hypospadias					x				x	x			x			x	
	Semen quality				x	x	x				x	x		x	x	x	x	x
	Sperm DNA damage				x	x					x	x		x	x		x	
	Reproductive hormones		x			x	x				x	x		x	x	x	x	x

Health outcome		HBM4EU priority substances																
		Acrylamide	Aniline family	Aprotic solvents	Arsenic	Bisphenols	Cadmium	Chromium VI	Diisocyanates	Flame retardants	Lead	Mercury	Mycotoxins	Pesticides	PAHs	PFAS	Phthalates + DINCH	UV-filters
	Fertility & Fecundity				x	x	x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x
	Fetal development	x			x	x	x			x		x		x	x	x	x	x
	Kidney function				x		x				x	x	x	x	x	x		x
	Liver function											x	x		x	x		x
	Osteoporosis				x	x	x				x	x			x	x	x	
Hematological system	Anemia		x		x		x	x			x	x					x	
	Hemoglobin levels				x		x	x			x	x			x	x	x	
	Basophilic stippling										x							
	Gestational thrombocytopenia				x		x	x			x							
	Red blood cell count							x										
	Hematocrit							x							x			
	Eosinophilia							x										
	Hemolysis														x			
	Hematological cells number alterations													x				

Health outcome		HBM4EU priority substances																
		Acrylamide	Aniline family	Aprotic solvents	Arsenic	Bisphenols	Cadmium	Chromium VI	Diisocyanates	Flame retardants	Lead	Mercury	Mycotoxins	Pesticides	PAHs	PFAS	Phthalates + DINCH	UV-filters
	Monoclonal gammopathy													x				
	Methemoglobinemia		x															
Asthma					x		x	x	x		x	x		x	x	x	x	
Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)					x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x			
Skin irritation and inflammation		x	x	x	x			x	x					x	x			
Cognitive development and neurological disorders	ADHD					x	x			x	x	x		x	x	x	x	
	Autism										x	x	x	x			x	
	Amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS)			x			x				x	x		x				
	Parkinson's disease			x							x	x		x				
	Alzheimer's disease				x		x				x	x		x				
Cancer	Breast/ other female cancer	x		x		x	x							x	x		x	
	Prostate cancer						x							x				
	Childhood cancers										x			x				

Health outcome		HBM4EU priority substances															
		Acrylamide	Aniline family	Aprotic solvents	Arsenic	Bisphenols	Cadmium	Chromium VI	Diisocyanates	Flame retardants	Lead	Mercury	Mycotoxins	Pesticides	PAHs	PFAS	Phthalates + DINCH
	Lymphoma/non-Hodking's lymphoma								x				x				
	Bladder/ urothelial cancer		x		x								x				
	Lung/respiratory cancer				x	x		x						x			
	Thyroid cancer								x				x			x	
	Stomach/ colon cancer						x		x								
	Kidney/liver/ pancreatic cancer	x			x	x						x			x		
	Skin cancer				x								x				
	Brain cancer									x							
	Other					x	x			x							

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22 Appendixes

22.1 Appendix 1: Carotid Doppler ultrasonography protocol

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Carotid doppler ultrasonography protocol

Rationale

Ischemic heart disease and stroke are worldwide number one and two causes of death (WHO, 2019a). High blood pressure, glucose and lipids and overweight and obesity predict risk for cardiovascular diseases and end-points (WHO, 2019b). Silent arterial wall alterations precede clinical vascular events and indicate atherosclerotic disease (Touboul et al., 2012). Early morphological changes in the arterial walls can be visualised by carotid Doppler ultrasonography which is a noninvasive, commonly available and one of the best techniques for detection of the early stages of arterial with high-resolution (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Carovac et al., 2011; Kokubo et al., 2018).

Local intima-media thickness (IMT) in the carotid arteries associates with the cardiovascular risk factors and the incidence of cardiovascular diseases, and is, additionally, an independent risk factor for stroke and myocardial infarction. IMT is used as a parameter of atherosclerosis. However, in addition to early atherosclerosis, it reflects non-atherosclerotic medial hypertrophy (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Kokubo et al., 2018; Laurent et al., 2006; ACCF, 2012).

The result of the IMT measurement is dependent of the operator, and therefore, it's important to use standardised techniques (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Kokubo et al., 2018; Laurent et al., 2006; ACCF, 2012).

This guideline gives a common description about how to conduct a carotid ultrasonography for adults in health examination survey.

Basic background about ultrasonography and measuring carotid artery with it

Medical ultrasonography

Medical ultrasonography is a diagnostic imaging technique which is used for imaging internal body structures. Ultrasound waves have higher frequencies that are audible to human ear (>20,000 Hz), and in ultrasonography technique waves are sent from probe to tissue and back from tissue to probe. Different tissues have different reflection properties for ultrasound and the image is formatted by computer according to these reflections. The energy of ultrasound generally decreases with the distance and, therefore, the quality of the image decrease in the distal part of the field. The higher the frequency of ultrasound is the higher is the resolution and the lower is the depth to explore (Touboul et al., 2012; Carovac et al., 2011).

The most commonly used technique is B-mode imaging which displays the acoustic impedance of two-dimensional cross-section of the tissue. In vascular imaging this technique is combined with Doppler technique which images movement of the tissues and their velocity. With these techniques in the area of carotid artery, for instance, can be visualised anatomy, blood flow, IMT and stenosis of arteries (Touboul et al., 2012; Carovac et al., 2011).

Color Doppler technique

Color Doppler gives color-encoded velocity information in ultrasonography measurement and it is a good tool for visualising blood flow in the vessels and finding stenotic segments. In this technique should be used a linear probe with a measurement angle between 30° and 60°. The right angle is

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substantial for measurement. It might help to find the angle if operator pushes head to side to create a bit angle between the probe surface and the artery (Lee, 2014; Carovac et al., 2011; ACCF, 2012).

It's important to adjust velocity of the blood flow in Doppler while the velocity is fastest in the stenotic segment of vessel and an aliasing artifact can be seen. The scale setting for velocity should be adjusted for each subject, yet, the normal velocity in the common carotid artery is 30–40 cm/sec. There is a consensus for the diagnosis of carotid artery stenosis by Doppler ultrasonography and a good example of reporting this (please see reference number 4) (Lee, 2014; Carovac et al., 2011).

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<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:ColourDopplerA.jpg>. Date last accessed 2 April 2019.

Figure 12: Color Doppler ultrasonography picture from common carotid artery

Anatomy of carotid arteries and technique for differentiating sides and internal and external carotid arteries (ICA and ECA)

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<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Gray506.svg>. Last accessed April 2 2019.

Figure 13: Anatomy of arteries descending from the aorta

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https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Blausen_0170_CarotidArteries.png. Date last accessed April 2 2019.

Figure 14: Anatomy of carotid arteries

Right and left common carotid arteries

It's important to visualise anatomy on both sides on the neck properly while the location of the occluded artery should be determined. The right carotid artery arises from the right brachiocephalic artery and the most proximal segment of the common carotid artery can be visualised by ultrasonography. The left common carotid artery arises from the aortic arch and the proximal

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segment of the left common carotid artery can't be visualised by ultrasonography (Picture 2) (Lee, 2014).

ICA and ECA

ICA and ECA should be differentiated on both sides. ICA is larger than ECA and located posterior and lateral to the ECA. ICA does not have branches but ECA has (such as the lingual artery). The Doppler spectrums from the ICA show a lower resistive pattern, and the velocity difference between the systolic and diastolic phase of the ICA is smaller than that of the ECA. "Temporal tapping" is an artefact sign which can be induced only on ECA. On this technique fingertips are placed on the ipsilateral temporal artery. This generates a serration-like artifact to the Doppler spectrum on the ECA in the analysed side (Picture 3) (Lee, 2014).

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Figure 15: Microscopic anatomy of an artery

Measuring IMT

IMT is measured on the distal part of the common carotid artery on a wall segment without focal lesions. Compared to common carotid artery ICA has an angle of the beam and is located deeper, and additionally, focal atherosclerotic lesions are much more common in the ICA (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014).

IMT is measured with an ultrasonography device as a two-dimensional (2D) gray-scale image. In optimal view carotid artery should be parallel to the probe surface to minimise the overestimation of the IMT from the diagonal measurement and in a longitudinal image. This view passes by the center of the carotid artery and shows two bright interfaces along the artery wall. The upper bright line is the interface between the blood and intima and the lower bright line is the interface between the media and adventitia layer. The interface between the intima and media does not produce any interface. The distance between the upper and lower bright line represents the thickness of the intima and media layer (Picture 4) (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Carovac et al., 2011).

Plaques and stenosis

Plaque is defined as a focal change which encroaches minimum 0.5 mm or 50% of the surrounding IMT in the wall of arteria or has a thickness of >1.5 mm from the media-adventitia to the intima-lumen interface. The classification of stenosis is normal (no plaque, no stenosis), plaque but no stenosis, mild stenosis (<50%), moderate stenosis (50–69%) and severe stenosis (70–99%) (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; ACCF, 2012).

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When predicting risk for cardiovascular events also morphology of the plaque is important, and it's recommended describe plaques morphology according to standards. This includes plaque's echogenicity (echogenic, echolucent, heterogeneous or iso-echoic plaque, the last meaning intima media complex), surface (smooth, irregular or ulcerated) and the presence of ulceration which means depression on the plaque's surface (cystic, bridge-shaped, sponge-shaped or a simple depression) and stenosis. Additionally, plaque's size should be measured (length and height), though, volume of the plaque can't be determined on 2D-scan (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014).

Protocol

Equipment

There are multiple ultrasonography devices on market and the selection of device should occur according to the requirements in the current study. Common requirements for ultrasonography device in health examination survey are that the device should be reliable, simple to use, fast, strong, in common use and filling common standards. To keep up a constant quality the use of the same device type for all participants through the survey is recommended (Touboul et al., 2012; Carovac et al., 2011; Kokubo et al., 2018; Laurent et al., 2006; ACCF, 2012)

A linear probe should be used in the measurements of carotid artery. The general settings for an optimal image quality are: appropriate depth of focus (30–40 mm), optimal frame rate (5–25 Hz) and appropriate gain settings (minimal intraluminal artifacts) (Touboul et al., 2012; Carovac et al., 2011; Laurent et al., 2006; Koivistoinen et al., 2012; Raitakari et al., 2003).

Each manufacturer producing ultrasonography devices has their own instructions for use. Manufacturers have a responsibility to produce devices and software which satisfies the common standards and recommendations. However, the user is responsible for ensuring that the used device and software satisfies these recommendations before, during and after the survey.

Figure 16: Ultrasonography device

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Setting up measurement site

Carotid ultrasonography should be performed in a safe, quiet, comfortable and private place if possible, and the subject should be treated with dignity and respect. Subject's personal data should be handled in a confidential and secure way. If possible, cultural sensitivities should be respected. Each measurement point should have a bed, space for ultrasonography device, probe and other required articles and a seat for the examiner, and the measurement points should at least be divided with curtains (Lee, 2014; Laurent et al., 2006).

Exclusion criterion

Carotid ultrasonography should not be performed if subject can't transfer to exam table by his-/herself or with assistance, for instance if subject is sitting on wheelchair. No other exclusion criterion.

Measurement procedures

The measurement position

Before the survey should be decided whether the carotid ultrasonography is performed on overhead or lateral position. In the overhead position technician sits beyond subject's head beside the end of the examination table and uses two hands for ultrasonography. In this position the sonic window can be made wider which offers a clear view to the carotid artery especially from the posterolateral projection. Lateral sitting position is used in most other ultrasonography examinations. In this position it's easy to control ultrasonography device but view to the right posterior projection is more difficult. Between these two the overhead position is recommended. To ensure reproducibility and high quality of the measurements the same position should be used for each measurement during the survey (Lee, 2014; Laurent et al., 2006).

The measurement protocol

It's a different examination when a technician performs carotid ultrasonography in health examination survey with a standard technique and when a physician performs a clinical carotid ultrasonography in the department of radiology as a part of clinical examination. In health examination survey the ultrasonography technique should be simple, fast and performed in routine with the same standardised measurement protocol for each subject (Touboul et al., 2012; Kokubo et al., 2018; ACCF, 2012; Koivistoinen et al., 2012; Raitakari et al., 2003; Heistaro, 2008).

There is no single standardised method for measuring IMT and, therefore, in previous surveys protocols have been various depending on the resources and focus of the survey. For instance, in one previous study the mean IMT of the left carotid artery was measured by technician, in another study the mean IMT was determined from the right carotid artery from three subsequent measurements by technician and in third ultrasonography was performed on both sides by a physician (Touboul et al., 2012; Kokubo et al., 2018; Koivistoinen et al., 2012; Raitakari et al., 2003; Heistaro, 2008).

In one of these studies the IMT measurement protocol was following: technician focused the image on the posterior wall of the artery and the quality of the image was optimised. To record an image a 25 mm wide and 15 mm high a resolution box function (zoom) was used. This zoomed image was recorded from an angle which showed the greatest distance between the lumen-intima interface and the media-adventitia interface. Then a moving scan with 5 s duration was recorded. The scan included a view about the beginning of the carotid bifurcation and the common carotid artery. This recorded data was stored in digital format for subsequent off-line analysis (Raitakari et al., 2003).

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The protocol for the current health examination survey should be determined according to the focus of the survey and available resources.

General

It should be checked daily that equipment and all supplies are available for each subject.

Technician should clean hands by washing them and/or using alcohol gel before, after and in between each subject.

The ultrasonography probe should be cleaned in between each subject.

The examination bed should be positioned on right position (tilted about 45°) (Lee, 2014).

The use of soft paper for cleaning ultrasonography gel after performing examination is recommended.

Preparing ultrasonography device, general

Ultrasonography device should be prepared for survey and for each measurement according to manufacturer's guidelines. This includes programming filters and other software according to general regulations and checking these regularly to achieve desirable sensitivity and specificity (Carovac et al., 2011; Laurent et al., 2006; Koivistoinen et al., 2012). General instructions for ultrasonography device:

Ultrasonography device should be cleaned when necessary.

Device's parts should be inspected regularly for fraying or other damage and it should be checked regularly that all parts are attached safely.

The device should have enough battery charge.

It should be decided beforehand whether a paper printout of measured results is printed out, in addition to, digitally saved data.

Other preparations before the measurement

Room temperature should be kept stable (22 ± 1 °C) (Laurent et al., 2006).

Subject should be informed beforehand that he/she should not eat or drink in 3 hours and use alcohol in 10 hours before measurement (Laurent et al., 2006).

Daily procedures during the survey

- Check that all necessary equipment and supplies are available for every day and subject.
- Check that all settings on device are correct.
- Check that exam bed is clean.

Measurement procedure for standard carotid ultrasonography (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Laurent et al., 2006)

Enter the following data on computer before performing ultrasonography:

- Subjects ID code (and name and surname if necessary)
- Age
- Sex
- Date and time of the measurement

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Protocol

1. Ask subject to take of shirt so that neck and over part of the chest are open and easily visible.
2. Place bed in position with 45° upright.
3. Ask subject to lie on supine position on the bed arms located at the side of the body and legs side by side. Subject should lie on this position at least 10 minutes before the measurement.
4. The subject should feel as comfortable as possible and the neck should be relaxed.
5. Ask him/her to breathe regularly and not to talk or move during the measurement.
6. Protect clothes with a paper from gel if necessary.
7. Subject's neck should be tilted about 45° on the side of the artery being examined.
8. Put gel on the area measured.
9. Check that you have a moving ultrasonography picture with a good quality on computer's screen.
10. Search and visualise carotid arteries and anatomy of the area
11. Optimise the quality of your view.
12. Make measurements. Do each measurement routinely with the same standard technique as beforehand determined.
13. Save the determined data digitally and print one version for the survey (if this belongs to the protocol).
14. Clean subject's neck and chest from the gel.
15. Clean the bed, probe, ultrasound device and the room for the next subject.

Artefacts and possible errors

Technician should understand the basic technical background about ultrasound, recording ultrasonography, the effect of various factors for the quality and appearance in ultrasonography and various messages about errors from used ultrasonography device. Below are listed some common technical errors (Lee, 2014):

1. The most common reason for a bad quality on ultrasonography picture is a poor contact between ultrasonography probe and skin. Suggestion: add gel.
2. Another common reason for a bad image quality is that the settings are not right. Suggestion: optimise the quality of the image.
3. And a third common reason for bad image quality is a technical error. Suggestion: check routinely computer's settings, check that you use the right ultrasonography probe and that the probe is right side up.

Contraction on sternocleidomastoideus cause poor ultrasound penetration. Suggestion: try to make the subject feel as comfortable as possible.

Calcified atheroma and a difficulty to find a proper ultrasound window. Suggestion: try different ultrasound window. In this does not help, subject might need after the survey another imaging modality to describe atheroma.

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Tension on lead wires.

Wrong placement of ultrasonography probe. Suggestion: check placement of the probe.

Interference from nearby electrical equipment. Suggestion: Check beforehand that there is no equipment near which could cause interference. Watches, glasses, rings and bracelets do not cause interference.

Variation in body habitus, such as marked obesity

Poor quality in carotid ultrasonography noticed afterwards. Suggestion: check the quality of determined measurements and saved and printed data in routine. Survey should, additionally, have an official quality control program which should detect if there is repeating problem in quality.

Analysing carotid ultrasonography

IMT should be measured with the same, beforehand determined and standardised process for each subject. Technician has a remarkable responsibility to measure IMT with the same process for each subject. Technique for measuring IMT with ultrasonography includes many possible failures and measurements errors and is dependent on technician's technique and experience. Therefore, survey should also have a continuous quality control organised by the coordinating team (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; ACCF, 2012). To ensure quality, digitally stored scans should be analysed after the survey manually by another reader blinded to participant's personnel data. To ensure reproducibility some subjects should be re-examined after the initial visit (a random sample) (Raitakari et al., 2003).

Information to be recording

Beforehand should be determined that which variables are measured and how these are measured and reported. There are available forms for reporting measured variables (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; ACCF, 2012; Raitakari et al., 2003). Determined variables from carotid thickness should be saved digitally and one paper copy printed for survey purpose (if so determined in study protocol).

There should be a plan how and where the measured data is transmitted and saved and where a backup copy is saved after each subject and survey day. Additionally, there should be a backup plan if measured data can't be saved electronically (for instance taking a printed copy from each measurement). If saving a printed copy for survey purpose the copies should be stored in cool, dry and dark place.

If IMT not measured according to determined instructions or at all, this and the reason should be recorded. The reasons not to measure IMT could be that subject refuses, there is no time to measure IMT, subject is physically or mentally unable to cooperate or do not understand instructions, carotid arteria can't be visualised, equipment does not work, paper run out etc.

Feedback to participants

Subject should have a possibility to discuss with a nurse or a doctor to get an interpretation from measured results and information where to search for more medical help or examinations when carotid ultrasonography is not interpreted as normal. The feedback can be organised also by phone after the survey. There are international clinical guidelines for specialists for follow-up and treatment indications for measured carotid stenosis. However, interpreting results from IMT measurement is normally not a job for a general practitioner and they should not a responsibility to interpret results from a survey (ACCF, 2012).

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Safety

There are no major risks in measuring IMT. However, there should be a backup plan if technician suspect that subject is feeling uncomfortable or the measured results are extremely abnormal. This could be for instance a medical background to consult by phone.

Ultrasonography devices and probes should qualify the current norms. If suspicion of malfunction (broken wire etc) the device should not be used and replaced with another similar one. If carotid thickness is not measured this should be recorded.

Quality assurance

General

Beforehand should be determined and standardised which variables are measured and how these are measured and reported. A standardised form for reporting measured variables should be used (Touboul et al., 2012; ACCF, 2012).

To guarantee the quality and reproducibility of an IMT measurement in survey, there should be a continuing quality control program according to beforehand agreed regulations. There should be a coordinating office/ fieldwork supervisor in charge for quality control, standardisation and technicians' education and support before and during the survey. The common quality control in survey includes calibration and test-performance procedures and technician's control for the quality of each carotid thickness measurement during and after measurement.

Manufacturer's guidelines about device's the standard hygienic regulations and other procedures performed routinely weekly, daily, in between each subject and when an error occur should be followed. Device should be checked regularly to ensure that the standards are met and replaced with another similar one if device is not working in regular tests or in practice as it should be. Each check should be recorded in the log book.

Training for technicians performing carotid Doppler ultrasonography

The high-quality education of technician is the most important guarantee for a qualified and reproducible carotid IMT measurement (see instructions above and Pictures 2, 3 and 4). Measuring IMT by ultrasonography is especially dependent of technician's skills and technique. Technicians should follow a standard measurement protocol (Touboul et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; ACCF, 2012; Koivisto et al., 2012). The education should cover both theoretical learning and training in practice – including sufficiently performed measurements of carotid artery according to survey's protocol with the device used in survey, working with the ultrasonography device and software used in survey, learning the quality control and hygienic rules associating with ultrasonography working. This education can be organised in specific courses or by coordinators in the current survey.

In addition to technical expertise, technicians should have a basic clinical knowledge about vessels anatomy, background about IMT measurement and background about ultrasonography. This includes primary education for health-related sciences, such as nursing or medical assistant.

Acceptability and reproducibility criterions

Standardised protocol agreed beforehand should be followed. Measuring IMT not according to these criterions does not fulfill acceptability and reproducibility criterions.

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Calibration

Device should be calibrated according to manufacturer's guidelines. Each check should be recorded in the log book.

Regular check-ups

The importance of qualified education for technicians measuring carotid thickness can't highlight excessively. Technician's should control the quality of each IMT measurement to ensure that the quality criteria are fulfilled. Technicians' should perform a regular quality control and keep a log book about the regular checks. Additionally, the coordinating office/ fieldwork supervisors should participate in regular quality control during the fieldwork by observing measurements regularly in practice and monitoring recorded data.

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22.2 Appendix 2: Standardised questions for HBM4EU, EHES and EHIS

Authors: Tolonen Hanna (THL)

Appendix table 1: Standardised questions for HBM4EU, EHES and EHIS

Health outcome	HBM4EU question(s) https://www.hbm4eu.eu/online-library/ folder Quidelines, Protocols and SOPs/Harmonised questionnaires	EHES question(s) http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-302-701-5	EHIS question(s) https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/8762193/KS-02-18-240-EN-N.pdf/
Obesity	How tall are you without shoes (in cm)? ____ cm How much do you weight without clothes and shoes (in kg)? ____ kg	How tall are you without shoes? (in cm) ____ cm How much do you weight without clothes and shoes? (in kg) ____ kg	How tall are you without shoes? in [cm] ____ ____ [cm] How much do you weigh without clothes and shoes? in [kg] ____ [kg]
Asthma	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed Asthma (allergic asthma included) Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ Specific questions under Mycotoxins		During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No Asthma (allergic asthma included)

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	<p>Specific question for Arsenic: Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?</p> <p>Asthma Yes No Don't know (nearly) never 1-3 per month 1 per week 2-3 per week 4-6 per week Everyday</p>		
COPD	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), emphysema Never Yes, in the past 12 months</p>		<p>During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No Chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, emphysema</p>

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	Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ ____		
CHD	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed - A myocardial infarction - Coronary heart disease (angina pectoris) Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ ____	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? Yes No - Myocardial infarction (heart attack) - Coronary heart disease or angina pectoris	During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No - A myocardial infarction (heart attack) or chronic consequences of myocardial infarction - A coronary heart disease or angina pectoris
Hypertension	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed High blood pressure (hypertension) Never Yes, in the past 12 months	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? Yes No High blood pressure (hypertension)	During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No High blood pressure

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	<p>Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p> <p>Specific question under Arsenic, Mercury</p> <p>Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?</p> <p>Hypertension Yes No Don't know (nearly) never 1-3 per month 1 per week 2-3 per week 4-6 per week Everyday</p>		
Antihypertensive medication	During the past two weeks, have you used any medicines that were prescribed for you by a doctor for...? - High blood pressure	During the past two weeks, have you used any medicines that were prescribed for you by a doctor? Yes No	

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	Yes No Don't know	Were the medicines for...? (Asked if the previous question = "Yes") - High blood pressure	
High cholesterol	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed Elevated blood cholesterol Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? Yes No Elevated blood cholesterol	During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No High blood lipids
Stroke	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed Stroke (cerebral haemorrhage, cerebral thrombosis) Never Yes, in the past 12 months	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? Yes No Stroke (cerebral haemorrhage, cerebral thrombosis)	During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No A stroke (cerebral haemorrhage, cerebral thrombosis) or chronic consequences of stroke

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	Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ ____		
Osteoporosis	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed Osteoporosis Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know Age at diagnosis ____ ____		
Diabetes	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed Diabetes Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? Yes No Diabetes	During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions? Yes No Diabetes

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	Age at diagnosis ____ ____		
Liver function	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?</p> <p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Cirrhosis of the liver, liver dysfunction</p> <p>Never</p> <p>Yes, in the past 12 months</p> <p>Yes, more than 1 year ago</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p>		<p>During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions?</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Cirrhosis of the liver</p>
Kidney function	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?</p> <p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Kidney disease or dysfunction</p> <p>Never</p> <p>Yes, in the past 12 months</p> <p>Yes, more than 1 year ago</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p>		<p>During the past 12 months, have you had any of the following diseases or conditions?</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Kidney problems</p>

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Cancer	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?</p> <p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Cancer (malignant tumour, also including leukaemia and lymphoma) (see next question to specify kind of cancer)</p> <p>Never Yes, in the past 12 months Yes, more than 1 year ago Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p> <p>Additional question on cancer types: If you answered "Yes" for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer.</p> <p>Bladder Blood Bone Breast Cervix (cervical) Colon Esophagus (esophageal) Brain</p>		

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	Gallbladder Kidney Larynx/ Windpipe Leukaemia Liver Lung Lymphoma/ Hodgkin's disease Melanoma Mouth/ tongue/lip Nervous System Ovary (ovarian) Pancreas (pancreatic) Rectum (rectal) Skin (non-melanoma) Skin (don't know what kind) Rectum (rectal) Soft tissue (muscle or fat) Stomach Testis (testicular) Thyroid Uterus (uterine) Other, Specify.....		
ADHD	Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?		

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	<p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Attention deficit disorders (ADD, ADHD)</p> <p>Never</p> <p>Yes, in the past 12 months</p> <p>Yes, more than 1 year ago</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p>		
Autism spectrum disorder (ASD)	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?</p> <p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Autism</p> <p>Never</p> <p>Yes, in the past 12 months</p> <p>Yes, more than 1 year ago</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ____ ____</p>		
Parkinson's disease	<p>Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor?</p>		

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	<p>If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p> <p>Parkinson's disease</p> <p>Never</p> <p>Yes, in the past 12 months</p> <p>Yes, more than 1 year ago</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>Age at diagnosis ___ ___</p>		
Skin irritation	<p>Specific question for Arsenic and Mercury:</p> <p>Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?</p> <p>Wording in Arsenic: Skin irritation, hyperkeratinisation and hyperpigmentation</p> <p>Wording in Mercury: Skin rashes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p> <p>Don't know</p> <p>(nearly) never</p> <p>1-3 per month</p> <p>1 per week</p> <p>2-3 per week</p> <p>4-6 per week</p> <p>Everyday</p>		

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22.3 Appendix 3: Summaries of different cancer diseases and associated environmental chemicals

Authors: Hanna Elonheimo (THL), Elsi Haverinen (THL) and Laura Paalanen (THL)

Appendix table 2: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Acrylamide and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast, endometrial and ovarian cancers	Adani, G., Filippini, T., Wise, L. A., Halldorsson, T. I., Blaha, L., & Vinceti, M. (2020). Dietary Intake of Acrylamide and Risk of Breast, Endometrial, and Ovarian Cancers: A Systematic Review and Dose-Response Meta-analysis.	UK, Netherlands Japan, Sweden Italy, Switzerland USA	N: 18 studies of 10 different study populations (16 cohort- and 2 case-control studies) Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: general population, cancer patients and healthy subjects	Acrylamide intake was associated with a slightly increased risk of ovarian cancer, especially among never smokers. For endometrial cancer, risk was highest at intermediate levels of exposure and the association was more linear and positive among never smokers. For breast cancer, there was evidence of a null or inverse relation between exposure and risk, especially among never smokers and postmenopausal women. In premenopausal women, breast cancer risk increased linearly with acrylamide intake starting at 20 µg/day of intake. High acrylamide intake was associated with increased risk of ovarian and endometrial cancers in relatively linear manner, particularly among never smokers. On the contrary, there was little association between acrylamide intake and breast cancer risk, except for premenopausal women.
Endometrial cancer	Je Y. (2015). Dietary acrylamide intake and risk of endometrial cancer in prospective cohort studies.	Netherlands, Sweden USA ,France Italy , Spain UK, Greece , Germany Denmark , Norway	N: 4 prospective cohort studies (incl. 453 355 female participants and 2 019 endometrial cancer cases) Setting: cohort Target group: general population, endometrial cancer patients and healthy subjects	Overall, no association detected between dietary acrylamide intake and endometrial cancer risk (pooled relative risk, RR, for high vs. low intake= 1.10, 95% CI 0.91-1.34). However, high acrylamide intake was significantly associated with increased risk of endometrial cancer in never smoking women (pooled RR for high vs. low intake= 1.39, 1.09-1.77). Pooled RRs for an increase of 10 µg/day were 1.04 (0.97-1.11) for all women and 1.11 (1.04-1.19) for never smoking women.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
14 different cancers	Pelucchi, C., Bosetti, C., Galeone, C., & La Vecchia, C. (2015). Dietary acrylamide and cancer risk: an updated meta-analysis.	Not specified	N: 32 studies Setting: case-control, cohort Target group: general population, cancer patients and healthy subjects	For most cancers investigated, no meaningful associations were detected. The summary RRs for high vs. low acrylamide intake were 0.87 for oral and pharyngeal, 1.14 for esophageal, 1.03 for stomach, 0.94 for colorectal, 0.93 for pancreatic, 1.10 for laryngeal, 0.88 for lung, 0.96 for breast, 1.06 for endometrial, 1.12 for ovarian, 1.00 for prostate, 0.93 for bladder and 1.13 for lymphoid malignancies. The RR reached borderline significance only for kidney cancer (RR= 1.20, 95% CI 1.00-1.45). The corresponding continuous estimates were between 0.95 and 1.03; none of them significant. For never-smokers, there were borderline associations detected between dietary acrylamide and endometrial (RR= 1.23, 1.00-1.51) and ovarian (1.39, 0.97-2.00) cancers.

Appendix table 3: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Cadmium and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Larsson, S. C., Orsini, N., & Wolk, A. (2015). Urinary cadmium concentration and risk of breast cancer: a systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis.	USA, Japan China , Lithuania	N: 2 cohort- (with 67 breast cancer deaths and a total of 10 472 women), 5 case-control- (1 416 cases and 5 083 controls) and 1 cross-sectional studies Setting: cohort, case-control, cross-sectional	In the cohort studies there was no consistent association between U-Cd and breast cancer mortality. In case-control and cross-sectional studies, the pooled odds ratio (ORs) were 2.24 (95% CI 1.50-3.34; I ² = 63.4%) for the highest vs. lowest category of Cd concentration and 1.66 (1.23-2.25) for each 0.5- µg/g creatinine increase of Cd concentration; meaning a 66% increased risk of breast cancer. The ORs were statistically significant in 4 studies. Meta-analysis suggested that a high Cd exposure can be a risk factor for breast cancer.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
			Target group: breast cancer patients and healthy subjects	
Lung cancer	Chen, C., Xun, P., Nishijo, M., & He, K. (2016). Cadmium exposure and risk of lung cancer: a meta-analysis of cohort and case-control studies among general and occupational populations.	USA, Japan UK , Sweden, France Canada	N: 3 cohort studies in general population (22 551 participants and 354 events), 5 occupational cohort studies (4 205 participants and 180 events) and 3 occupational case-control studies (4 740 cases and 6 268 controls). Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: general and occupational population	In the general population, the weighted RR of lung cancer when comparing the highest to the lowest category of Cd exposure was 1.42 (95% CI 0.91-2.23). In 3 occupational cohort studies and 3 occupational case-control studies the weighted risk estimates of lung cancer were 0.68 (0.33-1.41) and 1.61 (0.94-2.75), respectively. There was no linear association, however. The association was statistically significant when comparing participants exposed to Cd with non-exposed. Cd exposure may increase risk of lung cancer.
Breast cancer	Rahim, F., Jalali, A., & Tangestani, R. (2013). Breast cancer frequency and exposure to cadmium: a meta- analysis and systematic review.	Japan, Canada , Turkey Kuwait , Lithuania Poland , USA Pakistan, Germany Taiwan , Finland	N: 13 case-control studies (978 exposed cases and 1 279 controls) Setting: case-control Target group: breast cancer patients (both Cd-exposed and non-exposed)	No statistically significant difference detected in frequencies of breast cancer between Cd-exposed and control groups; the summary estimate of mean difference 0.71 (95% CI 0.33-1.08). However, statistically significant differences found in the frequencies of breast cancer between Cd-exposed and control groups among Asian compared with Caucasian population; the summary estimates of mean difference were 1.41 (0.62-2.28) vs. 0.25 (-0.09-0.6), respectively. A difference in the frequencies of breast cancer between Cd-exposed and control groups in peripheral venous blood sampling methods detected; the summary estimate of mean difference 1.41 (0.46-2.37). The frequencies of breast cancer might be an indicator of early genetics effect for Cd-exposed populations.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Cancer mortality	Larsson, S. C., & Wolk, A. (2016). Urinary cadmium and mortality from all causes, cancer and cardiovascular disease in the general population: systematic review and meta-analysis of cohort studies.	Belgium , USA , Japan	N: 9 cohort studies, of which 4 on cancer (1332 deaths from cancer) (all-cause mortality 6 studies, CVD mortality 5 studies) Setting: cohort Target group: general population	The overall hazard ratio (HR) for the highest vs. lowest category of U-Cd was 1.39 (95% CI 0.96-1.99; I ² =75.9%) for cancer mortality. In an analysis restricted to 6 cohort studies of populations with a mean U-Cd concentration of ≤1 µg/g creatinine, the HR was 1.56 (0.98-2.47; 81.0%) for cancer mortality. Even low-level Cd exposure is associated with increased mortality.
Cancer risk Hormone-related cancers (prostate, breast, endometrial and ovarian)	Cho, Y. A., Kim, J., Woo, H. D., & Kang, M. (2013). Dietary cadmium intake and the risk of cancer: a meta-analysis.	USA, Japan, Sweden	N: 2 case-control studies (746 cases and 1069 controls), 6 cohort studies (309 103 participants and 12 859 cancer cases) Setting: case-control and cohort Target group: general population	Dietary Cd intake revealed no statistically significant association with cancer risk (RR=1.10, 95% CI 0.99-1.22, for highest vs. lowest dietary Cd group). However, there was a strong evidence of heterogeneity between the studies. Positive associations observed between dietary Cd intake and cancer risk among studies with Western populations (RR=1.15, 1.08-1.23) and studies investigating some hormone-related cancers (prostate, breast and endometrial cancers).
Breast cancer	Lin, J., Zhang, F., & Lei, Y. (2016). Dietary intake and urinary level of cadmium and breast cancer risk: A meta-analysis.	USA, Japan, China	N: 11 studies (6 on the association between the dietary Cd intake level and 5 on the U-Cd level and the breast cancer risk) Setting: cohort, case-control, observational, RCT Target group: breast cancer patients and healthy subjects	Higher U-Cd levels associated with an increased risk for breast cancer (highest vs. lowest quantile, pooled odds ratio (OR)=2.24, 95% CI 1.49-3.35 and a 1 µg/g creatinine increase in U-Cd caused a 1.02-fold increase of breast cancer (pooled OR=2.02, 1.34-3.03). No significant association was found between Cd exposure and breast cancer risk for dietary Cd intake (highest vs. lowest quantile, pooled relative risk (RR)=1.01, 0.89-1.15). Cd exposure may cause an increased risk of breast cancer, and U-Cd level can be a reliable biomarker.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Total cancer and lung cancer risk	Nawrot, T. S., Martens, D. S., Hara, A., Plusquin, M., Vangronsveld, J., Roels, H. A., & Staessen, J. A. (2015). Association of total cancer and lung cancer with environmental exposure to cadmium: the meta-analytical evidence.	USA, Belgium	N: 7 studies (4 NHANES III and 2 CadmiBel Study), in meta-analysis 3 prospective population studies (20 459 participants, 2 NHANES III, the Strong Heart Study and the CadmiBel Study) Setting: cohort Target group: general population	The relative risk (RR) of total cancer, associated with a doubling of the U-Cd concentration, ranged within the different studies from 1.18 to 1.31 and the pooled RR was 1.22 (95% CI 1.13-1.31; p <0.0001). In lung cancer, the RR was 1.21-1.70 for a doubling of the U-Cd concentration, and the pooled RR was 1.68 (1.47-1.92; p <0.0001). Low-level environmental Cd-exposure is a risk factor for both total and lung cancer.
Renal cancer	Song, J. k., Luo, H., Yin, X. h., Huang, G. l., Luo, S. y., Lin, d., Yuan, D. B., Zhang, W., & Zhu, J. g. (2015). Association between cadmium exposure and renal cancer risk: a meta-analysis of observational studies.	USA, UK, Finland Australia, Denmark Germany, Sweden Canada	N: 9 studies (10 case-control studies incl. 6 013 incident cases and 21 104 controls and 1 cohort study incl. 9 renal cancer cases and 1 732 participants) Setting: case-control and cohort Target group: occupational and non-occupational	A high Cd exposure significantly increased renal cancer 1.47 times (OR=1.47, 95% CI 1.27-1.71, for highest vs. lowest category of Cd categories). A high Cd exposure was associated with increased renal cancer risk and the association was higher for occupational exposure compared to non-occupational exposure.
Pancreatic cancer	Chen, C., Xun, P., Nishijo, M., Sekikawa, A., & He, K. (2015). Cadmium exposure and risk of pancreatic cancer: a meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies and case-control studies among individuals without occupational exposure history.	USA, Japan, Spain	N: 6 studies (4 prospective cohort studies incl. 112 934 participants with 335 events and 2 case-controls studies incl. 177 cases and 539 controls) Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: general population, pancreatic	The summarised RR was 2.05 (95% CI 1.58-2.66) comparing the highest to the lowest category of Cd exposure. The positive association was prevalent in men (RR=1.78, 1.04-3.05) but not in women (RR=1.02, 0.63-1.65).

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
			cancer patients and healthy subjects	
Prostate cancer	Ju-Kun, S., Yuan, D. B., Rao, H. F., Chen, T. F., Luan, B. S., Xu, X. M., Jiang, F. N., Zhong, W. D., & Zhu, J. G. (2016). Association Between Cd Exposure and Risk of Prostate Cancer: A PRISMA-Compliant Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.	USA, UK, Netherlands Germany, Italy, Taiwan Sweden, Japan	N: 22 studies (8 case-control and 14 cohort studies; 12 studies on occupational and 10 on non-occupational exposure) Setting: case-control, cohort Target group: occupational and non-occupational	In the general population, no association between high Cd exposure and increased prostate cancer (OR 1.21, 95% CI 0.91-1.64). In populations with occupational Cd exposure, the combined standardised mortality ratio of the association between Cd exposure and risk of prostate cancer was 1.66 (1.10-2.50). Furthermore, in the general population, high dietary Cd (D-Cd) intake (OR 1.07, 0.96-1.20) and U-Cd concentration (OR 0.86, 0.48-1.55) was not associated with the increased risk of prostate cancer. High occupational Cd exposure may be associated with the increased risk of prostate cancer. There was a significant heterogeneity among the studies, however.
Pathophysiology of cancer	Ebrahimi, M., Khalili, N., Razi, S., Keshavarz-Fathi, M., Khalili, N., & Rezaei, N. (2020). Effects of lead and cadmium on the immune system and cancer progression.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Recent studies have shown, that Cd may have a carcinogenic and estrogenic function incl. alterations in the immune cells and inflammatory markers. Some studies have demonstrated a significant association between Cd levels and various cancers. However, the results are inconclusive since some studies have concluded that no relationship exists.
Prostate cancer	Zhang, L., Zhu, Y., Hao, R., Shao, M., & Luo, Y. (2016). Cadmium Levels in Tissue and Plasma as a Risk Factor for Prostate Carcinoma: a Meta-Analysis.	Finland, Germany, Nigeria, Poland, China, USA, Pakistan	N: 11 studies (14 case-control studies) Setting: case-control Target group: Prostate cancer patients and healthy subjects	According to the pooled data Cd levels of prostate tissues were significantly higher in prostate cancer patients than in healthy controls; standard mean difference (SMD)=3.17, 95% CI 0.60-5.74, p<0.05. In plasma the corresponding figures were (SMD=4.07, 2.01-6.13, p<0.05). However, there was no difference in hair and nail Cd levels between the cases and the controls. Cd exposure might influence the tumorigenesis of prostate tissues.

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Appendix table 4: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Chromium (VI) and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main finding and conclusions:
Stomach cancer	Welling, R., Beaumont, J. J., Petersen, S. J., Alexeeff, G. V., & Steinmaus, C. (2015). Chromium VI and stomach cancer: a meta-analysis of the current epidemiological evidence.	Regions: Europe, North America, Asia	N: 56 studies and 74 individual RR estimates on stomach cancer and Cr(VI) exposure or work in an occupation associated with high Cr(VI) exposure (63 results from cohort and 11 from case-control studies) Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: occupational, stomach cancer patients and healthy subjects	The summary RR for all the studies combined was 1.27 (95% CI 1.18-1.38, p <0.001). The summary RR for stomach cancer was higher (RR=1.41, 1.18-1.69, p <0.001) in analyses which were limited to only the studies identifying increased risk of lung cancer. The results indicate that Cr(VI) is a stomach carcinogen in humans.
Sinonasal cancer (SNC)	Binazzi, A., Ferrante, P., & Marinaccio, A. (2015). Occupational exposure and sinonasal cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis.	UK, USA, Netherlands, Italy, Japan, Italy, France, Norway, Canada, Sweden, Finland, Estonia, Germany	N: 28 studies (11 cohort and 17 case-control studies) Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: occupational, SNC patients and healthy subjects	An increased risk of SNC for exposures to Cr(VI) compounds was observed (pooled RR=18.0, 95% CI 14.55-22.27) was observed. However, several sources of heterogeneity were detected in subset analyses. The results offer indications to the occupational etiology of SNC.

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Appendix table 5: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Lead and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Brain cancer	Ahn, J., Park, M. Y., Kang, M. Y., Shin, I. S., An, S., & Kim, H. R. (2020). Occupational Lead Exposure and Brain Tumors: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.	Sweden, Finland, USA China, Australia, Russia China, UK	N: 18 studies (12 cohort and 7 case-control studies) Setting: cohort, case-control Target group: occupational, brain cancer patients and healthy subjects	No significant association between Pb exposure and risk of benign and malignant brain tumors was detected (pooled OR=1.11, 95% CI 0.95-1.29). However, when including only malignant brain tumors, the risk of brain tumor was significantly increased (pooled OR=1.13, 1.04-1.24). The results provide suggestive evidence of an association between Pb compound exposure and brain tumor.
Meningioma and brain cancer	Meng, Y., Tang, C., Yu, J., Meng, S., & Zhang, W. (2020). Exposure to lead increases the risk of meningioma and brain cancer: A meta-analysis.	Australia, Canada France, Germany Israel, New Zealand UK, USA, China, Sweden	N: 12 studies (7 case-control and 5 cohort studies) (3 of the 7 case-control studies on the relationship between childhood brain tumors and parents' risk of Pb exposure) Setting: case-control, cohort Target group: general population, brain cancer patients and healthy subjects	In the case-control studies Pb exposure was associated with gliomas and meningiomas with the risk OR=0.82 (95% CI 0.69-0.95) and OR=1.06 (0.65-1.46), respectively. In the cohort studies Pb exposure was associated with brain cancer and meningiomas with the risk OR=1.07 (0.95-1.19) and OR=1.06 (0.94-1.17), respectively. Furthermore, the risk of childhood brain tumors associated with parental Pb exposure with OR=1.17 (0.99-1.34). Parental exposure to Pb may be a risk factor for brain tumors in children. According to case-control studies Pb exposure might not be a risk factor for all brain tumors, but cohort studies indicate that Pb is a risk factor for brain tumors. Pb might be a risk factor for meningiomas and brain cancers.
Pathophysiology of cancer	Ebrahimi, M., Khalili, N., Razi, S., Keshavarz-Fathi, M., Khalili, N., & Rezaei, N. (2020). Effects of lead and cadmium on the immune system and cancer progression.	Not applicable	Not applicable	Recent studies have shown, that Pb may have a carcinogenic and estrogenic function incl. alterations in the immune cells and inflammatory markers. Some studies have demonstrated a significant association between Pb levels and various cancers. However, the results are inconclusive since some studies have concluded that no relationship exists.

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Appendix table 6: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Arsenic and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Urothelial cancer	Di Giovanni, P., Di Martino, G., Scampoli, P., Cedrone, F., Meo, F., Lucisano, G., Romano, F., & Staniscia, T. (2020). Arsenic Exposure and Risk of Urothelial Cancer: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis.	Taiwan, Chile, USA	N: n=9 in review, n=8 in meta-analysis Setting: Case-control studies (n=8), cohort study (n=1), inclusion criterion: observational studies on exposure to As in drinking water and urinary tract cancer Target group: general population	Arsenic metabolites were significantly associated to urothelial cancer. All the As metabolites considered in this study resulted to be significantly associated to urothelial cancer, respectively: iAs% 3.51 (1.21–5.82) (p=0.003), MMA with WMD=2.77 (1.67–3.87) (p<0.001) and DMA with WMD= -4.56 (-7.91–1.22) (p=0.008).
Urothelial cancer, skin cancer, lung cancer, breast cancer, all-cancer	Kuo, C. C., Moon, K. A., Wang, S. L., Silbergeld, E., & Navas-Acien, A. (2017). The Association of Arsenic Metabolism with Cancer, Cardiovascular Disease, and Diabetes: A Systematic Review of the Epidemiological Evidence.	Taiwan, Argentina, Chile, USA, Eastern Europe	N: 12 Setting: Case-control studies (n=10), prospective cohort studies (n=2) Target group: General population / hospital setting	Of five studies focusing on urothelial cancer, four reported a positive association with MMA%, three with iAs% and DMA%, and three with primary and secondary methylation indices. Of the two studies on lung cancer, both reported an association with MMA%, and one also reported associations with iAs% and DMA%. For skin cancers, the estimated relative risks comparing the highest to lowest category of MMA% were consistent for all studies (RR range from 1.4 to 5.5), although only one study association was statistically significant. Only one study on breast cancer was included which indicated that women with higher %MMA and/or primary methylation index had an increased breast cancer risk.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Bladder cancer	Christoforidou EP, Riza E, Kales SN, Hadjistavrou K, Stolidi M, Kastania AN, Linos A. Bladder cancer and arsenic through drinking water: a systematic review of epidemiologic evidence.	Taiwan, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Argentina, USA and Chile.	N: 20 Setting: ecological studies, case-control studies, cohort studies, meta-analyses Target group: Majority of studies among populations from areas with high arsenic concentrations in drinking water.	Most of the studies reported higher risks of bladder cancer incidence or mortality in areas with high arsenic concentrations in drinking water compared to the general population or a low arsenic exposed control group. Furthermore, most of the studies provided evidence of statistically significant increases in bladder cancer risk at high concentrations of arsenic (>50 µg L ⁻¹). Assessing bladder cancer risk at lower exposure concentrations requires further investigation.
Skin cancer and bladder cancer	Gamboa-Loira, B., Cebrián, M. E., Franco-Marina, F., & López-Carrillo, L. (2017). Arsenic metabolism and cancer risk: A meta-analysis.	Taiwan, Argentina, Mexico, Chile, USA	N: 13 Setting: Case-control studies, prospective cohort studies Target group: General population / hospital setting	The summary association measures between cancer and %iAs were: 0.92 (0.27–3.12) for bladder and 1.15 (0.75–1.77) for lung cancer. The corresponding association measures for %MMA were: 1.79 (1.42–2.26) for bladder, 2.44 (1.57–3.80) for lung and 1.97 (0.96–4.03) for skin cancer. The summary measures between cancer and %DMA were: 0.62 (0.22–1.75) for bladder and 0.58 (0.36–0.93) for lung. Also, the authors concluded that methylation should be taken into account when assessing the potential iAs carcinogenicity risk.
Skin cancer	Matthews, N. H., Fitch, K., Li, W. Q., Morris, J. S., Christiani, D. C., Qureshi, A. A., & Cho, E. (2019). Exposure to Trace Elements and Risk of Skin Cancer: A Systematic Review of Epidemiologic Studies.	Not reported in the article	N: 3 for cutaneous melanoma and 9 for keratinocyte carcinoma Setting: Case-control and cohort studies and one cross-sectional study Target group: General population	Exposure to arsenic was associated with increased risk of keratinocyte carcinoma. Too few studies existed on melanoma to draw conclusions.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Liver cancer	Wang, W., Cheng, S., & Zhang, D. (2014). Association of inorganic arsenic exposure with liver cancer mortality: A meta-analysis.	Taiwan, Japan, Chile, Argentina	N: 7 articles including 12 studies Setting: 7 cohort studies and 5 ecological studies Target group: general population	The meta-SMR with 95% CI of liver cancer for the highest versus lowest category of iAs exposure level in drinking water was 1.80 (1.61 to 2.02). An increased risk of liver cancer mortality was found in both females [1.80 (1.45 to 2.24)] and males [1.84 (1.56 to 2.16)]. The authors concluded that long-term iAs exposure through drinking water increases the risk of liver cancer mortality.
Lung cancer and bladder cancer	Boffetta, P., & Borron, C. (2019). Low-Level Exposure to Arsenic in Drinking Water and Risk of Lung and Bladder Cancer: A Systematic Review and Dose-Response Meta-Analysis.	Taiwan, Chile, Bangladesh, USA, Argentina, Finland	N: 5 (lung cancer) and 8 (bladder cancer) Setting: Case-control studies, cohort studies Target group: General population	The meta-analysis provided strong evidence of lack of an increased risk of lung and bladder cancer in categories of exposure with mean/midpoint up to 150 µg/L arsenic in drinking water. The meta-analysis of case-control studies also resulted in a meta-RR of 1.03 (95% CI: 0.99-1.07) for lung cancer. For bladder cancer, the meta-analysis resulted in a summary RR of 1.02 (95% CI: 0.97-1.07).
Lung cancer	Lamm, S. H., Ferdosi, H., Dissen, E. K., Li, J., & Ahn, J. (2015). A Systematic Review and Meta-Regression Analysis of Lung Cancer Risk and Inorganic Arsenic in Drinking Water.	Chile, Taiwan, USA	N: 6 Setting: ecological studies, case-control studies, cohort study Target group: general population	No increased level of lung cancer risk at approximately 100–150 µg/L arsenic was found.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Lung cancer	Yuan, T., Zhang, H., Chen, B., Zhang, H., & Tao, S. (2018). Association between lung cancer risk and inorganic arsenic concentration in drinking water: a dose-response meta-analysis.	Chile, Argentina, Taiwan, Bangladesh, Japan, USA, Denmark, Italy	N: 15 in total, 8 case-control studies in dose-response meta-analysis Setting: Case-control studies, cohort studies Target group: not indicated	Significantly increased risks of lung cancer on exposure to both full range (RR = 1.21; 95% confidence interval [CI] = 1.05-1.37) and low to moderate range (RR = 1.18; 95%CI = 1.00-1.35) of arsenic-containing water were identified. The conclusion was that the lung cancer risk is significantly increases among people exposed to inorganic arsenic via drinking water.

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Appendix table 7: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Pesticides and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Bladder cancer	Liang, Z., Wang, X., Xie, B., Zhu, Y., Wu, J., Li, S., Meng, S., Zheng, X., Ji, A., & Xie, L. (2016). Pesticide exposure and risk of bladder cancer: A meta-analysis.	America, Europe, Africa (only regions reported)	N: 9 Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: Not indicated	The pooled OR estimates indicated that pesticide exposure was associated with an increased risk of bladder cancer (OR=1.649, 95% CI 1.22-2.22). Similar results were discovered in both case-control group and cohort group (OR=2.08, 95% CI 1.18-3.64, OR=1.15, 95% CI 1.07-1.22, respectively).
Non-Hodgkin lymphoma	Schinasi, L., & Leon, M. E. (2014). Non-Hodgkin lymphoma and occupational exposure to agricultural pesticide chemical groups and active ingredients: a systematic review and meta-analysis.	USA, Canada, Sweden, France, Italy, Iceland, Czech Republic, Germany, Ireland, Spain, Australia, New Zealand	N: 44 (20 on herbicides, 4 on fungicides and 17 on insecticides) Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: occupational exposure groups	In conclusion, positive associations between non-hodgkin lymphoma and carbamate insecticides, organophosphate (OP) insecticides, the phenoxy herbicide 2-methyl-4-chlorophenoxyacetic acid (MCPA), and lindane were found.
Non-Hodgkin Lymphoma	Luo, D., Zhou, T., Tao, Y., Feng, Y., Shen, X., & Mei, S. (2016). Exposure to organochlorine pesticides and non-Hodgkin lymphoma: a meta-analysis of observational studies.	USA, Norway, Denmark, Sweden, Canada, France, Germany, Spain	N: 13 studies (6 nested case-control, 1 case-cohort and 6 case-control) Setting: case-control, case-cohort Target group: general population, NHL patients and healthy subjects	The summary OR of the included studies was 1.40, 95% CI 1.27-1.56. OR estimates in sub groups showed strong associations for dichlorodiphenyldichloroethylene (DDE, OR= 1.38, 1.14-1.66), hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH, OR= 1.42, 1.08-1.87), chlordane (OR= 1.93, 1.51-2.48) and hexachlorobenzene (HCB, OR= 1.54, 1.20-1.99). Total OCPs investigated was significantly positively associated with non-hodgkin lymphoma risk.
Prostate cancer	Van Maele-Fabry, G., Libotte, V., Willems, J., & Lison, D. (2006). Review and meta-analysis of risk estimates for prostate cancer in pesticide manufacturing workers. Cancer causes & control.	USA, the Netherlands, Denmark, United Kingdom, Germany	N: 18 Setting: cohort studies Target group: Pesticide manufacturing workers	The meta-rate ratio estimate for all studies was 1.28 (95% CI 1.05–1.58). Furthermore, after grouping into broad classes of pesticides, increased pooled rate ratios were observed for each group with a borderline statistical significance for all phenoxy herbicides.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Prostate cancer	Van Maele-Fabry, G., & Willems, J. L. (2004). Prostate cancer among pesticide applicators: a meta-analysis.	USA, Canada, United Kingdom, Sweden, Italy, Norway, the Netherlands, Iceland, and two studies including several countries	N: 22 Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: Occupational groups (pesticide applicators)	The meta-rate ratio for prostate cancer was 1.24 (95% CI 1.06–1.45). The increased risk appears more marked in North America than in Europe.
Prostate cancer	Silva, J. F., Mattos, I. E., Luz, L. L., Carmo, C. N., & Aydos, R. D. (2016). Exposure to pesticides and prostate cancer: systematic review of the literature.	USA (n=38), Canada (n=3), Italy, The Netherlands, Australia, Malaysia, Japan, Guadeloupe	N: 49 Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: occupational pesticide exposure	Most studies (32 articles) found a positive association between prostate cancer and pesticides or agricultural occupations, with estimates ranging from 1.01 to 14.10. In 11 studies, exposed individuals were more than twice as likely to develop prostate cancer than unexposed individuals.
Prostate cancer	Lewis-Mikhael, A. M., Bueno-Cavanillas, A., Ofir Giron, T., Olmedo-Requena, R., Delgado-Rodríguez, M., & Jiménez-Moleón, J. J. (2016). Occupational exposure to pesticides and prostate cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis.	Not reported in the main manuscript	N: 52 in review, 25 in meta-analysis Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: occupational pesticide exposure	No association was found between low exposure to pesticides and prostate cancer, but association was significant for high exposure, pooled OR 1.33 (1.02 to 1.63), p=0.024. Positive findings were mostly confined to farmers exposed to high levels of specific groups of pesticides.
Prostate cancer	Budnik, L. T., Kloth, S., Velasco-Garrido, M., & Baur, X. (2012). Prostate cancer and toxicity from critical use exemptions of methyl bromide: environmental protection helps protect against human health risks.	USA	N: 91 studies, of which 5 epidemiological on cancer or toxicity; 3 of them on prostate cancer (included in the meta-analysis) Setting: case-control, cohort, data analysis Target group: occupational (e.g. farmers), general population	Exposure to methyl bromide was associated with a slightly increased risk of prostate cancer (OR= 1.21, 95% CI 0.98-1.49, p=0.076).

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Cutaneous melanoma	Stanganelli, I., De Felici, M. B., Mandel, V. D., Caini, S., Raimondi, S., Corso, F., Bellerba, F., Quaglino, P., Sanlorenzo, M., Ribero, S., Medri, M., Farnetani, F., Feliciani, C., Pellacani, G., Gandini, S., & IMI the Italian Melanoma Intergroup (2020). The association between pesticide use and cutaneous melanoma: a systematic review and meta-analysis.	USA, Iceland, Denmark, the Netherlands, United Kingdom, Italy, Brazil	N: 9 Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: Pesticide users	The summary relative risks for the categories 'herbicides - ever exposure', 'insecticides - ever exposure', 'any pesticide - ever exposure' and 'any pesticide - high exposure' resulted 1.85 (95% CI: 1.01, 3.36), 1.57 (95% CI: 0.58, 4.25), 1.31 (95% CI: 0.85, 2.04) and 2.17 (95% CI: 0.45, 10.36), respectively. In conclusion, individuals exposed to herbicides are at an increased risk of cutaneous melanoma.
Thyroid cancer	Han, M. A., Kim, J. H., & Song, H. S. (2019). Persistent organic pollutants, pesticides, and the risk of thyroid cancer: systematic review and meta-analysis.	The US, French Polynesia, Korea, Norway, Slovakia, Spain and one international cohort	N: 15 in review, 8 in meta-analysis Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: not specified but not only occupational exposure groups included	Pesticide exposure showed positive, statistically significant associations with thyroid cancer (OR=1.48, 95% CI=1.15-1.91). After subgroup analysis, herbicide exposure (OR=3.00, 95% CI=1.38-6.54) and agricultural exposure to pesticides (OR=1.86, 95% CI=1.04-3.32) was associated with an increased risk of thyroid cancer.
Thyroid cancer	Alsen, M., Sinclair, C., Cooke, P., Ziadkhanpour, K., Genden, E., & van Gerwen, M. (2021). Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals and Thyroid Cancer: An Overview.	Norway , USA, France, Spain	N: 14 studies on different pesticides (1 nested case-control, 12 cohort and 1 case-control) Setting: nested case-control, case-control, cohort Target group: occupational (e.g. farmers, plant and production workers), general population, thyroid cancer patients and healthy subjects	Exposure to certain pesticides may potentially be associated with increased risk of thyroid cancer.

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Wan, M., Co, V. A., & El-Nezami, H. (2021). Endocrine disrupting chemicals and breast cancer: a systematic review of epidemiological studies.	USA, Mexico, Brazil, Canada, Denmark, Norway, Egypt, India, Belgium, Slovakia. China, Japan, Iran, Italy, France	N: 43 for DDT or its metabolites, 4 for TCDD or dioxin exposure Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: Population-based or hospital-based studies	Eleven epidemiological studies out of 43 studies reported positive associations between DDT or its metabolites in lipid, serum or plasma and breast cancer incidences. On the other hand, epidemiological studies did not provide a consistent link between dioxin exposure and risk of breast cancer in women.
Breast cancer	Rocha, P., Oliveira, V. D., Vasques, C. I., Dos Reis, P., & Amato, A. A. (2021). Exposure to endocrine disruptors and risk of breast cancer: A systematic review.	Individual countries not indicated in the paper.	N: 37 of which 21 focused on pesticides Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target group: Cases were women in the pre- and postmenopausal phases with in situ and/or invasive breast cancer	No meta-analysis was conducted. Based on individual studies included in the review, the pesticides dichlorodiphenyl-dichloroethylene (p,p'-DDE), aldrin, and lindane were associated with increased odds of breast cancer (OR of 9.65 for p,p'-DDE; 1.84 for aldrin; 1.76 for lindane). Mirex (OR 2.42) and dichlorodiphenyl-trichloroethane (p,p'-DDT, OR 1.008) were also associated with higher odds of breast cancer.
Breast cancer	Leso, V., Ercolano, M. L., Cioffi, D. L., & Iavicoli, I. (2019). Occupational Chemical Exposure and Breast Cancer Risk According to Hormone Receptor Status: A Systematic Review.	USA	N: 10, of which 2 included pesticides Setting: cross-sectional, cohort, case-control or retrospective Target group: occupational, breast cancer patients and healthy subjects	Some positive associations were reported between OP insecticides, some reported possible relationships and some no relationships. Therefore, the evidence was contradictory.
Childhood leukemia	Van Maele-Fabry, G., Gamet-Payrastre, L., & Lison, D. (2019). Household exposure to pesticides and risk of leukemia in children	Two international studies with participants from Europe, Middle East, Asia, South America, North	N: 15 Setting: case-control and cohort studies	A statistically significant association between residential pesticide exposure and childhood leukemia was observed by combining all studies (summary-odd ratio estimate: 1.57; 95% CI: 1.27-1.95). Statistically significant increased risks were observed for all types

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Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
	and adolescents: Updated systematic review and meta-analysis.	America and Australasia; individual countries included: USA, Canada, Colombia, China, Brazil, Italy, Costa Rica, USA, Iran, Germany	Target group: children <18 years	of leukemia, and specifically for exposure during pregnancy, indoor exposure and prenatal exposure to insecticides. In conclusion, a positive association between domestic pesticide exposure and childhood leukemia is confirmed.
Childhood cancer	Vinson, F., Merhi, M., Baldi, I., Raynal, H., & Gamet-Payrastre, L. (2011). Exposure to pesticides and risk of childhood cancer: a meta-analysis of recent epidemiological studies.	Not indicated	N: 40 Setting: case-control and cohort studies Target group: Children potentially exposed to pesticides after birth, during pregnancy, before conception or 'ever'	The risk of lymphoma and leukaemia increased significantly in exposed children when their mother was exposed during the prenatal period (OR=1.53; 95% CI 1.22 to 1.91 and OR=1.48; 95% CI 1.26 to 1.75). The risk of brain cancer was correlated with paternal exposure either before or after birth (OR=1.49; 95% CI 1.23 to 1.79 and OR=1.66; 95% CI 1.11 to 2.49). In conclusion, the incidence of childhood cancer appears to be associated with parental exposure during the prenatal period.
Childhood leukemia	Wigle, D. T., Turner, M. C., & Krewski, D. (2009). A systematic review and meta-analysis of childhood leukemia and parental occupational pesticide exposure.	Not indicated	N: 35 Setting: case-control and cohort studies Target group: children with maternal or paternal occupational pesticide exposure	Childhood leukemia was associated with prenatal maternal occupational pesticide exposure (OR = 2.09; 95% CI, 1.51-2.88) whereas there was no overall association between childhood leukemia and any paternal occupational pesticide exposure (OR = 1.09; 95% CI, 0.88-1.34). Childhood leukemia risk was also elevated for prenatal maternal occupational exposure to insecticides (OR = 2.72; 95% CI, 1.47-5.04) and herbicides (OR = 3.62; 95% CI, 1.28-10.3).

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Appendix table 8: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Mycotoxins and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Liver, breast, and cervical cancer	Claeys, L., Romano, C., De Ruyck, K., Wilson, H., Fervers, B., Korenjak, M., Zavadil, J., Gunter, M. J., De Saeger, S., De Boevre, M., & Huybrechts, I. (2020). Mycotoxin exposure and human cancer risk: A systematic review of epidemiological studies.	Tunisia, Philippines, Singapore, China, Sudan, Thailand, South Africa, Taiwan	N: 14 Setting: case-control or longitudinal cohort studies Target population: not reported	Overall, a positive association between the consumption of aflatoxin-contaminated foods and primary liver cancer risk was verified. Furthermore, the systematic review incorporates clear observations of dose-dependent associations between aflatoxins and liver cancer risk. For the association between zearalenone and its metabolites and breast cancer risk, conflicting results were found. Also, no significant associations between hepatocellular carcinoma and fumonisin B1 exposure were observed in included studies.

Appendix table 9: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Phthalates and various different cancers identified

Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Zuccarello, P., Oliveri Conti, G., Cavallaro, F., Copat, C., Cristaldi, A., Fiore, M., & Ferrante, M. (2018). Implication of dietary phthalates in breast cancer. A systematic review.	Alaska, Northern Mexico, China and USA	N=6 epidemiological studies included in the analysis from years 2000-2018. Setting: The study designs were case-control. Target group: general population	The epidemiological studies performed so far have not established any definite correlation between exposure to the various phthalates and the risk of breast cancer.

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Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Wan, M., Co, V. A., & El-Nezami, H. (2021). Endocrine disrupting chemicals and breast cancer: a systematic review of epidemiological studies.	Northern Mexico, USA x 4,	N=5 Setting: 1 nested case-control study, two case-control studies, 1 cross-sectional survey, 1 population-based case-control study Target group: general population	Two studies found no association, as three studies observed a positive association between breast cancer risk and phthalate exposure (MCP, MCNP, MCOP, MEHP and DEHP).
Breast cancer	Rocha, P., Oliveira, V. D., Vasques, C. I., Dos Reis, P., & Amato, A. A. (2021). Exposure to endocrine disruptors and risk of breast cancer: A systematic review.	Mexico, USA	N: 3 Setting: cross-sectional, and case-control Target population: general population	Although one study included in this review indicated a negative association between exposure to phthalates and breast cancer, two other recent researches shows evidence of positive correlation between exposure to phthalates and increased cancer risk.
Breast cancer	Liu, G., Cai, W., Liu, H., Jiang, H., Bi, Y., & Wang, H. (2021). The Association of Bisphenol A and Phthalates with Risk of Breast Cancer: A Meta-Analysis.	USA, Alaska Native, Poland, and Northern Mexico	N: 6 studies focused on phthalates Setting: case-control Target population: total of 7280 breast cancer cases and controls	The urinary phthalate metabolite MBzP and MiBP were negatively associated with breast cancer (OR = 0.73, 95% CI: 0.60–0.90; OR = 0.75, 95% CI: 0.58–0.98, respectively). However, the overall ORs for MEP, MEHHP, MEHP, MEOHP, MCP, and MBP 0.96 (95% CI: 0.62–1.48), 1.12 (95% CI: 0.88–1.42), 1.13 (95% CI: 0.74–1.73), 1.01 (95% CI: 0.74–1.40), 0.74 (95% CI: 0.48–1.14), and 0.80 (95% CI: 0.55–1.15), respectively, suggesting no significant association. Phthalate metabolites MBzP and MiBP were passively associated with breast cancer, whereas no associations were found between MEP, MEHHP, MEHP, MEOHP, MCP, and MBP and breast cancer.

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Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Thyroid cancer	Alsen, M., Sinclair, C., Cooke, P., Ziadkhanpour, K., Genden, E., & van Gerwen, M. (2021). Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals and Thyroid Cancer: An Overview.	China, Italy	N: 3 Setting: 1 cross-sectional, 2 case-control studies Target population:	<p>One study observed that patients with reported serum levels of DEHP had a significantly higher risk of DTC compared to unexposed patients (OR: 15.07; 95% CI: 1.59–142.13).</p> <p>A case-control study investigating six urinary phthalate metabolites and thyroid cancer demonstrated that the summation of DEHP metabolites was positively associated with PTC (OR: 3.51; 95% CI: 1.64–7.49).</p> <p>The third study observed that thyroid cancer showed a significant positive association for MMP (OR: 1.11; 95% CI: 1.01–1.22), MEHHP (OR: 1.53; 95% CI: 1.19–1.96) and MEHP (OR: 1.46; 95% CI: 1.09–1.914). Urinary MBP and MBzP were inversely associated with thyroid cancer (OR: 0.45; 95% CI: 0.34–0.60) and (OR: 0.71; 95% CI: 0.60–0.85) respectively. There was a difference for gender where the association of MEHP with thyroid cancer was significant in females (OR: 1.90 (95% CI: 1.06–3.41) and non-significant in males (OR: 1.33 (95% CI: 0.95–1.86)</p>

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Appendix table 10: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and different cancers identified

Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Rocha, P., Oliveira, V. D., Vasques, C. I., Dos Reis, P., & Amato, A. A. (2021). Exposure to endocrine disruptors and risk of breast cancer: A systematic review.	USA	N: 1 Setting: case-control Target population: general	Detectable levels of PAH were positively associated with higher odds of breast cancer (OR 2.04; 95 % CI 1.06–3.93). The association increased with higher levels of PAH (\geq median) and by a higher level of absolute breast cancer risk (10-year risk \geq 3.4%: OR=4.09, 95% CI=1.38-12.13). However, the observation on the associations of PAHs and breast cancer was based on only one study (Shen, J., Liao, Y., Hopper, J. L., Goldberg, M., Santella, R. M., & Terry, M. B. (2017). Dependence of cancer risk from environmental exposures on underlying genetic susceptibility: an illustration with polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and breast cancer. <i>British journal of cancer</i> , 116(9), 1229–1233. https://doi.org/10.1038/bjc.2017.81), and more studies are needed to confirm the findings.
Breast cancer	Leso, V., Ercolano, M. L., Cioffi, D. L., & Iavicoli, I. (2019). Occupational Chemical Exposure and Breast Cancer Risk According to Hormone Receptor Status: A Systematic.	USA Canada	N: 10, of which 3 included PAHs Setting: cross-sectional, cohort, case-control or retrospective Target group: occupational, breast cancer patients and healthy subjects	Some positive associations were reported between PAHs and breast cancer. However, one study failed to show a significant association.
Lung cancer	Singh, A., Kamal, R., Ahamed, I., Wagh, M., Bihari, V., Sathian, B., & Kesavachandran, C. N. (2018). PAH exposure-associated lung cancer: an updated meta-analysis.	Canada, Denmark, Sweden, China, Norway, France, Britain, Finland, Italy, Netherlands & one study including 10 European countries	N: 24 Setting: Cohort studies Target population: Occupational exposure groups	The results of the meta-analysis by industry showed a significantly increased risk ratio for lung cancer for subjects occupationally exposed to PAHs in the coal/coke and the iron/steel foundry industry compared to other industries. The risk ratios for the rest of the industries were not significant.

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Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Respiratory (lung) and urinary tract cancers	Rota, M., Bosetti, C., Boccia, S., Boffetta, P., & La Vecchia, C. (2014). Occupational exposures to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and respiratory and urinary tract cancers: an updated systematic review and a meta-analysis to 2014.	Canada, Sweden, Australia, China, Germany, Italy, USA	N:13 Setting: cohort studies between years 2006-2014 Target population: workers from aluminum production industries (seven studies), iron and steel foundries (two studies), asphalt workers (two studies), and carbon black production (two studies).	In the meta-analysis, an excess risk of respiratory tract cancers (mainly lung cancer) was observed in iron and steel foundries (pooled relative risk (RR) 1.31, 95 % CI 1.08–1.59 from 14 studies), while a weak excess risk (pooled RR 1.08, 95 % CI 0.95–1.23 from 11 studies) emerged for aluminum production. A borderline increased risk was also observed for cancer of the bladder in the aluminum production (pooled RR 1.28, 95 % CI 0.98– 1.68 from 10 studies) and in iron and steel foundries (pooled RR 1.38, 95 % CI 1.00–1.91 from 9 studies).
Lung cancer	Armstrong, B., Hutchinson, E., Unwin, J., & Fletcher, T. (2004). Lung cancer risk after exposure to polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons: a review and meta-analysis.	Norway, France, USA, Italy, UK, Japan, Holland, China, Germany, Sweden, Canada, Denmark	N: 39 Setting: cohort studies Target population: occupational epidemiologic studies	The authors concluded that the average estimated unit relative risk (URR) at 100 µg/m ³ years benzo[a]pyrene was 1.20 [95% confidence interval (CI), 1.11–1.29] and was not sensitive to particular studies or analytic methods. However, the URR varied by industry. The estimated means in coke ovens, gasworks, and aluminum production works were similar (1.15–1.17). Average URRs in other industries were higher but imprecisely estimated, with those for asphalt (17.5; CI, 4.21–72.78) and chimney sweeps (16.2; CI, 1.64–160.7) significantly higher than the three above. There was no statistically significant variation of URRs within industry or in relation to study design (including whether adjusted for smoking), or source of exposure information.

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Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Larynx cancer	Wagner, M., Bolm-Audorff, U., Hegewald, J., Fishta, A., Schlattmann, P., Schmitt, J., & Seidler, A. (2015). Occupational polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon exposure and risk of larynx cancer: a systematic review and meta-analysis.	Not reported	N: 92 in qualitative synthesis, 63 in meta-analysis Setting: cohort studies, case-control studies Target population: workers exposed to PAHs	The pooled effect size was 1.45 (95% CI 1.30 to 1.62) for larynx cancer incidence and 1.34 (95% CI 1.18 to 1.53) for larynx cancer mortality. Only few studies allowed an investigation of dose-response, but these studies indicated a positive dose-response effect. The meta-analysis suggests a robust positive association between PAH and larynx cancer.
Larynx cancer	Paget-Bailly, S., Cyr, D., & Luce, D. (2012). Occupational exposures and cancer of the larynx- systematic review and meta-analysis.	Not stated separately for studies focusing on PAHs	N: <30 Setting: Case-control and cohort studies Target population: Workers exposed to PAHs	A significantly increased meta-RR (1.29; 95% CI 1.10 to 1.52) for larynx cancer was found for subjects exposed to PAHs. Furthermore, a significantly increased meta-RR was found for foundry workers (1.41; 95% CI 1.05 to 1.90).
Cancers in the oral cavity and larynx	Paget-Bailly, S., Cyr, D., & Luce, D. (2012). Occupational exposures to asbestos, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and solvents, and cancers of the oral cavity and pharynx: a quantitative literature review.	Germany, Italy, Sweden, Canada, Denmark, China, UK, Norway, France, Australia, Netherlands, USA & one with "Europe"	N: 22 Setting: case-control and cohort studies Target population: occupational populations	Overall, a moderate but yet significant association between PAHs exposure and cancer of the oral cavity and larynx was found (meta-RR 1.14; 95% CI 1.02–1.28). The authors conclude that future studies should overcome past limitations in terms of sample size, characterisation of exposure, and classification of cancer sites.

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Appendix table 11: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Bisphenol A and different cancers identified

Cancer type:	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Liu, G., Cai, W., Liu, H., Jiang, H., Bi, Y., & Wang, H. (2021). The Association of Bisphenol A and Phthalates with Risk of Breast Cancer: A Meta-Analysis.	USA, Poland	N= 5 studies including 5668 participants (1661 breast cancer cases and 4007 controls) Setting: case-control Target population: Adult women	The overall OR for the highest versus lowest BPA levels and breast cancer risk was 0.85 (95% CI: 0.69–1.05), indicating no significant association.
Breast cancer	Wan, M., Co, V. A., & El-Nezami, H. (2021). Endocrine disrupting chemicals and breast cancer: a systematic review of epidemiological studies.	Poland, USA	N: 2 Setting: Population-based case-control study and cross-sectional study Target population: Adult women	The included studies found no significant association between BPA exposure and breast cancer risk.
Thyroid cancer	Alsen, M., Sinclair, C., Cooke, P., Ziadkhanpour, K., Genden, E., & van Gerwen, M. (2021). Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals and Thyroid Cancer: An Overview.	China, Italy	N:2 Setting: cross-sectional Target population: general population	In a study conducted in China, higher urinary BPA (>2.84 ng/mL) was compared to the lower urinary BPA and association of thyroid cancer, revealing an OR: 3.57 (95% CI: 1.37–9.30). In a study from Italy, serum levels BPAF, an analogue to BPA, was positively associated with differentiated thyroid cancer (OR: 15.07; 95% CI: 1.59–142.13).

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Appendix table 12: Reviews, systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis on Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and different cancers identified

Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Breast cancer	Wan, M., Co, V. A., & El-Nezami, H. (2021). Endocrine disrupting chemicals and breast cancer: a systematic review of epidemiological studies.	Greenland x2, Denmark, USA, France	N: 3 Setting; Three case-control studies and two nested case-control studies	Three studies identified an increased risk for breast cancer from PFOA exposure, and two articles observed no association.
Breast cancer	Zeinomar, N., Oskar, S., Kehm, R. D., Sahebzada, S., & Terry, M. B. (2020). Environmental exposures and breast cancer risk in the context of underlying susceptibility: A systematic review of the epidemiological literature.	Not specified	N: 5 Setting: - Target population: general population	Two publications considered early onset of BC by stratifying by menopausal status or by age at baseline and both did not report statistically significant increased premenopausal BC risk associated with exposure. In one study of premenopausal BC, higher PFHxS were associated with a significant decreased risk of BC in women aged 40 years or younger (quintile 5 vs. quintile 1 RR=0.41, 95%CI=0.17, 0.96), while higher levels of PFOSA were associated with a significant increased risk of BC in women aged 40 years or younger (quintile 5 vs. quintile 1 RR 2.45, 95% CI = 1.00, 6.00). Three studies examined gene-environment interactions and serum concentrations of PFASs. These studies report an increased B Crisk (ORs 1.7–18) for high serum levels of PFOS and PFOA and variants in CYP1A1, COMT, or CYP17 A1 genes.
Thyroid cancer	Alsen, M., Sinclair, C., Cooke, P., Ziadkhanpour, K., Genden, E., & van Gerwen, M. (2021). Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals and Thyroid Cancer: An Overview.	USA	N: 4 Setting: 1 cohort, 3 case-control studies Target population: people living close to factory, occupational exposure	The association of thyroid cancer and PFAS exposure yielded inconclusive results. One study found some association (not significant) and three studies found no association of exposure and development of cancer.

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Cancer type	Study:	Included countries:	Studies (N), setting and target group:	Main findings and conclusions:
Liver cancer	Fenton, S. E., Ducatman, A., Boobis, A., DeWitt, J. C., Lau, C., Ng, C., Smith, J. S., & Roberts, S. M. (2021). Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substance Toxicity and Human Health Review: Current State of Knowledge and Strategies for Informing Future Research.	Not stated separately for studies presented	N:4 Setting: Target population: occupational, people living near contaminated area	The review observed inconclusive results and furthermore concluded that detecting associations between PFAS exposure and liver disease and liver cancer are difficult to study for reasons including lethality, selection of comparison populations, and alterations of excretion mechanics associated with disease states.
Kidney cancer	Stanifer JW, Stapleton HM, Souma T, Wittmer A, Zhao X, Boulware LE. 2018. Perfluorinated chemicals as emerging environmental threats to kidney health: A scoping review.	Not stated separately for studies presented	N:8 Setting: retrospective cohort studies Target population: occupational exposure, Communities surrounding manufacturers	In the review the authors examine mortality rates (standardised mortality ratio), hazard ratios and odds ratios. In the 8 published studies long-chain PFAS exposure was associated with kidney cancer or kidney cancer mortality, with risks ranging from 1.07 to 12.8.

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22.4 Appendix 4. Summaries of hematological diseases and environmental chemicals.

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Appendix table 13: Summary of the studies exploring the association between lead and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Mohan, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Prospective cohort study	India	Children (15-24m)	-	Anemia	102	There was no significant association between elevated BLLs and childhood anemia.	↔
Case-control									
Nassef, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case-control	Egypt	Children (6-12y)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	90 cases/ 30 controls	The concentrations of Pb were significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher in IDA patients than in controls.	↑
Ahamed, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case-control	India	Children (3-12y)	Environmental exposure (in consequence of small-scale industries in the area)	Aplastic anemia	17 cases/ 51 controls	BLL was significantly higher in the study group when compared with the control group ($p < 0.05$). The δ -ALAD activity, a biomarker of Pb exposure was significantly lower in the study group as compared to the control group ($p < 0.05$).	↑
Shah, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case-control	Pakistan	Children (1-10y)	-	Anemia	132 cases/ 134 controls	The mean levels of Pb in the biological samples of non-anemic children from all ages were found to be significantly lower than those recorded in anemic children, in both genders.	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Geltman, <i>et al.</i>	2019	Cross-sectional	USA	Refugee children (<7y)	Refugees from Sub-Saharan Africa, East Asia, and Pacific, Europe and Eurasia, Near East (North Africa and the Middle East), South and Central Asia, and Western Hemisphere	Anemia	3054	Children with anemia were significantly more likely than children without anemia to have elevated BLLs (OR = 2.88; 95% CI, 2.14-3.88)	↑
Anticona, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Cross-sectional	Peru	Children and adolescents (0-17y)	Environmental exposure (geographic locations of residency selected concerning their history of oil exposure (number of oil spills nearby). Participants' families had lived in the area for the past 5 years).	Anemia	330	The bivariate analysis did not find a significant difference in the proportion of anemia when comparing groups according to BLLs ≥ 5 mg/dL.	↔
Gaman, <i>et al.</i>	2019	Cross-sectional	Romania	Children (3m-12y)	-	Anemia	89	There was no association between anemia and BLLs, possibly explained by the low prevalence of BLL >100mg/mL (3.4% of the sample).	↔
López-Rodríguez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Mexico	Children (6-12y)	-	Anemia	296	No difference in wt% of Pb between anemic and non-anemic children.	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Bouftini, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	Morocco	Children (6m-12y)	Environmental exposure (90 participants lived in a considered exposure area - industrial area; 60 lived in an area considered unexposed)	Hypochromic microcytic anemia	150	Out of the 19 children with BLLs $\geq 100\mu\text{g/L}$, 7 presented hypochromic microcytic anemia.	-
Martins, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Argentina	Children (1-6y)	-	Anemia	319	Median BLLs significantly differed between those who had anemia and those who had not (2.69 (2.30-3.15) vs. 2.15 (1.98-2.33), $p = 0.012$). Logistic regression: association between a BLLs $>5 \mu\text{g/dL}$ and anemia was not statistically significant.	$\uparrow / \leftrightarrow$
Swaddiwudhipong, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Cross-sectional	Thailand	Children and adolescents (1-14y)	-	Anemia	695	The BLLs were significantly higher in children with anemia compared with those with normal Hb values (10.16 ± 1.65 vs. 8.45 ± 1.76 , $p < 0.01$). Multiple logistic regression analysis revealed a significant relationship between elevated BLLs and anemia.	\uparrow

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Thebo, <i>et al.</i>	2019	Cross-sectional	India	Adolescents (10-16y)	-	Anemia	200	Regarding 14-16-year-old girls, a significant increase of Pb was found in anemic people ($p < 0.001$) in comparison to controls.	↑
Choi, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Korea	Children (8-23m)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	210	BLLs were also significantly higher in infants with IDA compared to those without IDA ($p < 0.001$). IDA was significantly associated with higher BLLs (a-OR: 9.9, $p = 0.030$).	↑
Kordas, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Uruguay	Mothers (16-45y) and children (13.9-55.1m)	Environmental exposure	Anemia	106 mothers/ 108 children	Elevated BLLs and anemia together were observed in 8% of children and 11% of mothers. In neither group was anemia associated with $BLL \geq 5$ mg/dL ($p > 0.1$).	↔
Suh, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Korea	Female adults and adolescents (>10y)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	10169	BLLs did not differ between the IDA group and those without IDA. IDA was not associated with BLLs ($p = 0.625$).	↔
Meltzer, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Norway	Female smoker adults (17-38y)	-	Anemia	267	There was no association between Pb and anemia.	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Plante, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Canada	Female adults (18–74y)	-	Anemia	466	The prevalence of anemia in subjects with high Pb levels was not higher than that observed in the rest of the sample.	↔
Hsieh, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Taiwan	Adults (21-65y)	Occupational exposure (Pb battery, Pb stearate, and Pb bullion factories)	Anemia	751	Cumulative exposure to Pb in the workplace was significantly associated with anemia risk. Some confounders such as menstruation, smoking, and working status may influence the relationships between BLL and hematological indicators.	↑
Ahmad, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Cross-sectional	Bangladesh	Adolescents and adults (14-60y)	Occupational exposure (workers of industries manufacturing Pb-acid batteries)	Anemia	118	High BLL was found to be related to anemia of the workers. Those who were anemic had significantly ($p < 0.001$) higher mean BLL (81.83 ± 26.27) than those who were not anemic (58.81 ± 23.89).	↑

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Basit, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	Pakistan	Adults (17- 65y)	Occupational exposure (Group 1 – Battery workers involved directly with LAB manufacturing, n = 40; Group 2 – Non Battery workers, who were indirectly involved, n = 10)	Anemia	50	In group 1, 40 (100%) workers were found to be anemic and had lower Hb levels and higher mean BLL. While in group 2 (n = 10) only 40% of workers had anemia. The subjects that had anemia had higher mean BLL than those who did not have it.	↑
Örün, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Turkey	Female adults 2m postpartum (17-41y)	-	Anemia	144	The mothers with a history of anemia at any time had higher breast milk Pb levels than those without anemia (median Pb levels = 21.1 versus 17.9 µg/l, respectively; p = 0.0052).	↑
Dadpour, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cross-sectional	Iran	Adults diagnosed with Pb poisoning (19-81y)	-	Anemia	82	Among all, 70 individuals (85.4%) were anemic.	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Case reports and case series									
Breeher, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case report	USA	Male adult (69y)	“Bhasma” - Ayurvedic medication	Anemia	1	The patient was found to have a Hb level of 6.4 gm/dL. On further laboratory evaluation, a BLL of 94 µg/dL was obtained. After the family suggested the Ayurvedic “Bhasma” medication could be the cause, it was analysed for heavy metals and found to contain 19,400 mg/kg of Pb and 1,430 mg/kg of arsenic.	-
Kute, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case report	India	Adult (35y)	Ingestion of Sindoor 5–10 gm per year for 11 years for religious purposes	Anemia	1	Laboratory data included Hb 9.2 g/dL. Diagnosis of Pb nephropathy was confirmed by identification of potential sources of Pb exposure (Sindoor due to definitive evidence of excessive past Pb exposure from Sindoor) indicated by high BLL and presence of extrarenal features of Pb poisoning (hypertension, anemia, Pb line, hyperuricemia).	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Breyre, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Case report	USA	Male adult (26y)	Ayurvedic herbal medications	Anemia	1	The patient was admitted and noted to be anemic (Hb: 9.1 g/dL) with a BLL of 94.8 µg/dL. Extracts from the Ayurvedic supplements were evaluated with spectroscopy and a peak with Pb was found.	-
Kaneko, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Case report	Japan	Male adult (24y)	Occupational exposure	Normocytic anemia	1	A complete blood count revealed normocytic anemia; the Hb level was 7.3 g/dL with a mean corpuscular volume of 86.3 fL and a reticulocyte count of $2.81 \times 10^4/\mu\text{L}$. Detection of an elevated BLL of 100 µg/dL confirmed a diagnosis of Pb poisoning.	-
Gunturu, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case report	USA	Female adult (58y)	Ayurvedic herbal medicine	Normocytic normochromic anemia	1	Laboratory studies revealed normochromic normocytic anemia with Hb of 7.7 g/dL, hematocrit of 22.6%, MCV 87 fL, and normal iron studies. This triggered a screening for heavy metals, which revealed an elevated BLL of 102 µg/dL.	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Chambial, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Case report	India	Male adult (73y)	Intake of herbal medicines for 8m to control diagnosed Diabetes Mellitus	Normocytic hypochromic anemia	1	The patient was diagnosed to have Pb toxicity attributable to consumption of a homemade powdered herbal remedy prescribed by an ayurvedic practitioner (BLL: 118.5 µg/dL). Hb level was 9.8g%, and a peripheral blood smear was suggestive of normocytic hypochromic anemia which was supported by serum iron and total iron-binding capacity levels.	-
Akshatha, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case report	India	Male adolescent (13y)	Native medicine in the form of syrup for the past two years	Microcytic hypochromic anemia	1	Hb was 7gm%, total leucocyte count was 3500 cu mm and platelet count was 1,33,000cu mm. Peripheral smear showed microcytic hypochromic anemia. BLL was 59.5µg/dl.	-
Nazma, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Case report	India	Male adult (28y)	Occupational exposure (working in an unorganised Pb-based manufacturing unit for 4 years)	Microcytic hypochromic anemia	1	Results of various laboratory investigations were normal except Hb - 8.5 g/dl, and BLL - 115 µg/dl. Peripheral smear revealed microcytic hypochromic anemia.	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Toto, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Case report	Italy	Female child (5y)	Accidental ingestion of a metal ring	Microcytic hypochromic anemia	1	Blood sample revealed hypochromic microcytic anemia— Hb: 7.4 g/dL. Pb level was found to be 352 µg/dL and urinary Pb was 1556 µg/dL. These values suggest a hemolysis erythrocyte in Pb poisoning.	-
Gupta, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case report	India	Male adult (28y)	Ayurvedic medication	Microcytic hypochromic anemia	1	The Hb level was 8 g/dl and the peripheral smear demonstrated the classical microcytic and hypochromic picture. BLL was estimated, and it was grossly increased — 145 µg/dL.	-
Nicolli, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Case report	Italy	Female adult (65y)	Cooking pots	Sideroblastic anemia	1	Blood analysis of the past year showed progressive sideroblastic anemia. The laboratory analysis confirmed the suspicion: BLL was 885 µg/L and in urine 285 µg/L.	-
Muller, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case report	Bhutan	Male adult (42y)	Bhutanese traditional medicines to treat a resolutive Bell's palsy a few months earlier.	Hemolytic anemia	1	Blood tests revealed hemolytic anemia with the Hb level at 90 g/l.	-
Petracca, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case series	Italy	Male adults (35-54y)	Occupational exposure (Pb recycling plants)	Normocytic normochromic anemia	4	All cases presented high BLL. Except for case 2, blood tests showed normocytic, normochromic anemia, with reticulocytosis.	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Qasim, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case series	Pakistan	Male adults (case 1: 40y; case 2: 38y)	Occupational exposure (battery manufacturing plant)	Anemia	2	Case 1: serum Pb levels were 98.83 µg/dl, and had anemia (Hb:7.2 g/dl). Case 2: Pb levels were 120.20 µg/dl, and had anemia (Hb was 7.1 gm/dl).	-
Wu, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case series	Taiwan	Male adult (75y)	Inappropriate topical use of Pb-containing herbal mixtures	Microcytic anemia	1	Laboratory results included microcytic anemia (Hb 7.1 g/dL, mean corpuscular volume 70 fl). Heavy metal screen subsequently showed a BLL of 226 g/dL. The Pb content of the herbal patch was 517 mg/g (51.7% Pb by weight).	-

(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.

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Appendix table 14: Summary of the studies exploring the association between lead and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Case-control									
Nassef, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case-control	Egypt	Children (6–12y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	90 cases/30 controls	There was a negative correlation between Hb concentration and serum Pb concentration ($r = 0.811$, $p = 0.01$).	↓
Goel, <i>et al.</i>	2019	Case-control	India	Children and adolescents (0.5-13y); cases with neurological complaints	Occupational exposure (making artificial jewelry)	Hemoglobin levels	15 cases/14 controls	There was a significant negative correlation between BLL and Hb which showed that the BLL linearly increased with decreases on the Hb (Pearson's $r = -0.537$, $p = 0.003$). On linear regression, BLL ($\beta = -0.361$, $p = 0.049$, $R^2 = 0.330$) continued to significantly influence Hb after adjusting for age.	↓
Mitchell, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case-control	Thailand	US-bound refugee children and adolescents (6m - 14y)	Possibly Pb-acid car batteries used in camp households to generate power for electronic items	Hemoglobin levels	64 cases/578 controls	Lower Hb was significantly associated with elevated BLL (Wilcoxon $p = .0054$).	↓
Cross-sectional									
Reddy, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	India	Children and adolescents (9-14y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	195	Hb levels did not correlate with BLLs.	↔
Counter, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Cross-sectional	Ecuador	Children and adolescents (2-15y)	Hand-to-mouth ingestion of Pb-contaminated food,	Hemoglobin levels	66	A Spearman correlation analysis showed no statistically significant association between	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
					dust, and soil, and the inhalation of air-borne particulates from the heavily Pb-contaminated smoke produced by the glazing kilns			Hb level and BLL in this study group (tied Z = -.400, tied p = .689).	
Moawad, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Egypt	Children and adolescents (6- 18y)	Environmental and occupational exposure	Hemoglobin levels	400	A total of 113 children had BLLs in the range of 10 to 20 µg/dL. The mean values of Hb were inversely correlated with BLLs. Children involved in pottery workshops had the highest BLLs and the lowest Hb values.	↓
Rasoul, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Cross-sectional	Egypt	Children (grades 1, 3 and 5)	-	Hemoglobin levels	90	The mean Hb level was significantly lower in students with BLL ≥ 10 µg/dL than those with BLL < 10 µg/dL (12.63±1.02g/dL vs. 12.11±1.12g/dL, p = 0.004) There was a significant negative correlation between BLL and Hb level (r = 0.196; p = 0.03).	↓
Rondó, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Brazil	Children (2-11y)	Environmental exposure (residence near a closed Pb manipulating metal industry)	Hemoglobin levels	384	There were statistically significant negative associations between BLL and Hb (p = 0.019).	↓

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Kordas, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Uruguay	Mothers (16–45y) and children (13.9–55.1m)	Environmental exposure	Hemoglobin levels	106 mothers/ 108 children	BLL and Hb were modestly correlated in children (Spearman's rho = 0.21, p = 0.05) but not the mothers (p = 0.42).	Children: ↓ Mothers: ↔
Chen, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	China	Adults	Food from contaminated environment	Hemoglobin levels	308	The Hb was significantly lower in the high (BLL ≥ 100 g/L) exposure group relative to those with the least exposure (BLL < 100 g/L) in women (p < 0.05) after adjusting for age and weight. But for men, no such significant differences were found. Spearman's correlation analysis showed that there was a negative correlation between Hb and BLL (p < 0.01).	Females: ↓ Males: ↔
Örün, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Turkey	Female adults 2m postpartum (17-41y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	144	According to the Spearman correlation analysis, no significant correlation was observed between the maternal Hb level and the level of Pb milk (rs = -0.036 p = 0.672).	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Kim, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Cross-sectional	South Korean	Adults (≥ 20 y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	5888	A twofold increase in BLL or erythrocyte Pb was associated with a 0.285 g/dL increase or 0.088 g/dL decrease in Hb level, respectively. There was a 0.416 g/dL increase or 0.143 g/dL decrease in Hb, respectively, in the highest, compared with the lowest quartile of BLL and erythrocyte Pb, respectively.	↓
Dadpour, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cross-sectional	Iran	Adults diagnosed with Pb poisoning (19-81y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	82	Those with increasing BLL, the levels of Hb ($p = 0.011$, $r = -0.279$) showed significant decrease.	↓
Ahmad, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Cross-sectional	Bangladesh	Adolescents and adults (14-60y)	Occupational exposure (workers of industries manufacturing Pb-acid batteries)	Hemoglobin levels	118	Respondents who had lower Hb levels had higher mean BLL.	↓

(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.

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Appendix table 15: Summary of the studies exploring the association between lead and basophilic stippling

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Ahmad, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Cross-sectional	Bangladesh	Adolescents and adults (14-60y)	Occupational exposure (workers of industries manufacturing Pb-acid batteries)	Basophilic stippling	118	Three blood samples showed red blood cells with basophilic stippling.	-
Case reports and case series									
Muller, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case report	Bhutan	Female adult (42y)	Bhutanese traditional medicines to treat a resolute Bell's palsy a few months earlier.	Basophilic stippling	1	A blood smear was performed and showed basophilic stippling that was highly evocative of heavy metal poisoning.	-
Qasim <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case series	Pakistan	Male adults (case 1: 40y; case 2: 38y)	Occupational exposure (battery manufacturing plant)	Basophilic stippling	2	Case 1: Serum Pb levels were 98.83 µg/dl, and there was no basophilic stippling. Case 2: Pb levels were 120.20 µg/dl and there was no basophilic stippling.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 16: Summary of the studies exploring the association between lead and gestational thrombocytopenia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Bao, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Prospective cohort study	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.81y (3.56)]	-	Gestational thrombocytopenia	3911	There was no association between gestational thrombocytopenia and a 10-fold increase in urinary Pb in multiple-metal models.	↔
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

Appendix table 17: Summary of the studies exploring the association between cadmium and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
López-Rodríguez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Mexico	Children (6-12y)	-	Anemia	296	No difference in wt% of Cd was found between anemic and non-anemic children.	↔
Muller, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	USA	Adults [mean: 52.2y (9.59)]	Occupational exposure (Navy military aircraft maintenance repair facility workers)	Anemia	331	Blood and urine Cd levels were normal in 17 anemic workers.	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Wai, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Cross-sectional	Japan	Adults (42-67y)	-	Anemia	1141	There was no association between Cd and the risk of anemia.	↔
Ahn, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Republic of Korea	Adolescents (10-18y)	Lifestyle (smoking, type of housing)	Iron deficiency anemia	1472	Mean blood Cd concentration was 0.30 µg/L in Korean adolescents. IDA was significantly associated with higher blood Cd concentrations ($p < 0.05$).	↑
Suh, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Korea	Female adults and adolescents (>10y)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	10169	Blood Cd (log-transformed) differed between the IDA group and the non-IDA group ($p < 0.001$). Path analyses also showed IDA was significantly associated with an elevated blood Cd level (log-transformed) after adjusting for age and BMI ($\beta = 0.48$, $SE = 0.04$, $p < 0.001$) ($R^2 = 0.54$).	↑
Silver, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Cross-sectional	USA	Children and adolescents (3-19y)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	5224 (1430 for urine subsample)	Odds of IDA were associated with an increasing category of blood Cd. Adjusted ORs for high blood Cd (≥ 0.5 µg/L) versus $< LOD$ were 1.74 (1.30-2.34) for IDA.	↑
Choi, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Korea	Children (8-23m)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	210	Blood Cd levels were not significantly higher in infants with IDA compared to those without IDA ($p < 0.001$).	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Case-control									
Shah, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case-control	Pakistan	Children (1-10y)	-	Anemia	132 cases/ 134 controls	The mean levels of Cd in the biological samples of non-anemic children from all ages were found to be significantly lower than those recorded in anemic children, in both genders.	↑
Ikeda, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case-control	Japan	Never smoker adults (20-89y)	-	Anemia	716 cases/ 2148 controls	Cd-U for the anemia group was significantly ($p < 0.05$) greater than that for the control-1 group, as observed, creatinine-corrected and specific gravity-corrected. The Cd-U was higher in the anemia group, but no changes were observed in a1-MG-U, b2-MG-U, or NAG-U.	↑
Nassef, <i>et al.</i>	2014	Case-control	Egypt	Children (6-12y)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	90 cases/ 30 controls	The concentrations of Cd were significantly ($p < 0.0001$) higher in IDA patients than in controls.	↑
Case reports									
Raval, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case report	USA	Male adult (51y)	-	Hemolytic anemia	1	Laboratory findings showed hemolytic anemia. Testing revealed a highly increased Cd concentration in whole blood of 106.5 µg/L.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 18: Summary of the studies exploring the association between cadmium and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Örün, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Turkey	Female adults 2m postpartum (17-41y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	144	Spearman correlation analysis showed no significant correlation between the maternal Hb level and the level of Cd in breast milk ($r_s = -0.118$ $p = 0.162$).	↔
Chen, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	China	Adults	Food from a contaminated environment	Hemoglobin levels	308	The level of Hb decreased with increasing BCd. Hb also decreased with increasing BCd in women and men, but no significant differences were found. Spearman's correlation analysis showed that there was a negative correlation between Hb and BCd ($p = 0.13$).	↓
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 19: Summary of the studies exploring the association between cadmium and gestational thrombocytopenia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Bao, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Cohort	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.81y (3.56)]	-	Gestational thrombocytopenia	3911	We observed that a 10-fold increase in urinary Cd was significantly associated with increased odds for gestational thrombocytopenia in different trimesters [OR 95%CI: 1.80 (1.26, 2.56), 1.65 (1.05, 2.59) and 1.54 (1.02, 2.33) in the first, second and third trimesters, respectively]. In the sensitivity analysis that excluded women with pregnancy complications, increased ORs of gestational thrombocytopenia were still associated with increased urinary Cd concentration.	↑
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 20: Summary of the studies exploring the association between cadmium and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Chen, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	China	Adults	Food from a contaminated environment	Hemoglobin levels	308	For those women with a high BLL (≥ 100 g/L)/low level of BCd (< 4 g/L), and those with a high BLL (≥ 100 g/L)/high level of BCd (≥ 4 g/L), the Hb was decreased by 4.5 g/L and 8.3 g/L compared to those with lower levels of BCd (< 4 g/L) and BPb (< 100 g/L) after adjusting for age and weight. Similar results were also found in men with a decrease of Hb by 5.4 g/L and 10.7 g/L, respectively. The women and men with high BLL would have a low Hb regardless of BCd level, but there was no significant difference.	↔
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 21: Summary of the studies exploring the association between arsenic and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Case-control									
López-Rodríguez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional nested case-control study	Mexico	Children (6-12y)	-	Anemia	296	As concentration was higher in the anemic group in comparison to the non-anemic group (0.041 ± 0.11 vs. 0.014 ± 0.05 ; $p < 0.05$).	↑
Taj, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Case-control	Pakistan	Adolescents and adults ($\geq 12y$)	-	Aplastic anemia	428	Regarding As exposure, only univariate logistic regression showed that exposure to As was significantly associated with aplastic anemia cases.	↑
Cross-sectional									
Choi, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Korea	Children (8-23m)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	210	Blood As levels were not correlated with iron deficiency anemia.	↔
Surdu, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	Romania	Pregnant and non-pregnant women (18-44y)	Consumption of As-contaminated drinking water	Anemia	217	Compared to women without anemia, women with anemia had higher drinking water As concentrations. The concentration was particularly high in 10 women with pregnancy anemia. The effect estimates for 'any' anemia suggested a near doubling in prevalence associated with qualitative As exposure, adjusted for education and cigarette smoking. The suggested effect was even stronger for pregnancy anemia, in which As-	↑

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
								exposed women had an almost three-fold higher confounder-adjusted prevalence than unexposed women.	
Case report and case series									
Yoshimura, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case report	Japan	Male adult (~20y)	Occupational exposure (factory of gallium extraction)	Anemia	1	On admission, anemia, hematuria, and renal and liver dysfunction were observed. The total As content in the serum was 244.8 µg/l at admission. In the speciation analysis, four kinds of As compounds derived from arsine metabolism were detected in serum and urine. The concentrations of arsenite, arsenate, monomethylarsonic acid, and dimethylarsinic acid in serum at admission were 45.8, 5.2, 17.9, and 9.3 µg/l, respectively.	-
Laskar, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Case report	India	Male adult (52y)	As contaminated groundwater	Anemia	1	The patient had microcytic anemia. His serum As level was above the normal range (11 µg/L).	-
Dani	2013	Case report	Germany	Female adult (47y)	Anthropogenic-environmental exposure (childhood living in a gold-mining region)	Anemia	1	Diagnosis of osteoresorptive As intoxication. The patient showed manifestations of chronic As intoxication. The As concentration in the urine of the patient was initially 500 µg/l (0.5 ppm, 2.5 µg/mg creatinine/dl, u-As: Phosphate of 26 µg/mmol), a value that has been associated with Hb of <10 g/dl. The osteoporosis that ensued at the beginning of her menopause and the	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
								vitamin D insufficiency were probably the triggers of the osteoresorptive As intoxication.	
Shumy, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Case report	Bangladesh	Male adolescent (17y)	Ingestion of "Phita" (herbal mixture)	Anemia	1	Initial laboratory investigations showed a leukopenia (3800/ mL) with a normal differential, and anemia (Hb 7 g/dL). The As level of a hair sample was indeed found to be 19.3 mg/kg (normal <3 mg/kg).	-
Wu, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case series	Taiwan	Male adult (51y)	Anal Use of Herbo-Metallic Ointments (herbal mixtures)	Anemia	2	Clinical presentation of one of the patients consistent with As and Hg poisoning. Important laboratory results included normocytic anemia with a Hb level of 9.4 g/dL. The urine metal analyses on hospital day 21 showed an As level (541 µg/g creatinine) and Hg level (5.8 µg/L above normal). The herbal prescription was available containing Pb tetraoxide. Other mixtures contained other heavy metals (As, Hg) and Pb in clinically significant concentration.	-

(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.

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Appendix table 22: Summary of the studies exploring the association between arsenic and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Case-control									
López-Rodríguez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional nested case-control study	Mexico	Children (6-12y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	296	As concentration were related to the Hb level (Spearman's rank correlation: $r = -0.441$, $p < 0.01$).	↓
Cross-sectional									
Parvez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Bangladesh	Adults (36-65y)	Consumption of As-contaminated drinking water	Hemoglobin levels	103	A significant inverse correlation was observed between urinary As and Hb.	↓
Ameer, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	Argentina	Female adults (18-65y),	-	Hemoglobin levels	225	In linear regression analysis with adjustment for age, urinary As concentrations were inversely associated with Hb.	↓
Taheri, <i>et al.</i>	2016	Cross-sectional	Iran	Adults (13-77y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	36	The relationship between hair As and Hb in the population was insignificant.	↔
Prasad, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Cross-sectional	India	Females adults	Drinking water	Hemoglobin levels	281	Nail As content influenced reduction of Hb per 1 µg/g increase in As in nails.	↓
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 23: Summary of the studies exploring the association between arsenic and gestational thrombocytopenia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Bao, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Cohort	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.81y (3.56)]	-	Gestational thrombocytopenia	3911	Only during the 2nd trimester, a 10-fold increase of urinary As was associated with reduced odds of gestational thrombocytopenia (OR=0.58, 95% CI: 0.38-0.88).	↓
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

Appendix table 24: Summary of the studies exploring the association between mercury and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Case-control									
Al-Amodi, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Case-control	Saudi Arabia	Adults (>18y)	The exposed dental staff dealt with the amalgam (Hg vapors)	Anemia	43 exposed dental staff; 40 non-exposed dental-staff; 56 control group (19 with amalgam filling; 37 without amalgam filling)	The median of Hg hair and nail in anemic exposed dental staff was higher than the non-anemic in the same group but without significant difference.	↔

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Plante, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Canada	Female adults (18-74y)	-	Anemia	466	The prevalence of anemia in subjects with high Hg levels was not higher than that observed in the rest of the sample.	↔
Choi, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Korea	Children (8-23m)	-	Iron deficiency anemia	210	Blood Hg levels were not correlated with IDA.	↔
Örün, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Cross-sectional	Turkey	Female adults 2m postpartum (17-41y)	-	Anemia	144	Postpartum anemia in the mothers did not affect the Hg level in breast milk in the 2nd postpartum month.	↔
Case reports and case series									
Priya, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Case report	India	Female adult (19y)	Self-intravenous injection of elemental Hg	Aplastic anemia	1	Investigations revealed pancytopenia with a Hb of 5.7 g/dl, a total WBC count of 3600 cells/cu.mm, and a platelet count of 15,000/cu.mm. Qualitative analysis of blood and urine for Hg was positive; quantitative analysis revealed a blood level of 58 mcg/l, and a urine level of 138 mcg/l (reference values are below 8 mcg/l in blood and 4 mcg/l in urine.	-
Yıldırım, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Case series	Turkey	5 family members (aged 20-54y)	Inhalation and/or dermal contact with Hg spilled on the floor that	Anemia, Neutropenia, and Thrombocytopenia	5	Laboratory results of all cases showed high Hg levels. Moreover, regarding hematological outcomes, case 1 revealed neutropenia e anemia;	-

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Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
					was only cleaned up 2 weeks later			case 2 also had neutropenia, and case 3 revealed anemia and thrombocytopenia. Clinical symptoms in all 5 cases were confirmed to be due to Hg exposure based on urea and/or whole blood analysis.	
Wu, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Case series	Taiwan	Male adult (51y)	Use of Herbo-Metallic Ointments	Anemia	2	Clinical presentation of one of the patients consistent with As and Hg poisoning. Important laboratory results included normocytic anemia with a Hb level of 9.4 g/dL. The urine metal analyses on hospital day 21 showed an As level (541 µg/g creatinine) and Hg level (5.8 µg/L above normal). The herbal prescription was available containing Pb tetraoxide. Other mixtures contained other heavy metals (As, Hg) and Pb in clinically significant concentration.	-

(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.

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Appendix table 25: Summary of the studies exploring the association between mercury and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Weinhouse, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	USA	Children (<12y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	1387 (83 sub-sample)	In the total sample, the initial bivariate association between total hair Hg and Hb was not statistically significant and remained nonsignificant after adjustment for age, sex, and BMI. In the same bivariate association in the sub-sample, which contained a higher proportion of anemic children, an inverse relationship between total hair Hg and Hb ($\beta = -0.12$, $p = 0.06$, critical value 0.01) was observed. The inverse relationship between Hg and Hb remained significant (total Hg $\beta = -0.18$, $p = 0.01$, critical value 0.01) in the model adjusted for age, sex, BMI, and vitamin B12, although vitamin B12 was no longer significant in the model.	↔ ↓
Marques, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Cross-sectional	Brazil	Children (1-59m) from traditional and immigrant tin-mining families	Fish consumption	Hemoglobin levels	937	Among traditional villagers, children showed a significant correlation ($r = 0.2318$; $p = 0.0005$) between Hb concentrations and hair Hg concentrations.	↓
Örün, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Cross-sectional	Turkey	Female adults 2m postpartum (17-41y)	-	Anemia	144	No correlation between Hb concentration and breast-milk Hg level was determined (Spearman's rho coefficient = -0.052; $p = 0.536$).	↔
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 26: Summary of the studies exploring the association between chromium and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Shah, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	Pakistan	Children (1-10y)	-	Anemia	266	The concentrations of Cr in scalp hair, blood, and urine were found to be significantly lower in anemic patients of both genders when compared to control subjects of matched age groups ($p = 0.003-0.01$).	↓
López-Rodríguez, <i>et al.</i>	2017	Cross-sectional	Mexico	Children (6-12y)	-	Anemia	296	No difference in wt% of Cr between anemic and non-anemic children.	↔
Muller, <i>et al.</i>	2011	Cross-sectional	USA	Adults [mean: 52.2y (9.59)]	Occupational exposure (Navy military aircraft maintenance repair facility workers)	Anemia	331	Of the 15 participants with Cr(VI) > 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, only one had anemia.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 27: Summary of the studies exploring the association between chromium and hemoglobin levels, red blood cells, hematocrit, and eosinophilia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Case report									
Stepien, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Case report	Ireland	Male adult (57y)	Hip prosthesis	Hemoglobin levels, red blood cells, hematocrit, and eosinophilia	1	Blood film showed mild persistent eosinophilia with degranulation. RBC ($6.30 \times 10^{12}/L$), Hb (189 g/L), and hematocrit (0.572 L/L) were elevated. Preoperatively, plasma cobalt concentrations (903.32 $\mu\text{g}/L$; reference range 0.1–0.4) and Cr (71.32 $\mu\text{g}/L$; <0.5) were found to be markedly elevated.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

Appendix table 28: Summary of the studies exploring the association between chromium and gestational thrombocytopenia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Bao, <i>et al.</i>	2020	Prospective cohort study	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.81y (3.56)]	-	Gestational thrombocytopenia	3911	There was no association between gestational thrombocytopenia and a 10-fold increase in urinary Cr in multiple-metal models.	↔
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 29: Summary of the studies exploring the association between pesticides and hematological cells number alterations

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Freire, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cross-sectional	Brazil	Adults (>15y)	Outdoor abandonment of contaminated products	Eosinophilia and leukocytosis	847	Following bivariate analysis with hematological alterations, significantly higher levels of HCB were observed in men with eosinophilia ($p = .05$). Using multivariate analysis, eosinophilia was positively associated with levels of beta-HCH in men (OR = 1.06, 95%CI = 1.01–1.12). Significantly lower levels of beta-HCH ($p = .05$) and p,p'-DDE ($p = .02$) were observed in women with leukocytosis.	↑↓
Piccoli, <i>et al.</i>	2019	Cross-sectional	Brazil	Adults (18-69y)	Occupational exposure	Leucocyte counts and hemoglobin levels	275	Detectable serum levels of many organochlorine pesticides were associated with lower counts of leukocytes, monocytes, eosinophils, lymphocytes, neutrophils, and Hb levels.	↓
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 30: Summary of the studies exploring the association between pesticides and hemolysis

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Case series									
Bălăeț, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Case series	Romania	Male adults (27-50y)	Occupational exposure (agriculture)	Hemolysis	3	The accumulation of copper in the tissues is the result of repeated exposure for a few days every two or three months to copper–calcium fungicides, which were used at work, fungicides being used four times per year. In all three cases, although there was no anemia, only subnormal circulating Hb values, there was constant hemolysis. The absence of anemia is interpreted as the ability of the hematopoietic red marrow to compensate for hemolysis, as demonstrated by the fact that in the case of reducing the life of erythrocytes, erythropoietal activity may increase 6–8 times. However, this does not exclude the possibility that the hemolytic toxic action of Cu ²⁺ has been induced through ineffective erythropoiesis.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 31: Summary of the studies exploring the association between pesticides and monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Landgren, <i>et al.</i>	2015	Cohort	USA	Adults (55-89y), Vietnam veterans	Occupational exposure (aerial spray missions)	Monoclonal gammopathy of undetermined significance	958	When compared to the Veterans in the lowest TCDD level (≤ 3.65 ppt), the crude ORs for having MGUS were 2.09 (95% CI, 0.77–5.66; $p = 0.15$), 2.62 (95% CI, 1.00–6.88; $p = 0.05$), and 2.81 (95% CI, 1.08–7.31; $p = 0.03$) for Veterans with TCDD levels of 3.66–5.80 ppt, 5.81–10.92 ppt, and >10.92 ppt, respectively. After adjusting for covariates, the TCDD effect observed at the >10.92 ppt level did not reach the conventional significance level (adjusted OR = 2.43, 95% CI 0.92–6.44; $p = 0.07$).	↔
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 32: Summary of the studies exploring the association between phthalates and anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Jiang, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cross-sectional	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.6 (3.5)]	-	Anemia	1482	Higher urinary phthalate metabolites in the late third trimester were associated with prolonged blood clotting time and increased likelihood of anemia in pregnant women. Thus, we further explored the relationship between DEHP metabolites and the likelihood of anemia and found that elevated concentrations of DEHP metabolites were associated with an increased likelihood of anemia in the late third trimester.	↑
Cohort									
Zhu, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cohort	China	Pregnant women (18-44y)	-	Persistent anemia	3269	The urinary phthalate metabolites concentration of the pregnant women with persistent anemia was higher than that of the pregnant women without persistent anemia. Exposure to MMP, MBP, MEHP, MEOHP, and MEHHP increased the risk of anemia by 1.11-fold (95% CI: 1.07 to 1.15), 1.21-fold (95% CI: 1.15 to 1.27), 1.20-fold (95% CI: 1.14 to 1.26), 1.13-fold (95% CI: 1.05 to 1.20), and 1.16-fold (95% CI: 1.09 to 1.22), respectively, in the entire population.	↑
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 33: Summary of the studies exploring the association between phthalates and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	n	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Jiang, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cross-sectional	China	Pregnant women [mean: 28.6 (3.5)]	-	Hemoglobin levels	1482	Higher urinary phthalate metabolites in the late third trimester were associated with decreased Hb concentrations. We found a significant association between di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) metabolites (i.e. MEHP, MEHHP, MEOHP, and MECPP) and Hb.	↓
Cohort									
Zhu, <i>et al.</i>	2018	Cohort	China	Pregnant women (18-44y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	3269	We detected a significant inverse relationship between the metabolites and the Hb level, where 1 ln-transformed metabolite concentration increase in MBP, MBzP, MEHP, MEOHP, and MEHHP was associated with a Hb concentration decrease of 0.55 (95%CI: -0.74 to -0.35), 0.19 (95%CI: -0.33 to -0.05), 0.57 (95%CI: -0.77 to -0.37), 0.49 (95%CI: -0.75 to -0.23), and 0.54 (95%CI: -0.77 to -0.30) g/L, respectively.	↓
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 34: Summary of the studies exploring the association between aniline and methemoglobinemia and hemolytic anemia

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Case reports									
Kusin, <i>et al.</i>	2012	Case report	USA	Male adult (33y)	Ingestion of pure aniline (mixed with a soft drink to mask the taste)	Methemoglobinemia and hemolytic anemia	1	His methemoglobin concentration was 66.7% (normal: 1%–3%) and peaked at 79.6% at 6 hours after ingestion. The patient presented chemical-induced hemolytic anemia (Hb concentration was 5.8 g/dL). Results of toxicology screening of urine were positive for p-aminophenol, an aniline metabolite.	-
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 35: Summary of the studies exploring the association between polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons and hematological outcomes

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cross-sectional									
Sudakin, <i>et al.</i>	2013	Cross-sectional	USA	Adults (>18y)	-	Hemoglobin levels and hematocrit	2450	After adjusting for age, gender, race, education, and smoking, a positive association was observed between 1-hydroxynaphthalene urinary metabolite (NAP1) and Hb (0.39 ± 0.11 , $p = 0.0034$) as well as HCT (1.14 ± 0.28 , $p = 0.0009$). 2-hydroxynaphthalene urinary metabolite (NAP2) was not significantly associated with Hb or HCT.	↑
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									

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Appendix table 36: Summary of the studies exploring the association between perfluoroalkyl acids and hemoglobin levels

Author	Year	Design	Country	Sample	Source of exposure	Outcome	<i>n</i>	Main findings	Summary
Cohort									
Jain	2020	Cohort	USA	Adults (≥20y)	-	Hemoglobin levels	10183	<p>Among non-anemic participants, adjusted associations between WBHGB and every PFAA were positive and statistically significant except for PFDA among males and for PFNA among both males and females.</p> <p>Among anemic participants, adjusted associations between WBHGB and every PFAA were positive and statistically significant, except for PFHxS.</p>	↑
(↑) positive statistical association; (↓) statistical negative association; (↔) absence of statistical association; (-) no information provided.									